

The Quantum Mechanical Formalism Derived from the Probabilistic Nature of Quantitative Physical Predictions

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Abstract

It is a scientific truism nowadays that quantum mechanical predictions are of statistical or rather of probabilistic nature: a quantum theory assigns a probability distribution to each measurable quantity (observable) of a physical system prepared according to a given preparation prescription (state). Such sets of probability distributions represent the most general quantitative predictions of physical theories. The aim of this study is to determine all theoretical frameworks which yield such a kind of output taking the probabilistic nature of quantitative physical predictions as initial hypothesis. Astonishingly, this project succeeds with a minimal number of additional assumptions, which arise quite naturally in the course of the analysis, and which essentially amount to regularity conditions. The result is that there exist only two classes of physical theories providing quantitative probabilistic predictions: *classical theories* where observables are represented by real functions over a phase space and states are represented by probability measures upon the phase space, and *quantum theories* where observables are represented by selfadjoint operators acting on a complex Hilbert space and states are represented by state operators. On empirical grounds, classical theories cannot provide the all-encompassing, fundamental frame for the mathematical description of physical systems. Quantum theories remain, and there is no more complete formal frame for quantitative physical theories. As an additional result, it is shown that there exist physical systems which possess a quantum mechanical but no classical description; a prominent example is the spin system of two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles. The classical hidden variables model, which J. Bell relates to this system in order to prove his theorem, cannot be a true description of it because no such classical model exists, and Bell's theorem loses its foundation.

Für Madeleine

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Classical statistical mechanics and quantum mechanics both provide probabilistic theoretical predictions. In classical mechanics, probabilistic aspects take effect if the initial conditions of the equations of motion can be specified solely by a probability distribution. The probabilistic nature of quantum mechanical predictions is more fundamental. It is the consequence of the fact that quantum mechanical observable algebras are not commutative. However, the probabilistic nature of quantitative physical predictions is not a mere formal consequence of the mathematical structure of quantum theories either. The logical dependency is rather reverse: it is shown in this report that the mathematical structures of quantum and of classical theories are the consequence of the statement that quantitative physical predictions are probabilistic and, in addition, that they are the only possible mathematical frames of quantitative physical theories.

If the postulate of the probabilistic nature of quantitative physical predictions is chosen as the initial hypothesis, then one is confronted with the request for justification. We think that this postulate possesses deeper roots than simply being a consequence of a theoretical framework suggested by empirical evidence: it is founded in the epistemological characteristics of physical statements. This epistemological background is sketched in section 1.2. The epistemological analysis results, first of all, in a precise meaning of the terms of 'physical law', 'physical system', and 'quantitative physical predictions'. The basic notions of 'observable' and 'state' are introduced and their epistemological status as theoretical terms contrary to terms applicable to material realisations of physical systems is established. The most general quantitative theoretical prediction for a physical system is then identified as a set of real probability measures that depend on the observables and on the states of this system. This is the main initial hypothesis of the analysis presented in this report. We emphasise that deterministic theories are included in this scheme: the probability measures are then concentrated onto a single point for every observable of the physical system and for a certain class of states.

The methodology used in this study is mathematical: consequences are deduced from hypotheses. The result of the study is that there are only two classes of quantitative physical theories if their probabilistic nature is presupposed: classical theories where observables are represented by real functions over a phase space and states are represented by probability measures upon the phase space, and quantum theories where observables are represented by selfadjoint operators acting on a complex Hilbert space and states are represented by state operators. Section 1.3 is a summary of the course of the analysis.

Classical and quantum theories rest on the same epistemological foundations and they are devised for the same purpose namely to provide predictions of the properties of material physical systems. The idea of realism and objectivity attributed to classical physics applies, therefore, to the quantum mechanical description as well (typical argumentations contesting this view are presented and refuted in appendix A). It is, however, important to be aware of the structural peculiarities of the two classes of physical theories. The decisive difference between classical and quantum theories is that classical observables form a commutative algebra, whereas the algebra of quantum mechanical observables is not commutative. This difference cannot

be bridged: there are, in general, no classical hidden variables models for quantum theories (*cf.* chapter 3 of Ref. [1]). A related and even more fundamental consequence is that there exist physical systems which possess a quantum mechanical but no classical description (see appendix B).

Classical and quantum theories are both consequences of the initial probability hypothesis complemented with a few additional regularity postulates. Although classical theories provide useful descriptions in many domains of physics and are still the only available in some fields, there is no doubt that quantum theories provide the fundamental formal frame for microscopic as well as for macroscopic physical systems and not classical theories.

1.1 Previous work on the topic and the motivation to write this report

The initial incentive to concern myself with the topic of this report was the feeling that an essential element was missing in my previous report on the statistical interpretation of quantum mechanics [1] namely the answer to the question why the quantum mechanical formalism is based on complex Hilbert spaces. Tentative answers taken from an analysis of the shortcomings of classical physics or of typical quantum effects can be found in the opening sections of almost all textbooks on quantum theory. But the rigour of argumentation is usually considerably weaker here than in the remaining parts of the books. This cannot be considered to be a satisfactory foundation of the quantum mechanical formalism. A different and much more convincing approach to the problem was developed by the so-called 'School of Geneva' in the nineteen sixties and seventies. It is presented chiefly in the PhD thesis of C. Piron [2], in his subsequent monograph [3], and in the textbook of J. M. Jauch [4]. An early contribution in this direction is the paper of G. Birkhoff and J. von Neumann [5], published in 1936.

The community of mathematical physicists seems to accept this analysis as the conclusive answer to the above question (see *e.g.* [6, Volume 3, 2.2,35]). Why, then, this report?

In my opinion, there are several assumptions here that deserve criticism. First of all, the starting point of the analysis is awkwardly chosen: the building blocks of the so-called propositional calculus, the *propositions*, are defined as classes of yes/no experiments on physical systems [3, p. 20], [4, p. 73, 74] and the propositional calculus is based upon statements about these classes [3, p. 19 – 25], [4, p. 72 – 78]: a proposition a is *true* if the results of the corresponding experiments are certainly yes. A relationship $a \leq b$ between propositions is introduced by the condition "if a is true, then b is true", a logical implication. A logical connotation is given also to two binary operations, the meet and the join, by the conditions " $a \wedge b$ is true if and only if a is true and b is true" and " $a \vee b$ is true" if a or b are true, then $a \vee b$ is true". For every proposition a , a proposition a' based on the the same yes/no experiments is given by the condition that the result of a' is 'no' if the result of a is 'yes', and vice versa.

These definitions are complemented by a set of axioms in order to make the relationship $a \leq b$ a partial order, a' the complement of a , and the set of propositions of a physical system a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, atomic, and weakly modular lattice. Although a' and the basic relationships $a \leq b$, $a \wedge b$, $a \vee b$ are defined in analogy to the corresponding relationships in formal logic and a part of the axioms is motivated with this analogy, it is (rightly) stated that "... [the propositional] calculus has an entirely different meaning from the analogous calculus used in formal logic", [4, p. 77] and similarly in [2, p. 441]. This somehow undermines their reasoning. A further unsatisfactory aspect is that the notions of 'observable' and of 'state' are absent at the beginning albeit implicitly used and are introduced only towards the end in a rather abstract manner, [3, 2-4] and [4, 6-2 – 6-5].

All these difficulties disappear at once if the postulate of the probabilistic nature of quantitative physical predictions is adopted as the starting point of the analysis. The appropriate mathematical formulation of this postulate in terms of probability measures, which depend on the observables and on the states of the physical

system considered, is due to G. W. Mackey [7]. Although this postulate is motivated by empirical evidence, it is not based upon empirical hypotheses. Its justification is given by the epistemological considerations sketched in section 1.2, which are guided by the idea that the kind of answers depends also on the kind of questions qualified as 'physical'.

The analysis is of mathematical kind: results are deduced from postulates. The possibility to define real functions of observables already on this very general level is a central feature and discloses the above propositions as *projections*, characteristic functions of observables with a geometrical connotation. The set of the projections of an observable, its *projection system*, possesses a rich structure, which includes all the properties that had to be imposed above as axioms: it forms a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, atomic, separable, additive, and distributive lattice. In order to characterise the *projection system of a physical system* containing a set of different observables, it suffices to dismiss distributivity, but to keep the remaining properties of the projection systems of the observables, in particular, that there is solely one orthocomplement of a projection. This structure is a sufficient basis for the analysis. Specific physical configurations must be taken into account only towards the end in order to exclude real and quaternion Hilbert spaces.

This new access to the topic requires new considerations in order to fit the existing mathematical machinery into it. In addition, my main sources, Piron's thesis, his monograph, and Jauch's textbook, leave out a considerable part of the intricate mathematical deductions. The authors refer to textbooks on projective geometry. One may content oneself with simply believing the relevant theorems, which are readily formulated but laborious to prove, or one is forced to study textbooks on the subject and to get acquainted with a new terminology and with new manners of reasoning. I decided to choose the second alternative. Fortunately, it turned out that the textbook of R. Baer [8] fits exceedingly well into the context of the present study and provides an elegant and concise demonstration of the fundamental representation theorem.

Having done all this work for myself, I found the results interesting enough to present them to the scientific community as a report written in a coherent fashion and with a consistent terminology. The extensive size of the report is due to an endeavour after completeness: the required elements of lattice theory, which usually is not in the curriculum even of theoretical physicists, are presented from scratch while deducing the properties of projection systems of observables; the basics of probability theory, of linear algebra, and its connection with projective geometry are given in the main body of the text and in several appendices; the proofs of almost all lemmata, theorems, and corollaries are provided. I hope to have thereby facilitated the access to the subject of this report.

1.2 Epistemological preliminary remarks

The following considerations are a summary of chapter 2 of Ref. [1].

A characteristic feature of physical thinking is that an individual observation is considered an instance of a general law. Physicists expect nature to follow causal laws that can be formulated without explicit reference to geographical, historical, or personal circumstances. The causes can be brought about, in principle, by everybody, everywhere, at every time, and are expected to always entail the same consequences. Because the validity of causal laws is asserted for all physical situations where they apply, these laws have the logical form of universal implications [9]: "*At every place, for every time, and for every observer $C \rightarrow P$* ". The symbol C denotes the physical system and initial and boundary conditions specifying the physical situation, P the asserted consequences. Processes that follow universal causal laws are important because their results can be predicted to a certain extent. These processes are the basis for the human command on nature, for engineering and technology.

In the present context, the notions of physical system, of observables, and of states all have a theoretical meaning. They are constituents of mathematical models which describe the structure of a material object

and provide predictions of its behaviour. In physics, universality presupposes, in addition, the capability to realise, in an *experiment*, the material representation of a physical system together with specific initial and boundary conditions representing its *state*. An experiment that can be confronted with a theoretical prediction is divided into two parts in a natural way. First, the *state* of the physical system must be *prepared* on its material realisation. In a second step, the *value of an observable*, denoting a physical property of the this material realisation, is *measured*. This value can then be compared with the theoretical prediction P . Usually, many repetitions of the experiment are necessary to decide whether the sample of measured values is compatible with the prediction.

The preparation of the state of a physical system and the subsequent measurement of an observable value are logically distinct parts of an experiment which is devised to test theoretical predictions. State preparation determines the behaviour of the system afterwards, it points towards the future, whereas a measurement reveals the value of an observable at the very moment of the measurement. The value of the observable may be changed by the measurement, but its value after the measurement is of no importance for the test of theoretical predictions. The system may even cease to exist after the measurement, *e.g.* when a particle is absorbed by a detector. State preparation and the measurement of an observable value are both necessary and distinct parts of an experiment and should not be merged into one diffuse notion of 'measurement'.

The universality of physical statements has an important consequence: such a statement is not only asserted for the actual physical situation under consideration, but is assumed to be equally valid for every situation of the same kind. Universality and the abstraction from individuality make physical descriptions indirect in a specific manner: theoretical physical statements and the expressions and terms with which they are formulated refer directly to the abstract class of 'physical systems of the same kind' or 'experimental arrangements', to 'preparation instructions', and to 'measurement instructions'. They refer to a concretely realised physical system with its concretely realised preparations and measurements only in so far as it is a member of the infinite class of experiments to which this theoretical description applies. This opens the scene for probabilistic statements about different measurement results obtained under identical experimental conditions, for causal statements that are not deterministic. *The most general quantitative, theoretical prediction for an experiment is the prediction how probable the different outcomes of measurements performed under identical conditions will be.* Causal laws are then possible, in general, only for these probability predictions not for measurement values except if the probability measure of the corresponding observable is concentrated onto a single point. In this way, deterministic predictions of measurement values are nevertheless included in this scheme.

It is a decisive point that physical theories do not directly provide predictions of the properties of individual systems (the values of its observables), but provide predictions of probability distributions of such properties. Consequently, the terms used to formulate these predictions, as 'observable' or 'state', refer to the mentioned classes of physical systems *not* to their individual material realisations. This is the essence of the *Statistical Interpretation [of quantum mechanics]*, according to which a pure state (and hence also a general state) provides a description of certain statistical properties of an ensemble of similarly prepared systems, but need not provide a complete description of an individual system [10, p. 360]. The conception of a pure state as a complete and exhaustive description of an *individual system* is, therefore, an epistemological misconception, which entails the numerous logical and interpretatory difficulties of the so called Copenhagen or Orthodox Interpretation of quantum mechanics, as *e.g.* Schrödinger's cat paradox, 'fundamental measurement problems', the 'collapse of the wave function' if an observer takes notice of the result of a measurement, and so on¹. No such problems occur in the statistical interpretation (see chapter 5 and

¹We contrast the Copenhagen and the statistical interpretation by means of the version of Bohm and Aharonov [11] of the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen thought experiment [12] (see chapter 5 of Ref. [1] and appendix A for technical details): two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles A and B are bound into an instable system of total spin 0 and disintegrate conserving total spin. No physical interactions between the particles exist during a certain time after disintegration; each particle is considered to be free. The quantum mechanical analysis of the spin space of the single particles yields the following result [1, p. 38]: after disintegration, each separated, free particle belongs to a statistical ensemble whose spin state is a perfect mixture *i.e.* a measurement of the spin in any spin direction

section 4.4 of Ref. [1]).

If a pure state is *not* a property of an individual material system, then what *are* its properties? The answer is: the values of its observables (see section 2.3 of Ref. [1]). These values are objective properties of the material system, which can be determined, in principle, with an appropriate measurement. It is, however, not possible in a quantum mechanical description to *prepare* the system in such a way that all these definite observable values can simultaneously be sharply predicted. This is the meaning of Heisenberg's uncertainty relations. Classical theories provide this possibility, but fail to be the fundamental theoretical framework.

Heisenberg's uncertainty relations indicate, therefore, a limitation of physical predictability and, consequently, of human command on nature on principle. It is remarkable that the characterisation of physical laws as universal implications and their quantitative predictions as probability statements result in quantum mechanical laws setting bounds to physical predictability. Nevertheless, the question '*Can Quantum-Mechanical Description of Physical Reality Be Considered Complete?*', the title of the famous EPR-paper [12], must definitively be answered in the positive in the light of this report: there is no empirically correct and more complete theoretical physical framework. Rather, one has to state that classical theories are incomplete in a much more fundamental manner than only being empirically unsatisfactory. There are physical systems, for which a quantum mechanical but no classical description exist [15, p. 382], [1, sections 3.4, 3.6], among others, ironically, the system of the two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles described in footnote 1, which is used by J. S. Bell [16] to derive his correlation formula within the scope of classical theories. It follows that this

yields the value $+\frac{\hbar}{2}$ or $-\frac{\hbar}{2}$ with equal probability 0.5. On the other hand, the combined system of the two particles is still prepared in the pure state of total spin 0, which entails that the spins of the particles A and B are strictly anticorrelated: if the measurement of a spin component in a given direction of particle A yields the value $+\frac{\hbar}{2}$, then the corresponding measurement of the spin component in the same direction of particle B yields the value $-\frac{\hbar}{2}$ with certainty.

In the Copenhagen interpretation, a pure state is considered a property of an individual system. But the conclusion is then inevitable that the mentioned spin measurement on particle A immediately generates, on particle B, the pure spin state belonging to the eigenvalue $-\frac{\hbar}{2}$ of the spin component in the given direction because a subsequent measurement of this spin component of particle B produces the value $-\frac{\hbar}{2}$ with certainty. However, there is no physical interaction between the particles at that time by hypothesis — a puzzling situation. This '*spooky interaction at a distance*' (Einstein [13, p. 158]) is considered a classically incomprehensible feature of so-called entangled quantum systems, and far reaching conclusions about the epistemological nature of quantum theories are drawn, *e.g.* that the quantum mechanical description be nonlocal. This assertion is discussed and refuted in chapter 6 of Ref. [1].

The situation presents itself much less mysteriously in the statistical interpretation. The desired state of total spin 0 is the result of a suitable state preparation and presupposes certain properties of the interaction between the particles before disintegration. For both particles, the spin values in any direction result from the course of the interaction between the particles during disintegration, and they are objective properties of the particles, which can be determined by measurements. The spin state of each isolated particle after separation is a perfect mixture, as already stated. The individual spin values are given after the interaction between the particles has ceased, and they are constant in time afterwards as long as the particles are free; otherwise the strict spin-spin anticorrelation would be destroyed. This anticorrelation is, therefore, a consequence of the preparation of the initial system and is kept up as long as both particles are free. That both particles are free after disintegration is taken seriously: a manipulation on particle A cannot exert any effect on particle B. No inconsistencies or enigmatic situations are in sight: correlations do not induce causal interactions.

But what use can then be made of the spin anticorrelation? We remember that a mixed state is a convex superposition of pure states. A random sample of values of an observable measured on a system prepared according to a mixed state can be subdivided into subsamples belonging to the same observable and to systems prepared according to prescriptions given by pure states. Let's assume now that a series of pairs of spin-correlated particles is emitted by a source and that the particles of these pairs are analysed by two distant experimentalists, Alice and Bob. Alice performs measurements of a spin component on her series of particles A. If Bob knows that the result of the measurement of Alice on a given particle is $+\frac{\hbar}{2}$, then he can conclude from the strict anticorrelation that the result of a measurement of the same spin component on his related particle B will certainly be equal to $-\frac{\hbar}{2}$ and that this particle belongs, therefore, to a sample prepared into the pure state of the spin value $-\frac{\hbar}{2}$ of the given spin component. Without this information, Bob only knows that the particle belongs to the sample described by a perfect mixture. Hence, the spin anticorrelation between related pairs of particles and the information obtained from Alice enables Bob to subdivide his set of particles belonging to a perfect mixture into subsamples belonging to pure states. This subdivision can be executed by mere book keeping without physical manipulation of the particles B in this particular case. Clearly, the important event is that Bob gets the information from Alice, which enables him to take specific actions, and not the moment of Alice's measurement, which does not exert any influence whatever on Bob's particles.

We remark that Bennet et al. draw a similar picture in their paper on teleporting quantum states [14]: "*Alice makes a joint measurement on her EPR particle and the unknown quantum system, and sends Bob her classical result of this measurement. Knowing this, Bob can convert the state of his EWR particle into an exact replica of the unknown state $|\phi\rangle$ which Alice destroyed.*"

correlation formula, which is the basis of Bell's inequalities, cannot concern spin-spin correlations because a classical theory of this quantum mechanical system does not exist irrespective whether this classical theory is considered to be local or not or whether it reproduces the quantum mechanical predictions or not (see appendix B). This severely queries the bearing of the theorem formulated in Ref. [16].

A second topic that needs some consideration is the notion of *probability* (see section 2.2 of Ref. [1]). Probability can be understood in two fundamentally different manners: *objective interpretations* assign probabilities to events as an objective measure of the frequency of their occurring whereas *subjective interpretations* assign probabilities to statements or assertions as a measure of the subjective knowledge or belief that a statement is true. To say that the result of quantitative physical theories are probabilistic predictions for measured observable values clearly indicates an objective interpretation of probabilities. This specific objective interpretation is termed *the propensity interpretation of probability* by K. Popper, according to which, in the context of physical experiments, "*probabilities characterize the disposition, or the propensity, of the experimental arrangement to give rise to certain characteristic frequencies when the experiment is often repeated. [These probabilities] may be looked upon as properties of this arrangement*" [17, p. 67]. We specify that the notion of 'experimental arrangement' refers to the mentioned theoretical classes of physical systems where the probability measures depend on the observables and the states associated with these classes of physical systems.

The representation of probabilities as mathematical objects is sketched in appendix C. Probability theory is based there on Kolmogorov's axiomatics and presents itself as a branch of measure theory with its own emphasis. This widely accepted mathematical basis of probability theory reflects the intuitive meaning of probability and lies behind its use in quantum mechanics and in classical statistical physics.

1.3 Summary of contents

The analysis starts with the postulate that the quantitative predictions of a physical theory are given by a set of probability measures $P_{A,s}$ where $P_{A,s}(\sigma)$ is the probability to find the value of the observable A in the set σ of real numbers if A is measured on a material realisation of a physical system prepared according to the state s . It is important and appropriate that the notions of 'observable' and 'state' are *both* introduced as general terms right at the beginning and on an equal footing. This corresponds to the manner how we perceive and describe our material environment namely as a collection of objects with their constant and varying properties. Or to give a more specific example: the predictions for a system of classical mechanics characterised by its equations of motion depend on both, on the observable considered and on the initial conditions for the equations of motion, the state. The same situation applies to predictions in the Heisenberg picture of quantum mechanics.

In mathematical terms (see appendix C): a real probability space $(\Omega_A, \mathcal{B}(\Omega_A), P_{A,s})$ is attributed to every observable A and to every state s where Ω_A , the *spectrum* of A , denotes the set of all possible measurement values of A , and $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_A)$ denotes the set of the Borel sets over Ω_A . The observable A is then the *stochastic variable* that maps the point ξ in Ω_A , an *elementary event* in the terminology of probability theory, to the real number ξ . The *expectation value* $E_s(A)$ of the observable A and the state s is given by the integral $E_s(A) = \int_{\Omega_A} \xi dP_{A,s}((-\infty, \xi])$.

A *real function* $f(A)$ of an observable A is defined by the identity $P_{f(A),s}(\sigma) = P_{A,s}(f^{-1}(\sigma))$ valid for all Borel sets σ provided that the full inverses $f^{-1}(\sigma)$ are Borel sets, too. This definition specifies the set of *real Borel functions*. The *projections* $a(\sigma) \equiv \chi_\sigma(A)$, characteristic functions of the observable A , are Borel functions. Projections possess only the two measurement values 0 and 1 and are, therefore, completely characterised by the set of their expectation values for all states. The expectation values of the projection a fulfils the inequality $0 \leq E_s(a) \leq 1$.

The set of all projections derived from an observable A is the *projection system* \mathcal{P}_A of this observable. It is $E_s(a(\sigma)) = P_{A,s}(\sigma)$. Hence, we may study the set $\{E_s(a)\}$ of the expectation values of all projections a of the projection system \mathcal{P}_A for all states s as well as the set of the probability measures $\{P_{A,s}(\cdot)\}$ of all observables A for all states.

The projection systems \mathcal{P}_A possess a rich structure. First of all, a *partial order* $a \leq b$ is established between certain pairs of projections a and b in \mathcal{P}_A by the condition that $E_s(a) \leq E_s(b)$ for all states s . The projection $0 \equiv \chi_\emptyset(A)$ has the expectation value 0 for all states, and the projection $I \equiv \chi_{\Omega_A}(A)$ has the expectation value 1 for all states. Hence, it is $0 \leq a \leq I$ for every projection a in \mathcal{P}_A . An algebraic structure, equivalent to the partial order in \mathcal{P}_A , is provided by the two binary operations *join*, $a \vee b$, and *meet*, $a \wedge b$, defined for all pairs a, b of projections as their supremum and infimum, respectively. Two projections a and b are *disjoint*, $a \perp b$, if $0 \leq E_s(a) + E_s(b) \leq 1$ for all states *i.e.* if the sum of the projections a and b defined by the sum of their expectation values is again a projection. The equation $E_s(a') = 1 - E_s(a)$ determines the projection a' as the *orthogonal complement* or *orthocomplement* of the projection a , it is $a' \perp a$. Additional structural properties of the projection system \mathcal{P}_A of the observable A are derived in section 2.3: \mathcal{P}_A is a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, distributive, atomic, separable, and additive lattice. A *spectral representation of an observable* can be constructed in striking analogy to the spectral decomposition of selfadjoint operators acting on a complex Hilbert space. In a distributive lattice, orthocomplementation and complementation are equivalent, and a given projection possesses one and only one (orthogonal) complement. Distributivity characterises the projection systems of classical theories, section 2.5.

In chapter 3, the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} of a physical system is considered. It is generated from the set union of the atoms of all projection systems \mathcal{P}_A of the physical system. The definitions of partial order, of disjointness, and of orthocomplementation remain unchanged. \mathcal{P}_{PhS} contains the projections 0 and I common to all observables. Hence, it is a bounded, complete, and orthocomplemented lattice. Distributivity can no longer be requested because the projection systems of quantum theories should be included. However, in order to characterise the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} , it suffices to dispense with distributivity, and to retain all other properties of the projection systems \mathcal{P}_A , in particular, separability, atomicity and that there is one and only one orthocomplement of a projection. To require that the orthocomplement in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is unique is equivalent to the postulate that \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is *weakly modular*. It results that the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, weakly modular, separable, atomic, and additive lattice. This characterisation constitutes the axiomatic basis of the subsequent analysis.

In chapter 4, the notion of the *rank* $\nu(a)$ of a projection a is introduced as an intrinsic property of the projection. The *rank of a projection system* is the rank of its unit projection I . An important feature is the *rank formula*, $\nu(a) + \nu(b) = \nu(a \vee b) + \nu(a \wedge b)$, valid for any two projections a and b of a projection system of *finite rank*. As a consequence of this formula, weakly modular projection systems of finite rank are *modular*. Irreducible, weakly modular projection systems of infinite rank are not modular.

It is shown in chapter 5 that any projection system decomposes into a distributive projection system and the direct product of irreducible, weakly modular projection systems. The subsequent analysis is concentrated on irreducible, weakly modular but not distributive projection systems of finite rank not less than three, which are, therefore, modular. Projection systems of this kind are projective geometries.

In chapter 6, it is shown that irreducible projection systems of finite rank greater or equal than three are projectively equivalent to the system of subspaces of a left vector space. An explicit construction of this left vector space is given. Its dimension is equal to the rank of the projection system. It is indispensable for the construction of the associated vector spaces and of their (not necessarily commutative) fields that these projection systems are modular.

Projection systems are orthocomplemented. In chapter 7, the consequences of orthocomplementation are shown: the field of the related finite dimensional left vector space possesses an *involution anti-automorphism*, a generalisation of complex conjugation in the case of complex numbers, and the vector space possesses a

definite semi-bilinear form. The orthogonal complement of a subspace is expressed in terms of this semi-bilinear form. The semi-bilinear form and the representation of orthocomplements by this form, both constructed for finite dimensional vector spaces, is extended to the case of the representations of irreducible projection systems of infinite rank.

A projection is determined by the set of its expectation values for all states. These expectation values are real numbers, which are calculated from the elements of the related vector space by some mathematical procedure. Hence, the field of this vector space must contain the real numbers as a subfield, which limits the choice of possible fields to the real numbers, the complex numbers, and to the quaternions according to the theorem of Frobenius. In all three cases, the semi-bilinear form is a strictly positive Hermitian scalar product. It induces a norm of the vector space, which allows to complete the vector space to a *Hilbert space* by adding the limit vectors of all convergent vector series. It is shown in appendix G that an irreducible projection system is projectively equivalent to the lattice of closed subspaces of a Hilbert space.

Mathematical analysis has revealed so far that an irreducible, weakly modular component of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is projectively equivalent to the lattice of closed subspaces of a Hilbert space based upon the real numbers, the complex numbers, or the quaternions. In order to further differentiate between these possibilities, specific *physical* contexts must be taken into account with the result that solely complex Hilbert spaces are suited to describe quantum mechanical systems.

Real Hilbert spaces are ruled out by the following observation: the spectral representation of observables shows that they are linear combinations of projections. Projections obviously correspond to symmetric operators on a real Hilbert space, and this is true for all observables as a consequence of their spectral representation. The position operator \mathbf{x} is symmetric, indeed, but the linear momentum \mathbf{p} and the angular momentum \mathbf{L} are antisymmetric. Hence, the observable system of a point mass, the most elementary physical system, cannot be represented on the basis of a real Hilbert space.

Quaternion Hilbert spaces are ruled out because quaternion multiplication is not commutative, which makes the construction of definite tensor products impossible. Tensor products are an indispensable formal tool in order to describe composite physical systems based on the descriptions of their parts. Tensor products are needed *e.g.* to describe composite systems where all observables of part 1 commute with all observables of part 2, which signifies that the two parts are physically independent. Therefore, the indispensable concept of spatially confined physical systems isolated from their environments cannot be expressed in 'quaternion quantum mechanics'.

Hence, the system of the closed subspaces of a *complex* Hilbert space is the only possible basis to describe quantum mechanical projection systems. Projections are represented by projectors, idempotent and selfadjoint operators on the complex Hilbert space. The representation of observables by selfadjoint operators is then a consequence of the spectral decomposition theorem for observables mentioned above, and the representation of states by state operators follows from Gleason's theorem.

With this result, the proof is furnished that a quantitative physical theory is either a classical theory or a quantum theory based on a complex Hilbert space if the probabilistic nature of the theory is specified by the set of postulates compiled in section 3.4.

Chapter 2

The projection system of an observable

2.1 The probabilistic structure of quantitative physical theories

In this section, the notion of 'probabilistic predictions of physical theories' is specified. The basic terms of quantitative physical theories are *observables* A, B, \dots corresponding to the measurable quantities of the physical system in question, and *states* s_1, s_2, \dots corresponding to the preparation of specific initial or boundary conditions of the system. The most general quantitative prediction for a physical system is a probabilistic prediction for the the values of an observable A measured on individual, material realisations of the system, which is treated according to the preparation instruction which corresponds to the state s . The expression 'probabilistic prediction' is now specified by postulating that a quantitative physical theory provides *real probability measures* $P_{A,s}(\sigma)$ that indicate the probability with which the measured value $m[A]$ of the observable A falls into the real Borel set σ if an individual material realisation of the system is prepared corresponding to the state s . Or, the values $m[A]_1, m[A]_2, \dots, m[A]_n$ of the observable A measured on individual physical systems prepared in accordance with the preparation instruction s form a random test of the probability measure $P_{A,s}$. This corresponds to the accepted use of probability in quantum mechanics as well as in classical statistical physics.

The contents of the preceding paragraph may be stated as the postulate¹ of the **Probabilistic Structure of the quantitative Predictions of physical theories**:

PSP The formal scheme of quantitative physical theories contains two different kinds of terms, namely observables and states. A theory assigns a real probability space $(\Omega_A, \mathcal{B}(\Omega_A), P_{A,s})$ to an observable A and a state s .

The notion of 'probability space' is explained in appendix C. The sample space Ω_A is a subspace of the real numbers \mathbb{R} and defined at the opening of section 2.3. The carrier of the probability measures $P_{A,s}$ can be extended from Ω_A to the total set \mathbb{R} of real numbers with the definition $P_{A,s}(\sigma) = 0$ for $\sigma \subseteq \Omega'_A$. Postulate PSP corresponds to the Axom I of Mackey's axiomatics of quantum mechanics [7, p. 63].

The following separation postulates conduce to the economy of description:

S1 Observables separate states. Two states s_1 and s_2 are identical, $s_1 = s_2$, if $P_{A,s_1}(\sigma) = P_{A,s_2}(\sigma)$ for all observables A and for all Borel sets σ in $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$.

¹Although the analysis is of mathematical kind and we strive for mathematical rigour as far as reasonably feasible, we prefer the notion of 'postulate' instead of 'axiom', the term used by many authors in this field. We emphasise thereby that it is a matter of physics as well as of mathematics.

S2 States separate observables. Two observables A and B are identical, $A = B$, if $P_{A,s}(\sigma) = P_{B,s}(\sigma)$ for all states s and for all Borel sets σ in $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$.

The separation postulates correspond to Mackey's Axiom II [7, p. 63]. They state that an observable A is uniquely characterised by the set of the probability measures $\{P_{A,s}(\cdot)\}$ of all states s which are considered to constitute preparation prescriptions for the physical system, and a state s is uniquely characterised by the set $\{P_{A,s}(\cdot)\}$ of all observables A that are assumed to be measurable.

The separation postulates are not restrictions, but the convention not to use different names for the same object. Furthermore, they ensure the mutual consistency of the sets of observables and states considered. The questions how states are prepared or how observables are measured in physical practice is no topic here. In any case, it is surely not reasonable to assume the existence of states that cannot be prepared or the existence of measurement values that cannot be measured *on principle*.

In addition, an operational meaning of the identity $A = B$ must be provided for individual measurements: if A is measured on an individual system yielding the measured value $m[A] = \alpha$ then this is also regarded a measurement of B with the same measured value $m[B] = \alpha$. This is the only reasonable definition if the value of an observable is considered an objective property of the individual system. If, on the contrary, $m[B] = \beta \neq \alpha$ is assumed for individual measurements, then an explication must be provided why many independent realisations of B -measurements yield a random sample of the probability distribution $P_{A,s}$.

This formal description of physical theories is very general. It entails, nevertheless, an astonishingly rich structure of the observable space due to the properties of Borel sets, Borel functions, probability measures, and stochastic variables (see appendix C). This structure is described in the subsequent sections.

2.2 Properties of states

The states of a projection system form a *convex set*: let s_1, s_2, \dots be a countable sequence of states of the system and ρ_1, ρ_2, \dots a countable sequence of real numbers such that $\rho_n > 0$ and $\sum_n \rho_n = 1$. The sum

$$P_{A,s}(\sigma) \equiv \sum_n \rho_n P_{A,s_n}(\sigma)$$

is then well defined for every real Borel set σ and is a probability measure for every observable A . It determines a state s as a convex linear combination of the states s_n symbolically denoted by:

$$s = \sum_n \rho_n s_n$$

If the state s is a convex linear combination of a finite number N of states s_n , then every random sample of values $m[A]_1, m[A]_2, \dots, m[A]_M$ with $M \gg N$ of the observable A measured on systems prepared in the state s can be subdivided into samples belonging to the same observable measured on systems prepared in the states s_n . In the limit $M \rightarrow \infty$, the number ρ_n indicates the relative frequency with which the measured values fall into the subsample belonging to s_n .

2.3 Properties of observables

We begin this section with some definitions. The *spectrum* Ω_A of the observable A is defined by analogy with the spectrum of a selfadjoint operator on a Hilbert space [4, p. 52, 100]: a Borel set σ is called a *A-null set* if $P_{A,s}(\sigma) = 0$ for all states s . Let $\{\sigma_i : i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ be the set of all open *A-null sets*. Then $\sigma_0 = \bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \sigma_i$

is also open and A -null. The spectrum Ω_A of A is the complement of σ_0 and is, therefore, closed. A point ω of the spectrum Ω_A can alternatively be characterised by the condition that there is at least one state s_ω such that $P_{A,s_\omega}([-\epsilon + \omega, +\epsilon + \omega]) > 0$ for all $\epsilon > 0$. The point ω belongs to the *discrete spectrum* if $\lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} P_{A,s_\omega}([-\epsilon + \omega, +\epsilon + \omega]) > 0$; it is a point of the *continuous spectrum* if this limit equals 0. The discrete spectrum contains at most countably many points as a consequence of the corresponding property of the distribution function in probability theory (see appendix C). An observable A is called *discrete* if its spectrum is purely discrete. The observable A is represented by the stochastic variable, which maps a point ξ of the sample space Ω_A onto ξ in \mathbb{R} .

A *real function* $f(A)$ of an observable A can already be defined on the level of probability spaces. Let f be a Borel function (*i.e.* the full inverse $f^{-1}(\sigma)$ of a Borel set σ is again a Borel set), which is defined on the spectrum Ω_A of A . Then it is

$$P_{f(A),s}(\sigma) = P_{A,s}(f^{-1}(\sigma)) \quad (2.1)$$

for every state and for every Borel set σ in $\mathcal{B}(f(\Omega_A))$. This means that a measurement of the observable A on a system prepared according to the state s yielding the value $m[A] = \alpha$ is also a measurement of the observable $f(A)$ yielding the measurement value $f(\alpha)$: $m[f(A)] = f(m[A])$. In accordance with this identity, the *expectation value of an observable* $f(A)$, given the state s , equals

$$E_s(f(A)) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\xi) dF_{A,s}(\xi) \quad (2.2)$$

where $F_{A,s}$ is the *distribution function* of the observable A and the state s defined by

$$F_{A,s}(\xi) \equiv P_{A,s}((-\infty, \xi]) \quad (2.3)$$

(*cf.* Eqns. (C.4) and (C.5)). The integral is a Stieltjes integral, see [18, Chapt. III], and [4, Chapt. 1] for a short introduction into measure and integration theory. Relationship (2.2) is based on the identity

$$P_{A,s}((\xi_1, \xi_2]) = F_{A,s}(\xi_2) - F_{A,s}(\xi_1)$$

for $\xi_1 < \xi_2$.

The *variance* or *dispersion* of an observable A in the state s is defined by

$$\text{Var}_s(A) \equiv E_s((A - E_s(A))^2) = E_s(A^2) - E_s(A)^2$$

The *unit observable* I is given by the condition that its measurement value $m[I]$ always equals 1. It is $F_{I,s}(\xi) = \Theta(\xi - 1)$ and, therefore, $dF_{I,s}(\xi) = \delta(\xi - 1) d\xi$, and $E_s(I) = 1$ for all states s . The last result may also be derived directly from equation (2.2) with arbitrary observables by setting $f(\xi) \equiv 1$ because $\lim_{\xi \rightarrow +\infty} F_{A,s}(\xi) = 1$ for all observables and states.

The *characteristic function* χ_σ of a Borel set σ is defined by

$$\chi_\sigma(\xi) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \xi \in \sigma \\ 0 & \text{if } \xi \notin \sigma \end{cases}$$

It is $(\chi_\sigma)^{-1}(\{1\}) = \sigma$ and $(\chi_\sigma)^{-1}(\{0\}) = \sigma'$. Hence, the characteristic function χ_σ uniquely determines the set σ . For consistency, we define $\chi_\emptyset(\xi) = 0$ for all $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$. Then it is $\chi_\sigma^2 = \chi_\sigma$ for all Borel sets σ , and it follows from the definitions of inclusion, of complement, of the intersection, and of the union of sets that

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 \subseteq \sigma_2 & \text{ if and only if } \chi_{\sigma_1} \chi_{\sigma_2} = \chi_{\sigma_1} \\ \chi_{\sigma'} & = 1 - \chi_\sigma \\ \chi_{\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2} & = \chi_{\sigma_1} \chi_{\sigma_2} \\ \chi_{\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2} & = \chi_{\sigma_1} + \chi_{\sigma_2} - \chi_{\sigma_1} \chi_{\sigma_2} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

These relationships imply the *distributivity* of σ -fields:

$$\begin{aligned}\chi_{\sigma_1 \cup (\sigma_2 \cap \sigma_3)} &= \chi_{(\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2) \cap (\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_3)} \\ \chi_{\sigma_1 \cap (\sigma_2 \cup \sigma_3)} &= \chi_{(\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) \cup (\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_3)}\end{aligned}\tag{2.5}$$

It is, furthermore, for $\Delta \subseteq \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$

$$\chi_\sigma^{-1}(\Delta) = \begin{cases} \emptyset & \text{if } 0 \notin \Delta \text{ and } 1 \notin \Delta \\ \sigma & \text{if } 0 \notin \Delta \text{ and } 1 \in \Delta \\ \sigma' & \text{if } 0 \in \Delta \text{ and } 1 \notin \Delta \\ \mathbb{R} & \text{if } 0 \in \Delta \text{ and } 1 \in \Delta \end{cases}$$

which reveals that characteristic functions are Borel functions, indeed.

2.3.1 Projections

A *projection* Q is a discrete observable possessing the two observable values 0 and 1 *i.e.* the spectrum $\Omega_Q = \{0\} \cup \{1\}$ ². The expectation value of a projection Q satisfies the inequality

$$0 \leq E_s(Q) \leq 1$$

for all states s . In addition, a projection is idempotent

$$Q^2 = Q$$

This result is verified by taking into account that $(x^2)^{-1}(\cdot)$ is the identity map on $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_Q) = \{\emptyset, \{0\}, \{1\}, \Omega_Q\}$. Therefore, $P_{Q^2, s}(\sigma) = P_{Q, s}((x^2)^{-1}(\sigma)) = P_{Q, s}(\sigma)$ for all states s and all Borel sets σ in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_Q)$.

The variance of the projection Q is given by

$$\text{Var}_s(Q) = E_s(Q^2) - E_s(Q)^2 = E_s(Q) - E_s(Q)^2 = E_s(Q) (1 - E_s(Q))$$

$\text{Var}_s(Q) = 0$ is equivalent to $E_s(Q) = 0$ or $E_s(Q) = 1$.

The probability measure $P_{Q, s}$ is completely determined by the expectation value $E_s(Q)$:

$$P_{Q, s}(\sigma) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 0 \notin \sigma, 1 \notin \sigma \\ E_s(Q) & \text{if } 0 \notin \sigma, 1 \in \sigma \\ 1 - E_s(Q) & \text{if } 0 \in \sigma, 1 \notin \sigma \\ 1 & \text{if } 0 \in \sigma, 1 \in \sigma \end{cases}\tag{2.6}$$

Hence, a projection Q is completely specified by the set $\{E_s(Q)\}$ of its expectation values for all states s .

The distribution function of a projection is given by

$$F_{Q, s}(\xi) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \xi < 0 \\ 1 - E_s(Q) & \text{if } 0 \leq \xi < 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } \xi \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

²Observables with only the two values 0 and 1 are usually termed 'propositions' [5, 2, 4] or 'questions' [7], and a logical meaning is given to the orthocomplement, to the join, and to the meet of propositions. Although this point of view is upheld by many authorities, this terminology does not seem helpful to me for the present purpose but rather misleading. The notion of 'projection' emphasises that the object under consideration is a particular kind of observable with a geometrical connotation.

The observables $\chi_\sigma(A)$ are projections; the measurement value 1 of $\chi_\sigma(A)$ means that the measurement value of A lies in the Borel set σ . The probability measure $P_{A,s}(\sigma)$ can be recovered as the expectation value of the projection $\chi_\sigma(A)$ in the state s

$$P_{A,s}(\sigma) = E_s(\chi_\sigma(A)) \quad (2.7)$$

which implies that an observable A can alternatively be characterised by the probability measures $P_{A,s}$ or by the expectation values of the set $\{\chi_\sigma(A) : \sigma \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})\}$ for all states s . Equation (2.1) follows from equation (2.7) and from the identity

$$\chi_\sigma(f(\xi)) = \chi_{f^{-1}(\sigma)}(\xi) \quad (2.8)$$

The *spectral decomposition of the observable A* may be defined by

$$Q_A(\xi) \equiv \chi_{(-\infty, \xi]}(A) \quad (2.9)$$

and has the following properties:

- (1) If $\xi_1 \leq \xi_2$ then $Q_A(\xi_1) Q_A(\xi_2) = Q_A(\xi_2) Q_A(\xi_1) = Q_A(\xi_1)$
- (2) $\lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} Q_A(\xi + \epsilon) = Q_A(\xi)$
- (3) $\lim_{\xi \rightarrow -\infty} Q_A(\xi) = 0$
- (4) $\lim_{\xi \rightarrow +\infty} Q_A(\xi) = 1$
- (5) $E_s(Q_A(\xi)) = F_{A,s}(\xi)$

As a consequence of property (5), the expression (2.2) for the expectation values of the observable $f(A)$ and the state s can symbolically be formulated as a relationship solely between observables:

$$f(A) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\xi) dQ_A(\xi) \quad (2.10)$$

This expression may be termed the *spectral representation of $f(A)$* . The integrals in equation (2.2) and, hence, in equation (2.10) are defined for a vast class of bounded real functions $f(\xi)$. This is in striking analogy to the spectral representation of a bounded, selfadjoint operator acting on a complex Hilbert space [18, Sec. 120]. $Q_A(\xi)$ is a projector in this case and the distribution function $F_{A,s}(\xi)$ its quantum mechanical expectation value in the state s , which is given by the trace formula.

In the sequel, we use the abbreviated notation

$$a(\sigma) \equiv \chi_\sigma(A) \quad (2.11)$$

to describe projections derived from an observable A in order to emphasise their dependence on the Borel sets σ and to harmonise the notation with the one of lattice theory: lattice elements are denoted by small latin characters. The set of all projections derived from an observable A is the *projection system \mathcal{P}_A* of A .

2.4 The structure of the projection system \mathcal{P}_A

In this section, the mathematical structure of \mathcal{P}_A is investigated. This structure is determined by the properties of the expectation values $E_s(a)$, which uniquely characterise the projection a according to equation

(2.6) and, as a consequence of equations (2.7) and (2.11), by the properties of probability measures. For all states s , $E_s(a)$ is a real number with

$$0 \leq E_s(a) \leq 1 \quad (2.12)$$

and it is

$$E_s(a(\emptyset)) = 0 \text{ and } E_s(a(\Omega_A)) = 1 \quad (2.13)$$

A third property, the additivity of expectation values, which is connected with the σ -additivity of probability measures, is stated below in paragraph **G**.

We now describe the properties of the set \mathcal{P}_A in the paragraphs **A** to **H** and summarise them in section 2.4.1.

A A *partial ordering* in \mathcal{P}_A (see appendix C) is given by the definition³ [7, p. 64]

$$a \leq b \text{ if and only if } E_s(a) \leq E_s(b) \text{ for all states } s \quad (2.14)$$

The relation $a < b$ means $a \leq b$ and $a \neq b$.

The projection system \mathcal{P}_A is *bounded i.e.* there is exactly one least and one greatest projection in \mathcal{P}_A , denoted by 0 and I , for which the inequalities

$$0 \equiv a(\emptyset) \leq a \leq a(\Omega_A) \equiv I \quad (2.15)$$

are fulfilled for all projections $a \in \mathcal{P}_A$. Note that $E_s(a(\sigma)) = 0$ for all states s if σ is contained in the complement Ω'_A of the spectrum Ω_A of A . The map $\sigma \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow a(\sigma)$ is, therefore, not necessarily one to one. It is, infact,

$$a(\sigma) = a(\sigma \cap \Omega_A) \quad (2.16)$$

for all real Borel sets σ . For a proof, remember that the projection $a(\sigma)$ is, as any observable, determined by the set of its probability distributions for all states s , therefore, by the set of its expectation values for all states. Now $\sigma = \sigma \cap \mathbb{R} = \sigma \cap (\Omega_A \cup \Omega'_A) = (\sigma \cap \Omega_A) \cup (\sigma \cap \Omega'_A)$ and $(\sigma \cap \Omega_A) \cap (\sigma \cap \Omega'_A) = \sigma \cap (\Omega_A \cap \Omega'_A) = \sigma \cap \emptyset = \emptyset$. The expectation value $E_s(a(\sigma))$ is a probability measure on the Borel field $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ according to equation (2.7). Therefore, $E_s(a(\sigma)) = E_s(a(\sigma \cap \Omega_A)) + E_s(a(\sigma \cap \Omega'_A)) = E_s(a(\sigma \cap \Omega_A))$ because $\sigma \cap \Omega'_A \subseteq \Omega'_A$ implies $0 \leq E_s(a(\sigma \cap \Omega'_A)) \leq E_s(a(\Omega'_A)) = 0$.

Theorem 2.1 *It is*

$$a(\sigma_1) \leq a(\sigma_2) \text{ if and only if } \sigma_1 \cap \Omega_A \subseteq \sigma_2 \cap \Omega_A \quad (2.17)$$

for real Borel sets σ_1 and σ_2 .

Proof We substitute $\sigma \cap \Omega_A$ by σ in order to alleviate terms. Consider $\sigma_1 \subseteq \sigma_2$, which is equivalent to $\sigma_2 = \sigma_1 \cup (\sigma_2 \cap \sigma_1')$. Clearly, it is $\sigma_1 \cap (\sigma_2 \cap \sigma_1') = \emptyset$. Hence, $\chi_{\sigma_2}(A) = \chi_{\sigma_1}(A) + \chi_{\sigma_2 \cap \sigma_1'}(A)$ implying $E_s(a(\sigma_2)) = E_s(a(\sigma_1)) + E_s(a(\sigma_2 \cap \sigma_1')) \geq E_s(a(\sigma_1))$ for all states s .

To prove the converse, note that $E_s(a(\sigma_1)) \leq E_s(a(\sigma_2))$ is equivalent to $\int (\chi_{\sigma_2}(\xi) - \chi_{\sigma_1}(\xi)) dF_{A,s}(\xi) \geq 0$. The observable $\chi_{\sigma_2}(A) - \chi_{\sigma_1}(A)$ is discrete with values 1, 0, -1. It is $\chi_{\sigma_2}(A) - \chi_{\sigma_1}(A) = \chi_{\sigma_+}(A) - \chi_{\sigma_-}(A)$ with $\sigma_+ = \sigma_2 \cap \sigma_1'$ and $\sigma_- = \sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2'$. Furthermore, it is $\sigma_+ \cap \sigma_- = \emptyset$ or $\sigma_+ \subseteq \sigma_-'$, which implies, for all states s , that $E_s(a(\sigma_+)) \leq 1 - E_s(a(\sigma_-))$ as shown in the first part of the proof, and that

$$0 \leq E_s(a(\sigma_2)) - E_s(a(\sigma_1)) = E_s(a(\sigma_+)) - E_s(a(\sigma_-)) \leq 1 - 2E_s(a(\sigma_-))$$

³The definition of the relationship $a \leq b$ given by Piron and Jauch (see section 1.1) can be formulated in our terminology as follows: "It is $E_s(b) = 1$ for every state s with $E_s(a) = 1$." Definition (2.14) implies the condition of Piron and Jauch, but the latter covers only a very particular case.

If σ_- is not empty, then this inequality is violated for some state because there exists then a point ω in σ_- , an atom p_ω in $a(\sigma_-)$ and a state s_ω such that $1 = E_{s_\omega}(p_\omega) \leq E_{s_\omega}(a(\sigma_-)) \leq 1$ as shown in section 2.5. Hence, $\sigma_- = \sigma_1 \cap \sigma'_2 = \emptyset$ and

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_1 \cap (\sigma_2 \cup \sigma'_2) = (\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) \cup (\sigma_1 \cap \sigma'_2) = \sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2$$

or $\sigma_1 \subseteq \sigma_2$.

qed

An immediate consequence of the relationship (2.17) is the following equivalence

$$a(\sigma_1) = a(\sigma_2) \quad \text{if and only if} \quad \sigma_1 \cap \Omega_A = \sigma_2 \cap \Omega_A \quad (2.18)$$

The relationship (2.17) connects the order relation between projections in \mathcal{P}_A with the order relation in the Borel σ -field $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ as described in appendix C. In particular, this relationship implies that any two projections $a(\sigma_1 \cap \Omega_A)$ and $a(\sigma_2 \cap \Omega_A)$ of \mathcal{P}_A have a supremum, $a((\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2) \cap \Omega_A)$, and an infimum, $a((\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) \cap \Omega_A)$.

B The structure of \mathcal{P}_A based on partial order possesses an equivalent algebraic description with two binary operations, which are defined for all pairs of projections in \mathcal{P}_A , namely the *join*

$$a(\sigma_1 \cap \Omega_A) \vee a(\sigma_2 \cap \Omega_A) \equiv \sup(a(\sigma_1 \cap \Omega_A), a(\sigma_2 \cap \Omega_A)) = a((\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2) \cap \Omega_A) \quad (2.19)$$

and the *meet*

$$a(\sigma_1 \cap \Omega_A) \wedge a(\sigma_2 \cap \Omega_A) \equiv \inf(a(\sigma_1 \cap \Omega_A), a(\sigma_2 \cap \Omega_A)) = a((\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) \cap \Omega_A) \quad (2.20)$$

The definitions of join and meet as least upper bound, or supremum, and as greatest lower bound, or infimum, entail that

$$\begin{aligned} a \leq b & \text{ if and only if } a \vee b = b \\ a \leq b & \text{ if and only if } a \wedge b = a \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

The \leq relation can, therefore, be defined in terms of join or meet, whereas join and meet are defined in terms of the \leq relation by equations (2.19) and (2.20). It follows from equations (2.15), (2.19), (2.20) that $0 \vee a = a$, $0 \wedge a = 0$ and $a \vee I = I$, $a \wedge I = a$ for every projection a .

In view of the property ($\Sigma 3$) of the Borel σ -field $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ and of the definition (2.14) of the partial order, a more general definition of join and meet is appropriate. Let $\Phi = \{a_i : i \in \mathbb{I}\}$, where \mathbb{I} denotes a finite or countably infinite index set, be a set of projections in \mathcal{P}_A . The join of all projections in Φ , $\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i$, is then defined as its supremum with the two properties

- (i) For every projection a in Φ , it is $a \leq \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i$.
- (ii) If b is a projection in \mathcal{P}_A such that $a_i \leq b$ for all a_i , then $\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i \leq b$.

The meet of all projection in Φ , $\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i$, is defined accordingly as infimum. With these definitions, the projection system \mathcal{P}_A becomes a *lattice*⁴. Note that the expectation value $E_s(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i)$ is, in general, *not* a function of the $\{E_s(a_i)\}$ except if all pairs (a_i, a_j) , $i \neq j$, are disjoint (see paragraphs **E** and **G**).

The *absorption identities* are a further consequence of the definitions of join and meet as supremum and infimum:

⁴A comprehensive introduction into lattice theory is given by G. Grätzer [19].

- (Ab1) $a \vee (a \wedge b) = a$ for all a, b implying $a \wedge b \leq a$
 (Ab2) $a \wedge (a \vee b) = a$ for all a, b implying $a \vee b \geq a$

The cases $b = 0$ in (Ab2) and, subsequently, $b = a$ in (Ab1) show that join and meet are *idempotent*

- (Id1) $a \vee a = a$
 (Id2) $a \wedge a = a$

Join and meet are *monotone*

- (Mo1) $a \vee b \leq a \vee c$ if $b \leq c$
 (Mo2) $a \wedge b \leq a \wedge c$ if $b \leq c$
 (Mo3) $a \vee b \leq c$ if and only if $a \leq c$ and $b \leq c$
 (Mo4) $c \leq a \wedge b$ if and only if $c \leq a$ and $c \leq b$

The laws (Mo3) and (Mo4) imply that [19, p. 71]

$$a \vee (b \wedge c) \leq (a \vee b) \wedge (a \vee c) \quad (2.22)$$

$$(a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c) \leq a \wedge (b \vee c) \quad (2.23)$$

because e.g. $a \wedge b \leq a$ and $a \wedge b \leq b \leq b \vee c$.

Join and meet are, furthermore, *commutative*

- (Cm1) $a \vee b = b \vee a$
 (Cm2) $a \wedge b = b \wedge a$

and *associative*

- (As1) $(a \vee b) \vee c = a \vee (b \vee c) \equiv a \vee b \vee c$
 (As2) $(a \wedge b) \wedge c = a \wedge (b \wedge c) \equiv a \wedge b \wedge c$

So far, we have shown that the projection system \mathcal{P}_A fulfils the defining properties of a bounded lattice, namely to be a set of elements provided with a partial order subjected to the inequalities (2.15), or, equivalently, with two binary operations join and meet, which satisfy the laws of commutativity (Cm), of associativity (As), and of absorption (Ab) as axiomatic identities. The lattice \mathcal{P}_A possesses, however, additional properties.

C The Borel σ -field $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_A)$ is *distributive* according to equation (2.5) and, hence, also the set \mathcal{P}_A :

- (Di1) $a \wedge (b \vee c) = (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c)$
 (Di2) $a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge (a \vee c)$

for all projections a, b, c in \mathcal{P}_A .

D The projection system \mathcal{P}_A is *complete*. An ordered set \mathcal{L} is termed *complete* if each finite or countably infinite family of elements $\{a_i \in \mathcal{L}, i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ admits a supremum as well as a infimum in \mathcal{L} . The completeness of \mathcal{P}_A is a consequence of the completeness of the Borel σ -field:

$$\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a(\sigma_i) = a\left(\bigcap_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \sigma_i\right)$$

$$\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a(\sigma_i) = a\left(\bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \sigma_i\right)$$

E A complement a^\sim of an element a of bounded lattice is defined by the conditions

$$(Co2) \quad a \wedge a^\sim = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad a \vee a^\sim = I$$

If $a = a(\sigma \cap \Omega_A)$, then it follows from equations (2.16), (2.19), and (2.20) that $a^\sim = a(\sigma' \cap \Omega_A)$.

Lemma 2.1 *Let a, b, c be elements of a distributive lattice. If $a \wedge b = 0$, $a \wedge c = 0$, and $b \vee a = c \vee a$, then $b = c$.*

Proof Consider

$$\begin{aligned} b &= b \vee (a \wedge c) = (b \vee a) \wedge (b \vee c) \\ c &= c \vee (a \wedge b) = (c \vee a) \wedge (c \vee b) \end{aligned}$$

qed

As a consequence, an element a can have at most one complement in a distributive lattice. Now, if a^\sim is a complement of a , then, likewise, a is a complement of a^\sim . $(a^\sim)^\sim$ is also a complement of a^\sim and, therefore,

$$(Co1) \quad (a^\sim)^\sim = a$$

It is $0^\sim = 0 \vee 0^\sim = I$ and $I^\sim = I \wedge I = 0$. A further consequence of the uniqueness of the complement in a distributive lattice is

Theorem 2.2 (De Morgan's identities for distributive lattices) [19, p. 97] *In a bounded distributive lattice, if the elements a and b have complements a^\sim and b^\sim , respectively, then $a \vee b$ and $a \wedge b$ have complements $(a \vee b)^\sim$ and $(a \wedge b)^\sim$, respectively, and it is*

$$\begin{aligned} (a \vee b)^\sim &= a^\sim \wedge b^\sim \\ (a \wedge b)^\sim &= a^\sim \vee b^\sim \end{aligned}$$

Proof In order to verify the second identity, it suffices to prove that

$$\begin{aligned} (a \wedge b) \vee (a^\sim \vee b^\sim) &= I \\ (a \wedge b) \wedge (a^\sim \vee b^\sim) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

These two equations are readily checked by using the distributive identities (Di1) and (Di2):

$$\begin{aligned} (a \wedge b) \vee (a^\sim \vee b^\sim) &= (a \vee a^\sim \vee b^\sim) \wedge (b \vee a^\sim \vee b^\sim) = I \wedge I = I \\ (a \wedge b) \wedge (a^\sim \vee b^\sim) &= (a \wedge b \wedge a^\sim) \vee (a \wedge b \wedge b^\sim) = 0 \vee 0 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The first identity follows from the second by considering complements and using (Co1).

qed

It follows from equations (2.21) and from De Morgan's identities that

$$(Co3) \quad a \leq b \quad \text{implies} \quad b^\sim \leq a^\sim$$

Two projections a and b are called *disjoint*, $a \perp b$, if

$$E_s(a) + E_s(b) \leq 1 \tag{2.24}$$

for all states s [7, p. 64]. Any reasonable definition of the sum $A + B$ of two observables must fulfil the condition

$$E_s(A + B) = E_s(A) + E_s(B) \quad (2.25)$$

for all states s . However, this condition does not suffice, in general, to define the sum $A + B$ because an observable A is *not* characterised by its expectation values for all states but by its probability distributions $P_{A,s}(\cdot)$ for all states. Projections *are* defined by their expectation values, which all lie in the interval $[0, 1]$. The characterising property of two disjoint projections of a projection system is that their functional sum is again a projection: if $a(\sigma_1) \perp a(\sigma_2)$ and $\sigma_i \subseteq \Omega_A$, then $\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2 = \emptyset$ and $a(\sigma_1) + a(\sigma_2) = a(\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2)$; $\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2 = \emptyset$ is a consequence of lemma 2.2.

We have seen that every projection $a = a(\sigma \cap \Omega_A)$ in \mathcal{P}_A possesses a single complement $a^\sim = a(\sigma' \cap \Omega_A)$. However, the natural definition of the complement a' of the projection a is given by the condition

$$E_s(a') = 1 - E_s(a) \quad (2.26)$$

for all states s : this definition coincides with the fact that projections are characterised by their expectation values. Obviously, it is $a \perp a'$, and the projection a' defined by (2.26) is, therefore, an *orthogonal complement* or *orthocomplement* of a with the evident properties

- (Oc1) $(a')' = a$
- (Oc2) $a \perp a'$ and $a \vee a' = I$
- (Oc3) $a \leq b$ implies $b' \leq a'$

The existence of this orthocomplement is an intrinsic property of the set \mathcal{P}_A and needs no further justification. The notion of 'orthogonal complement' will find its explication at the end of section 7.2.3.

The following lemma is an immediate consequence of the definitions (2.24) and (2.26).

Lemma 2.2 *It is $a \perp b$ if and only if $a \leq b'$.*

According to equation (2.21), $a \leq b'$ implies $a \wedge b' = a$ and $a \wedge b = (a \wedge b') \wedge b = a \wedge (b' \wedge b) = a \wedge 0 = 0$. The relationship (2.26) defines a complement in the sense of conditions (Co1), (Co2), (Co3), too⁵.

Due to equation (2.2) and to the separation postulate S2, condition (2.26) is equivalent to the functional relationship $a' = I - a$, which means, on the level of individual measurements, that the measurement of a is also a measurement of a' with $m[a'] = 1 - m[a]$.

Theorem 2.3 (De Morgan's identities for orthocomplemented lattices) *In a complete, bounded, orthocomplemented lattice, it is*

$$\begin{aligned} (a \vee b)' &= a' \wedge b' \\ (a \wedge b)' &= a' \vee b' \end{aligned}$$

Proof These identities are an immediate consequence of (Oc3) and of the characterisations of join and meet as least upper bound and greatest lower bound, respectively: the projection $m \equiv a \wedge b$ is determined by

⁵An orthogonal complement b of the projection a is defined by the conditions $a \perp b$ and $a \vee b = I$ in analogy to the definition (Co2) of a complement. Piron [3, p. 8] and Jauch [4, p. 76] define orthocomplementation by the set of conditions (Co1), (Co2), and (Co3) characteristic of complementation, and consider disjointness $a \perp b$ to be a derived quantity being equivalent to the condition $a \leq b'$ [3, p. 29], [4, p. 86]. The definitions (2.24) of disjointness and (2.26) of the orthocomplement fulfil this relationship. But if $a \perp b$ is *defined* by $a \leq b'$, then $a \perp a'$ is a consequence of $a \leq a = (a')'$, and every complement is then also an orthocomplement. An independent definition of disjointness, not based on complementation, is required in order to enable the distinction between complement and orthocomplement.

the conditions that $m \leq a$, $m \leq b$, and if x is a projection with $x \leq a$ and $x \leq b$, then it is $x \leq m$. By (Oc3), this is equivalent to the conditions that $a' \leq m'$, $b' \leq m'$, and if $a' \leq y$ ($\equiv x'$), $b' \leq y$, then $m' \leq y$. Therefore, $m' = a' \vee b'$. The equation $(a \vee b)' = a' \wedge b'$ is shown analogously.

qed

The relationship between complementation and orthocomplementation depends on the type of projection system considered. In a classical projection system discussed in section 2.5, a projection a corresponds to the characteristic function $\chi_{\sigma_a}(\lambda)$ of a Borel set σ_a of the phase space Λ . There is a one-to-one correspondence between these Borel sets and the projections of the classical projection system. The maximal projection I corresponds to the total phase space, the complement a' to the set complement σ'_a of σ_a in Λ . A classical projection system is distributive and the complement is given by the properties (Co1) – (Co3). Now it is

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_a \cap (\sigma_b \cup \sigma'_b) = (\sigma_a \cap \sigma_b) \cup (\sigma_a \cap \sigma'_b)$$

and $\sigma_a \cap \sigma_b = \emptyset$ implies $\sigma_a = \sigma_a \cap \sigma'_b$ and, therefore, $\sigma_a \subseteq \sigma'_b$ i.e. a complement is also an orthocomplement in a distributive lattice. We have already shown that the converse is generally true. Hence, complementation and orthocomplementation are equivalent in a distributive projection system, and the (ortho)complement a' of a projection a is unique.

In a weakly modular projection system discussed in the subsequent chapters, complementation does, in general, not imply orthocomplementation. This can be deduced from lemma 4.5 stating for a weakly modular, but not distributive projection system that, if a, b, q are projections and p is an atom (see paragraph **F**) such that $p \not\leq a$, $p \vee a = b$, $q \not\leq a$, and $q \leq b$, then (i) q is an atom (which may be different from p) and $q \vee a = b$, and (ii) the atom $r = a' \wedge b$ is the only orthocomplement of a with respect to b . For an atom p , the relationships $p \not\leq a$ and $p \wedge a = 0$ are equivalent. Therefore, the atoms p, q, r are all complements of a with respect to b . It is either $p \neq r$ or $q \neq r$ or both. Hence, complementation and orthocomplementation cannot be the same in a weakly modular projection system.

F The set \mathcal{P}_A is *atomic*. In order to state this feature, two definitions are needed. Let $a < b$ be projections. b covers a if $a \leq x \leq b$ implies either $x = a$ or $x = b$. A projection p covering 0 is called an *atom* or a *point*. The atomicity of \mathcal{P}_A means that

- (At) For any projection a in \mathcal{P}_A with $0 < a$ there is at least one atom $p \leq a$.
- (Cov) (Covering law) Let $a < I$ be a projection and $p \not\leq a$ an atom in \mathcal{P}_A . Then $p \vee a$ covers a .

For the proof of the statement (At), note that isolated real numbers are elements of the Borel σ -field $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$. The set of atoms of \mathcal{P}_A is given by all projections $a(\{\omega\})$ with the real number ω being in the spectrum Ω_A . The statement (At) follows from the fact that, for $a(\sigma) \neq 0$, σ can be chosen in Ω_A as shown in the proof of the relationship (2.17). $a(\sigma) \neq 0$ implies $\emptyset \neq \sigma \subseteq \Omega_A$ and there exists an atom $p = a(\{\omega\})$ with ω in σ .

In order to show that statement (Cov) is valid for the distributive lattice \mathcal{P}_A , consider an atom p and a projection a in \mathcal{P}_A . Then it is either $p \leq a$ or $p \leq a'$ because the relationships $0 \leq p \wedge a \leq p$ and $0 \leq p \wedge a' \leq p$ imply that $p \wedge a$ and $p \wedge a'$ are both either equal to 0 or to p . Two times 0 cannot occur because $p = p \wedge I = p \wedge (a \vee a') = (p \wedge a) \vee (p \wedge a') = 0 \vee 0 = 0$. But two times p is not possible either because it follows from $p = p \wedge a$ and $p = p \wedge a'$ that $p = p \wedge p = p \wedge a \wedge p \wedge a' = p \wedge (a \wedge a') = p \wedge 0 = 0$. Therefore, it is either $p \wedge a = 0$ and $p \wedge a' = p$, i.e. $p \leq a'$, or $p \wedge a = p$ and $p \wedge a' = 0$, i.e. $p \leq a$.

Assume now that $p \leq a'$, which implies $p = p \wedge a' = (p \vee a) \wedge a'$ because of (Di1), and consider $a \leq x \leq p \vee a$. It follows from (Mo2) that $a \wedge a' = 0 \leq x \wedge a' \leq (p \vee a) \wedge a' = p$. Because p is an atom, it is either $x \wedge a' = 0$ or $x \wedge a' = p$. Again with (Di1), one obtains

$$x = x \wedge I = x \wedge (a \vee a') = (x \wedge a) \vee (x \wedge a') = a \vee (x \wedge a')$$

because $a \leq x$, and it is, therefore, either $x = a$ or $x = p \vee a$ i.e. $p \vee a$ covers a . That the statement (Cov) is valid in the projection system \mathcal{P}_A depends on its distributivity in an essential manner.

Theorem 2.4 *Every projection a in \mathcal{P}_A is the join of all atoms p below a*

$$a = \bigvee_{p \leq a} p \quad (2.27)$$

and all pairs $p \neq q$ of atoms below the projection a are mutually disjoint.

Proof The second statement of the theorem is a consequence of the definition of atoms and of the order relations $0 \leq p \wedge q \leq p$ and $0 \leq p \wedge q \leq q$, which implies that either $p = q$ or $p \wedge q = 0$. The equation $p \wedge q = 0$ entails that $p \leq q'$ in a distributive lattice.

To prove the first statement, note that the alternative, $p \leq a$ or $p \leq a'$ is valid in the distributive projection system \mathcal{P}_A as shown above. It follows from the completeness of \mathcal{P}_A that the projection $b \equiv \bigvee_{p \leq a} p$ exists and from monotony that $b \leq a$. To show equality, note that

$$a = a \wedge I = a \wedge (b \vee b') = (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge b') = b \vee (a \wedge b')$$

If the projection $a \wedge b' \neq 0$, then it is below a and not below b , and it contains at least one atom according to (At). But this contradicts the hypothesis that b contains *all* atoms of a . Therefore, $a \wedge b' = 0$ and $a = b$.

qed

G The projection system \mathcal{P}_A is *additive*: let $\{a(\sigma_i) : i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ denote a set of pairwise disjoint projections, $a(\sigma_i) \perp a(\sigma_j)$ for $i \neq j$, where the index set \mathbb{I} is either finite or countably infinite. Then

$$(Ad) \quad 0 \leq E_s\left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i\right) = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} E_s(a_i) \leq 1$$

for all states s i.e. $a \equiv \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i$ is a projection and $a(\sigma) = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a(\sigma_i)$ with $\sigma = \bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \sigma_i$. Property (Ad) corresponds to the σ -additivity (K3) of probability measures (see appendix C). The statement (Ad) is Mackey's Axiom V [7, p. 65]. It is appropriate in our context to consider also continuous index sets. The sums must then be replaced by Stieltjes integrals.

The additivity of \mathcal{P}_A is closely related to the continuity property

$$(Con) \quad \text{If } b_1 \geq \dots \geq b_n \dots \text{ is a sequence of projections in the projection system } \mathcal{P}_B \\ \text{of an observable } B \text{ such that } \bigwedge_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n = 0, \text{ then } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_s(b_n) = 0 \text{ for any state } s.$$

as is shown by the following

Theorem 2.5 [20, p. 46] *(i) The property (Ad) for a countably infinite set of projections in the projection system \mathcal{P}_B of an observable B implies the continuity property (Con).*

(ii) The statement (Con) and the statement (Ad) for finite sets of projections imply the validity of the statement (Ad) for countably infinite sets of projections.

Proof (i) Consider the probability space $(\Omega_B, \mathcal{B}(\Omega_B), P_{B,s})$ and an infinite sequence of projections $\{b_n\}$ in \mathcal{P}_B with $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_n \geq \dots$ and $\bigwedge_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n = 0$. It is

$$b_n = \bigvee_{k=n}^N (b_k \wedge b'_{k+1}) \vee \left(\bigwedge_{k=n+1}^{N+1} b_k \right)$$

for all $N \geq n$ because $(b_n \wedge b'_{n+1}) \vee (b_{n+i} \wedge b'_{n+i+1}) = b_n \wedge b'_{n+i+1}$ for all natural numbers i , which implies that $\bigvee_{k=n}^N (b_k \wedge b'_{k+1}) = b_n \wedge b'_{N+1}$. It is, furthermore, $b_{N+1} = \bigwedge_{k=n+1}^{N+1} b_k = \bigwedge_{k=1}^{N+1} b_k$ and, therefore,

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \bigwedge_{k=n+1}^N b_k = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \bigwedge_{k=1}^N b_k = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad b_n = \bigvee_{k=n}^{\infty} (b_k \wedge b'_{k+1})$$

The terms $b_k \wedge b'_{k+1}$ are all pairwise disjoint, *i.e.* it is $(b_j \wedge b'_{j+1}) \wedge (b_k \wedge b'_{k+1}) = 0$ for $j \neq k$ in the distributive lattice \mathcal{P}_B , and it follows with the additivity property (Ad) that

$$E_s(b_n) = \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} E_s(b_k \wedge b'_{k+1})$$

But this is the rest of the convergent sum

$$E_s(b_1) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} E_s(b_k \wedge b'_{k+1})$$

which implies that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_s(b_n) = 0$.

(ii) Consider the countably infinite set $\{a_i\}$ of pairwise disjoint projections in \mathcal{P}_B and define

$$b_n \equiv \bigvee_{k=n}^{\infty} a_k$$

Clearly $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_n \geq \dots$. Any atom $p \leq b_1$ is exactly below one of the pairwise disjoint projections a_k , $p \leq a_j$ say. But then $p \not\leq a_{j+n}$ and, therefore, $p \not\leq b_{j+n}$ for all n in \mathbb{N} , which implies that $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \bigwedge_{k=1}^N b_k = 0$. It is $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} a_i = \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i \vee b_n$ and $b_n \perp \bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i$ because $b_n \perp a_i$ is equivalent to $b_n \leq a'_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, n-1$, and, therefore,

$$b_n \leq \bigwedge_{i=1}^{n-1} a'_i = \left(\bigvee_{i=1}^{n-1} a_i \right)'$$

by the monotony property (Mo4). Hence, according to finite additivity,

$$E_s \left(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} a_i \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} E_s(a_i) + E_s(b_n)$$

for an arbitrary natural number n . But $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_s(b_n) = 0$ by the continuity property (Con).

qed

H The distributive projection system \mathcal{P}_A is *separable* *i.e.* it contains a countable set \mathcal{D} such that the smallest sublattice of \mathcal{P}_A containing \mathcal{D} is \mathcal{P}_A itself. \mathcal{D} is said to *generate* \mathcal{P}_A . These definitions accord with those given in appendix C: the separability of \mathcal{P}_A is a consequence of the separability of the Borel σ -field $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$: if $\{\sigma_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a generating set of $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$, then $\{a(\sigma_n \cap \Omega_A) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a generating set of \mathcal{P}_A .

The functional relationship $B = f(A)$ between two observables A and B is defined for Borel functions $f(\cdot)$ and given by the equation $\mathcal{P}_{B,s}(\sigma) = \mathcal{P}_{A,s}(f^{-1}(\sigma))$ between probability measures or by the equation $b(\sigma) = a(f^{-1}(\sigma))$ between the projections of the projection systems \mathcal{P}_B and \mathcal{P}_A because of the definition (2.11) and of $\chi_{\sigma}(f(\xi)) = \chi_{f^{-1}(\sigma)}(\xi)$. This readily entails the inclusion $\mathcal{P}_B \subseteq \mathcal{P}_A$. The converse is also true as shown by a theorem due to V. S. Varadarajan:

Theorem 2.6 [21, p. 205] *If the (separable) projection systems of the observables A and B fulfil $\mathcal{P}_B \subseteq \mathcal{P}_A$, then there exists a real Borel function f defined on the spectrum Ω_A of A such that $B = f(A)$.*

Proof The map $\sigma \in \mathcal{B}(\Omega_A) \rightarrow a(\sigma) \in \mathcal{P}_A$ is one-to-one according to the equivalence (2.18). The proof of the theorem consists in the construction of the function f^{-1} and from that of the function f which fulfils the equation $B = f(A)$. It suffices to define f^{-1} on a generating set of the separable Borel σ -field $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_B)$, for which we choose $\{(-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$, r_1, r_2, \dots being an enumeration of the rational numbers for which $(-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B \neq \emptyset$. This implies $\bigcup_n ((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B) = \Omega_B$. Let b_n denote the projection $b_n \equiv b((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B)$ in \mathcal{P}_B . If $r_m < r_n$, then it is $b_m \leq b_n$ according to theorem 2.1.

For each projection b_n , there exists exactly one set σ_n in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_A)$ such that $b_n = a(\sigma_n)$ according to the hypothesis of the theorem and the above remarks. The sequence $\{\sigma_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ possesses the properties

1. $a(\sigma_n) = b_n, \sigma_n \in \mathcal{B}(\Omega_A)$
2. $\sigma_m \subseteq \sigma_n$ if $r_m < r_n$
3. $a(\bigcup_n \sigma_n) = b(\Omega_B) = I$

Property 2 is a consequence of theorem 2.1. Obvious generalisations of Eqns. (2.19) and (2.20) imply

$$a(\bigcup_n \sigma_n) = \bigvee_n a(\sigma_n) = \bigvee_n b_n = \bigvee_n b((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B) = b(\bigcup_n ((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B)) = b(\Omega_B) = I$$

which verifies property 3. The equation $a(\bigcup_n \sigma_n) = I$ indicates, in addition, that $\bigcup_n \sigma_n = \Omega_A$.

The function f with

$$f^{-1}((-\infty, \xi) \cap \Omega_B) = \bigcup_{\{n: r_n < \xi\}} \sigma_n$$

is a Borel function because a countable union of Borel sets σ_n is a Borel set. For any number ξ in Ω_B , it is

$$\begin{aligned} a(f^{-1}((-\infty, \xi) \cap \Omega_B)) &= a(\bigcup_{\{n: r_n < \xi\}} \sigma_n) = \bigvee_{\{n: r_n < \xi\}} a(\sigma_n) \\ &= \bigvee_{\{n: r_n < \xi\}} b((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B) = b(\bigcup_{\{n: r_n < \xi\}} ((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B)) = b((-\infty, \xi) \cap \Omega_B) \end{aligned}$$

The relationship $b(\sigma) = a(f^{-1}(\sigma))$ is valid for the elements of the generating set $\{(-\infty, \xi) \cap \Omega_B : \xi \in \mathbb{R}\}$ of $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_B)$ and, hence, for arbitrary Borel sets in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_B)$.

As for the expression of the function f , note, first, that its domain D_f is equal to $\bigcup_n \sigma_n = \Omega_A$, which is the range of f^{-1} . It follows from the above definitions that

$$a(\sigma_n) = b_n = b((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B) = a(f^{-1}((-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B))$$

which implies $f(\sigma_n) = (-\infty, r_n] \cap \Omega_B$ according to the equivalence (2.18) and because $f f^{-1}$ is the identity map on the domain $\mathcal{D}_{f^{-1}} = \Omega_B$ of f^{-1} . For any number ω in Ω_A , it is, therefore, $f(\omega) \leq r_n$ for every index n with the property that ω lies in σ_n . Hence, we have

$$f(\omega) = \inf\{r_n : \omega \in \sigma_n\}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

qed

2.4.1 Summary

To summarise: \mathcal{P}_A is a lattice *i.e.* a set of elements provided with a partial order defined by the properties (O) in appendix C or, equivalently, provided with two binary operations *join*, equation (2.19), and *meet*, equation (2.20), which are commutative (Cm), associative (As) and fulfil the absorption identities (Ab). This lattice is, furthermore, *bounded*, equation (2.15), *distributive* (Di), *orthocomplemented* (Oc) and, therefore, *complemented* (Co), *complete*, paragraphe **D**, *atomic* (At) and (Cov), *additive* (Ad), and *separable*, paragraphe **H**. There is only *one* orthocomplement a' of the projection a . A bounded, orthocomplemented, complete, atomic, additive, and separable lattice is termed a *projection system*. A *classical* projection system is, in addition, distributive.

2.5 Projection systems of classical theories

The classical projection system \mathcal{P}_A shall now be characterised in more detail. For this purpose, we define an atom $a(\{\omega\})$ as a limit of non-atomic projections: the atom $p_\omega \equiv a(\{\omega\})$ associated with the point ω of the spectrum Ω_A is defined by

$$p_\omega = \lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} \chi_{[\omega-\epsilon, \omega]}(A) \quad (2.28)$$

The expectation value of p_ω in the state s is then, according to equation (2.2),

$$\begin{aligned} E_s(p_\omega) &= \lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \chi_{[\omega-\epsilon, \omega]}(\xi) dF_{A,s}(\xi) = \lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} \int_{\omega-\epsilon}^{\omega} dF_{A,s}(\xi) \\ &= \lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} (F_{A,s}(\omega) - F_{A,s}(\omega - \epsilon)) = \lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} P_{A,s}((\omega - \epsilon, \omega]) \end{aligned}$$

The state s_ω with the distribution function

$$F_{A,s_\omega}(\xi) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } \xi < \omega \\ 1 & \text{for } \xi \geq \omega \end{cases}$$

may be termed *the atomic state associated with the point ω in Ω_A* . It possesses the following properties

$$E_{s_\omega}(p_{\omega'}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \omega' = \omega \\ 0 & \text{if } \omega' \neq \omega \end{cases}$$

and

$$E_{s_\omega}(f(A)) = f(\omega), \quad \text{Var}_{s_\omega}(f(A)) = 0$$

Consequently, equation (2.2) yields

$$E_s(f(A)) = \int E_{s_\xi}(f(A)) dF_{A,s}(\xi) \quad (2.29)$$

If ω is a point of the Borel set σ in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_A)$, then $E_{s_\omega}(a(\sigma)) = 1$ because $p_\omega \leq a(\sigma)$ implies

$$1 = E_{s_\omega}(p_\omega) \leq E_{s_\omega}(a(\sigma)) \leq 1$$

For a projection $a(\sigma)$ and because of the identity $E_s(a(\sigma)) = P_{A,s}(\sigma)$, equation (2.29) becomes

$$P_{A,s}(\sigma) = \int P_{A,s_\xi}(\sigma) dF_{A,s}(\xi)$$

for all Borel sets σ in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega_A)$. Hence, every state s is a convex linear combination of atomic states s_ω . There is a one-to-one correspondence between the points ω of the spectrum Ω_A , the atoms p_ω , and the atomic states s_ω . The observables $f(A)$ form a commutative algebra.

A *classical theory* is slight generalisation of the above structure. The set of elementary events, the *phase space* Λ , is a separable measure space, *e.g.* $\Lambda \subseteq \mathbb{R}^N$ for some number N in \mathbb{N} . A state s corresponds to a probability measure μ_s on Λ which makes Λ a probability space $(\Lambda, \mathcal{B}(\Lambda), \mu_s)$ for each state. The probability measure of an *atomic state* is concentrated onto one point λ of the phase space. An observable A is represented by a measurable, real function \tilde{A} on the phase space Λ , and its expectation value in the state s is given by

$$E_s(A) = \int_{\Lambda} \tilde{A}(\lambda) d\mu_s(\lambda) \quad (2.30)$$

The projection $a(\sigma)$ in \mathcal{P}_A is represented by the characteristic function

$$\chi_\sigma(\tilde{A}(\lambda)) = \chi_{\tilde{A}^{-1}(\sigma)}(\lambda) \quad (2.31)$$

or, equivalently, by the set $\tilde{A}^{-1}(\sigma) \subseteq \mathcal{B}(\Lambda)$. In particular, the equation

$$P_{A,s}(\sigma) = E_s(\chi_\sigma(A)) = \int_{\Lambda} \chi_{\tilde{A}^{-1}(\sigma)}(\lambda) d\mu_s(\lambda) \quad (2.32)$$

gives the probability distribution of the observable A in a classical theory. The equations (2.1), (2.30), (2.31), and (2.32) are consistent if the observable $f(A)$ is classically represented by $f(\tilde{A})$:

$$\mathcal{P}_{f(A),s}(\sigma) = E_s(\chi_\sigma(f(A))) = \int_{\Lambda} \chi_{(f(\tilde{A}))^{-1}(\sigma)}(\lambda) d\mu_s(\lambda) = \int_{\Lambda} \chi_{\tilde{A}^{-1}(f^{-1}(\sigma))}(\lambda) d\mu_s(\lambda) = P_{A,s}(f^{-1}(\sigma)) \quad (2.33)$$

The atom p_λ of the classical projection system may be defined in analogy to equation (2.28) as the limit of projections $\chi_{\Delta_n}(\cdot)$ where the sets $\Delta_n \subseteq \Lambda$ all contain the point λ , $\Delta_{n+1} \subset \Delta_n$, and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Delta_n = \{\lambda\}$.

It is reasonable to assume that any subset of the phase space Λ represents some projection of the classical theory and any measurable, real function on Λ represents some observable. This ensures that the set of all projections of a classical theory is a complete, distributive lattice. It is equally reasonable to assume that every probability measure on the phase space corresponds to a state. Both requirements are regularity conditions, without which a mathematical analysis is hardly possible.

The projection system of a classical theory possesses the same features as the projection system of an observable. A general state is a convex linear combination of atomic states. There exists a one-to-one correspondence between the points of the phase space, the atoms of the projection system, and the atomic states. The projection system is distributive. The observables form a commutative algebra. The proposition system \mathcal{P}_A of an observable A differs from the proposition system of a classical theory only in that the atoms of the former are parametrised by real numbers: its phase space is equal to the spectrum $\Omega_A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$.

Chapter 3

The projection system of a physical system

The *system of projections of a physical system*, \mathcal{P}_{PhS} , is generated by the set-union of the atoms of the projection systems \mathcal{P}_A of all observables A of this physical system. The definitions of the order relation (2.14), of the orthocomplement (2.26), and of the disjointness of projections (2.24) equally apply to \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . Equivalent projections are identified according to the separation postulate S2. The projection systems \mathcal{P}_A of observables are distributive and separable sublattices of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . \mathcal{P}_{PhS} contains, therefore, the projections 0 and I common to all projection systems \mathcal{P}_A , which implies that the operations join and meet are defined between arbitrary projections of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . Consequently, it is a bounded, complete, and orthocomplemented lattice.

In the present chapter, the entire characterisation of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is given: it is a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, weakly modular, separable, atomic, and additive lattice. This structure constitutes the axiomatic basis of the subsequent analysis in chapters 4 – 7.

3.1 Compatible projections and observables

The projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} cannot be distributive because it must also describe quantum systems, but it contains distributive subsystems, the projection systems of its observables. A set of projections contained in the projection system \mathcal{P}_A of some observable A is, therefore, distinguished from an arbitrary set of projections of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} by the property that it generates a distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} .

In order to grasp this issue more precisely, we introduce some definitions [4, p. 80]. Bounded, complete, and orthocomplemented lattices \mathcal{L} are considered. A subset of such a lattice is a *sublattice* if it is closed with respect to the lattice operations of \mathcal{L} i.e. \leq , \vee , \wedge , and orthocomplementation. If $\{\mathcal{L}_i : i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ is a family of sublattices of \mathcal{L} , then the intersection $\bigcap_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathcal{L}_i$ is also a sublattice of \mathcal{L} . Let now \mathcal{S} be any subset of \mathcal{L} and denote by $\{\mathcal{L}_i^{\mathcal{S}} : i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ the family of sublattices of \mathcal{L} that contain \mathcal{S} . The lattice $\mathcal{L}^{\mathcal{S}} = \bigcap_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathcal{L}_i^{\mathcal{S}}$ is the smallest lattice which contains \mathcal{S} , the *lattice generated by \mathcal{S}* .

The subset \mathcal{S} of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is a *compatible set of projections* if the lattice generated by \mathcal{S} is a distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . In particular, *two projections a and b are compatible*, $a \leftrightarrow b$, if the lattice generated by the four projections a , a' , b , and b' is distributive [3, p. 25]. *Two observables A and B are compatible*, $A \leftrightarrow B$, if the set $\mathcal{P}_A \cup \mathcal{P}_B$ is a compatible subset of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . It is obvious that $a \leftrightarrow b$ and $a \leftrightarrow b'$ are equivalent. Compatibility is not transitive: $a \leftrightarrow b$ and $b \leftrightarrow c$ do not necessarily imply that $a \leftrightarrow c$. An observable A is compatible with the Borel function $f(A)$ and it is $f(A) \leftrightarrow g(A)$ because $\mathcal{P}_{f(A)} \subseteq \mathcal{P}_A$ as shown in paragraph **H** of chapter 2, and the lattice generated by the subset $\mathcal{P}_{f(A)} \cup \mathcal{P}_{g(A)}$ of \mathcal{P}_A is a distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P}_A and, hence, of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} .

The most simple, non trivial projection system consists of the four elements $\{0, a, a', I\}$, a a projection,

The adequacy of the separability postulate is emphasised by the fact that it entails a remarkable generalisation of a theorem of von Neumann [22] on commuting families of selfadjoint, bounded operators in quantum mechanics to families of compatible observables in a separable projection system.

Theorem 3.2 [21, p. 206] *Let $\{A_i: i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ be a family of observables in a separable projection system \mathcal{P} . Then there exists an observable A and a family of Borel functions f_i such that $A_i = f_i(A)$ if and only if the observables A_i are mutually compatible, $A_i \leftrightarrow A_j$ for all $i, j \in \mathbb{I}$.*

Proof Assume that there is an observable A and a family $\{f_i: i \in \mathbb{I}\}$ of Borel functions and $A_i = f_i(A)$ for all $i \in \mathbb{I}$. It is shown in section 3.1 that then $A_i \leftrightarrow A_j$ for all $i, j \in \mathbb{I}$. Conversely, let \mathcal{L} be the distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P} generated by the projection systems \mathcal{P}_{A_i} with $A_i \leftrightarrow A_j$ for all $i, j \in \mathbb{I}$. The separability of \mathcal{P} implies the separability of \mathcal{L} . By theorem 3.1, there is an observable A such that $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{P}_A$. Clearly $\mathcal{P}_{A_i} \subseteq \mathcal{P}_A$, and by theorem 2.6 there exist Borel functions f_i such $A_i = f_i(A)$. This concludes the proof.

qed

The interesting inference from this theorem is the statement that an arbitrary Borel function $F(\mathbf{A})$ is a well defined observable for any set $\mathbf{A} = (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_N)$ of compatible observables in a separable projection system, *i.e.* $P_{F(\mathbf{A}),s}(\sigma) \equiv E_s(\chi_\sigma(F((f_1(A), f_2(A), \dots, f_N(A))))))$ is defined for any Borel function $F: \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for all Borel sets σ and for all states s .

We have defined \mathcal{P}_{PhS} as the projection system generated by the union of the atomes of the projection systems of all observables of the physical system considered. Theorem 3.2 reveals that it suffices to take into account a maximal set of mutually noncompatible observables.

3.2.2 Weak modularity

It is the aim of the present study to find the link between the probabilistic structure of quantitative physical predictions and the Hilbert space structure appearing in quantum theory. The characterisation of the \mathcal{P}_{PhS} solely as a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, atomic, and separable lattice of projections clearly does not provide a structure which is sufficient for this task. On the other hand, distributivity is a too strong requirement as it excludes quantum theories. Hence, distributivity must be replaced by a weaker postulate. We follow Piron [2, p. 446], [3, p. 24] and Jauch [4, p. 86] and replace distributivity by the postulate of *weak modularity*

WM Any two projections a and b in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} with $a \leq b$ or $b \leq a$ are compatible, $a \leftrightarrow b$.

It is shown in section 3.1 that the compatibility of two projections implies that they belong to the projection system of *one* observable. The physical significance of weak modularity is, therefore, that the order relation $a \leq b$ between projections of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} occurs only between projections, which can be derived from a common observable. In a weakly modular lattice, disjoint projections $a \perp b$ are compatible as well as a and $a \vee b$ or a and $a \wedge b$. Weak modularity ensures the integrity of the projection system \mathcal{P}_A taken as distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} .

A useful algebraic characterisation of weak modularity in (ortho)complemented lattices is provided by

Theorem 3.3 [3, p. 24] *In a complemented lattice, the postulate of weak modularity, $a \leq b$ implies $a \leftrightarrow b$, is equivalent to the condition that $a \leq b$ implies $a = b \wedge (b' \vee a)$ or, equivalently, $b = a \vee (a' \wedge b)$ ¹.*

¹If $a < b$, then $a' \wedge b > 0$ and there exists an atom $p \leq a' \wedge b$ and $p \not\leq a$. This is an extension of property (At) to arbitrary pairs $a < b$. The condition that $a \leq b$ implies $b = a \vee (a' \wedge b)$ is used as the definition of weak modularity by some authors (see *e.g.* [23, p. 4]).

Proof If $a \leq b$ and $a \leftrightarrow b$, then clearly $b \wedge (b' \vee a) = a$ and $a \vee (a' \wedge b) = b$. Conversely, if $a \leq b$, then the lattice generated by a, a', b, b' consists of the eight elements $0, a, b', a' \wedge b, a', b, a \vee b', I$. A systematic check of the distributivity relation (Di1) for all combinations of three elements of this lattice reveals that the majority of these combinations already fulfils (Di1) due to the general characteristics (Mo), (Id), (Cm), (As), (Ab), (Co) of a complemented lattice excepted the cases $a = b \wedge (b' \vee a)$ and $b = a \vee (a' \wedge b)$, which must be postulated. In a complemented lattice, these two conditions are equivalent as are the distributivity laws (Di1) and (Di2).

qed

This theorem illustrates the notion of weak modularity. A lattice is called *modular* if any triplet $a \leq b$ and c of lattice elements fulfils the *modular law*

$$a \vee (c \wedge b) = (a \vee c) \wedge b \quad (3.1)$$

The two alternative and equivalent conditions in theorem 3.3 are special instances of the modular law with $c = b'$ and $c = a'$. Note, however, that modularity as well as distributivity are independent of (ortho)complementation in contrast to weak modularity.

It is shown in section 3.3 that the system of the subspaces of the quantum mechanical Hilbert space is weakly modular and even modular if the Hilbert space is finite dimensional, theorem 3.7.

The next theorem is due to G. Rose [24] and provides equivalent algebraic characterisations of weak modularity.

Theorem 3.4 *The following three statements are equivalent in a bounded, complete, and orthocomplemented projection system \mathcal{P} :*

- (i) *Let a and b be projections in \mathcal{P} . If $a \leq b$, then $b = a \vee (a' \wedge b)$ or, equivalently, $a = b \wedge (b' \vee a)$ i.e. \mathcal{P} is weakly modular.*
- (ii) *Let a, b, c be projections in \mathcal{P} . The conditions $a \vee b = a \vee c$, $a \perp b$, and $a \perp c$ imply $b = c$.*
- (iii) *There is exactly one orthocomplement to any projection a in \mathcal{P} i.e. if a' is the orthocomplement of a defined by equation (2.26) and if c is a projection in \mathcal{P} with $a \perp c$ and $a \vee c = I$, then $c = a'$.*

Proof

(i) implies (ii). The conditions $a \perp b$ and $a \perp c$ are equivalent to $b \leq a'$ and $c \leq a'$, lemma 2.2, which implies by (i) that

$$\begin{aligned} b &= a' \wedge (a \vee b) \\ c &= a' \wedge (a \vee c) \end{aligned}$$

and it is $b = c$ because $a \vee b = a \vee c$ by hypothesis.

(ii) implies (iii). Let c be an orthocomplement of a . According to the definition of an orthocomplement, it is $a \perp c$, $a \perp a'$, $a \vee c = a \vee a' = I$. Therefore $c = a'$.

(iii) implies (i). The orthocomplement a' of a defined by equation (2.26) fulfils the conditions (Oc1) – (Oc3) and De Morgan's identities, theorem 2.3. Consider now $a \leq b$ and define $c \equiv a \vee (b \wedge a')$. Then

$$b \vee c = b \vee a \vee (b \wedge a') = b \vee (b \wedge a') = b$$

because of the absorption law (Ab1). Hence, $c \leq b$ or $b' \leq c'$ i.e. $b' \perp c$. In addition, $c' \perp c$ and

$$b' \vee c = (b' \vee a) \vee (b \wedge a') = (b \wedge a')' \vee (b \wedge a') = I = c' \vee c$$

It follows from statement (ii) that $b' = c'$, and, therefore, $b = c = a \vee (a' \wedge b)$.

qed

It is $a' \wedge b \leq a'$ or $a \perp (a' \wedge b)$ according to lemma 2.2. If $a \leq b$, then the formula $b = a \vee (a' \wedge b)$ of theorem 3.3 provides a decomposition of the form $b = a \vee c$ with $a \perp c$. The statement (ii) of theorem 3.4 shows that this decomposition is unique in a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, weakly modular lattice.

More importantly, theorem 3.4 states that the weak modularity of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is equivalent to the condition that every projection a in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} possesses only one orthocomplement:

Corollary 3.1 *The projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is weakly modular if and only if the orthocomplement a' of a projection a in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} , given by $E_s(a') = 1 - E_s(a)$ for all states s , is the single orthocomplement of a : if a and c are projections in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} and if $c \leq a'$ and $c \vee a = I$, then $c = a'$.*

We remark that the system of the five projections $\{0, a, c, a', I\}$ subjected to the six conditions $a \vee a' = I$, $a \wedge a' = 0$, $c \vee a' = a'$, $c \wedge a' = c$, $c \vee a = I$, $c \wedge a = 0$ is distributive if and only if $c = a'$. This shows again that an orthocomplement $c \neq a'$ of a cannot be part of the projection system \mathcal{P}_A containing a . The existence of a complement c of a which is not in the projection system \mathcal{P}_A appears as an alien element. In addition, the condition imposed by the corollary is fulfilled if a' is an atom because $0 < c \leq a'$ implies then that $c = a'$. But I see no way to generally prove that $c \leq a'$ and $c \vee a = I$ implies $c = a'$ in a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, separable, atomic, but not distributive lattice. Hence, it seems necessary and it is reasonable to maintain the postulate of weak modularity, but to replace it by the equivalent and more descriptive regularity postulate that a' is the unique orthocomplement of *any* projection a in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} :

SOC The orthocomplement a' of the projection a given by $E_s(a') = 1 - E_s(a)$ for all states s is the single orthocomplement of a i.e. if a and c are projections in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} and if $c \leq a'$ and $c \vee a = I$, then $c = a'$.

3.2.3 Atomicity

The projection system \mathcal{P}_A is atomic. The projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is generated by the set-union of all atoms of the projection systems \mathcal{P}_A of the observables of the physical system considered i.e. every projection $a \neq 0$ in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is part of the projection system \mathcal{P}_A of some observable A and, hence, the join of a nonempty set of atoms of \mathcal{P}_A . This entails that the condition (At) of atomicity is valid also for \mathcal{P}_{PhS} .

The covering law (Cov) is valid in *modular* and hence also in *distributive* projection systems as a consequence of the defining property of atoms, $0 \leq x \leq p$ implies $x = 0$ or $x = p$: assume $p \not\leq a$ and $a \leq x \leq a \vee p$, which entails $x = (a \vee p) \wedge x$ by equation (2.21), and $0 = a \wedge p \leq x \wedge p \leq (a \vee p) \wedge p = p$ by monotony and absorption. It is, therefore, either $x \wedge p = 0$ or $x \wedge p = p$ and $x = (a \vee p) \wedge x = a \vee (x \wedge p)$ by modularity, equation (3.1), which implies that either $x = a$ or $x = a \vee p$. Hence, $a \vee p$ covers a .

In contrast, the covering law must be *postulated* for the weakly modular projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} :

COV Let $a < I$ be a projection and $p \not\leq a$ an atom in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . Then $p \vee a$ covers a , i.e. $a \leq x \leq p \vee a$ implies either $x = a$ or $x = p \vee a$.

It can be shown that this postulate is valid for quantum mechanical projection systems, see section 3.3. However, the vector space structure of the underlying Hilbert space is indispensable for the proof.

There is a useful equivalence to the covering law in a weakly modular lattice:

Theorem 3.5 *Let a be a projection and p be an atom with $p \not\leq a$ in a weakly modular and orthocomplemented lattice. Then the covering law is valid if and only if $(p \vee a) \wedge a'$ is an atom.*

Proof Assume the covering law and let $p \not\leq a$ be an atom. Consider $0 \leq x \leq (p \vee a) \wedge a'$, which implies $x \leq a'$ and $x \leq p \vee a$. The relation $x \leq a'$ entails $x = (x \vee a) \wedge a'$ due to theorem 3.3. The relation $x \leq p \vee a$ implies $a \leq x \vee a \leq p \vee a$ by monotony (Mo1) and with the covering law that either $x \vee a = a$, i.e. $x \leq a$ or $x \vee a = p \vee a$. The first alternative implies $x = 0$ because it is also $x \leq a'$. The second alternative yields $x = (p \vee a) \wedge a'$. Hence, $(p \vee a) \wedge a'$ is an atom.

To show the converse, consider $a \leq x \leq p \vee a$, which entails, by monotony, $0 \leq x \wedge a' \leq (p \vee a) \wedge a' \equiv q$, an atom by hypothesis. Hence, it is either $x \wedge a' = 0$ or $x \wedge a' = q$. It follows from $a \leq x$ and from theorem 3.3 that $x = a \vee (x \wedge a')$, and it is either $x = a$ or $x = a \vee q = a \vee (a' \wedge (p \vee a)) = p \vee a$ as a consequence of $a \leq p \vee a$ and of weak modularity. Therefore, $p \vee a$ covers a .

qed

This theorem and, hence, the covering law is crucially needed in the proof of lemma 4.5. This lemma is, in turn, essential in order to establish the notion of the rank of a proposition in section 4.2.

In a general lattice, two atoms p and q are either equal or it is $p \wedge q = 0$. This implies that distinct compatible atoms are disjoint because $p = p \wedge (q \vee q') = (p \wedge q) \vee (p \wedge q') = p \wedge q'$ i.e. $p \leq q'$. On the other hand, disjoint atoms are compatible by weak modularity. One has, therefore, the

Theorem 3.6 *In a weakly modular lattice, two distinct atoms are compatible if and only if they are disjoint.*

3.2.4 Additivity

The projection system \mathcal{P}_{PHS} is *additive* i.e. the property (Ad) applies to a countable or countably infinite set of mutually disjoint and, hence, compatible projections in \mathcal{P}_{PHS} . With repeated application of theorem D.3, one may show that this set generates a distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P}_{PHS} , which is the proposition system of an observable according to theorem 3.1. In our context, additivity is not an independent postulate but the consequence of the postulates PSP, SEP, and SOC.

3.3 Quantum mechanical projection systems

The mathematical description of a quantum mechanical system is based upon a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} with vectors $\phi, \psi \dots$. \mathcal{H} is a closed, complex vector space with Hermitean scalar product (ϕ, ϕ) inducing the norm $\|\phi\| = \sqrt{(\phi, \phi)}$ of a vector ϕ . The dimension of \mathcal{H} may be finite or countably infinite. A *subspace* \mathcal{V} is a subset of \mathcal{H} with the properties that the vectors $\phi - \psi$ and $\gamma\phi$, γ any complex number, are in \mathcal{V} if ϕ and ψ are, and, in addition, that it is closed i.e. the limit of a Cauchy sequence of vectors in \mathcal{V} is also in \mathcal{V} .

A *projection* a is represented by a projector Q_a with $Q_a = Q_a^* = Q_a^2$, Q_a^* denoting the adjoint operator of Q_a . The projector Q_a is uniquely characterised by the subspace \mathcal{V}_a of its eigenvectors to the eigenvalue 1, $\mathcal{V}_a = \{\phi \in \mathcal{H} : Q_a\phi = \phi\}$. The projection a can, therefore, be represented equally well by \mathcal{V}_a . We assume the set of projections to be complete in the sense that any subspace of \mathcal{H} corresponds to a projection; \mathcal{H} corresponds to I . An *atom* p is represented by the projector on the one dimensional subspace $\mathcal{V}_p = \{\gamma\phi_p : \gamma \in \mathbb{C}\}$ spanned by the vector $\phi_p \neq 0$.

The *partial order* $a \leq b$ corresponds to the set theoretical inclusion $\mathcal{V}_a \subseteq \mathcal{V}_b$ or, equivalently, to the algebraic

relationship

$$Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a = Q_a \quad (3.2)$$

Orthocomplementation is given by the relationship

$$Q_{a'} = I - Q_a \quad (3.3)$$

The space $\mathcal{V}_{a'}$ is, therefore, the orthogonal complement \mathcal{V}_a^\perp of \mathcal{V}_a , *i.e.* the space of all vectors being orthogonal to all vectors in \mathcal{V}_a , $\mathcal{V}_a^\perp = \{\phi \in \mathcal{H} : (\psi, \phi) = 0, \psi \in \mathcal{V}_a\}$, and *not* the set-theoretical complement \mathcal{V}'_a defined by $\mathcal{V}_a \cap \mathcal{V}'_a = \{0\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_a \cup \mathcal{V}'_a = \mathcal{H}$.

The *meet* $Q_{a \wedge b}$ projects onto the greatest closed subspace $\mathcal{V}_{a \wedge b}$ contained in \mathcal{V}_a and in \mathcal{V}_b . $\mathcal{V}_{a \wedge b}$ is equal to $\mathcal{V}_a \cap \mathcal{V}_b$, the set-theoretical intersection, because the intersection of closed subspaces is closed. In this respect, the situation is similar to the classical case. The projector $Q_{a \wedge b}$ is represented in terms of Q_a and Q_b by the formula $Q_{a \wedge b} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (Q_a Q_b)^n$ [4, p. 38]. It is

$$Q_{a \wedge b} = Q_a Q_b \text{ if and only if } Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a \quad (3.4)$$

as a consequence of the general formula. However, the direct proof is not difficult:

$$Q_a Q_b = Q_{a \wedge b} = Q_{a \wedge b}^* = (Q_a Q_b)^* = Q_b^* Q_a^* = Q_b Q_a$$

and, conversely, $Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a$ implies that $Q \equiv Q_a Q_b$ is a projector. $Q\phi = \phi$ is possible only if $Q_a \phi = \phi$ and $Q_b \phi = \phi$ *i.e.* if $\phi \in \mathcal{V}_a \cap \mathcal{V}_b$, and it is $Q = Q_{a \wedge b}$.

The *join* $Q_{a \vee b}$ projects onto $((\mathcal{V}_a + \mathcal{V}_b)^\perp)^\perp$, which is the smallest subspace containing the linear manifold $\mathcal{V}_a + \mathcal{V}_b$ (see appendix F for a definition of the sum of vector spaces). It follows from the identity $a \vee b = (a' \wedge b')'$ that

$$Q_{a \vee b} = Q_a + Q_b - Q_a Q_b \text{ if and only if } Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a \quad (3.5)$$

The projections a and b are *compatible*

$$a \leftrightarrow b \text{ if and only if } Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a \quad (3.6)$$

Proof If $Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a$, then the relationships (3.4) and (3.5) are valid, and the projectors corresponding to the 16 elements of the lattice generated by a, b, a', b' are all linear combinations of $I, Q_a, Q_b, Q_a Q_b$ and they commute all. Distributivity is easily checked. The converse is true because the distributive lattice of the 16 elements can be considered the projection system of some observable X with spectrum $\Omega_X = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, see section 3.1, and the corresponding projectors are characteristic functions $\chi_\sigma(\hat{X})$ where \hat{X} is the operator representing the observable X . There is a one-to-one correspondence between the mentioned 16 projectors and the subsets σ of Ω_X , and the relationship $\chi_{\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2} = \chi_{\sigma_1} \chi_{\sigma_2}$ yields $Q_{a \wedge b} = Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a$.

qed

The set of the projections on the subspaces of \mathcal{H} is *irreducible* because 0 and I are the only projections that commute with all projections acting on \mathcal{H} .

The *disjointness* $a \perp b$ of two projections is expressed by the condition

$$Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

as follows from lemma 2.2 and from equations (3.2) and (3.3). Disjointness is an orthogonality condition: consider the scalar product (ϕ, ψ) with $\phi \in \mathcal{V}_a$ and $\psi \in \mathcal{V}_b$. Then it is $(\phi, \psi) = (Q_a \phi, Q_b \psi) = (\phi, Q_a Q_b \psi) = 0$.

The set of projectors on the subspaces of \mathcal{H} is, furthermore, *atomic*, the projectors on one-dimensional subspaces of \mathcal{H} being the atoms. The condition (At) is trivially true. To show (Cov), let the projection a

be represented by the closed subspace $\mathcal{V}_a \subseteq \mathcal{H}$, and a' by its orthogonal complement \mathcal{V}_a^\perp . An atom $p \not\leq a$ is represented by a one-dimensional subspace $\mathcal{V}_p \equiv \{\gamma\phi : \|\phi\| = 1, \gamma \in \mathbb{C}\}$ where ϕ can be written as $\phi = \phi_{\parallel} + \phi_{\perp}$ with $\phi_{\parallel} \in \mathcal{V}_a$ and $\phi_{\perp} \in \mathcal{V}_a^\perp$, $\phi_{\perp} \neq 0$. This decomposition is unique. The projection $p \vee a$ is represented by the sum $\mathcal{V}_{p \vee a} = \mathcal{V}_a + \{\gamma\phi_{\perp} : \gamma \in \mathbb{C}\}$, which is closed, and $(p \vee a) \wedge a'$ is represented by $\mathcal{V}_{(p \vee a) \wedge a'} = \{\gamma\phi_{\perp} : \gamma \in \mathbb{C}\}$, which is a one-dimensional subspace and, hence, represents an atom. The covering law (Cov) follows then from theorem 3.5.

The set of projectors on the subspaces of a Hilbert space is *additive* because a sum of disjoint projectors is a projector: $Q^2 = (\sum_n Q_n)^2 = \sum_n Q_n^2 + \sum_{m \neq n} Q_m Q_n = \sum_n Q_n = Q$ because $Q_m Q_n = 0$ for $m \neq n$. Hence, $0 \leq E_s(Q) = E_s(\sum_n Q_n) = \sum_n E_s(Q_n) \leq 1$ for all states s .

Therefore, the set of projectors on the subspaces of \mathcal{H} is a projection system. This projection system is *weakly modular*. Infact, if $a \leq b$, then $Q_a Q_b = Q_b Q_a = Q_a$ and one has [3, p. 42]

$$Q_{b' \vee a} = I - Q_{b \wedge a'} = I - Q_b (I - Q_a) = I - Q_b + Q_b Q_a$$

and

$$Q_{b \wedge (b' \vee a)} = Q_b (I - Q_b + Q_b Q_a) = Q_b Q_a = Q_a$$

If the Hilbert space is finite dimensional, then the lattice of subspaces is even modular:

Theorem 3.7 [2, p. 444], [4, p. 85] *The lattice of the subspaces of a Hilbert space is modular if and only if the Hilbert space is finite dimensional.*

Proof Let a, b, c with $a \leq b$ denote projections, quantum mechanically represented by the closed subspaces $\mathcal{V}_a, \mathcal{V}_b, \mathcal{V}_c$ with $\mathcal{V}_a \subseteq \mathcal{V}_b$ of a complex Hilbert space. The task consists in checking the modular identity

$$a \vee (c \wedge b) = (a \vee c) \wedge b$$

If $a \leq b$, then $a \vee (c \wedge b) \leq (a \vee c) \wedge b$ in any lattice (see equation (2.22)). To show the converse relation $(a \vee c) \wedge b \leq a \vee (c \wedge b)$ in case of a *finite dimensional Hilbert space*, note that the sum of subspaces is a subspace in this case and, therefore, $\mathcal{V}_{a \vee c} = \mathcal{V}_a + \mathcal{V}_c$. Assume now that ϕ is a vector in $(\mathcal{V}_a + \mathcal{V}_c) \cap \mathcal{V}_b$. This implies that $\phi = \phi_a + \phi_c$ with ϕ_a in \mathcal{V}_a and ϕ_c in \mathcal{V}_c , and ϕ in \mathcal{V}_b . It is ϕ_a in \mathcal{V}_b by hypothesis and, therefore, also $\phi_c = \phi - \phi_a$ in \mathcal{V}_b . Hence, ϕ_c is in $\mathcal{V}_c \cap \mathcal{V}_b$ and $\phi = (\phi_a + \phi_c)$ is in $\mathcal{V}_a + (\mathcal{V}_c \cap \mathcal{V}_b)$.

In the case of *infinite dimensional Hilbert spaces*, the direct sum of subspaces is not necessarily closed: if \mathcal{V}_a and \mathcal{V}_c are infinite dimensional subspaces, then there exist in $\mathcal{V}_{a \vee c}$ limit vectors of sequences of vectors in $\mathcal{V}_a + \mathcal{V}_c$, which are not of the form $\phi_a + \phi_c$ with ϕ_a in \mathcal{V}_a and ϕ_c in \mathcal{V}_c . Let ψ denote such a limit vector in $\mathcal{V}_{a \vee c}$. In order to find an example violating the modularity condition, we may assume, in addition, that $\mathcal{V}_a \wedge c = \mathcal{V}_a \cap \mathcal{V}_c = \{0\}$ and choose $\mathcal{V}_b = \mathcal{V}_a + \{\gamma\psi : \gamma \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Consider now the subspace $\mathcal{V}_c \cap \mathcal{V}_b$. Every vector ϕ in $\mathcal{V}_c \cap \mathcal{V}_b$ is in \mathcal{V}_c and in \mathcal{V}_b i.e. $\phi = \gamma\psi + \phi_a$ with ϕ_a in \mathcal{V}_a . Hence, $\gamma\psi = \phi - \phi_a$ with ϕ in \mathcal{V}_c . By hypothesis, this is only possible if $\gamma\psi = 0$, which implies $\phi = \phi_a = 0$ because $\mathcal{V}_a \cap \mathcal{V}_c = \{0\}$ again by hypothesis. Therefore, $\mathcal{V}_c \cap \mathcal{V}_b = \mathcal{V}_{c \wedge b} = \{0\}$ implying $c \wedge b = 0$ and

$$\mathcal{V}_{a \vee (c \wedge b)} = \mathcal{V}_a$$

Furthermore, $\mathcal{V}_a \subseteq \mathcal{V}_{a \vee c}$ and $\{\gamma\psi : \gamma \in \mathbb{C}\} \subseteq \mathcal{V}_{a \vee c}$. Therefore, $\mathcal{V}_b \subseteq \mathcal{V}_{a \vee c}$ implying $b \leq a \vee c$ and

$$\mathcal{V}_{(a \vee c) \wedge b} = \mathcal{V}_b \supset \mathcal{V}_a$$

qed

3.4 Summary

The projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is generated by the set-theoretical union of the atoms of the projection systems \mathcal{P}_A of a maximal set of mutually noncompatible observables of the physical system considered. Equivalent atoms are identified according to the separation postulate S2. The definitions of the order relation, of the orthocomplement, and of the disjointness of projections are given by (2.14), (2.26), and (2.24) in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} , too. With these definitions, \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is a bounded, complete, and orthocomplemented lattice.

In chapter 2, the properties of the projection system \mathcal{P}_A of an observable A are derived based on the postulates

PSP The formal scheme of quantitative physical theories contains two different kind of terms, namely observables and states. A theory assigns a real probability space $(\Omega_A, \mathcal{B}(\Omega_A), P_{A,s})$ to an observable A and a state s .

S1 Observables separate states. Two states s_1 and s_2 are identical, $s_1 = s_2$, if $P_{A,s_1}(\sigma) = P_{A,s_2}(\sigma)$ for all observables A and for all Borel sets σ in $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$.

S2 States separate observables. Two observables A and B are identical, $A = B$, if $P_{A,s}(\sigma) = P_{B,s}(\sigma)$ for all states s and for all Borel sets σ in $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$.

The result is that \mathcal{P}_A is a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, distributive, separable, atomic, and additive lattice. Distributivity entails that complementation and orthocomplementation are identical and that any projection a in \mathcal{P}_A possesses solely one (ortho)complement a' .

The question arises, which properties of \mathcal{P}_A stay valid in the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} and which must be replaced. Distributivity cannot be maintained because this excludes quantum mechanical projection systems. Distributivity must be replaced by a weaker condition. The following postulate is appropriate:

SOC The orthocomplement a' of the projection a given by $E_s(a') = 1 - E_s(a)$ for all states s is the single orthocomplement of a i.e. if a and c are projections in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} and if $c \leq a'$ and $c \vee a = I$, then $c = a'$.

This postulate is equivalent to the postulate that \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is *weakly modular*:

WM Any two projections a and b in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} with $a \leq b$ or $b \leq a$ are compatible, $a \leftrightarrow b$.

The *separability* of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} must be postulated as a regularity condition, which is necessary for the analysis:

SEP The projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is separable i.e. every distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is separable.

The separability of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} implies that every distributive sublattice of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is the projection system of some observable.

Finally, the covering law must be postulated in order to ensure the *atomicity* of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} .

COV Let $a < I$ be a projection and $p \not\leq a$ an atom in \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . Then $p \vee a$ covers a , i.e. $a \leq x \leq p \vee a$ implies either $x = a$ or $x = p \vee a$.

To summarise: the set of postulates which characterise the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} consists of the postulates PSP, SOC, SEP, and COV or equivalently of PSP, WM, SEP, and COV. The postulates S1 and S2 solely express the convention that an object should bear only one designation. With these postulates, the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} becomes a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, weakly modular, separable, atomic, and additive lattice.

Chapter 4

Projection systems of finite rank

Theorem 2.4 states that any projection a in \mathcal{P}_A is the join of all atoms preceding a . The relationship $a = b \equiv \bigvee_{p \leq a} p$ is valid also in the case of a weakly modular but not distributive projection system because $a = p \vee a$ for any atom $p \leq a$ implies

$$a = \bigvee_{p \leq a} a = \bigvee_{p \leq a} (a \vee p) = \bigvee_{p \leq a} a \vee \bigvee_{p \leq a} p = a \vee b$$

hence $b \leq a$. But $b < a$ entails with weak modularity that $a = b \vee (b' \wedge a)$ with $b' \wedge a > 0$ and there exists an atom $p \leq b' \wedge a$ with $p \leq a$ and $p \not\leq b$, which contradicts the hypothesis that b is the join of *all* atoms preceding a . However, this representation is redundant whereas it is not redundant in a distributive lattice.

It turns out that the *minimal* number of atoms the join of which is equal to the projection a is an intrinsic property of a , its *rank*, a quantity comparable with the dimension of a vector space. As an important consequence, weakly modular projection systems of finite rank are even modular, theorem 4.4. This fact is fundamental in the subsequent analysis. The results derived for projection system of finite rank are generalised to projection systems of countably infinite rank towards the end of the analysis, theorem 7.6. Consequently, we consider in this chapter only projections which can be represented as the join of *finitely many atoms*.

4.1 Algebraical dependency

Algebraical dependency deals with sets of unspecified elements. The *algebraical dependency of an element q on a finite set of elements $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$* is characterised by the following properties (we adapt the presentation of B. L. van der Waerden in section 20 of Ref. [25]):

- (Dp1)** No element depends on the empty set. If p and q are elements and p depends on $\{q\}$, then $p = q$.
- (Dp2)** Every element p_i , $1 \leq i \leq m$, of the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ depends on this set.
- (Dp3)** If the element q depends on $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ but is independent of $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-1}\}$, then p_m depends on $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-1}, q\}$.
- (Dp4)** If the element r depends on the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ and if every element q_j of this set depends on the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$, then r depends on $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$.

The set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ *depends on the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$* if every element p_i depends on $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$. A finite set of elements is *independent* if none of its elements depends on the other elements of the set.

Properties (Dp2) and (Dp4) imply

Lemma 4.1 *If the element r depends on the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ and if the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ contains the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$, then r depends on the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$.*

This lemma entails in particular that the algebraical dependency of a set from an other set does not depend on the order of the elements in the sets.

Lemma 4.2 *If the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-1}\}$ is independent but the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-1}, p_m\}$ is not independent, then p_m depends on $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-1}\}$.*

Proof At least one of the elements of the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ must depend on the other elements of this set. The lemma is proven if this element is p_m . Assume now that *e.g.* the element p_{m-1} depends on $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-2}, p_m\}$. The element p_{m-1} cannot depend upon $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-2}\}$ by hypothesis. Hence, p_m depends on $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-2}, p_{m-1}\}$ by property (Dp3).

qed

Lemma 4.3 *A finite set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ contains an independent subset, on which all elements p_i , $1 \leq i \leq m$, depend.*

Proof Choose a maximal independent subset of elements out of the set $\{p_i : 1 \leq i \leq m\}$. Every element of this subset depends on it according to property (Dp2); every element not contained in the subset depends on it according to lemma 4.2.

qed

Two finite sets of elements $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ and $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ are *equivalent* if every element q_j depends on $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ and every element p_i depends on $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$. This relationship is an equivalence relation because it is reflexive by property (Dp2), symmetric by construction, and transitive by (Dp4).

Lemma 4.4 (Steinitz' exchange lemma) *If the set of elements $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ is independent and if each element q_j of this set depends on the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$, then there are exactly n elements p_i of the second set, which can be exchanged with the elements $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ such that the new set is equivalent to the initial set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$. Furthermore, it is $n \leq m$.*

Proof Assume that $\{p_{i_1}, \dots, p_{i_l}\}$ is a smallest subset of $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$, on which q_1 depends; there may exist several such sets. This subset is independent and p_{i_1} depends on the set $\{q_1, p_{i_2}, \dots, p_{i_l}\}$ by property (Dp3) and also on the set $\{q_1, p_{i_2}, \dots, p_{i_m}\}$ according to lemma 4.1. In addition, this last set is equivalent to the initial set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$. Assume now that the assertion of the lemma is shown if the elements $\{p_{i_1}, \dots, p_{i_{k-1}}\}$, $2 \leq k \leq n$, are exchanged against the elements $\{q_1, \dots, q_{k-1}\}$ yielding the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_{k-1}, p_{i_k}, \dots, p_{i_m}\}$, which is equivalent to the initial set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ by hypothesis. There is a smallest subset of $\{q_1, \dots, q_{k-1}, p_{i_k}, \dots, p_{i_m}\}$, on which q_k depends. This subset cannot consist solely of elements q_j because the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ is independent. It contains at least one of the elements $\{p_{i_k}, \dots, p_{i_m}\}$, and it consists of the elements $\{q_1, \dots, q_{k-1}, p_{i_k}, \dots, p_{i_l}\}$ with $k \leq l \leq m$ if the initial set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ is suitably ordered. Now, q_k depends on this set but *not* on the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_{k-1}, p_{i_{k+1}}, \dots, p_{i_l}\}$ by construction. According to (Dp3), p_{i_k} depends on the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_k, p_{i_{k+1}}, \dots, p_{i_l}\}$ and by lemma 4.1 also on $\{q_1, \dots, q_k, p_{i_{k+1}}, \dots, p_{i_m}\}$ and this set is equivalent to the initial set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$. This concludes the induction step. The process comes to an end with $k = m$ at the latest, and the set $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ is independent only if $n \leq m$.

qed

If the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ of the lemma is, in addition, independent, then the rôle of the sets $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ and $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ may be interchanged and it follows that $n \leq m$ and $m \leq n$. Hence $m = n$ i.e. equivalent, finite, and independent sets possess the same number of elements.

4.2 The rank of a projection

In our case, the elements of an algebraical dependency are atoms of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} , and we say that a projection a depends on the finite set of atoms $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ if $a \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i$.

Theorem 4.1 *This relationship induces an algebraical dependency within the set of atoms of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} .*

Proof One has to verify that properties (Dp1) – (Dp4) are valid for this definition. Postulates (Dp1), (Dp2), and (Dp4) are readily checked. No atom precedes a different atom. (Dp2) is a consequence of $p_j \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i$. Furthermore, it follows from $r \leq \bigvee_{j=1}^n q_j$ and $q_j \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i$ that

$$r \leq \bigvee_{j=1}^n q_j \leq \underbrace{\left(\bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i \right) \vee \dots \left(\bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i \right)}_{\text{total of } n \text{ terms}} = \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i$$

by monotony (Mo1) and by idempotence (Id1). This is property (Dp4).

In order to check property (Dp3) we remark that the hypotheses imply that p_m is independent of the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_{m-1}\}$ and define

$$a = \bigvee_{i=1}^{m-1} p_i, \quad p = p_m, \quad \text{and} \quad b = \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i = a \vee p > a$$

The hypotheses of (Dp3) are then

$$p \not\leq a, \quad q \not\leq a, \quad q \leq b = a \vee p \quad \text{which is equivalent to} \quad a \vee p \vee q = a \vee p$$

and the conclusion is

$$p \leq a \vee q \quad \text{which is equivalent to} \quad a \vee q \vee p = a \vee q$$

Hence, one has to show that $a \vee q = a \vee p = b$. We formulate this statement as a lemma, which is of independent interest:

Lemma 4.5 *Let a, b be projections of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} , p an atom with $p \leq b$, $p \not\leq a$, and $a \vee p = b$, and q a projection with $q \leq b$, $q \not\leq a$. Then*

- (i) $a \vee q = a \vee p = b$ and q is an atom.
- (ii) There is one and only one atom r such that $b = a \vee r$ and $r \perp a$.

Proof (i) It is $a < b$ and $q \leq b$, which implies that $a \vee q \leq b$ by monotony (Mo3), and, with theorem 3.3, that

$$b = a \vee p = (a \vee q) \vee (q' \wedge a' \wedge (a \vee p))$$

It follows from postulate COV and from theorem 3.5 that

$$a' \wedge b = a' \wedge (a \vee p) \equiv r$$

is an atom. Because $0 \leq q' \wedge r \leq r$, it is either $q' \wedge r = 0$ or $q' \wedge r = r$. The latter case means that $r \leq q'$ or $q \leq r'$. But it is also $q \leq b$ by hypothesis, and from monotony (Mo4) and with theorem 3.3, one obtains

$$q \leq b \wedge r' = b \wedge (a \vee b') = a$$

This conflicts with the hypothesis $q \not\leq a$. Therefore, $q' \wedge r = 0$ and $b = a \vee p = a \vee q$. The projection q is an atom because $a \vee q = a \vee p$ covers a .

(ii) Weak modularity implies that $b = a \vee (a' \wedge b) = a \vee r$. It is $r \leq b$, $r \leq a'$. According to the item (ii) of theorem 3.4, r is the only atom with $a \vee r = b$ and $r \perp a$.

qed

It is not necessary to presume in lemma 4.5 that the projection a and b are the join of finitely many atoms. The proof of lemma 4.5 concludes the proof of theorem 4.1.

qed

It follows from (Dp4) and from the monotony property (Mo3) that

$$a \equiv \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i = \bigvee_{j=1}^n q_j$$

for equivalent sets of atoms. If the equivalent sets $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ and $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ are both independent, then $m = n$ and the sets are termed *bases of the projection a*. The results obtained in the previous section can be formulated as follows:

If a projection has a finite basis, then all its bases are finite and contain the same number of atoms. If a projection has an infinite basis, then all its bases have infinitely many atoms. With this result, the number of atoms in a basis of the projection a is established as an intrinsic property of a , its *rank* $\nu(a)$. The projection 0 has rank $\nu(0) = 0$ by definition. The *rank of a projection system* is defined as the rank of its unit projection I . A projection system is called *of finite rank* if $\nu(I)$ is finite. These findings and lemma 4.3 yields the

Theorem 4.2 *Every projection which can be represented as the join of finitely many atoms possesses a finite basis. All bases of a projection a contain the same number of atoms, which is its rank $\nu(a)$.*

A set $\{q_1, \dots, q_m\}$ of mutually disjoint atoms is an independent set because the condition that $q_j \perp q_i$ for all indices $i \neq j$ implies $q_j \leq q'_i$ for all $i \neq j$ by lemma 2.2 and $q_j \leq \bigwedge_{i \neq j} q'_i = (\bigvee_{i \neq j} q_i)'$ by the monotony property (Mo4) and, therefore, $q_j \not\leq \bigvee_{i \neq j} q_i$. The set $\{q_1, \dots, q_m\}$ may be termed an *orthogonal basis of the projection* $\bigvee_{i=1}^m q_i$.

Lemma 4.6 *If the projection b is of finite rank, $\nu(b) = m$, and if $0 \leq a < b$, then there exists a set of atoms $\{q_1, \dots, q_k\}$ with $k \leq m$ such that $q_i \perp a$ and $q_i \perp q_j$ for $i \neq j$ and*

$$b = a \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^k q_i$$

Proof Due to weak modularity, $a < b$ implies that $b = a \vee c$ where $0 < c = a' \wedge b \leq a'$, hence $c \perp a$. By theorem 3.4 (ii), this projection c is the only one for which $c \perp a$ and $b = a \vee c$. The atomicity postulate (At) states that there exists an atom $q_1 \leq c \leq a'$, hence $q_1 \perp a$. Applying weak modularity again, one can write $c = q_1 \vee c_1$ where

$$c_1 = q'_1 \wedge c = q'_1 \wedge a' \wedge b = (a \vee q_1)' \wedge b$$

and

$$b = (a \vee q_1) \vee ((a \vee q_1)' \wedge b)$$

If $c_1 = 0$, then the theorem is proven. Otherwise, there is an atom $q_2 \leq c_1$, which implies that $q_2 \perp a$ and $q_2 \perp q_1$, and there exists a decomposition $c_1 = q_2 \vee c_2$ with $c_2 = q_2' \wedge c_1 = a' \wedge q_1' \wedge q_2' \wedge b$ and, therefore,

$$b = (a \vee q_1 \vee q_2) \vee ((a \vee q_1 \vee q_2)' \wedge b)$$

with $q_1 \perp a$, $q_2 \perp a$, and $q_1 \perp q_2$.

This procedure can be continued yielding

$$b = a \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^k q_i \vee \left((a \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^k q_i)' \wedge b \right)$$

with $q_i \perp a$ and $q_i \perp q_j$ for $i \neq j$ until it stops if $(a \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^k q_i)' \wedge b = 0$ and $b = a \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^k q_i$. This happens at the latest if $k = m$.

qed

The lemma states that an (orthogonal) basis of a projection a with $0 < a < b$, b of finite rank, can be extended to an (orthogonal) basis of b . If a is an atom preceding b , then the lemma shows by construction that every projection b of finite rank possesses an *orthogonal* basis.

4.3 The rank formula

The rank formula is a central property of projection systems of finite rank. Its most important consequence is that projection systems of finite rank are modular, theorem 4.4.

Theorem 4.3 (rank formula) *Let \mathcal{P} be a weakly modular projection system of finite rank. Then it is*

$$\nu(a) + \nu(b) = \nu(a \vee b) + \nu(a \wedge b)$$

for any two projections a and b in \mathcal{P} .

Proof We follow Piron [2, p. 460] and proceed in consecutive steps.

(a) If $\{p_1, \dots, p_m\}$ is a basis of the projection a and $\{q_1, \dots, q_n\}$ a basis of the projection b , then $a \vee b$ depends on the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_m, q_1, \dots, q_n\}$. According to lemma 4.3, this set contains an independent subset which is a basis of $a \vee b$ by theorem 4.2. Therefore,

$$\nu(a \vee b) \leq m + n = \nu(a) + \nu(b)$$

(b) It is $a \leq b'$ if and only if $a \leftrightarrow b$ and $a \wedge b = 0$ because $a \leq b'$ implies $a \leftrightarrow b$ by weak modularity and is equivalent to $a \wedge b' = a$ and, therefore, $a \wedge b = a \wedge b' \wedge b = 0$. Conversely, if $a \leftrightarrow b$ and $a \wedge b = 0$, then $a = a \wedge (b \vee b') = (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge b') = a \wedge b'$.

Consider now $a \leq b'$ and two atoms $p \leq a$ and $q \leq b$. It is then $p \leq a \leq b' \leq q'$, which implies $p \wedge q = 0$ i.e. $p \neq q$. Hence, if $a \leq b'$, then all atoms of a basis of a are different from all atoms of a basis of b and, therefore,

$$\nu(a \vee b) = \nu(a) + \nu(b)$$

(c) Consider two projections x and y with $x \wedge y = 0$. It is $x, y \leq x \vee y$ and with theorem 3.3

$$x \vee y = x \vee ((x \vee y) \wedge x') = y \vee ((x \vee y) \wedge y')$$

Furthermore, $(x \vee y) \wedge x' \leq x'$ and $(x \vee y) \wedge y' \leq y'$, and with (b) one has

$$\begin{aligned}\nu(x) + \nu((x \vee y) \wedge x') &= \nu(x \vee y) \\ \nu(y) + \nu((x \vee y) \wedge y') &= \nu(x \vee y)\end{aligned}$$

According to (a), it is

$$\nu(x \vee y) = \nu(x) + \nu(y) - \epsilon$$

with $\epsilon \geq 0$, which yields

$$\begin{aligned}\nu((x \vee y) \wedge x') &= \nu(x \vee y) - \nu(x) = \nu(y) - \epsilon \\ \nu((x \vee y) \wedge y') &= \nu(x \vee y) - \nu(y) = \nu(x) - \epsilon\end{aligned}$$

Now, $x \leq x \vee y$ and $y \leq x \vee y$ imply $(x \vee y) \leftrightarrow x'$ and $(x \vee y) \leftrightarrow y'$, and one obtains with $x \wedge y = 0$ and $(x \wedge y)' = I$

$$((x \vee y) \wedge x') \vee ((x \vee y) \wedge y') = (x \vee y) \wedge (x' \vee y') = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \wedge y)' = x \vee y$$

and with (a)

$$\nu(x \vee y) \leq \nu((x \vee y) \wedge x') + \nu((x \vee y) \wedge y') = \nu(x) + \nu(y) - 2\epsilon$$

and, finally,

$$\nu(x) + \nu(y) - \epsilon = \nu(x \vee y) \leq \nu(x) + \nu(y) - 2\epsilon$$

Hence, $\epsilon = 0$, and for arbitrary projections x, y with $x \wedge y = 0$ it is

$$\nu(x \vee y) = \nu(x) + \nu(y)$$

(d) Let $z = x \wedge y$ for two arbitrary projections x, y in \mathcal{P} . The relationships $z \leq x$ and $z \leq y$ imply with weak modularity that z and z' are compatible with x, x', y , and y' , and, consequently,

$$\begin{aligned}(x \wedge z') \wedge z &= 0 \\ (x \wedge z') \vee z &= (x \vee z) \wedge (z \vee z') = x \vee z = x \vee (x \wedge y) = x\end{aligned}$$

by absorption, and similarly with the pair y, z . Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}(i) \quad \nu(x) &= \nu(x \vee z') + \nu(z) \\ (ii) \quad \nu(y) &= \nu(y \vee z') + \nu(z) \\ (iii) \quad \nu(x \vee y) &= \nu((x \vee y) \wedge z') + \nu(z)\end{aligned}$$

because of $z \leq (x \vee y)$, of theorem 3.3 and of (c). Furthermore,

$$\begin{aligned}(x \wedge z') \vee (y \wedge z') &= (x \vee y) \wedge z' \\ (x \wedge z') \wedge (y \wedge z') &= (x \wedge y) \wedge z' = z \wedge z' = 0\end{aligned}$$

and again with (c)

$$(iv) \quad \nu((x \vee y) \wedge z') = \nu(x \wedge z') + \nu(y \wedge z')$$

The equations (i) – (iv) yield together

$$\nu(x) + \nu(y) = \nu((x \vee y) \wedge z') + 2\nu(z) = \nu(x \vee y) + \nu(x \wedge y)$$

for any two projections x, y , in \mathcal{P} .

qed

Lemma 4.7 *If $x \leq y$ are projections in a weakly modular projection system of finite rank and $\nu(x) = \nu(y)$, then $x = y$.*

Proof [2, p. 460] Consider two projections $x < y$, i.e. $x \leq y$ and $x \neq y$, in \mathcal{P} . By weak modularity,

$$y = x \vee (x' \wedge y) \text{ with } x' \wedge y \neq 0$$

From $x \wedge (x' \wedge y) = 0$, it follows with theorem 4.3 that

$$\nu(y) = \nu(x) + \nu(x' \wedge y) > \nu(x)$$

Therefore: $x \leq y$ and $\nu(x) = \nu(y)$ imply $x = y$.

qed

Theorem 4.3 has two important consequences. First:

Theorem 4.4 *A weakly modular projection system \mathcal{P} of finite rank is modular.*

Proof [2, p. 460] Consider projections a, b, c with $a \leq b$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(a \vee (c \wedge b)) &= \nu(a) + \nu(c \wedge b) - \nu(a \wedge c) \\ &= \nu(c \wedge b) + \nu(a \vee c) - \nu(c) \\ &= \nu(a \vee c) - \nu(c \vee b) + \nu(b) \\ &= \nu(a \vee c \wedge b) \end{aligned}$$

by a repeated application of theorem 4.3 and because $\nu(a \vee c) \wedge b + \nu(a \vee c \vee b) = \nu(a \vee c) + \nu(b)$ and $a \vee c \vee b = c \vee b$. It is in any lattice $a \vee (c \wedge b) \leq (a \vee c) \wedge (a \vee b) = (a \vee c) \wedge b$ as follows from equation (2.22) and $a \leq b$. From lemma 4.7, we conclude that

$$a \leq b \text{ implies } a \vee (c \wedge b) = (a \vee c) \wedge b$$

for projections a, b, c in \mathcal{P} . This is the modular law (3.1).

qed

Secondly, consider four distinct atoms p, q, r, s . According to theorem 4.3, it is $\nu(p \vee q) = \nu(r \vee s) = 2$ and $\nu((p \vee q) \wedge (r \vee s)) = 4 - \nu(p \vee q \vee r \vee s)$. Three different cases are possible:

- (i) $\nu(p \vee q \vee r \vee s) = 4$ and $\nu((p \vee q) \wedge (r \vee s)) = 0$: if none of the atoms p, q, r, s precedes the join of the other three atoms, then the meet of $p \vee q$ and $r \vee s$ is empty.
- (ii) $\nu(p \vee q \vee r \vee s) = 3$ and $\nu((p \vee q) \wedge (r \vee s)) = 1$: if one of the atoms precedes the join of the other three, the meet of $p \vee q$ and $r \vee s$ is an atom.
- (iii) $\nu(p \vee q \vee r \vee s) = 2$ and $\nu((p \vee q) \wedge (r \vee s)) = 2$: if two of the atoms precede the join of the other two, then $p \vee q = r \vee s$.

An immediate consequence of cases (ii) and (iii) is

Theorem 4.5 *Consider a projection system of finite rank not less than three. Given three distinct atoms p, q, r none of them precedes the join of the other two, an atom $s \leq p \vee q$, $s \neq p$ and $s \neq q$, and an atom $t \leq q \vee r$, $t \neq q$ and $t \neq r$. Then $u \equiv (p \vee r) \wedge (s \vee t)$ is an atom, $\nu(u) = 1$, with $u \leq p \vee r$ and $u \leq s \vee t$.*

Proof The assumptions of the theorem mean that $s \leq p \vee q \leq p \vee q \vee r$ and $t \leq q \vee r \leq p \vee q \vee r$. Therefore, $p \vee r \vee s \vee t \leq p \vee q \vee r$ by monotony (Mo1) and $\nu((p \vee q) \wedge (r \vee s))$ equals either 1 or 2. The value 2 is excluded because $p \vee r \neq s \vee t$ by hypothesis.

qed

Items (ii) and (iii) have a geometrical connotation. Call atoms 'points', the joins of two different atoms 'lines', three points on a line 'collinear', and the joins of three noncollinear points 'planes'. Items (ii) and (iii) state together that two lines in a plane have either exactly one point in common or the lines are identical.

That a projection system is complete signifies

A To every pair of distinct points there exists exactly one line that contains these two points.

The geometrical content of theorem 4.5 reads as

B If the points p, q, r are not collinear, if the points p, s, q are collinear and $s \neq p, s \neq q$, and if the points q, t, r are collinear and $t \neq q$ and $t \neq r$, then there is a point u such that p, r, u are collinear and s, t, u are collinear.

Finally, the statement B presupposes that

C Every line contains at least three different points.

It is shown in chapter 5 that a projection system is irreducible if the join of any pair of distinct atoms of this projection system contains at least three different atoms. The statements A, B, and C are the axioms of projective geometry given by Veblen and Young [26]. Piron [2, 3-1] and Jauch [4, 8-1] use this connection between irreducible projection systems of finite rank and projective geometries in order to map an irreducible projection system into a projective geometry, and they obtain the algebraic representation of such a projection system by means of this map and of the fundamental representation theorem stating that a projective geometry of dimension greater or equal than three is projectively equivalent to the system of the subspaces of some vector space. In chapter 6, this algebraic representation is derived directly for irreducible, weakly modular, not distributive projection systems of finite rank not less than three without an explicit reference to projective geometries.

Chapter 5

The decomposition of projection systems

It is shown in this chapter that any projection system, and hence also \mathcal{P}_{PHS} , is the union of a distributive and of a weakly modular, not distributive projection system, and that the latter is the direct product of irreducible projection systems.

5.1 Mathematical prerequisites

In this section, some definitions and tools used in the subsequent analysis of the algebraic structure of projection systems are given. As mentioned before, a lattice \mathcal{L} is a set of elements provided with an order structure, $(\mathcal{L}; \leq)$ or, equivalently, with an algebraic structure based on the two operations join and meet, $(\mathcal{L}; \vee, \wedge)$. Each of the two structures can be defined in terms of the other. But the combined use of both structures is important and characteristic of lattice theoretical proofs. The algebraic aspect allows to introduce additional algebraic concepts into lattice theory as 'homomorphisms', 'isomorphisms', 'center', and the structural principle of 'duality'. The definitions and theorems in this section are valid for bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, and weakly modular lattices and, hence, also for projection systems.

5.1.1 Lattice homomorphisms

A lattice homomorphism $\mu : \mathcal{L}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_2$ is a map which is defined on \mathcal{L}_1 and respects the order and the algebraic structure of the lattices: if $a \leq b$, then $\mu(a) \leq \mu(b)$ and so on. For our purposes, the following definition [3, p. 29, 31] is appropriate:

A *lattice homomorphism* is a map μ of a lattice \mathcal{L}_1 into a lattice \mathcal{L}_2 such that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad & a \perp b \text{ implies } \mu(a) \perp \mu(b) \\ \text{(ii)} \quad & \mu\left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i\right) = \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mu(a_i) \end{aligned}$$

The index set \mathbb{I} may be finite, countable, $\mathbb{I} = \mathbb{N}$, or continuous, $\mathbb{I} = \mathbb{R}$.

Theorem 5.1 *It follows from assumptions (i) and (ii) that*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(iii)} \quad & \mu(0_1) = 0_2 \\ \text{(iv)} \quad & \mu(a') = \mu(a)' \wedge \mu(I_1) \\ \text{(v)} \quad & \mu\left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i\right) = \bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mu(a_i) \end{aligned}$$

Proof

(iii) $0_1 \perp 0_1$ implies $\mu(0_1) \perp \mu(0_1)$ by property (i) and, therefore, $\mu(0_1) = 0_2$ because $a \leq a'$ if and only if $a = 0$.

(iv) It is $a' \perp a$, which implies $\mu(a') \leq \mu(a)'$ with property (i) and lemma 2.2. It follows with theorem 3.3 and property (ii) that

$$\mu(a') = \mu(a)' \wedge (\mu(a) \vee \mu(a')) = \mu(a)' \wedge \mu(a \vee a') = \mu(a)' \wedge \mu(I_1)$$

(v) It is

$$\begin{aligned} \mu\left(\bigwedge_{i \in I} a_i\right) &= \mu\left(\left(\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i'\right)'\right) = \left(\mu\left(\bigvee_{i \in I} a_i'\right)\right)' \wedge \mu(I_1) \\ &= \left(\bigvee_{i \in I} \mu(a_i')\right)' \wedge \mu(I_1) = \left(\bigwedge_{i \in I} \mu(a_i')'\right) \wedge \mu(I_1) \\ &= \bigwedge_{i \in I} (\mu(a_i')' \wedge \mu(I_1)) = \bigwedge_{i \in I} \mu((a_i')') = \bigwedge_{i \in I} \mu(a_i) \end{aligned}$$

qed

Statements (iii) and (iv) with $a = 0_1$ imply that $\mu(I_1) \leq I_2$, and statement (v) that $\mu(a) = \mu(a \wedge I_1) = \mu(a) \wedge \mu(I_1)$ or $\mu(a) \leq \mu(I_1)$ for all elements a of \mathcal{L}_1 ; $\mu(I_1)$ is the upper bound of the lattice $\mu(\mathcal{L}_1)$ which is a sublattice of \mathcal{L}_2 .

A map μ of a lattice \mathcal{L}_1 onto a lattice \mathcal{L}_2 is a *lattice isomorphism* if μ is one-to-one, and μ and μ^{-1} are homomorphisms. It is then $\mu(I_1) = I_2$ and $\mu(a') = \mu(a)'$. Two lattices \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 are called *isomorphic*, $\mathcal{L}_1 \simeq \mathcal{L}_2$, if there exists a lattice isomorphism between the two lattices.

5.1.2 The duality principle

The fact that the axiomatic basis of lattices $(\mathcal{L}; \vee, \wedge)$, namely commutativity, associativity, and absorptivity, remain unchanged if the symbols \vee and \wedge are interchanged leads to the

Duality principle for lattices [19, p. 14] *Let Φ be a statement about lattices expressed in terms of \vee and \wedge . The statement Φ^δ is the dual of Φ obtained from Φ by interchanging \vee and \wedge . If Φ is true for all lattices, then Φ^δ is also true for all lattices. If Φ involves \leq and maybe 0 and I in addition to \vee and \wedge , then one has to interchange \vee and \wedge , replace \leq by \geq , and interchange 0 and I .*

The duality principle is valid for distributive, complemented lattices because (Di2) is the dual of (Di1), and the properties (Co1) – (Co3) are self-dual. It is also valid for weakly modular, orthocomplemented lattices. The two conditions $a = b \wedge (b' \vee a)$ and $b = a \vee (a' \wedge b)$ if $a \leq b$, characterising weak modularity, are the duals of each other. The properties (Oc1) – (Oc3) are self-dual because the orthocomplement (2.26) is also a complement and the property (Oc2) may be completed to $a \perp a'$, $a \wedge a' = 0$, $a \vee a' = I$, and $a \perp a'$ is equivalent to $a \leq a$.

5.1.3 Segments

Let $a \neq 0$ be a projection in the lattice \mathcal{L} . The set $[0, a] \equiv \{x \in \mathcal{L} : x \leq a\} = \{x \wedge a : x \in \mathcal{L}\}$ is called a *segment* of \mathcal{L}^1 . Clearly, $[0, I] = \mathcal{L}$.

¹Grätzer [19, p. 35] terms the set $[a, b] \equiv \{x \in \mathcal{L} : a \leq x \leq b\}$ an *interval*. With Piron [3, p. 30], we choose the notion of 'segment' for the case $[0, a]$, which is of particular interest for our purposes.

Let \mathcal{L} be a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, and weakly modular lattice and $a \neq 0$ a projection in \mathcal{L} . The projection

$$x'^a \equiv a \wedge x'$$

is the *relative orthocomplement of the projection x in $[0, a]$* . Accordingly, the *relative disjointness $x \perp^a y$ of projections x, y in $[0, a]$* is given by the condition

$$x \leq y'^a$$

Theorem 5.2 *The relative orthocomplement and the relative disjointness possess the following properties:*

- (i) $(x'^a)'^a = x$
- (ii) $x'^a \perp^a x$ and $x'^a \vee x = a$ ²
- (iii) $x_1 \leq x_2$ implies $(x_2)'^a \leq (x_1)'^a$
- (iv) $0'^a = a, a'^a = 0$
- (v) Let $0 \leq x \leq y \leq a$. Then $y \wedge (y'^a \vee x) = x$ and $x \vee (x'^a \wedge y) = y$ i.e. the segment $[0, a]$ is weakly modular with respect to the relative orthocomplement $x \rightarrow x'^a$.

Proof The proofs of items (i) to (iv) are evident if the compatibility of x and $x \wedge a$ due to weak modularity is taken into account. To prove item (v), one needs, in addition, the compatibilities $y \leftrightarrow x$ and $y \leftrightarrow a$ and obtains

$$\begin{aligned} y \wedge (y'^a \vee x) &= y \wedge ((a \wedge y') \vee x) = (y \wedge a \wedge y') \vee (y \wedge x) = 0 \vee x = x \\ x \vee (x'^a \wedge y) &= (x \vee x'^a) \wedge (x \vee y) = a \wedge y = y \end{aligned}$$

qed

This theorem states that the segment $[0, a]$ is a bounded, complete, relatively orthocomplemented, and weakly modular lattice with maximal element a .

A compatibility question arises in the case $0 \leq x \leq a \leq b$ because the segment $[0, a]$ can be considered a segment in \mathcal{L} with relative orthocomplement $a \wedge x'$ or as a segment in $[0, b]$ with relative orthocomplement $a \wedge x'^b$. But both cases amount to the same:

$$a \wedge x'^b = a \wedge b \wedge x' = a \wedge x'$$

The following theorem characterises segments in projection systems:

Theorem 5.3 *A segment $[0, a]$ of a separable and atomic projection system \mathcal{P} is a separable and atomic projection system with top element a .*

Proof It remains to verify the separability and the atomicity of the segment. The separability of $[0, a]$ follows from the inclusion $[0, a] \subseteq \mathcal{P}$. The atomicity is also given by inclusion with an evident modification of the postulate (COV):

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{COV}') \quad & \text{Let } b < a \text{ be a projection and } p \not\leq b \text{ an atom in } [0, a]. \\ & \text{Then } p \vee b \text{ covers } b. \end{aligned}$$

(COV') is the restriction of (COV) to the projection system $[0, a]$.

qed

²Theorem 3.4 implies that the relative orthocomplement x'^a is unique.

5.1.4 The center of a lattice

The *center* $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L})$ of a lattice \mathcal{L} is the set of elements in \mathcal{L} which are compatible with all elements in \mathcal{L} .

Theorem 5.4 *The center of a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, and weakly modular lattice is a bounded, complete, complemented, and distributive lattice.*

Proof Boundedness and distributivity are trivial. Complementation and orthocomplementation are equivalent in a distributive lattice. The center is complete because it follows from theorem D.3 that $\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i$ and $\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} a_i$ belong to the center if all projections a_i, i in \mathbb{I} , do.

qed

The center $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L})$ always contains the elements 0 and I . The center is *trivial* if it consists only of 0 and I .

5.1.5 Direct product and reducibility of lattices

The *direct product* $\mathcal{L} \equiv \mathcal{L}_1 \times \mathcal{L}_2$ of two lattices is the set of the pairs $\{(a_1, a_2) : a_1 \in \mathcal{L}_1, a_2 \in \mathcal{L}_2\}$ where join and meet are defined by the corresponding operations on the components

$$\begin{aligned} (a_1, a_2) \vee (b_1, b_2) &\equiv (a_1 \vee b_1, a_2 \vee b_2) \\ (a_1, a_2) \wedge (b_1, b_2) &\equiv (a_1 \wedge b_1, a_2 \wedge b_2) \end{aligned}$$

The following properties are immediate:

- $(0_1, 0_2)$ and (I_1, I_2) are the elements 0 and I in \mathcal{L}
- $(a_1, a_2)' = (a_1', a_2')$
- $(a_1, a_2) \leq (b_1, b_2)$ if and only if $a_1 \leq b_1$ and $a_2 \leq b_2$
- $(a_1, a_2) \leftrightarrow (b_1, b_2)$ if and only if $a_1 \leftrightarrow b_1$ and $a_2 \leftrightarrow b_2$
- $\mathcal{L}_1 \times \mathcal{L}_2 \simeq \mathcal{L}_2 \times \mathcal{L}_1$
- The maps $a_1 \in \mathcal{L}_1 \rightarrow (a_1, 0_2) \in \mathcal{L}$ and $a_2 \in \mathcal{L}_2 \rightarrow (0_1, a_2) \in \mathcal{L}$ are lattice homomorphisms
- The direct product $\mathcal{L}_1 \times \mathcal{L}_2$ is a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, and weakly modular lattice if both components \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 are
- $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L}_1 \times \mathcal{L}_2) \simeq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L}_1) \times \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L}_2)$
- The center of $\mathcal{L}_1 \times \mathcal{L}_2$ contains at least the four elements $(0_1, 0_2), (0_1, I_2), (I_1, 0_2), (I_1, I_2)$ and is, therefore, not trivial
- The definition of the direct product can be extended to a family of lattices $\{\mathcal{L}_i : i \in \mathbb{I}\}$: $\mathcal{L} \equiv \prod_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathcal{L}_i$

A lattice \mathcal{L} is *reducible* if it is isomorphic to a direct product of two lattices; otherwise it is *irreducible*.

Theorem 5.5 *A lattice \mathcal{L} is reducible if and only if its center is not trivial.*

Proof We have already shown that the center $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L})$ is not trivial if \mathcal{L} is reducible. To show the converse, assume that the center of \mathcal{L} contains an element z different from 0 and I . Then z' is also in the center. Any element a in \mathcal{L} can be written as

$$a = a \wedge I = a \wedge (z \vee z') = (a \wedge z) \vee (a \wedge z')$$

where $a \wedge z \leq z$ and $a \wedge z' \leq z'$, and it is

$$\begin{aligned} (a \wedge z) \wedge (b \wedge z) &= (a \wedge b) \wedge z \\ (a \wedge z) \vee (b \wedge z) &= (a \vee b) \wedge z \end{aligned}$$

and accordingly with z' because of the compatibility of z and z' with all elements of \mathcal{L} . Hence, the map $a \in \mathcal{L} \rightarrow (a \wedge z, a \wedge z')$ defines a lattice isomorphism: $\mathcal{L} \simeq [0, z] \times [0, z']$.

qed

One has, therefore, the following situation: let z_1 and z_2 be two projections in $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L})$ such that $z_1 \wedge z_2 = 0$ and $z_1 \vee z_2 = I$. Then it is $\mathcal{L} \simeq [0, z_1] \times [0, z_2]$. The generalisation to the case where the center $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{L})$ is generated by the set $\{z_i\}$ with $z_i \wedge z_j = 0$ for $i \neq j$ and $\bigvee_i z_i = I$ is obvious if one takes into account theorem D.2.

5.2 The perspectivity of atoms

Two atoms p_1 and p_2 are called *perspective*, in symbols $p_1 \sim p_2$, if there exists an atom $p_3 \leq p_1 \vee p_2$, which is different from p_1 and from p_2 . Lemma 4.5 states that

$$p_1 \vee p_2 = p_1 \vee p_3 = p_2 \vee p_3 \tag{5.1}$$

for perspective pairs p_1 and p_2 , which means in geometrical terms that a line is given by an arbitrary pair of its points. Such a relationship between three different atoms is not possible in a distributive lattice [4, p.107] because it is in this case

$$p_3 \wedge (p_1 \vee p_2) = (p_3 \wedge p_1) \vee (p_3 \wedge p_2)$$

The lefthand side of this equation is equal to p_3 because $p_3 \leq p_1 \vee p_2$, but the righthand side is equal to 0 because the meet of different atoms equals 0. Hence, a pair of perspective atoms cannot be compatible.

The converse is also true. Assume that the pair p and q of atoms in an orthocomplemented, weakly modular, and atomic lattice is not perspective *i.e.* if r is an atom, then $0 < r < p \vee q$ implies that either $r = p$ or $r = q$. Consider now the element $r \equiv (p \vee q) \wedge p'$. According to theorem 3.5, r is an atom. It is $r \leq p'$ and $r \leq p \vee q$ implying $r \neq p$ and $r = q$ by hypothesis. Therefore, $q \leq p'$ and $q \leftrightarrow p$ by weak modularity, and it results

Theorem 5.6 *A pair p and q of different atoms in an orthocomplemented, weakly modular, and atomic lattice is compatible if and only if it is not perspective.*

or, equivalently,

Corollary 5.1 *In an orthocomplemented, weakly modular, and atomic lattice, any pair p and q of different atoms is either compatible and not perspective or perspective and not compatible.*

It is illustrative to compare classical and quantum mechanical projection systems in regard of perspectivity. In a distributive projection system, the atom p_i is represented by the characteristic function of the set $\{\omega_i\}$ consisting of a single point of the phase space (see section 2.5). The projection $p_1 \vee p_2$ is represented by the characteristic function of the union $\omega_1 \cup \omega_2$, which implies that p_1 and p_2 are the only atoms preceding $p_1 \vee p_2$. Lemma 4.5 is, therefore, trivially true. This contrasts with the situation in a quantum mechanical projection system (see section 3.3). The atoms p_1 and p_2 are represented there by the projectors Q_1 and Q_2 on the one-dimensional subspaces $\mathcal{V}_i = \{\gamma\phi_i : \gamma \in \mathbb{C}, \|\phi_i\| > 0\}$ of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and the projection $p_1 \vee p_2$ is represented by the projector on the subspace $\mathcal{V}_{p_1 \vee p_2} = \{\phi : \phi = \gamma_1\phi_1 + \gamma_2\phi_2, \gamma_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Clearly, $\mathcal{V}_{p_1 \vee p_2}$ contains many different one-dimensional subspaces of the form $\{\phi : \phi = \gamma(\gamma_1\phi_1 + \gamma_2\phi_2)\}$ where $\gamma, \gamma_i \in \mathbb{C}$ and γ_1 and γ_2 are fixed. Hence, there are many atoms $p \leq p_1 \vee p_2$ different from p_1 or to p_2 , and lemma 4.5 indicates an important structural property.

In reducible, not distributive projection systems, there exist non-perspective pairs of atoms. This can be shown as follows [4, p. 108]: the center of a reducible projection system \mathcal{P} contains at least one pair of projections $\{z, z'\}$, different from $\{0, I\}$, that are compatible with every projection a in \mathcal{P} yielding the decomposition

$$a = a \wedge I = a \wedge (z \vee z') = (a \wedge z) \vee (a \wedge z')$$

with $(a \wedge z) \wedge (a \wedge z') = 0$. This means for an atom r that either $r \leq z$ or $r \leq z'$. Assume now that p, q, r are three distinct atoms with $p \leq z, q \leq z'$, and $r \leq p \vee q$. Lemma 4.5 implies then that $p \vee q = r \vee q$ and $p \vee q = r \vee p$. If $r \leq z$, then $q \leq p \vee q = r \vee p \leq z$ according to the monotony property (Mo3), and if $r \leq z'$, then $p \leq p \vee q = r \vee q \leq z'$. This contradicts the initial assumptions in both cases. Therefore, it is either $r = p$ or $r = q$ and it results

Theorem 5.7 *If a projection system is reducible, then it contains at least one nonperspective pair of atoms. Or by contraposition: if all pairs of atoms of a projection system are perspective, then this projection system is irreducible.*

5.3 The decomposition theorem for projection systems

Let \mathcal{P} denote a projection system, \mathcal{A} the set of its atoms. With respect to perspectivity, the set \mathcal{A} is the union of three disjoint subsets:

1. the set \mathcal{A}_1 of all atoms with no perspective partners
2. the set \mathcal{A}_2 of atoms forming isolated joins $p \vee q$ of perspective atoms *i.e.* the atoms $r \leq p \vee q$ are the only atoms in \mathcal{A} , which are perspective to p or to q
3. the rest \mathcal{A}_3

Clearly, it is $\mathcal{A}_1 \cap \mathcal{A}_2 = \emptyset, \mathcal{A}_1 \cap \mathcal{A}_3 = \emptyset, \mathcal{A}_2 \cap \mathcal{A}_3 = \emptyset$, and $\mathcal{A}_1 \cup \mathcal{A}_2 \cup \mathcal{A}_3 = \mathcal{A}$. We now discuss the properties of these three sets.

The set \mathcal{A}_1 of atoms generates a distributive projection system with top element

$$z = \bigvee_{p \in \mathcal{A}_1} p$$

as a consequence of theorem 5.6 and of theorem D.3. The segment $[0, z]$ is a classical projection system as described in section 2.5. The phase space of the corresponding classical theory is parametrised by the set \mathcal{A}_1 of atoms, a state is represented by a probability measure and an observable by a measurable, real function on the phase space.

Perspectivity is evidently symmetric. As for the set \mathcal{A}_2 , it follows from equation (5.1) that $p \sim q$ and $r \leq p \vee q$ imply $q \sim r$ and $p \sim r$, which means that perspectivity is transitive in this case. By construction, \mathcal{A}_2 decomposes into disjoint sets of atoms each set generating a segment of rank two: if l is defined by $l \equiv p \vee q$ for a pair of atoms in \mathcal{A}_2 , then $[0, l]$ is a segment in \mathcal{P} and the relative complement $r^{ll} = r' \wedge l$ is an atom preceding l .

To each perspective pair $p \sim q$ in \mathcal{A}_3 , there exists at least one third atom r , $r \not\leq p \vee q$, such that $r \sim p$ or $r \sim q$. It is a consequence of theorem 4.5 that perspectivity is transitive also in \mathcal{A}_3 [27]: if p, q, r are three atoms none of them precedes the join of the two others, then $p \sim q$ and $q \sim r$ imply $p \sim r$. The symmetry and the transitivity of perspectivity suffice to prove that \mathcal{A}_3 decomposes into disjoint subsets of perspective atoms. This can be shown with the usual arguments: let the set $\mathcal{K}_q \subseteq \mathcal{A}_3$ be defined by

$$\mathcal{K}_q \equiv \{p \in \mathcal{A}_3 : p \sim q\}$$

All atoms in \mathcal{K}_q are perspective to all other atoms in \mathcal{K}_q because $p \sim q$ and $r \sim q$ imply $q \sim r$ and $p \sim r$. Two non-perspective atoms belong to different perspectivity classes by the construction of these classes. Therefore, the subsets \mathcal{K}_p and \mathcal{K}_q of the the set \mathcal{A}_3 are either disjoint (their intersection is void) if $p \not\sim q$, or they are identical if $p \sim q$. The set union $\bigcup_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathcal{K}_i$ of all these disjoint subsets is equal to \mathcal{A}_3 also by construction. To achieve this result, it is not necessary to assume that perspectivity is reflexive³, $p \sim p$, which does not make sense because p is the only atom preceding $p \vee p$.

In the subsequent discussion, one can treat the sets \mathcal{A}_2 and \mathcal{A}_3 on equal grounds. Hence, a weakly modular projection system decomposes into a distributive part discussed in section 2.5 and a weakly modular but not distributive part. We consider, therefore, a weakly modular, nondistributive projection system \mathcal{P} whose set \mathcal{A} of atoms decomposes into the disjoint subsets of perspectivity classes \mathcal{K}_i .

Theorem 5.8 *Every weakly modular, but not distributive projection system \mathcal{P} is the direct product of irreducible projection systems.*

Proof We consider the decomposition of the set \mathcal{A} of all atoms p of \mathcal{P} into its perspectivity classes \mathcal{K}_i with $\mathcal{K}_i \cap \mathcal{K}_j = \emptyset$ if $j \neq i$ and $\bigcup_i \mathcal{K}_i = \mathcal{A}$. Define the projections z_i by

$$z_i \equiv \bigvee_{p \in \mathcal{K}_i} p \tag{5.2}$$

It is

$$z_i \wedge z_j = \bigvee_{p \in \mathcal{K}_i} p \wedge \bigvee_{q \in \mathcal{K}_j} q = \bigvee_{p \in \mathcal{K}_i} (p \wedge \bigvee_{q \in \mathcal{K}_j} q) = \bigvee_{p \in \mathcal{K}_i, q \in \mathcal{K}_j} (p \wedge q) = 0 \tag{5.3}$$

because it is $p \wedge q = 0$ for any pair of distinct atoms, and the atoms p in \mathcal{K}_i and q in \mathcal{K}_j are not perspective and, hence, compatible according to theorem 5.6. Theorem D.3 is applied twice. Furthermore,

$$\bigvee_i z_i = \bigvee_i \left(\bigvee_{p \in \mathcal{K}_i} p \right) = \bigvee_{p \in \bigcup_i \mathcal{K}_i} p = \bigvee_{p \in \mathcal{A}} p = I \tag{5.4}$$

The set of atoms in \mathcal{K}_i generate the segment $[0, z_i]$. Next, we show that the set $\{z_i\}$ generates the center $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{P})$. First of all, z_i is compatible with every projection a_i in $[0, z_i]$ by weak modularity. But z_i is also compatible with every projection a_j in $[0, z_j]$, $j \neq i$, because z_i is compatible with every atom p_j in $[0, z_j]$ according to theorem 5.6 and, therefore, $z_i \leftrightarrow a_j = \bigvee_{p \leq a_j} p$ by theorem D.3. The segments $[0, z_i]$ are irreducible projection systems according to theorems 5.3 and 5.7 *i.e.* the projections 0 and z_i are the only contributions of the segment $[0, z_i]$ to the center $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{P})$.

³Frink [27], Piron [2], and Jauch [4] term perspectivity an equivalence relation therefore postulating reflexivity.

The considerations in section 5.1.5 entail that

$$\mathcal{P} \simeq \prod_i [0, z_i] \quad (5.5)$$

in the sense of a lattice isomorphism.

The proof of the theorem is, however, not yet accomplished with this result. The structure of the state space of \mathcal{P} must also be discussed in addition to its lattice structure. To this end, consider $z_i \neq z_j$. It is

$$z_i = z_i \wedge (z_j \vee z'_j) = (z_i \wedge z_j) \vee (z_i \wedge z'_j) = z_i \wedge z'_j$$

by equation (5.3), and it is, therefore, for arbitrary projections a in \mathcal{P}

$$\begin{aligned} (a \wedge z_i) \wedge (a \wedge z_j)' &= (a \wedge z_i) \wedge (a' \vee z'_j) \\ &= (a \wedge z_i \wedge a') \vee (a \wedge z_i \wedge z'_j) = 0 \vee (a \wedge z_i) = a \wedge z_i \end{aligned}$$

because all projections involved are mutually compatible. Therefore, $(a \wedge z_i) \perp (a \wedge z_j)$, and one obtains with equation (D.6), from the decomposition $a = a \wedge I = a \wedge (\bigvee_i z_i) = \bigvee_i (a \wedge z_i)$, and from the additivity of \mathcal{P} that

$$E_s(a) = \sum_i E_s(a \wedge z_i) \quad (5.6)$$

for any projection a in \mathcal{P} and all states s of the state space S . In particular, it is

$$1 = E_s(I) = \sum_i E_s(z_i) \quad \text{and} \quad 0 \leq E_s(a \wedge z_i) \leq E_s(z_i) \quad (5.7)$$

for all states s , all projections a , and every index i .

It is an important result derived at the end of the study that the lattice structure of an irreducible projection systems completely determines its state space (see section 7.4.3). In view of this result and of equation (5.7), we can construct a state $s_i(s)$ of the state space S_i of the projection system $[0, z_i]$ by the conditions

$$E_{s_i(s)}(z_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad E_s(a \wedge z_i) = \rho_i(s) E_{s_i(s)}(a \wedge z_i)$$

for all projections a . The case $a = I$ shows that $\rho_i(s) = E_s(z_i)$. Therefore,

$$E_s(a) = \sum_i E_s(a \wedge z_i) = \sum_i E_s(z_i) E_{s_i(s)}(a \wedge z_i) \quad (5.8)$$

i.e. the state s is a convex linear combination of the states $s_i(s)$

$$s = \sum_i E_s(z_i) s_i(s)$$

if we add the evident formal requirement that $E_{s_i(s)}(a \wedge z_j) = 0$ for $j \neq i$.

The segment $[0, z_i]$ is a projection system; the projection z_i plays the rôle of the unit with respect to the state space S_i of $[0, z_i]$: $E_{s_i}(z_i) = 1$ for all states s_i in S_i . This remark completes the proof of the theorem.

qed

Equations (5.5) and (5.8) indicate how the weakly modular but not distributive projection system \mathcal{P} decomposes into its irreducible components $[0, z_i]$. Every projection a in \mathcal{P} is split into its components $a \wedge z_i$ in the segments $[0, z_i]$, and every state s of the state space of \mathcal{P} is a convex linear combination of states s_i in the state space S_i of $[0, z_i]$, which contribute only to the expectation values of the component $a \wedge z_i$.

The central result of the analysis in this chapter is that only two different structural classes of projection systems occur: distributive projection systems and irreducible, non-distributive, but weakly modular projection systems. A quantum theory with irreducible operator algebra (*i.e.* only 0 and I commute with all operators) is an example of the second class. The aim of the present study is to show that this is the generic case, which reveals, in addition, that classical and quantum theories, introduced in [1] as examples of the formal structure of quantitative physical theories, are infact the only possibilities.

In view of the axioms B and C of Veblen and Young, we note that only *irreducible* projection systems of *finite rank not less than three* are projective geometries.

Chapter 6

The algebraic representation of irreducible projection systems of finite rank

In this chapter, a vector space is constructed whose system of subspaces is projectively equivalent to a given irreducible component of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} of finite rank not less than three. The main reference for this chapter is the textbook of R. Baer [8]. The basic notions and theorems of vector spaces are compiled in appendix E.

The close relationship between irreducible projection systems and projective geometries is worked out in section 4.2. We will take profit of this connection by using geometrical terms whenever appropriate: projections of rank 1 (atoms) are called *points*, projections of rank 2 *lines*, projections of rank 3 *planes*. Two different points p and q define the unique line $l = p \vee q$; two different lines l_1 and l_2 in a plane (the rank of the join $l_1 \vee l_2$ is equal to 3) meet in one point $l_1 \wedge l_2$; different points p_1, \dots, p_n are called *collinear* or *complanar* if the rank $\nu(\bigvee_{i=1}^n p_i)$ equals 2 or 3, respectively. A few line drawings serve for visualisation. However, all mathematical derivations will be strictly algebraical *i.e.* based on the postulates and the lattice theoretical methods and results stated in the previous chapters, in particular on the rank formula, theorem 4.3. We adopt Baer's compact exponential notation of projectivities $\pi : a \rightarrow a^\pi$ instead of the more common functional notation $\pi : a \rightarrow \pi(a)$. Note the reversal of order in the succession of maps: $a^{\pi_1 \pi_2} = (a^{\pi_1})^{\pi_2}$ corresponds to $\pi_2 \pi_1(a) = \pi_2(\pi_1(a))$.

6.1 Projectivities upon lattices

Let \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 denote two bounded and complete lattices. A *projectivity* π is a map of the elements of \mathcal{L}_1 upon the elements of \mathcal{L}_2 with the following properties:

(P1) If a is an element of \mathcal{L}_1 , then a^π is a uniquely determined element of \mathcal{L}_2 , and, for an element b in \mathcal{L}_2 , there exists one and only one element a in \mathcal{L}_1 such that $a^\pi = b$.

(P2) If a and b are elements of \mathcal{L}_1 , then $a \leq b$ if and only if $a^\pi \leq b^\pi$.

A projectivity is, therefore, a one-to-one, order preserving map of the set \mathcal{L}_1 onto the set \mathcal{L}_2 . \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 are (*projectively*) *equivalent* if there exists a projectivity between them. Projectively equivalent lattices are identical in terms of the order structure of lattices. In lattice theory, projectivities are also termed *lattice isomorphisms* [19, p. 28]. Additional properties of projectivities are readily deduced:

(P3) $a = b$ if and only if $a^\pi = b^\pi$; $a < b$ if and only if $a^\pi < b^\pi$.

(P4) Projectivities preserve join and meet.

This is a consequence of the definitions of join and meet as supremum and infimum of a finite or countably infinite set of elements in \mathcal{L} (see paragraph **B** in section 2.4).

(P5) $0_1^\pi = 0_2$ and $I_1^\pi = I_2$.

The projections 0 and I are defined by the condition $0 \leq a \leq I$ for all projections a .

(P6) Projectivities preserve the covering property and, hence, map atoms on atoms.

The projection a covers b if $b \leq x \leq a$ implies either $x = b$ or $x = a$. An atom covers 0 . A projectivity can, therefore, alternatively be defined as a one-to-one map of the set of atoms of \mathcal{L}_1 onto the set of atoms of \mathcal{L}_2 which preserves join and meet.

(P7) Projectivities preserve the relationships distributivity, (Di1) and (Di2), and modularity (3.1).

(P8) Projectivities map a set of dependent (independent) atoms on a set of dependent (independent) atoms.

This is a consequence of the fact that the notions of 'dependence and independence of atoms and of projections' are defined on the basis of the order relations \leq and $\not\leq$, see section 4.2. (P6) and (P8) entail

(P9) Projectivities map a basis onto a basis.

(P10) Projectivities preserve rank: if there exists a projectivity of \mathcal{L}_1 upon \mathcal{L}_2 , then $\nu(I_1) = \nu(I_2)$.

because an atom is a projection of rank 1 and every basis of a projection contains the same number of independent points.

It is trivial that every projectivity possesses an inverse. *Autoprojectivities* are projectivities of a bounded and complete lattice onto itself. An autoprojectivity is a *permutation* of the set of atoms of \mathcal{L} which preserves join and meet.

6.2 The theorem of Desargues

Desargue's theorem is a basic theorem of projective geometry and fundamental also for the analysis in this chapter. It is valid for irreducible projection systems of rank greater than three. The proof is crucially based on theorem 4.3.

Theorem 6.1 (Desargues) *In an irreducible projection system of finite rank greater than three, consider three different lines l_a, l_b, l_c that all contain the point p . The different points a_1 and a_2 are on l_a , the points b_1 and b_2 on l_b , the points c_1 and c_2 on l_c . None of the points $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, c_1, c_2$ is equal to p . Assume finally that $a_1 \vee b_1 \neq a_2 \vee b_2$, $a_1 \vee c_1 \neq a_2 \vee c_2$, and $b_1 \vee c_1 \neq b_2 \vee c_2$. Then $q \equiv (a_1 \vee b_1) \wedge (a_2 \vee b_2)$, $r \equiv (a_1 \vee c_1) \wedge (a_2 \vee c_2)$, and $s \equiv (b_1 \vee c_1) \wedge (b_2 \vee c_2)$ are three collinear points.*

Proof [26, p. 40] **(a)** Assume that the lines l_a, l_b, l_c are *complanar*. Let l_p be a line containing the point p but not being contained in the plane $a_1 \vee b_1 \vee c_1 = a_2 \vee b_2 \vee c_2$ and denote by p_1 and p_2 any two points on l_p different from p . The lines $a_1 \vee p_1$ and $a_2 \vee p_2$ precede the plane $l_a \vee l_p$ and intersect in a point a . Similarly, the lines $b_1 \vee p_1$ and $b_2 \vee p_2$ intersect in a point b , and $c_1 \vee p_1$ and $c_2 \vee p_2$ intersect in a point c . The points $p_1,$

a, a_1 precede the line $l_{1a} = a \vee a_1 = a \vee p_1$ and the points p_1, b, b_1 precede the line $l_{1b} = b \vee b_1 = b \vee p_1$, and it is $l_{1a} \wedge l_{1b} = p_1$. This implies that the points a, a_1, b, b_1 all precede the plane $p_1 \vee a \vee b$. The lines $a \vee b$ and $a_1 \vee b_1$ meet, therefore, in a point q , which precedes, in addition, the plane $p \vee a_1 \vee b_1$ because $q \leq a_1 \vee b_1$. The line $a \vee b$ does not precede in the plane $p \vee a_1 \vee b_1 = p \vee a_2 \vee b_2$ and meets this plane in one point, namely in q . Hence, the lines $a \vee b$ and $a_2 \vee b_2$ also meet in q . Similarly, the lines $a \vee c, a_1 \vee c_1$, and $a_2 \vee c_2$ meet in a point r , and $b \vee c, b_1 \vee c_1$, and $b_2 \vee c_2$ meet in s . The distinct points q, r, s all precede the different planes $a \vee b \vee c$ and $a_1 \vee b_1 \vee c_1 = a_2 \vee b_2 \vee c_2$, which meet in a line. Hence, the points q, r, s are collinear. The steps of the above proof rely on repeated applications of theorem 4.3.

(b) Consider the system of the points $p_1, a, a_1, b, b_1, c, c_1$ and of the lines $l_{1a} = a \vee a_1, l_{1b} = b \vee b_1, l_{1c} = c \vee c_1$ constructed in paragraph (a). This system of points and lines meets all presuppositions of Desargue's theorem: the lines l_{1a}, l_{1b} , and l_{1c} are different and meet in the point p_1 , but they are *not complanar*, the distinct points a and a_1 precede the line l_{1a} , and so on. The line l_p not preceding the plane $a_1 \vee b_1 \vee c_1$ meets this plane in the point p , and the lines $l_a = p \vee a_1, l_b = p \vee b_1, l_c = p \vee c_1$ are complanar. It follows from the considerations in (a) that $q = (a \vee b) \wedge (a_1 \vee b_1), r = (a \vee c) \wedge (a_1 \vee c_1)$, and $s = (b \vee c) \wedge (b_1 \vee c_1)$ are three collinear points.

qed

Desargues' theorem is valid for projective geometries of rank three if they are embedded in projective geometries of finite rank greater than three. Desargues' theorem need not to be valid for not embedded projective geometries of rank three; the Moulton plane provides a counterexample.

Figure 6.1: Desargues' Theorem

6.3 The representation theorem for irreducible projection systems of finite rank

The considerations in this section resulting in theorem 6.3 follow the presentation by R. Baer [8, VII.5], which exceedingly well accords with the results derived in the previous chapters. Throughout in this section, a and b denote projections in an irreducible component of \mathcal{P}_{PHS} of finite rank. The rank $\nu(a)$ of a is greater or equal than three and a covers b , i.e. $\nu(a) = \nu(b) + 1 \geq 3$. In addition, the validity of Desargues' theorem is assumed if $\nu(a) = 3$. The fact that these components are orthocomplemented will not be used in the considerations of this section.

Some definitions are needed. \mathcal{S}_a denotes the segment $[0, a]$, $\mathcal{S}_b \equiv [0, b]$. \mathcal{S}_a and \mathcal{S}_b are irreducible, modular projection systems according to theorem 4.4.

The set Γ_b^a is the set of all autoprojectivities π of \mathcal{S}_a with the property that $c^\pi = c$ for every projection $c \leq b$. It is obvious that the projectivities in Γ_b^a form a group. By definition, every point $p \leq b$ is a fixed point of every projectivity π in Γ_b^a , $p^\pi = p$.

A point $p \leq a$ is a center of the projectivity π in Γ_b^a if

(ce) $c \vee p = c^\pi \vee p$ for every projection $c \leq a$.

If p is a center of π and $c \equiv q \neq p$ is a point, then property (ce) states that p , q , and q^π are collinear. The case $q = p$ reveals that a center p of the projection π is a fixed point, $p^\pi = p$. If p is a fixed point of π , then it is also a fixed point of π^{-1} . If p is a center of π , then it is also a center of π^{-1} . Property (ce) implies that $c \vee p = (c \vee p)^\pi$ for any projection $c \leq a$. If property (ce) is valid for all points preceding a projection $c \leq a$, then (ce) is valid for c , too. The identity projectivity, $c^\pi = c$ for all projections $c \leq a$, is denoted by $\pi = 1$.

Lemma 6.1 [8, p. 292] *Every projectivity $\pi \neq 1$ in Γ_b^a possesses exactly one center (which we denote by $z(\pi)$).*

Proof (a) We show, first, that every point r preceding a is a fixed point of π if π has two centers. Assume, therefore, that the distinct points p and q are both centers of the projectivity π in Γ_b^a and consider a third point $r \leq a$. If $r \leq b$, then $r^\pi = r$ according to the definition of Γ_b^a .

If $r \not\leq b$ and $r \not\leq p \vee q$, then it follows from property (ce) that $r \vee p = r^\pi \vee p$ and $r \vee q = r^\pi \vee q$. Because $r \vee p$ and $r \vee q$ are different lines, it is

$$r = (r \vee p) \wedge (r \vee q) = (r^\pi \vee p) \wedge (r^\pi \vee q) = ((r \vee p) \wedge (r \vee q))^\pi = r^\pi$$

If, finally, $r \not\leq b$ but $r \leq p \vee q$, then consider a point $s \leq a$ with $s \not\leq b$ and $s \not\leq p \vee q$. Then $s^\pi = s$ as already shown. It is $r \vee s \leq a$ by monotony (Mo3) and $r \vee s \not\leq b$ by hypothesis. Because $\nu(b) = \nu(a) - 1$ and according to theorem 4.3, the meet $t = b \wedge (r \vee s)$ is a point which is different from r and from s because $t \leq b$. Furthermore, $t \leq r \vee s$ implies $t \vee s \leq r \vee s$ and $t \vee s = r \vee s$ because $t \vee s$ and $r \vee s$ are both of rank 2 (see the proof of theorem 4.4). Therefore,

$$r = (r \vee s) \wedge (p \vee q) = (t \vee s) \wedge (p \vee q) = (t^\pi \vee s^\pi) \wedge (p^\pi \vee q^\pi) = ((r \vee s) \wedge (p \vee q))^\pi = r^\pi$$

Hence, we have shown that every point $r \leq a$ is a fixed point of π if π has two centers. But every projection $c \leq a$ is the join of points by theorem 4.2 and, therefore, $c = c^\pi$ by property (P4) and $\pi = 1$. It follows that projectivities in Γ_b^a different from 1 have at most one center.

(b) We show now that the projectivity $\pi \neq 1$ in Γ_b^a possesses at least one center. We distinguish two cases:

Case 1 There exists a fixed point r of π with $r \leq a$ and $r \not\leq b$. If s with $s \leq a$ and $s \not\leq b$ is a point different from r , then $t = b \wedge (r \vee s)$ is a third point. It follows from lemma 4.7 that $r \vee t = r \vee s$. Clearly, $t^\pi = t$ and, therefore,

$$r \vee s = r \vee t = r^\pi \vee t^\pi = (r \vee t)^\pi = (r \vee s)^\pi = r^\pi \vee s^\pi = r \vee s^\pi \quad (6.1)$$

and r is the center of π according to property (ce). Equation (6.1) is trivially true for $s \leq b$.

Case 2 Every fixed point of π precedes b . Consider two different points r and s preceding a neither of which precedes b . The point $t = b \wedge (r \vee s)$ is a fixed point of π . Furthermore, $r \vee r^\pi$ and $s \vee s^\pi$ are well determined different lines because neither r nor s is a fixed point. Therefore, again with $r \vee s = r \vee t$,

$$\begin{aligned} r \vee r^\pi \vee s \vee s^\pi &= r^\pi \vee r \vee t \vee s^\pi = r^\pi \vee r \vee t^\pi \vee s^\pi \\ &= r^\pi \vee r \vee (t \vee s)^\pi = r^\pi \vee r \vee (r \vee s)^\pi \\ &= r \vee r^\pi \vee s^\pi \end{aligned}$$

which implies that the different lines $r \vee r^\pi$ and $s \vee s^\pi$ are complanar and that $(r \vee r^\pi) \wedge (s \vee s^\pi) \equiv u$ is a point. In addition, $b \wedge (r \vee r^\pi) \equiv v \leq r \vee r^\pi$ is a fixed point and it is

$$r \vee r^\pi = r^\pi \vee v = r^\pi \vee v^\pi = (r \vee v)^\pi = (r \vee r^\pi)^\pi$$

and likewise $s \vee s^\pi = (s \vee s^\pi)^\pi$. Hence

$$u = (r \vee r^\pi) \wedge (s \vee s^\pi) = (r \vee r^\pi)^\pi \wedge (s \vee s^\pi)^\pi = ((r \vee r^\pi) \wedge (s \vee s^\pi))^\pi = u^\pi$$

and u is a fixed point and, hence, $u \leq b$. In addition, $u \leq r \vee r^\pi$ and $u = v$ because the meet $b \wedge (r \vee r^\pi)$ is a single point. Therefore, we have shown that if $r \not\leq b$ and $s \not\leq b$ are points preceding a , then the lines $r \vee r^\pi$ and $s \vee s^\pi$ are invariant under π and it is

$$b \wedge (r \vee r^\pi) = b \wedge (s \vee s^\pi) = v$$

All lines $r \vee r^\pi$ with $r \not\leq b$ meet in the same point $v \leq b$ which is the center of π .

qed

It is appropriate to discuss now the case $\nu(a) = 2$. The projection b is then a point preceding the line a and the set Γ_b^a consists of all one-to-one maps π of the points preceding the line a onto the points preceding a which leave the point b invariant. Assume now that p is a center of the projectivity π in Γ_b^a and that r is a point preceding a . The defining property (ce) of a center, $r \vee p = r^\pi \vee p$, solely expresses here that the center p is a fixed point if $r = p$, and, for $r \neq p$, the triviality that r and r^π precede a . These conditions do not exclude that a second point $q \neq p$ preceding a is also a center of π . Or, as for the part (a) of the foregoing proof, it is always $r \leq p \vee q = a$ if $\nu(a) = 2$ and the case $r \not\leq b$, $r \not\leq p \vee q$ necessary to conclude the argument is wanting.

Lemma 6.2 [8, p. 294] *If p, q, r are three different but collinear points preceding a and $p \not\leq b$ and $q \not\leq b$, then there exists one and only one projectivity π in Γ_b^a such that r is its center $z(\pi)$ and $q = p^\pi$.*

Proof (a) Uniqueness of the projectivity π . Assume that there are two projectivities π_1 and π_2 with $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2) = r$ and $p^{\pi_1} = p^{\pi_2} = q$. Then the projectivity $\pi' \equiv \pi_2^{-1}\pi_1$ is in Γ_b^a and satisfies $p = p^{\pi'}$, $r = r^{\pi'}$ and $c^{\pi'} \vee r \equiv c^{\pi_2^{-1}\pi_1} \vee r = c^{\pi_1} \vee r = c \vee r$ for every projection $c \leq a$ i.e. $r = z(\pi')$. Because $a = p \vee b$, it is

$$p \vee c = (p \vee b) \wedge (p \vee c) = p \vee (b \wedge (p \vee c))$$

Figure 6.2: Case 1a

The second step is an application of the modular law [if $u \leq v$, then $(u \vee w) \wedge v = u \vee (w \wedge v)$] with $u = p$, $v = p \vee c$, $w = b$; remember that \mathcal{S}_a is modular. Both atoms p and $b \wedge (p \vee c) \leq b$ are invariant under π' . Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} p \vee c &= p \vee (b \wedge (p \vee c)) = p^{\pi'} (b \wedge (p \vee c))^{\pi'} \\ &= (p \vee (b \wedge (p \vee c)))^{\pi'} = (p \vee c)^{\pi'} = p^{\pi'} \vee c^{\pi'} = p \vee c^{\pi'} \end{aligned}$$

for every projection $c \leq a$ which reveals that p is a center of π' in Γ_b^a in addition to the center r . It follows from lemma 6.1 that $\pi' = 1$ or $\pi_1 = \pi_2$: the projectivity π of the lemma is unique.

(b) Existence of the projectivity π . Baer begins this second part of the proof with a remark: "To prove the existence of at least one transformation meeting our requirements it will be convenient to exclude the case when one [and consequently every] line carries exactly three points. In the case when lines carry just three points our method will not be workable, but a slightly simpler, though similar method may be used; and thus we leave the details in this case as an exercise to the reader." [8, p. 294]. Clearly, this exceptional case is of no importance in our context.

Consider now any line l_p through p which is different from the line $p \vee r$. The line l_p has one and only one point $l_p \wedge b$ in common with b because

$$\nu(l_p \wedge b) = \nu(l_p) + \nu(b) - \nu(l_p \vee b) = 2 + \nu(b) - \nu(a) = 1$$

by theorem 4.3. Choose points p_1 and p_2 different from p with $p_1, p_2 \leq l_p$ but $p_1, p_2 \not\leq b$. As a consequence, $p \vee r, p_1 \vee r$, and $p_2 \vee r$ are three different lines through the point r which all precede the plane $l_p \vee r$ but do not precede b .

The point p, q, r are collinear by hypothesis. Set now

$$l_q = (l_p \wedge b) \vee q, \quad q_1 = l_q \wedge (p_1 \vee r), \quad q_2 = l_q \wedge (p_2 \vee r)$$

q, q_1, q_2 are well determined points all not preceding b , and $q, q_1, q_2, l_p \wedge b$ are four different points that all precede l_q . It follows from $l_q \geq l_p \wedge b$ that $l_q \wedge b \geq l_p \wedge b \wedge b = l_p \wedge b$ by monotony (Mo2) and idempotence and, in addition, $l_q \wedge b = l_p \wedge b$ because $\nu(l_q \wedge b) = \nu(l_p \wedge b) = 1$.

Consider a point $x \leq a$, $x \neq r$, and $x \not\leq b$. This point x can precede at most one of the three different lines $p \vee r, p_1 \vee r, p_2 \vee r$. Assume that $x \not\leq p \vee r$ and $x \not\leq p_1 \vee r$. We distinguish now three cases:

Case 1a $x \leq l_p$. Then $x^* = l_q \wedge (x \vee r)$ is a well defined point preceding the line l_q and the points $l_p \wedge b = l_q \wedge b, r, x, p, p_1, p_2, x^*, q, q_1, q_2$ all precede the plane $l_p \vee r$.

Case 1b $x \leq l_q$. The positions of the points x and x^* are interchanged.

Figure 6.3: Case 2

Case 2 $x \not\leq l_p$ and $x \not\leq l_q$. The plane $l_p \vee x = p \vee p_1 \vee x$ meets b in the line $l = (p \vee p_1 \vee x) \wedge b$ because it is by theorem 4.3

$$\nu(l) = \nu((p \vee p_1 \vee x) \wedge b) = \nu(p \vee p_1 \vee x) + \nu(b) - \nu(p \vee p_1 \vee x \vee b) = 3 + \nu(b) - \nu(a) = 2$$

The points $(p \vee p_1) \wedge b$, $(p \vee x) \wedge b$, and $(p_1 \vee x) \wedge b$ precede l and the lines l , l_p , and l_q meet in the point $(p \vee p_1) \wedge b$. The line $p \vee x$ meets b in the point $(p \vee x) \wedge b$, and the line $p_1 \vee x$ meets b in an other point $(p_1 \vee x) \wedge b$. Corresponding sides of the triangles $p, q, (p \vee x) \wedge b$ and $p_1, q_1, (p_1 \vee x) \wedge b$ meet in the points

$$\begin{aligned} (p \vee q) \wedge (p_1 \vee q_1) &= r \\ (p \vee [(p \vee x) \wedge b]) \wedge (p_1 \vee [(p_1 \vee x) \wedge b]) &= x \\ (q \vee [(p \vee x) \wedge b]) \wedge (q_1 \vee [(p_1 \vee x) \wedge b]) &= x^* \end{aligned}$$

These three points are collinear by Desargue's theorem 6.1 i.e. $x^* \leq x \vee r$, and it is $x^* \leq q \vee [(p \vee x) \wedge b]$, $x^* \leq q_1 \vee [(p_1 \vee x) \wedge b]$. Hence, the lines $x \vee r$, $q \vee [(p \vee x) \wedge b]$, $q_1 \vee [(p_1 \vee x) \wedge b]$ have the point x^* in common. Furthermore, it is $(p \vee x) \wedge b \leq p \vee x$ and $(p \vee x) \wedge b \leq q \vee x^*$ by equation (5.1). The point $x \leq x \vee r$ neither precedes $p \vee r$ nor $p_1 \vee r$ because r is the only point common to $x \vee r$ and $p \vee r$, and to $x \vee r$ and $p_1 \vee r$. The result of this discussion may be restated in the following

Lemma (a) *If the point x is neither precedes $p \vee r$ nor $p_1 \vee r$ nor b , then*

$$(x \vee r) \wedge [q \vee (p \vee x) \wedge b] = (x \vee r) \wedge [q_1 \vee (p_1 \vee x) \wedge b]$$

is a well determined point x^ and it is $(p \vee x) \wedge (q \vee x^*) = (p \vee x) \wedge b$.*

Analogous statements can be derived if $x \not\leq p \vee r$ and $x \not\leq p_2 \vee r$, or if $x \not\leq p_1 \vee r$ and $x \not\leq p_2 \vee r$. With all these results, a point to point map $x \rightarrow x^*$ can be defined according to the following rules:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
x^* = x & \text{if } x = r \text{ or if } x \leq b \\
x^* = q & \text{if } x = p \\
x^* = p & \text{if } x = q \\
x^* = (x \vee r) \wedge (q \vee [(p \vee x) \wedge b]) & \text{if } x \not\leq p \vee r \\
x^* = (x \vee r) \wedge (q_1 \vee [(p_1 \vee x) \wedge b]) & \text{if } x \not\leq p_1 \vee r \\
x^* = (x \vee r) \wedge (q_2 \vee [(p_2 \vee x) \wedge b]) & \text{if } x \not\leq p_2 \vee r
\end{array}$$

It is a consequence of lemma (a) that the map $x \rightarrow x^*$ is a single valued map from points to points. An other single valued map $x^* \rightarrow x$ is obtained by interchanging the rôles of p and q throughout in the above derivation. Consequently, the map $x \rightarrow x^*$ is a one-to-one map from points of \mathcal{S}_a onto points of \mathcal{S}_a whose only fixed points are r and the points preceding b . Finally, x, x^*, r are three different collinear points in all cases except the first.

Suppose now that x and y are two different points neither of which is equal to r and neither of which precedes b . It is impossible that x and y precede all the three different lines $p \vee r, p_1 \vee r, p_2 \vee r$. Therefore, one may assume without loss of generality that neither x nor y precedes $p \vee r$. Assume that $x \vee y$ and $x^* \vee y^*$ are different lines, which implies that $x \vee x^*$ and $y \vee y^*$ are different lines, too. The three lines $p \vee q, x \vee x^*, y \vee y^*$ are different and meet all in the point r by the definition of the $*$ -map and by the hypothesis that p, q, r are collinear. The corresponding lines of the triangles p, x, y and q, x^*, y^* meet in the points

$$\begin{aligned}
(p \vee x) \wedge (q \vee x^*) &= (p \vee x) \wedge b \\
(p \vee y) \wedge (q \vee y^*) &= (p \vee y) \wedge b \\
(x \vee y) \wedge (x^* \vee y^*) &
\end{aligned}$$

according to lemma (a). These three points are collinear by Desargues' theorem. The first two points precede b and so does the total line $((p \vee x) \wedge b) \vee ((p \vee y) \wedge b)$ and, hence, also the point $(x \vee y) \wedge (x^* \vee y^*)$. Neither $x \vee y$ nor $x^* \vee y^*$ precede b which means that the lines $x \vee y$ and $x^* \vee y^*$ meet b in the same point namely in $(x \vee y) \wedge (x^* \vee y^*)$. Therefore, we have shown the following statement:

Lemma (b) *If x and y are two different points neither of which precedes b , then $(x \vee y) \wedge b = (x^* \vee y^*) \wedge b = (x \vee y) \wedge (x^* \vee y^*)$.*

We consider, next, a projection $d, 0 < d \leq a$. According to theorem 4.2, the projection d possesses a finite basis $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ of points x_k such that $d = \bigvee_{k=1}^n x_k$. We define the projection d^π by

$$d^\pi = \bigvee_{k=1}^n x_k^* \quad (6.2)$$

Clearly, $a^\pi = a$, and $0 < c \leq d \leq a$ implies $0 < c^\pi \leq d^\pi$. In order to verify properties (P1) and (P2) for the map $d \rightarrow d^\pi$, it remains to show that, conversely, $c^\pi \leq d^\pi$ implies $c \leq d$.

It is already established that the map between the points x and x^* is one-to-one. In addition, the set $\{x_1^*, \dots, x_n^*\}$ is independent and, hence, a basis of d^π . We show now that $x \leq d$ if $x^* \leq d^\pi$.

For any point $x^* \leq d^\pi$, there is an index $k, 1 \leq k \leq n$, such that $x^* \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^k x_i^*$ but $x^* \not\leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^*$. The proof of the assertion $x \leq d$ is performed by induction:

$k = 1$: If $x^* = x_1^*$, then $x = x_1$.

$2 \leq k \leq n$: Assume that $y^* \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^*$ implies $y \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i$ and take a point x^* such that $x^* \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^k x_i^*$ but $x^* \not\leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^*$. One has to show that $x \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^k x_i$ in consideration of the induction hypothesis.

Figure 6.4: Lemma (b)

If $x^* = x_k^*$, then $x = x_k$ as above. Hence, we assume that $x^* \neq x_k^*$. Then $x^* \vee x_k^* \equiv l^*$ is a line and $x^* \vee x_k^* \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^k x_i^*$ by monotony (Mo3), and it follows from the modular law (3.1) that

$$l^* = x^* \vee x_k^* = \bigvee_{i=1}^k x_i^* \wedge (x^* \vee x_k^*) = \left(x_k^* \vee \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^* \right) \wedge (x^* \vee x_k^*) = x_k^* \vee \left(\bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^* \wedge (x^* \vee x_k^*) \right) = x_k^* \vee y^*$$

with

$$y^* \equiv \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^* \wedge (x^* \vee x_k^*) \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^*$$

(Choose $x_k^* = a$, $x^* \vee x_k^* = b$, and $\bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^* = c$). Now, l^* is a line, and it is $x^* \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^k x_i^*$ and $x^* \not\leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i^*$ by hypothesis. Therefore, y^* is a point according to theorem 4.3, and it is $y \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i$ by the induction hypothesis.

It follows from $y^* \leq x^* \vee x_k^*$ and from lemma 4.5 that

$$l^* \equiv x^* \vee x_k^* = x_k^* \vee y^* = x^* \vee y^* \quad (6.3)$$

As a consequence, $y^* \neq x_k^*$, $y^* \neq x^*$, and x^* , y^* , x_k^* are collinear points.

If two of the different points y^* , x^* , x_k^* precede b , then all these points precede b and, therefore, fixed points. If one of the points y^* , x^* , x_k^* , e.g. x_k^* , precedes b , then it follows from lemma (b) and from $x_k^* \leq x^* \vee y^*$ that $x_k^* = x_k$ is the common intersection of the lines $x^* \vee y^*$ and $x \vee y$ with b i.e. $x_k \leq x \vee y$. If none of three points y^* , x^* , x_k^* precedes b , then $l^* \wedge b$ is a point different from y^* , x^* , x_k^* . It follows from lemma (b) and from equation (6.3) that this point $l^* \wedge b$ precedes the lines $x \vee y$, $x_k \vee y$, and $x \vee x_k$ so that y , x , x_k are collinear. Hence, it is true in every case that

$$x \leq y \vee x_k \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i \vee x_k = \bigvee_{i=1}^k x_i$$

This completes the induction step and, with $k = n$, the proof that the point $x \leq d$ whenever $x^\pi \equiv x^* \leq d^\pi$.

Hence, properties (P1) and (P2) are verified for atoms. Consider now two projections c and d with $c^\pi < d^\pi$. According to lemma 4.6, there exists an orthogonal basis $\{p_1^*, \dots, p_m^*\}$ of c^π which can be extended to an orthogonal basis $\{p_1^*, \dots, p_m^*, \dots, p_n^*\}$, $n > m$, of d^π . Hence, there exist three projections $c^\pi = \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i^*$, $e^\pi = \bigvee_{i=m+1}^n p_i^*$, $d^\pi = \bigvee_{i=1}^n p_i^*$ and, in accordance with the definition (6.2) of the map π and with the result just obtained, it is $c = \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i$, $e = \bigvee_{i=m+1}^n p_i > 0$, $d = \bigvee_{i=1}^n p_i$ implying $d = c \vee e$ or $c \leq d$. The map π fulfills, therefore, the properties (P1) and (P2) of a projectivity. In addition, all points $p \leq b$ are fixed points of π . Therefore, if $c \leq b$ then

$$c^\pi = \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i^* = \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i^\pi = \bigvee_{i=1}^m p_i = c$$

which is the defining property of a projectivity in Γ_b^a . Finally, we have $p^\pi = p^* = q$ and $x \vee r = x^* \vee r = x^\pi \vee r$ for any point $x \leq a$. Hence, $r = z(\pi)$ according to the definition (ce) of a center, and this completes the proof of lemma 6.2.

qed

According to lemma 6.2 there is exactly one projectivity π^{-1} with $z(\pi^{-1}) = r$ and $p = q^{\pi^{-1}}$ which shows again that $z(\pi^{-1}) = z(\pi)$.

Lemma 6.3 [8, p. 297] *If the projectivities π_1 , π_2 , and $\pi_1\pi_2$ in Γ_b^a are all different from 1, then $z(\pi_1\pi_2) \leq z(\pi_1) \vee z(\pi_2)$.*

Proof (a) If $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2) \equiv z$, then it follows from property (ce) that

$$c \vee z = c_1^\pi \vee z = (c^{\pi_1})^{\pi_2} \vee z = c^{\pi_1\pi_2} \vee z$$

for any projection $c \leq a$ and that $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2) = z(\pi_1\pi_2)$.

(b) Assume now that $z(\pi_1)$ and $z(\pi_2)$ are different points. Choose a line $l \leq a$, $l \not\leq b$ such that neither $z(\pi_1)$ nor $z(\pi_2)^{\pi_1^{-1}}$ nor $z(\pi_1\pi_2)$ precede l . The meet $l \wedge b \leq b$ is a point, and it is

$$l \wedge b = (l \wedge b)^{\pi_1} = (l \wedge b)^{\pi_2} = (l \wedge b)^{\pi_1\pi_2}$$

Let $x \not\leq b$ and $y \not\leq b$ denote two different points preceding l . The lines

$$l = x \vee y, \quad l^{\pi_1} = x^{\pi_1} \vee y^{\pi_1}, \quad l^{\pi_1\pi_2} = x^{\pi_1\pi_2} \vee y^{\pi_1\pi_2}$$

all meet in the point $l \wedge b$ and are all different because *e.g.* $l = l^{\pi_1}$ implies that the points $x, x^{\pi_1}, y, y^{\pi_1}$ all precede l and, hence, also $z(\pi_1) \leq l$ contrary to the hypothesis. The lines $x \vee x^{\pi_1}$ and $y \vee y^{\pi_1}$ are different and meet in $z(\pi_1)$, the lines $x^{\pi_1} \vee x^{\pi_1\pi_2}$ and $y^{\pi_1} \vee y^{\pi_1\pi_2}$ are different and meet in $z(\pi_2)$, and the lines $x \vee x^{\pi_1\pi_2}$ and $y \vee y^{\pi_1\pi_2}$ are different and meet in $z(\pi_1\pi_2)$. The triangles $x, x^{\pi_1}, x^{\pi_1\pi_2}$ and $y, y^{\pi_1}, y^{\pi_1\pi_2}$ represent the configuration of Desargues' theorem 6.1 which entails that $z(\pi_1)$, $z(\pi_2)$, and $z(\pi_1\pi_2)$ are collinear.

qed

With these preparations, we are ready to derive the desired algebraic equivalence of the irreducible projection system \mathcal{S}_b being covered by a projection system \mathcal{S}_a of finite rank not less than three. The validity of Desargues' theorem is assumed if the rank $\nu(a) = 3$. The basic algebraic terms and theorems used in the following discussions are taken from chapter III of Ref. [8] and from Ref. [25].

We remind of the following alternative for projectivities π in Γ_b^a , the set of all autoprojectivities π of \mathcal{S}_a with the property that $c^\pi = c$ for every projection $c \leq b$: it is either $\pi = 1$ and every point preceding a is a center, or else $\pi \neq 1$ and π possesses exactly one center $z(\pi)$ according to lemma 6.1.

An additional definition is needed: let $c \leq a$ be a projection. Then $\Gamma(c)$ is the set of all projectivities π in Γ_b^a with center $z(\pi) \leq c$ the projectivity $\pi = 1$ being added. We define $\Gamma(0) = \{1\}$, $\mathcal{A} \equiv \Gamma(a) = \Gamma_b^a$, and $\mathcal{B} \equiv \Gamma(b)$. It follows from monotony (Mo3) that $p \vee q$ precedes c if the points p and q precede c and, hence, from lemma 6.3 that the elements of $\Gamma(c)$ form a group.

Lemma 6.4 [8, p. 298]

- (i) \mathcal{B} is a normal subgroup of \mathcal{A} .
- (ii) \mathcal{B} is a commutative group.
- (iii) Mapping the projection $c \leq b$ upon $\Gamma(c) \subseteq \Gamma(b) \equiv \mathcal{B}$ is a projectivity.
- (iv) The endomorphisms η of the group \mathcal{B} satisfying $\Gamma(c)^\eta \subseteq \Gamma(c)$ for every element $c \leq b$ form a field \mathbb{F} .
- (v) The subgroup \mathcal{D} of \mathcal{B} satisfies $\mathcal{D}^\mathbb{F} \subseteq \mathcal{D}$ if and only if $\mathcal{D} = \Gamma(d)$ for some $d \leq b$.

Proof (i) \mathcal{B} is a subgroup of the group \mathcal{A} as already stated. If $\pi_1 \neq 1$ and π_2 are projectivities in \mathcal{A} , then it is for any projection $c \leq a$

$$\begin{aligned} c \vee z(\pi_1)^{\pi_2} &= (c^{\pi_2^{-1}} \vee z(\pi_1))^{\pi_2} \\ &= (c^{\pi_2^{-1}\pi_1} \vee z(\pi_1))^{\pi_2} \\ &= c^{\pi_2^{-1}\pi_1\pi_2} \vee z(\pi_1)^{\pi_2} \end{aligned}$$

It follows from the defining property (ce) of a center that $z(\pi_1)^{\pi_2} = z(\pi_2^{-1}\pi_1\pi_2)$. If, in particular, $\pi_1 \subseteq \mathcal{B}$ i.e. $z(\pi_1) \leq b$, then

$$z(\pi_2^{-1}\pi_1\pi_2) = z(\pi_1)^{\pi_2} = z(\pi_1) \quad (6.4)$$

for all projectivities π_2 in \mathcal{A} , which means that, together with π_1 , also $\pi_2^{-1}\pi_1\pi_2$ is in \mathcal{B} , or that $\pi_2^{-1}\mathcal{B}\pi_2 = \mathcal{B}$, or $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}$, respectively.

(ii) (a) Assume that $\pi_1 \neq 1$ and $\pi_2 \neq 1$ are in \mathcal{B} and $z(\pi_1) \neq z(\pi_2)$. Let $p \leq a$ be a point not preceding b and different from $z(\pi_1)$ and $z(\pi_2)$. Then, by property (ce), the points $p, p^{\pi_1}, z(\pi_1)$ are collinear and the points $p, p^{\pi_2}, z(\pi_2)$ are collinear, too. It is shown in the proof of lemma 6.1 that a fixed point $p^\pi = p \not\leq b$ is the center of π . Therefore, $p \neq p^{\pi_1} \not\leq b$ and $p \neq p^{\pi_2} \not\leq b$. The lines $l_1 = p \vee p^{\pi_1}$ and $l_2 = p \vee p^{\pi_2}$ meet in p , but meet b in the different points $z(\pi_1)$ and $z(\pi_2)$. These lines are, thus, different. Now it is, on the one hand, $p^{\pi_1\pi_2} \leq p^{\pi_1} \vee z(\pi_2)$. On the other hand, $p^{\pi_1} \leq p \vee z(\pi_1)$ implies with equation (6.4) that

$$p^{\pi_1\pi_2} \leq (p \vee z(\pi_1))^{\pi_2} = p^{\pi_2} \vee z(\pi_1)^{\pi_2} = p^{\pi_2} \vee z(\pi_1)$$

Therefore

$$p^{\pi_1\pi_2} = (p^{\pi_1} \vee z(\pi_2)) \wedge (p^{\pi_2} \vee z(\pi_1)) = p^{\pi_2\pi_1}$$

for all points $p \not\leq b$. For points $p \leq b$, the equality $p^{\pi_1\pi_2} = p^{\pi_2\pi_1}$ is valid anyway and, therefore, $\pi_1\pi_2 = \pi_2\pi_1$ if $z(\pi_1) \neq z(\pi_2)$.

(b) Assume now that $\pi_1 \neq 1$ and $\pi_2 \neq 1$ are in \mathcal{B} and $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2)$. According to lemma 6.2, there is a projectivity $\pi \neq 1$ in \mathcal{B} such that $z(\pi) \neq z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2)$. It is $z(\pi^{-1}) = z(\pi)$, and $\pi_1\pi = \pi\pi_1$ and $\pi_2\pi^{-1} = \pi^{-1}\pi_2$ as already shown. If $z(\pi\pi_1)$ is equal to $z(\pi_2\pi^{-1})$, then by lemma 6.3

$$z(\pi\pi_1) = z(\pi_2\pi^{-1}) = z(\pi_2\pi^{-1}\pi\pi_1) = z(\pi_2\pi_1) = z(\pi_2) = z(\pi_1)$$

But it is $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi\pi_1) \leq z(\pi) \vee z(\pi_1)$ again by lemma 6.3, which implies that the points $z(\pi)$ and $z(\pi_1)$ are identical contrary to our choice of π . Hence, $z(\pi\pi_1) \neq z(\pi_2\pi^{-1})$ and it follows from the results obtained in (a) that

$$\pi_2\pi_1 = \pi_2\pi^{-1}\pi\pi_1 = \pi\pi_1\pi_2\pi^{-1} = \pi_1\pi\pi^{-1}\pi_2 = \pi_1\pi_2$$

and this completes the proof of the commutativity of \mathcal{B} . Note that the condition $\nu(b) \geq 2$ is necessary for the proof.

(iii) Consider projections c and d such that $c < d \leq b$. It is an immediate consequence of the definition of the groups $\Gamma(\cdot)$ that $\Gamma(c) \subseteq \Gamma(d) \subseteq \Gamma(b) \equiv \mathcal{B}$. It follows from lemma 4.6 that there exists a point p such that $p \leq d$ but $p \not\leq c$. By lemma 6.2, there exists a projectivity $\pi \neq 1$ with $z(\pi) = p$. Then π belongs to $\Gamma(d)$ but not to $\Gamma(c)$ and it is $\Gamma(c) \subset \Gamma(d)$ which implies statement (iii).

(iv) We first recall the definition of an *endomorphism* η of the (commutative) group \mathcal{B} in an exponential notation: η is a one-to-one map $\pi \in \mathcal{B} \rightarrow \pi^\eta \in \mathcal{B}^\eta \subseteq \mathcal{B}$ defined for all projectivities π in \mathcal{B} such that

$$(\pi_1\pi_2)^\eta = \pi_1^\eta\pi_2^\eta = \pi_2^\eta\pi_1^\eta = (\pi_2\pi_1)^\eta$$

An associative but not necessarily commutative *multiplication* of endomorphisms is given by

$$\pi^{(\eta_1\eta_2)} = (\pi^{\eta_1})^{\eta_2}$$

with *neutral element* $\eta = 1$: $\pi^1 = \pi$ for every projectivity π in \mathcal{B} .

\mathcal{B} is a commutative group. This allows to define an associative and commutative *addition* of endomorphisms

$$\pi^{(\eta_1 + \eta_2)} \equiv \pi^{\eta_1}\pi^{\eta_2} = \pi^{\eta_2}\pi^{\eta_1} \equiv \pi^{(\eta_2 + \eta_1)}$$

with *neutral element* $\eta = 0$: $\pi^0 = 1$ for every projectivity π in \mathcal{B} . The following *distributive laws* are easily checked

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(\eta_1 + \eta_2) &= \eta\eta_1 + \eta\eta_2 \\ (\eta_1 + \eta_2)\eta &= \eta_1\eta + \eta_2\eta \end{aligned} \tag{6.5}$$

We denote by \mathbb{F} the set of all endomorphisms η of \mathcal{B} which satisfy $\Gamma(c)^\eta \subseteq \Gamma(c)$ for every $c \leq b$. \mathbb{F} is a (not necessarily commutative) ring. We show now that

(iv-a) *If $\eta \neq 0$ is in \mathbb{F} , then η is one-to-one.*

Proof Let π_1 and π_2 be projectivities in \mathcal{B} , not 1, such that $z(\pi_1) \neq z(\pi_2)$. Clearly, $\pi \subseteq \Gamma(z(\pi))$ by the definition of the sets $\Gamma(\cdot)$. It is then $\pi_i^\eta \subseteq \Gamma(z(\pi_i))^\eta \subseteq \Gamma(z(\pi_i))$, $i = 1, 2$, and $z(\pi_1\pi_2) \neq z(\pi_1)$ and $z(\pi_1\pi_2) \neq z(\pi_2)$ by lemma 6.3. Assume now that $\pi_1^\eta = 1$. The projectivity $(\pi_1\pi_2)^\eta = \pi_2^\eta$ belongs then to $\Gamma(z(\pi_1\pi_2))$ and to $\Gamma(z(\pi_2))$ and, therefore, $\pi_2^\eta \subseteq \Gamma(z(\pi_1\pi_2)) \cap \Gamma(z(\pi_2))$ implying $\pi_2^\eta = 1$ because $z(\pi_1\pi_2) \neq z(\pi_2)$. As a consequence, π_1^η and π_2^η are both either equal to 1 or both are different from 1 if $z(\pi_1) \neq z(\pi_2)$. If $\eta \neq 0$, then there is a projectivity π_1 in \mathcal{B} such that $\pi_1^\eta \neq 1$ which implies that $\pi_2^\eta \neq 1$ for all projectivities π_2 in \mathcal{B} with $z(\pi_1) \neq z(\pi_2)$.

If $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2)$, one deduces from lemma 6.2 and from $\nu(b) \geq 2$ that there exists a projectivity π in \mathcal{B} such that $z(\pi) \neq z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2)$. It follows then from $\pi_1^\eta = 1$ that $\pi^\eta = 1$ implying $\pi_2^\eta = 1$, and similarly from $\pi_1^\eta \neq 1$ that $\pi^\eta \neq 1$ and $\pi_2^\eta \neq 1$. Or $\pi^\eta = 1$ for some π in \mathcal{B} implies $\eta = 0$, and $\pi^\eta \neq 1$ for some π in \mathcal{B} implies $\eta \neq 0$. This proves the statement (iv-a).

If α is a projectivity in \mathcal{A} and β a projectivity in \mathcal{B} , then $\beta^{\tilde{\alpha}} \equiv \alpha^{-1}\beta\alpha$ is again a projectivity in \mathcal{B} because \mathcal{B} is a normal subgroup of \mathcal{A} . It follows from equation (6.4) that $z(\beta) = z(\alpha^{-1}\beta\alpha) = z(\beta^{\tilde{\alpha}})$ which implies that $\Gamma(c)^{\tilde{\alpha}} = \Gamma(c)$ for every projection $c \leq b$. Hence, we have shown that the inner automorphism $\tilde{\alpha}$ of \mathcal{B} induced by the projectivity α in \mathcal{A} belongs to the ring \mathbb{F} . The next step is the proof of the converse.

(iv-b) If η is an element in \mathbb{F} , then there exists a projectivity α in \mathcal{A} such that $\beta^\eta = \beta^{\tilde{\alpha}} \equiv \alpha^{-1}\beta\alpha$ for every projectivity β in \mathcal{B} .

Proof If $\eta = 0$, then $\beta^\eta = \beta = \alpha^{-1}\beta\alpha$ with $\alpha = 1$. If $\eta \neq 0$, then there exists a projectivity β in \mathcal{B} such that $\beta^\eta \neq \beta$. As a consequence of what is shown in the proof of (iv-a), neither β nor β^η is the identity. For any projectivity β in \mathcal{B} , β^η is in $\Gamma(z(\beta^\eta))$ and in $\Gamma(z(\beta))^\eta \subseteq \Gamma(z(\beta))$ and it is, therefore, $z(\beta^\eta) = z(\beta) \equiv z$. Since $\beta \neq \beta^\eta$, there exists a point $p \leq a$ such that $p^\beta \neq p^{\beta^\eta}$. Every point preceding b is a fixed point of every projectivity in Γ_b^a which implies that $p \not\leq b$. It follows that p, p^β , and p^{β^η} are three different points. Property (ce) implies that the points $p, p^\beta, z(\beta) = z$ are collinear and that the points $p, p^{\beta^\eta}, z(\beta^\eta) = z$ are collinear. Hence, $p, p^\beta, p^{\beta^\eta}$ are three collinear points. According to lemma 6.2, there is exactly one projectivity α in \mathcal{A} such that $p = z(\alpha)$ and $p^{\beta^\eta} = (p^\beta)^\alpha$. Because p is a fixed point of α and, therefore, of α^{-1} , it is

$$p^{\beta^\eta} = (p^\beta)^\alpha = p^{\beta\alpha} = p^{\alpha^{-1}\beta\alpha} = p^{\beta^{\tilde{\alpha}}}$$

β^η and $\beta^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ are projectivities in \mathcal{B} with the same center z according to equation (6.4) and with the same effects on the point p , which is neither their center z nor precedes b . It follows from lemma 6.2 that $\beta^\eta = \beta^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ for every β in \mathcal{B} .

Consider now the endomorphism κ in \mathbb{F} which is defined by the rule $\beta^\kappa = \beta^{\eta-\tilde{\alpha}}$ for every projectivity β in \mathcal{B} . Then $\beta^\kappa = \beta^{\eta-\tilde{\alpha}} = \beta^\eta(\beta^{\tilde{\alpha}})^{-1} = 1$ and it follows from considerations in the proof of (iv-a) that $\kappa = 0$ and $\eta = \tilde{\alpha}$. This implies that there exists, for every endomorphism $\eta \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} , a projectivity α in \mathcal{A} such that $\beta^\eta = \beta^{\tilde{\alpha}} = \alpha^{-1}\beta\alpha$ for every β in \mathcal{B} which is statement (iv-b).

It follows immediately from (iv-b) that every element $\eta \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} is an inner automorphism of \mathcal{B} which possesses an inverse in \mathbb{F} and this completes the proof of statement (iv).

(v) If $d \leq b$, then $\Gamma(d)$ is a subgroup of \mathcal{B} and it is $\Gamma(d)^\mathbb{F} \subseteq \Gamma(d)$ according to the definition of \mathbb{F} ; it is even $\Gamma(d)^\mathbb{F} = \Gamma(d)$ because \mathbb{F} contains the element 0. This proves the necessity of statement (v).

As for the sufficiency of (v), consider a subgroup \mathcal{D} of \mathcal{B} satisfying the condition $\mathcal{D}^\mathbb{F} \subseteq \mathcal{D}$. We show first:

(v-a) If $\pi_1 \neq 1$ is in \mathcal{D} and if $\pi \neq 1$ is a projectivity in \mathcal{B} such that $z(\pi) = z(\pi_1)$, then π is in \mathcal{D} .

Proof Let $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi) \equiv z$. Then $z \leq b$ because $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$ and π_1 and π are projectivities, not 1, in \mathcal{B} . Their fixed points precede b because a fixed point $p \not\leq b$ is a center according to the case 1 of the proof of lemma 6.1 and because every projectivity not 1 possesses one and only one center. If $p \leq a$ is any point not preceding b , then $p \neq p^{\pi_1}$ and $p \neq p^\pi$, and the points p, p^{π_1}, p^π, z are collinear. Assume, first, that $p^{\pi_1} = p^\pi$. Then $\pi_1 = \pi$ by lemma 6.2, which proves (v-a) for this case. If $p^{\pi_1} \neq p^\pi$, then it follows from lemma 6.2 that there exists a projectivity α in \mathcal{A} such that $z(\alpha) = p$ and $p^{\pi_1\alpha} = p^\pi$. As in the proof of (iv-b), one verifies that $p^\pi = p^{\alpha^{-1}\pi_1\alpha} = p^{\eta_1}$ for some element η_1 in \mathbb{F} and for every point $p \not\leq b$, which implies that $\pi \subseteq \pi_1^\mathbb{F} \subseteq \mathcal{D}^\mathbb{F} \subseteq \mathcal{D}$. This proves (v-a) for the second case. Next, we show:

(v-b) If π_1 and π_2 are projectivities in \mathcal{D} , π_1 and π_2 not 1, and if $z(\pi) \leq z(\pi_1) \vee z(\pi_2)$, then π is in \mathcal{D} .

Proof If $z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2)$ or if $z(\pi) = z(\pi_1)$ or if $z(\pi) = z(\pi_2)$, then $z(\pi) = z(\pi_1) = z(\pi_2)$ and the statement (v-b) is a direct consequence of (v-a). We assume, therefore, that $z(\pi), z(\pi_1), z(\pi_2)$ are three different, collinear points. If $p \not\leq b$ is a point, then $p, p^{\pi_1}, z(\pi_1)$ are three different, collinear points, and $p \vee z(\pi)$ and $p^{\pi_1} \vee z(\pi_2)$ are two different lines in the plane $p \vee z(\pi) \vee z(\pi_2)$. The point

$$q = (p \vee z(\pi)) \wedge (p^{\pi_1} \vee z(\pi_2))$$

does not precede b because $q \leq p \vee z(\pi)$ implies $p \leq q \vee z(\pi)$. In addition, it is $p^{\pi_1} \not\leq b$ and $q, p^{\pi_1}, z(\pi_2)$ are collinear. By lemma 6.2, there is a unique projectivity τ such that $z(\tau) = z(\pi_2)$ and $p^{\pi_1\tau} = q$. The projectivity τ is in \mathcal{B} and it follows from (v-a) that τ is in \mathcal{D} because π_2 is in \mathcal{D} . Likewise π_1 is in \mathcal{D} , which implies that $\pi_1\tau$ is in \mathcal{D} . It is $p^{\pi_1\tau} = q$ and the points $p, q, z(\pi_1\tau)$ are, therefore, collinear as are the points $p, q, z(\pi)$. Hence, $z(\pi_1\tau) = z(\pi_1\tau) \wedge b \leq (p \vee q) \wedge b$. But $(p \vee q) \wedge b$ is a point, which implies that $z(\pi_1\tau) = (p \vee q) \wedge b = z(\pi)$, and, by (v-a), that π is itself in \mathcal{D} , which was to prove. We continue with

(v-c) If π_1, \dots, π_n are a finite number of projectivities in \mathcal{D} and if $z(\pi) \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^n z(\pi_i)$, then π is in \mathcal{D} .

Proof The statement is certainly true for $n = 1$ and $n = 2$ as follows from (v-a) and (v-b). Hence, we proceed by induction and assume that (v-c) holds for $2 \leq k - 1$ with $k \leq n$. It is a consequence of (v-a) that π is in \mathcal{D} if $z(\pi) = z(\pi_k)$, and it follows from the induction hypothesis that π is in \mathcal{D} if $z(\pi) \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} z(\pi_i) \equiv c$. Therefore, we assume that $z(\pi) \neq z(\pi_k)$ and $z(\pi) \not\leq c$. If $z(\pi_k) \leq c$, then $\bigvee_{i=1}^k z(\pi_i) = \bigvee_{i=1}^{k-1} z(\pi_i) \vee z(\pi_k) = c \vee z(\pi_k) = c$ and π is in \mathcal{D} by the induction hypothesis. Therefore, we assume that $z(\pi_k) \not\leq c$. Then $l \equiv z(\pi) \vee z(\pi_k)$ is a line and $l \wedge c$ is a point different from $z(\pi)$ and from $z(\pi_k)$. Lemma 6.2 assures the existence of a projectivity $\pi' \neq 1$ in \mathcal{A} such that $z(\pi') = l \wedge c \leq c$, and it follows from the induction hypothesis that π' is in \mathcal{D} . Now, $z(\pi') \leq l = z(\pi) \vee z(\pi_k)$ implies $z(\pi) \leq z(\pi') \vee z(\pi_k)$ by equation (5.1), and π_k and π' are both in \mathcal{D} . Hence, π is in \mathcal{D} by (v-b). This completes the induction step and proves (v-c).

Define now the projection d by $d = 0$ if $\mathcal{D} = \{1\}$ and $d = \bigvee_{\pi \in \mathcal{D}, \pi \neq 1} z(\pi)$ otherwise. Clearly, it is $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \Gamma(d)$. For a projectivity π in $\Gamma(d)$, it is either $\pi = 1$ or $z(\pi) \leq d$. In the latter case, d precedes b being of finite rank, and d is, therefore, the join of finitely many basis elements. Hence, if $z(\pi) \leq d$, then π is in \mathcal{D} by (v-c). Therefore, we have shown that $\mathcal{D} = \Gamma(d)$. This completes the proof of (v) and of lemma 6.4.

qed

The proof of lemma 6.4 presupposes that the rank of the proposition system \mathcal{S}_a is finite but not less than three. The validity of Desargues' theorem is an important precondition, but this has to be assumed up to now if the rank $\nu(a) = 3$. Baer gets rid of this restriction with his Imbedding Theorem [8, p. 268], which may be formulated as follows:

Theorem 6.2 (Imbedding Theorem) Any irreducible, bounded, complete, complemented, modular lattice \mathcal{S} whose rank $\nu(\mathcal{S})$ is finite and not less than three is contained in a lattice \mathcal{P} with the same characteristics as \mathcal{S} and with $\nu(\mathcal{P}) > \nu(\mathcal{S})$.

Baer proves the "comparatively deep Imbedding Theorem" [8, p. 268] by an explicit construction of the lattice \mathcal{P} with the required properties. We must forego to present the proof and refer to Ref. [8, VII.4]. According to the imbedding theorem, the rank of \mathcal{P} is at least equal to four, and the theorem of Desargues is valid in this lattice and, consequently, in its sublattice \mathcal{S} of rank $\nu(\mathcal{S}) \geq 3$, too.

It is appropriate now to translate these results into the more familiar terminology of left vector spaces $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{B})$, the action of the field \mathbb{F} of scalars η on vectors \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{B} being multiplications from the left and the group operation in the commutative group of vectors being denoted as addition (see appendix E for definitions and theorems concerning vector spaces). The resulting equivalences are compiled in the table below:

$\pi \in \mathcal{B}$	\iff	$\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{B}$
$\pi = 1$	\iff	$\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0}$
$\pi_1 \pi_2 = \pi_2 \pi_1$	\iff	$\mathbf{b}_1 + \mathbf{b}_2 = \mathbf{b}_2 + \mathbf{b}_1$
π^η	\iff	$\eta \mathbf{b}$
$\pi^{(\eta_1 + \eta_2)} = \pi^{\eta_1} \pi^{\eta_2}$	\iff	$(\eta_1 + \eta_2) \mathbf{b} = \eta_1 \mathbf{b} + \eta_2 \mathbf{b}$
$(\pi_1 \pi_2)^\eta = \pi_1^\eta \pi_2^\eta$	\iff	$\eta(\mathbf{b}_1 + \mathbf{b}_2) = \eta \mathbf{b}_1 + \eta \mathbf{b}_2$
$\pi^{(\eta_1 \eta_2)} = (\pi^{\eta_1})^{\eta_2}$	\iff	$(\eta_2 \eta_1) \mathbf{b} = \eta_2(\eta_1 \mathbf{b})$
$\Gamma(p) = \{\pi_1^\eta : \eta \in \mathbb{F}, \pi_1 \neq 1\}$	\iff	$\mathcal{V}_p = \{\eta \mathbf{b}_1 : \eta \in \mathbb{F}, \mathbf{b}_1 \neq \mathbf{0}\}$

where $p < b$ is a point and π_1 a fixed projectivity in $\Gamma(p)$. Hence, the lattice isomorphism μ of section 5.1.1, defined by lemma 6.4 (v), is given by

$$\mu(p) = \{\eta \mathbf{b}_1 : \mathbf{b}_1 \in \mathcal{V}_p, \mathbf{b}_1 \neq \mathbf{0}, \eta \in \mathbb{F}\}$$

Accordingly,

$$\mu(p_1 \vee p_2) = \{\eta_1 \mathbf{b}_1 + \eta_2 \mathbf{b}_2 : \mathbf{b}_i \in \mathcal{V}_{p_i}, \mathbf{b}_i \neq \mathbf{0}, \eta_i \in \mathbb{F}\} = \mu(p_1) + \mu(p_2)$$

A point $q \leq p_1 \vee p_2$ is represented by a one-dimensional subspace of the vectorspace $\mu(p_1 \vee p_2)$, and so on.

The results obtained so far may then be summarised as follows. Consider the irreducible projection systems $\mathcal{S}_a \equiv [0, a]$ and $\mathcal{S}_b \equiv [0, b]$ where a and b are projections in an irreducible component of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} such that the rank $\nu(a) \geq 3$ but finite and that $a > b$, $\nu(a) = \nu(b) + 1$. Denote by Γ_b^a the set of all autoprojectivities π of \mathcal{S}_a with the property that $c^\pi = c$ for all projections $c \leq b$. Denote by $\Gamma(d)$ the set of all projectivities π of Γ_b^a with center $z(\pi) \leq d \leq a$. $\Gamma(d)$ is a group. Define $\mathcal{A} \equiv \Gamma(a) = \Gamma_b^a$, $\mathcal{B} \equiv \Gamma(b)$. \mathcal{B} is a normal, commutative subgroup of \mathcal{A} by lemma 6.4 (i), (ii). Let \mathbb{F} be the set of all endomorphisms of \mathcal{B} satisfying $\Gamma(c)^\eta \subseteq \Gamma(c)$ for every projection $c \leq b$. \mathbb{F} is a field by lemma 6.4 (iv). The pair $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{B})$ denotes the space \mathcal{B} of vectors over the field \mathbb{F} of scalars which act on the vectors from the left. If we write accordingly $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{C})$ instead of $\Gamma(c)$ and $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{D})$ instead of $\Gamma(d)$, then \mathcal{C} is a subspace of \mathcal{D} if and only if $c \leq d \leq b$ by lemma 6.4 (v). The statements lemma 6.4 (iii) and (v), imply

Theorem 6.3 *The irreducible projection system \mathcal{S}_b of rank $\nu(b) \geq 2$ is projectively equivalent to the partially ordered set of the subspaces of the left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{B})$ of dimension $\nu(b)$.*

The system of subspaces of a finite dimensional vector space is a complete, complemented, modular lattice [8, II.1]. The theorem states a converse namely that the setting consisting of complete, modular lattices $\mathcal{S}_a \equiv [0, a]$ and $\mathcal{S}_b \equiv [0, b]$, the rank $\nu(a)$ being not less than three but finite, and the projection a covering b allows the construction of a vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{B})$ whose system of subspaces is projectively equivalent to \mathcal{S}_b . The task is, however, not yet accomplished with theorem 6.3. First of all, the field \mathbb{F} constructed in lemma 6.4 may depend upon the choice of the projection b covered by a . Secondly, a representation theorem is needed for the irreducible projection system \mathcal{S}_a not only for its subsystems \mathcal{S}_b . Additional analysis is needed. We take profit of the richer structure of the equivalent vector spaces and will argue within this scheme. But, firstly, we prove two lemmata:

Lemma 6.5 *Let \mathbb{M} denote the multiplicative group of $\mathbb{F} - \{0\}$. Then \mathbb{M} is isomorphic to the quotient group \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B} .*

Proof It is shown in the proof of lemma 6.4 item (iv-b) that every endomorphism $\eta \neq 0$ of \mathcal{B} acting on the projectivities β in \mathcal{B} is an inner automorphism $\beta^\eta = \alpha^{-1}\beta\alpha$, α being a projectivity in \mathcal{A} . The map $\alpha \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \eta \in \mathbb{M}$ is a homomorphism and the set \mathcal{B} is contained in its kernel \mathcal{K} . But \mathcal{B} is already the complete kernel because the kernel of the homomorphism is a normal subgroup of \mathcal{A} and the projection a covers b implying that $\Gamma(b) \equiv \mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \equiv \Gamma(a)$ entails either $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{B}$ or $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{A}$. The group \mathcal{A} is not commutative, hence $\mathcal{K} \neq \mathcal{A}$. The lemma follows from the homomorphy theorem for groups [25, p. 32].

qed

Lemma 6.6 *If $p < b$ is a point and $\pi_1 \neq 1$ is a projectivity in $\Gamma(p)$, then the map $\eta \in \mathbb{F} \rightarrow \pi_1^\eta \in \Gamma(p)$ is a field isomorphism.*

Proof Define $\mathcal{M}_{\pi_1} \equiv \{\pi_1^\eta : \eta \in \mathbb{M}\}$, $\pi_1 \neq 1$. If $\pi \neq 1$ is a projectivity in \mathcal{M}_{π_1} , then $\pi = \pi_1^{\eta_1}$ for some $\eta_1 \neq 0$ in \mathbb{M} , and

$$\mathcal{M}_\pi = \{\pi^\eta : \eta \in \mathbb{M}\} = \{\pi_1^{(\eta_1 \eta)} : \eta \in \mathbb{M}\} = \{\pi_1^{(\eta_1 \eta)} : (\eta_1 \eta) \in \mathbb{M}\} = \mathcal{M}_{\pi_1}$$

Hence, any projectivity in $\Gamma(p)$ not equal to 1 may serve as the basis element π_1 of \mathcal{M}_{π_1} . Every endomorphism η in \mathbb{M} is one-to-one, lemma 6.4 item (iv-a), and maps $\pi \in \mathcal{M}_{\pi_1} \rightarrow \pi^\eta \in \mathcal{M}_{\pi_1}$ with $\pi^{(\eta_1 \eta_2)} = (\pi^{\eta_1})^{\eta_2}$ for every projectivity π in \mathcal{M}_{π_1} : the map $\eta \in \mathbb{M} \rightarrow \pi_1^\eta \in \mathcal{M}_{\pi_1}$ is a group isomorphism. The isomorphism regarding the additive group of \mathbb{F} is ensured by the property $\pi^{(\eta_1 + \eta_2)} = \pi^{\eta_1} \pi^{\eta_2}$ of an endomorphism and by the fact that $\Gamma(p) \subseteq \mathcal{B}$ is a commutative group with regard to the multiplication of projectivities. Replacing $\mathcal{M}_\pi = \{\pi^\eta : \eta \in \mathbb{M}\}$ by $\{\pi^\eta : \eta \in \mathbb{F}\}$ just adds the element 1 to \mathcal{M}_π and, therefore, $\{\pi^\eta : \eta \in \mathbb{F}\} = \mathcal{M}_\pi \cup \{1\} = \Gamma(p)$.

qed

With theorem 6.3, the total machinery of linear algebra is now available for the final analysis. We consider the following situation: p_1 and p_2 are two distinct points preceding the projection a of finite rank $\nu(a) \geq 3$. Weak modularity entails the decomposition $a = p_i \vee b_i$ with $p_i \perp b_i$ for $i = 1, 2$ and, consequently, $p_i \wedge b_i = 0$. The projections b_i are unique according to theorem 3.4 item (ii). It is

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(a) &= \nu(p_i \vee b_i) = \nu(p_i) + \nu(b_i) - \nu(p_i \wedge b_i) = \nu(b_i) + 1 \\ \nu(b_1 \wedge b_2) &= \nu(b_1) + \nu(b_2) - \nu(b_1 \vee b_2) \geq 2(\nu(a) - 1) - \nu(a) = \nu(a) - 2 \geq 1 \end{aligned}$$

by theorem 4.3. The groups $\Gamma_{b_i}^a$, $\Gamma_{b_i}(b_i)$, and $\mathbb{M}_i \simeq \Gamma_{b_i}^a / \Gamma_{b_i}(b_i)$ are then constructed and the groups \mathbb{M}_i completed to the fields \mathbb{F}_i by introducing the distributive addition, equations (6.5), and adding the element 0. The projections b_i are represented by the vector spaces $\mathcal{V}_{b_i} \simeq \mathbb{F}_i^{\nu(a)-1}$ and the irreducible projection systems \mathcal{S}_{b_i} are projectively equivalent to the system of the subspaces of the vector spaces $\mathbb{F}_i^{\nu(a)-1}$. There exists a point $p \leq b_1 \wedge b_2 \leq b_i$ because $b_1 \wedge b_2 \neq 0$. The point p is represented by a one-dimensional subspace of $\mathbb{F}_1^{\nu(a)-1}$ as well as of $\mathbb{F}_2^{\nu(a)-1}$. This implies that $\mathbb{F}_1 \simeq \mathbb{F}_2 \simeq \mathbb{F}$ and that any point $p \leq a$ is represented by the one-dimensional vector space $\mathcal{V}_p \simeq \mathbb{F}^1$ according to lemma 6.6. If p is any point preceding a , then $a = p \vee b$ with $b = p' \wedge a$ and $p \perp b$ entailing $p \wedge b = 0$. Hence, $\mathcal{V}_a = \mathcal{V}_p \oplus \mathcal{V}_b \simeq \mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)}$ and \mathcal{S}_a is projectively equivalent to the system of subspaces of \mathcal{V}_a . We summarise these results as

Theorem 6.4 (Representation Theorem) *Let a be a projection of an irreducible projection system of finite rank, $\nu(a) \geq 3$, and let $b < a$ be any projection that is covered by a . Denote by Γ_b^a the set of all autoprojectivities π of $\mathcal{S}_a \equiv [0, a]$ such that $c^\pi = c$ for all projections $c \leq b$, and by $\Gamma(b) \subseteq \Gamma_b^a$ the set of all autoprojectivities in Γ_b^a with center preceding b . Then the projection a is represented by the left vector space $\mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)}$ of dimension $\nu(a)$ over a field \mathbb{F} , and the projection system \mathcal{S}_a is projectively equivalent to the system of subspaces of this vector space. The multiplicative group of $\mathbb{F} - \{0\}$ is isomorphic to the quotient group $\Gamma_b^a / \Gamma(b)$ for any choice of the projection b .*

Chapter 7

The consequences of orthocomplementation

The field \mathbb{F} of the left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ constructed in lemma 6.4 is of rather abstract kind; that \mathbb{F} is a field is the only property emerging from this construction. Secondly, we mention that the orthocomplementation of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} is not directly used in chapter 6, but only implicitly in the characterisation of weak modularity by theorem 3.3. Weak modularity implies that every projection which is the join of finitely many atoms possesses a finite basis (theorem 4.2), is used to show the rank formula (theorem 4.3), and, in turn, to prove that a projection system of finite rank is modular (theorem 4.4). However, the orthocomplementation of \mathcal{P}_{PhS} and consequently of all its irreducible components is an additional internal symmetry of these lattices of projections, which corresponds to an additional structure of the vector space whose system of subspaces is projectively equivalent to the projection system. This structure is worked out in the present chapter. The argumentation is based on the content of sections IV.1, IV.2, IV.3 of Ref. [8]. The necessary mathematical background is given in the next section and in appendices E and F. Finally, it is shown that solely complex Hilbert spaces provide the suitable frame to describe quantum systems.

7.1 Dualities

A duality δ of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto the vector space $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ is defined by the following properties:

- (D1) δ maps every subspace \mathcal{M} of \mathcal{A} to a uniquely determined subspace \mathcal{M}^δ of \mathcal{B} .
- (D2) To every subspace $\mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{B}$ there is exactly one subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$ such that $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{M}^\delta$.
- (D3) It is $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{A}$ if and only if $\mathcal{N}^\delta \leq \mathcal{M}^\delta \leq \mathcal{B}$.

In short, a duality is a one-to-one map of the set of subspaces of \mathcal{A} onto the set of subspaces of \mathcal{B} that inverts the order of subspaces. Further properties of dualities are readily deduced:

- (D4) Dualities interchange sums and intersections.

This is an immediate consequence of the definitions of sum and intersection as supremum and infimum.

- (D5) It is $\{\mathbf{0}_\mathcal{A}\}^\delta = \mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{A}^\delta = \{\mathbf{0}_\mathcal{B}\}$.

It is a consequence of property (D5) that dualities of vector spaces of dimension one are trivial. Furthermore, every one-to-one map of the one-dimensional subspaces of a vector space of dimension two onto the subspaces of an other vector space of dimension two is a duality. Hence, non-trivial dualities are possible only between vector spaces of dimension greater or equal than three.

(D6) If \mathcal{P} is a *point* i.e. a subspace of \mathcal{A} with dimension $\nu(\mathcal{P}) = 1$, then \mathcal{B} covers \mathcal{P}^δ , and, conversely, if \mathcal{A} covers \mathcal{H} , then the dimension $\nu(\mathcal{H}^\delta) = 1$.

The reason is that there is no proper subspace between 0 and \mathcal{P} or between \mathcal{H} and \mathcal{A} .

The main goal of this section is to characterise vector spaces $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ which possess dualities and to find an algebraic representation of dualities. All vector spaces in the following considerations are finite dimensional.

Lemma 7.1 [8, p. 97] *If δ is a duality of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto the vector space $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ and if \mathcal{M} is a subspace of \mathcal{A} , then*

$$\nu(\mathcal{B}/\mathcal{M}^\delta) = \nu(\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M}))$$

$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})$ being the adjoint space of \mathcal{M} .

Proof Let $K = \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_l\}$ be a basis of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})$ and \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{S} denote the Galois correspondence (see section E.2.1) between \mathcal{M} and $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})$. It is $\mathcal{S}(k_i) \equiv \mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F})$ and, therefore,

$$\bigcap_{i=1}^l \mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F}) = \mathcal{S}\left(\sum_{i=1}^l k_i\mathbb{F}\right) = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})) = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{E}(\{\mathbf{0}\})) = \{\mathbf{0}\} \quad (7.1)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$\bigcap_{i \neq j} \mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F}) \not\subseteq \mathcal{S}(k_j\mathbb{F}) \quad (7.2)$$

for every $j = 1, \dots, l$. For a proof of this statement, note that the dimension $\nu(\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})) = \nu(\sum_{i=1}^l k_i\mathbb{F}) = l$ and the dimension of the proper subspace $\mathcal{N}_j \equiv \sum_{i \neq j} k_i\mathbb{F}$ of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})$ equals $l - 1$. Now $\mathcal{N}_j < \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})$ implies $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})) < \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}_j) = \bigcap_{i \neq j} \mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F})$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}_j) &> \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})) = \mathcal{S}\left(\sum_{i=1}^l k_i\mathbb{F}\right) = \bigcap_{i=1}^l \mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F}) \\ &= \left(\bigcap_{i \neq j} \mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F})\right) \cap \mathcal{S}(k_j\mathbb{F}) \\ &= \mathcal{S}\left(\sum_{i \neq j} k_i\mathbb{F}\right) \cap \mathcal{S}(k_j\mathbb{F}) \\ &= \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}_j) \cap \mathcal{S}(k_j\mathbb{F}) \end{aligned}$$

This proves (7.2) because $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}_j) = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}_j) \cap \mathcal{S}(k_j\mathbb{F})$ is equivalent to $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}_j) \leq \mathcal{S}(k_j\mathbb{F})$.

Consider now the map

$$k_i \in K \rightarrow k_i^* \equiv (\mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F}))^\delta$$

The Galois correspondences \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{S} are reciprocal dualities between \mathcal{M} and $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})$, theorem E.10, and it is $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{M})) \equiv \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M}))$ by lemma E.7. $k_i\mathbb{F}$ is a point of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M})$ and \mathcal{M} covers the subspace $\mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F})$ according to property (D6). It follows again from property (D6) that k_i^* is a point of $\mathcal{M}^\delta \leq \mathcal{B}$ and, consequently, that k_i^*/\mathcal{M}^δ is a point of the quotient space $\mathcal{B}/\mathcal{M}^\delta$. Dualities interchange sums and intersections. Hence, it follows from equation (7.1) and property (D5) that

$$\sum_{i=1}^l k_i^* \equiv \sum_{i=1}^l (\mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F}))^\delta = \left(\bigcap_{i=1}^l \mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F})\right)^\delta = \{\mathbf{0}\}^\delta = \mathcal{B}$$

implying $\sum_{i=1}^l k_i^*/\mathcal{M}^\delta = \mathcal{B}/\mathcal{M}^\delta$. In addition, it follows from the relationship (7.2) and from property (D3) that $(\mathcal{S}(k_j\mathbb{F}))^\delta \not\subseteq \sum_{i \neq j} (\mathcal{S}(k_i\mathbb{F}))^\delta$ for every $j = 1, 2, \dots, l$. Hence, $k_1^*/\mathcal{M}^\delta, \dots, k_l^*/\mathcal{M}^\delta$ is an independent set of points in $\mathcal{B}/\mathcal{M}^\delta$, and the elements $k_1^*/\mathcal{M}^\delta, \dots, k_l^*/\mathcal{M}^\delta$ form a basis of the vector space $\mathcal{B}/\mathcal{M}^\delta$. The dimension $\nu(\mathcal{B}/\mathcal{M}^\delta)$ is equal to the dimension $\nu(\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{M}))$.

qed

This lemma implies together with theorems E.8 (i) and E.9 that

Corollary 7.1 [8, p. 98] *If δ is a duality of the finite dimensional vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto the vector space $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ and if \mathcal{M} is a subspace of \mathcal{A} , then*

$$\nu(\mathcal{B}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{M}^\delta)$$

The case $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{A}$ implies $\nu(\mathcal{B}) = \nu(\mathcal{A})$: dual vector spaces of finite dimension possess equal dimensions.

7.1.1 The construction of the canonical dual vector space

A left vector space $(\mathbb{F}^*, \mathcal{A}^*)$ which is dual to the left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ can be constructed according to the following procedure [8, p. 98]:

The elements of the field \mathbb{F}^* are the same as the elements of the field \mathbb{F} and there is a one-to-one map γ' of \mathbb{F} onto \mathbb{F}^* such that

$$\begin{aligned} (\eta_1 + \eta_2)^{\gamma'} &= \eta_1^{\gamma'} + \eta_2^{\gamma'} \\ (\eta_1 \eta_2)^{\gamma'} &= \eta_2^{\gamma'} \eta_1^{\gamma'} \end{aligned}$$

for all η_1, η_2 in \mathbb{F} . \mathbb{F}^* is a field because $1^{\gamma'} = 1$, $(\eta^{\gamma'})^{-1} = (\eta^{-1})^{\gamma'}$, and the multiplication in \mathbb{F}^* defined above is associative.

The vectors of \mathcal{A}^* are elements of $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$ and there is a map γ'' of $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$ onto \mathcal{A}^* such that

$$\begin{aligned} (f_1 + f_2)^{\gamma''} &= f_1^{\gamma''} + f_2^{\gamma''} \\ (f\eta)^{\gamma''} &= \eta^{\gamma'} f^{\gamma''} \end{aligned}$$

for all f, f_1, f_2 in $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$ and η in \mathbb{F} . It follows that

$$(f\eta_1\eta_2)^{\gamma''} = (\eta_1\eta_2)^{\gamma'} f^{\gamma''} = \eta_2^{\gamma'} \eta_1^{\gamma'} f^{\gamma''}$$

It is evident that $(\mathbb{F}^*, \mathcal{A}^*)$ is a left vector space.

It is $\nu(\mathcal{A}^*) = \nu(\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})) = \nu(\mathcal{A})$ because the dimension $\nu(\mathcal{A})$ is finite. Note that $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is, in general, not isomorphic to $(\mathbb{F}^*, \mathcal{A}^*)$ because \mathbb{F} and \mathbb{F}^* are isomorphic only if \mathbb{F} is commutative. Every subspace M of the right vector space $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$ is also a subspace \mathcal{M}^* of the left vector space \mathcal{A}^* ; M and \mathcal{M}^* denote the same set of elements. According to theorem E.10, the Galois correspondence E is a duality of \mathcal{A} onto $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$ and the map

$$\delta^*: \mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A} \rightarrow E(\mathcal{M}) = M = \mathcal{M}^* \leq \mathcal{A}^* \quad (7.3)$$

is a duality of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{F}^*, \mathcal{A}^*)$, which is induced by the maps (γ', γ'') . The inverse duality $(\delta^*)^{-1}$ is given by the Galois correspondence \mathcal{S} . With regard to the identity of \mathcal{M}^* and M as sets, it is

$$(\delta^*)^{-1}: \mathcal{M}^* \leq \mathcal{A}^* \rightarrow \mathcal{S}(M) = \mathcal{S}(E(\mathcal{M})) = \mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A} \quad (7.4)$$

by lemma E.7, and $(\delta^*)^{-1}$ is induced by the maps $((\gamma')^{-1}, (\gamma'')^{-1})$ with similar characteristics as (γ', γ'') . In particular, it is $\eta_2^{(\gamma')^{-1}} \eta_1^{(\gamma'')^{-1}} = (\eta_1 \eta_2)^{(\gamma')^{-1}}$ and $\eta^{(\gamma')^{-1}} f^{(\gamma'')^{-1}} = (f \eta)^{(\gamma'')^{-1}}$.

The construction of the canonical dual vector space $(\mathbb{F}^*, \mathcal{A}^*)$ reveals that right vector space $(L(\mathcal{A}), \mathbb{F})$ can be interpreted as a left vector space, too. The canonical dual vector space can be constructed for any finite dimensional vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, which proves the

Theorem 7.1 (Existence Theorem) [8, p. 96] *Every finite dimensional vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ possesses a duality.*

7.1.2 Dualities are generated by anti-semilinear transforms

The notions of anti-isomorphism and of anti-semilinear transform are basic concepts of the algebraic characterisation of dualities. The one-to-one map α' of the field \mathbb{F} onto the field \mathbb{G} is an *anti-isomorphism* if

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & (\eta_1 + \eta_2)^{\alpha'} = \eta_1^{\alpha'} + \eta_2^{\alpha'} \\ (ii) \quad & (\eta_1 \eta_2)^{\alpha'} = \eta_2^{\alpha'} \eta_1^{\alpha'} \end{aligned}$$

for all elements η_1 and η_2 in \mathbb{F} .

The pair (α', α'') mapping the left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto the right vector space $(L(\mathcal{B}), \mathbb{G})$ is an *anti-semilinear transform* if α' is an anti-isomorphism of \mathbb{F} onto \mathbb{G} and α'' is a one-to-one map of the additive group \mathcal{A} onto the additive group $L(\mathcal{B})$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & (\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2)^{\alpha''} = \mathbf{a}_1^{\alpha''} + \mathbf{a}_2^{\alpha''} \\ (ii) \quad & (\eta \mathbf{a})^{\alpha''} = \mathbf{a}^{\alpha''} \eta^{\alpha'} \end{aligned}$$

The map α'' is an isomorphism between the additive groups of \mathcal{A} and $L(\mathcal{B})$ according to (i), and may be termed *anti-isomorphism of \mathcal{A} onto $L(\mathcal{B})$* in view of (ii). It presupposes in its definition the existence of the anti-isomorphism α' of the field \mathbb{F} onto the field \mathbb{G} .

Theorem 7.2 [8, p. 99] *If δ is a duality of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ and if the dimension of \mathcal{A} is not less than three but finite, then there exists an anti-semilinear transform (α', α'') that maps $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(L(\mathcal{B}), \mathbb{G})$.*

Proof The vector spaces $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ possess equal finite dimension according to corollary 7.1. In addition, there is the duality δ^* mapping $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ onto its dual space $(\mathbb{G}^*, \mathcal{B}^*)$, which is induced by the maps (γ', γ'') . The product

$$\pi = \delta \delta^*: \mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}^\delta \leq \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E(\mathcal{M}^\delta) \equiv \mathcal{M}^* \leq \mathcal{B}^*$$

is a projectivity of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}^*, \mathcal{B}^*)$, see equation (7.3). Because the dimension of \mathcal{A} is not less than three, this projectivity is induced by a semilinear transform (σ', σ'') mapping the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}^*, \mathcal{B}^*)$ according to theorem F.1. Therefore, $\delta = \pi(\delta^*)^{-1}$ is induced by a pair (α', α'') of maps with the following properties:

$\alpha' = \sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}$ is a one-to-one map of the field \mathbb{F} onto the field \mathbb{G} with

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & (\eta_1 + \eta_2)^{\alpha'} = (\eta_1 + \eta_2)^{\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}} = (\eta_1^{\sigma'} + \eta_2^{\sigma'})^{(\gamma')^{-1}} = \eta_1^{\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}} + \eta_2^{\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}} = \eta_1^{\alpha'} + \eta_2^{\alpha'} \\ (ii) \quad & (\eta_1 \eta_2)^{\alpha'} = (\eta_1 \eta_2)^{\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}} = (\eta_1^{\sigma'} \eta_2^{\sigma'})^{(\gamma')^{-1}} = \eta_2^{\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}} \eta_1^{\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}} = \eta_2^{\alpha'} \eta_1^{\alpha'} \end{aligned}$$

for all elements η_1, η_2 in \mathbb{F} .

$\alpha'' = \sigma''(\gamma'')^{-1}$ is a one-to-one map of the left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto the right vector space $(\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{B}), \mathbb{G})$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad (\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2)^{\alpha''} &= (\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2)^{\sigma''(\gamma'')^{-1}} = (\mathbf{a}_1^{\sigma''} + \mathbf{a}_2^{\sigma''})^{(\gamma'')^{-1}} = \mathbf{a}_1^{\sigma''(\gamma'')^{-1}} + \mathbf{a}_2^{\sigma''(\gamma'')^{-1}} = \mathbf{a}_1^{\alpha''} + \mathbf{a}_2^{\alpha''} \\ (ii) \quad (\eta\mathbf{a})^{\alpha''} &= (\eta\mathbf{a})^{\sigma''(\gamma'')^{-1}} = (\eta^{\sigma'} \mathbf{a}^{\sigma''})^{(\gamma'')^{-1}} = \mathbf{a}^{\sigma''(\gamma'')^{-1}} \eta^{\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}} = \mathbf{a}^{\alpha''} \eta^{\alpha'} \end{aligned}$$

for $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$ in \mathcal{A} and η in \mathbb{F} . The duality δ is, therefore, induced by the anti-semilinear transform

$$(\alpha', \alpha'') = (\sigma'(\gamma')^{-1}, \sigma''(\gamma'')^{-1})$$

qed

In the sequel, we define $\alpha \equiv (\alpha', \alpha'')$ with $\eta^\alpha \equiv \eta^{\alpha'}$ for η in \mathbb{F} and $\mathbf{a}^\alpha \equiv \mathbf{a}^{\alpha''}$ for \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} . Hence,

$$(\eta\mathbf{a})^\alpha = \mathbf{a}^\alpha \eta^\alpha \quad (7.5)$$

Corollary 7.2 [8, p. 99] *If δ is a duality of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ and if the dimension of \mathcal{A} is not less than three but finite, then there exists an anti-isomorphism α of the field \mathbb{F} onto the field \mathbb{G} and of the additive group \mathcal{A} onto the additive group $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{B})$ with property (7.5). It is*

$$\mathcal{M}^\alpha = \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{M}^\delta) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{M}^\delta = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{M}^\alpha)$$

for all subspaces \mathcal{M} of \mathcal{A} ; \mathbb{E} and \mathcal{S} are the Galois correspondences between \mathcal{B} and $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{B})$.

Proof The corollary is a consequence of the definition of the projectivity $\pi = \delta\delta^*$ and of (7.3) and (7.4).

qed

An important conclusion, which can be drawn from the proof of theorem 7.2, is that a duality δ of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ induces an anti-isomorphism α of \mathcal{A} onto $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{B})$.

7.1.3 Autodualities and semi-bilinear forms

In the following discussions, we consider the case $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B}) = (\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ i.e. *autodualities of \mathcal{A}* . The anti-isomorphism α between \mathbb{F} and \mathbb{G} is then an anti-automorphism of \mathbb{F} onto itself. The existence theorem 7.1 states that every vector space of dimension not less than three but finite possesses a duality. It is not true, however, that every such vector space possesses an autoduality because not every field possesses an anti-automorphism. If the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ possesses an autoduality δ , then, as a consequence of corollary 7.2, there must exist an anti-automorphism α of the field \mathbb{F} and an anti-isomorphism α of \mathcal{A} onto $\mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$ fulfilling equation (7.5). Hence, the product

$$\mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}^\alpha \equiv \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \quad (7.6)$$

is a uniquely determined element of \mathbb{F} defined for every pair \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} of vectors in \mathcal{A} .

The map $\phi: \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \in \mathbb{F}$ is a *semi-bilinear form* or α -*form* with the properties

(i) It is

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) &= \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) + \phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) \\ \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{c}) &= \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) + \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) \end{aligned}$$

for $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ in \mathcal{A} .

(ii) It is

$$\begin{aligned}\phi(\eta\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) &= \eta\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \\ \phi(\mathbf{a}, \eta\mathbf{b}) &= \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\eta^\alpha\end{aligned}$$

for \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} and η in \mathbb{F} .

According to corollary 7.2, it is, for an autoduality δ of \mathcal{A} and for every subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$,

$$\mathcal{M}^\delta = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{M}^\alpha) = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \mathbf{a}\mathcal{M}^\alpha = \{0\}\} \equiv \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathcal{M}) = \{0\}\} \quad (7.7)$$

We say that the *autoduality* δ of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is represented by the α -form ϕ if equation (7.7) is valid. However, not every α -form represents an autoduality; $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \equiv 0$ is a trivial counterexample. The following lemma characterises α -forms which represent autodualities.

Lemma 7.2 [8, p. 103] *If the α -form ϕ represents an autoduality δ of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ of dimension not less than three but finite, then*

(i) $\phi(\mathcal{A}, \mathbf{b}) = \{0\}$ implies $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0}$.

(ii) $\mathcal{A}^\alpha = \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$

(iii) $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathcal{A}) = \{0\}$ implies $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}$.

Proof If $\phi(\mathcal{A}, \mathbf{b}) = \{0\}$, then also $\{0\} = \phi(\mathcal{A}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}) \equiv \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{b})^\alpha$ or $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{S}((\mathbb{F}\mathbf{b})^\alpha) = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{b})^\delta$ according to corollary 7.2; \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{S} are the Galois correspondences between \mathcal{A} and $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$. This implies $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{b} = \{\mathbf{0}\}$ and $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0}$ because dualities interchange $\{0\}$ and \mathcal{A} . This proves statement (i).

According to corollary 7.2 and to property (D5), it is $\mathcal{A}^\alpha = \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{A}^\delta) = \mathcal{E}(\{0\}) = \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$. This proves statement (ii).

Assume the validity of statement (ii). If $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathcal{A}) = \{0\}$ for some vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} , then

$$\{0\} = \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathcal{A}) = \mathbf{a}\mathcal{A}^\alpha = \mathbf{a}\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$$

i.e. the vector \mathbf{a} is in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})) = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{E}(\{0\})) = \{0\}$ by lemma E.7. Hence $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}$.

qed

The existence of an autoduality δ of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ induces an α -form for this vector space, equation (7.6). To what extent does this autoduality determine the α -form? The answer is provided by

Theorem 7.3 [8, p. 105] *If the two semi-bilinear forms $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \equiv \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}^{\alpha_\phi}$ and $\psi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \equiv \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}^{\alpha_\psi}$ represent the same autoduality δ of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ of dimension not less than two but finite, then there exists an element $\kappa \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} such that*

$$\psi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\kappa$$

for all \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} . Conversely, $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ and $\psi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ represent the same autoduality for any number $\kappa \neq 0$.

Proof (a) The maps $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^{\alpha_\phi} \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$ and $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^{\alpha_\psi} \in \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$ are both anti-isomorphisms of \mathcal{A} onto $\mathcal{A}^{\alpha_\phi} = \mathcal{A}^{\alpha_\psi} = \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$, see lemma 7.2 (ii). The anti-isomorphisms α_ϕ and α_ψ comprise corresponding anti-automorphisms of the field \mathbb{F} . Consequently, there exists a semilinear transform $\tilde{\sigma} \equiv (\tilde{\sigma}', \tilde{\sigma}'')$ of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$ onto itself such that $(\mathbf{a}^{\alpha_\phi})^{\tilde{\sigma}} = \mathbf{a}^{\alpha_\psi}$ for every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} i.e. $\tilde{\sigma}' = (\alpha')_\phi^{-1}(\alpha')_\psi$ and $\tilde{\sigma}'' = (\alpha'')_\phi^{-1}(\alpha'')_\psi$.

Consider now any subspace \mathcal{M} of \mathcal{A} . According to corollary 7.2, it is $\mathcal{M}^\delta = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{M}^{\alpha_\phi}) = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{M}^{\alpha_\psi})$ and by the remark after lemma E.7

$$\mathcal{M}^{\alpha_\phi} = \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{M}^{\alpha_\phi})) = \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{M}^{\alpha_\psi})) = \mathcal{M}^{\alpha_\psi} \equiv \mathbb{M} \leq \mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$$

This identity is valid for all subspaces $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$ and, consequently, for all subspaces $\mathbb{M} \leq \mathbb{L}(\mathcal{A})$. Moreover, $\mathbb{M}^{\bar{\sigma}} = (\mathbb{M}^{\alpha_\phi^{-1}})^{\alpha_\psi} = \mathcal{M}^{\alpha_\psi} = \mathbb{M}$. The only semilinear transforms which leave invariant all subspaces of a vector space are multiplications with a number, lemma F.3 item (ii). Therefore, there is a number $\kappa \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} such that

$$\psi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}^{\alpha_\psi} = \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{b}^{\alpha_\phi})^{\bar{\sigma}} = \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}^{\alpha_\phi}\kappa = \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\kappa$$

for all vectors \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} .

(b) Assume that ϕ is an α -form and κ is an element of \mathbb{F} different from 0. Then

$$\psi(\mathbf{a}, \eta\mathbf{b}) \equiv \phi(\mathbf{a}, \eta\mathbf{b})\kappa = \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\eta^\alpha\kappa = \psi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\kappa^{-1}\eta^\alpha\kappa \equiv \psi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\eta^\beta$$

The map $\eta \rightarrow \eta^\beta$ is an anti-automorphism of the field \mathbb{F} namely the anti-automorphism $\eta \rightarrow \eta^\alpha$ followed by an inner automorphism, and ψ is a β -form. That ϕ and ψ represent the same autoduality is a consequence of equation (7.7).

qed

Assume now that $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \neq 0$ for some vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} . As a consequence of this theorem, there is a uniquely determined semi-bilinear form ψ representing the autoduality δ with $\psi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) = 1$.

7.2 Implications of orthocomplementation

We consider the irreducible projection system $\mathcal{S}_a \equiv [0, a]$ of finite rank and its representation by the projectively equivalent system of subspaces of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ whose dimension is equal to the rank of the projection a . The fact that every projection b in \mathcal{S}_a possesses a unique orthocomplement b'^a in \mathcal{S}_a will now be exploited step by step.

7.2.1 Orthocomplementation induces an autoduality

If the projection a corresponds to the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, the projection b in \mathcal{S}_a to the subspace \mathcal{M}_b of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, and if the orthocomplement $b'^a \equiv b' \wedge a$ corresponds to $\mathcal{M}_{b'^a}$, then the map

$$\delta': \mathcal{M}_b \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_{b'^a} \equiv \mathcal{M}^{\delta'} \tag{7.8}$$

defined for any projection $b \leq a$ is an autoduality of \mathcal{A} because

- (i) The postulate SOC that there exists one single orthocomplement of a projection corresponds to property (D1) of the autoduality δ' .
- (ii) Property (Oc1) implies (D2) because any projection $b \leq a$ is the orthocomplement $(b'^a)^{/a}$. Hence, the corresponding subspace \mathcal{M}_b is the image of $\mathcal{M}_{b'^a}$ under δ' according to equation (7.7).
- (iii) (Oc3), $c \leq b \leq a \Rightarrow 0 \leq c'^a \leq b'^a$, corresponds to (D3), $\mathcal{M}_b \leq \mathcal{M}_c \leq \mathcal{A} \Rightarrow \{\mathbf{0}\} \leq \mathcal{M}_c^{\delta'} \leq \mathcal{M}_b^{\delta'}$.

The existence of the autoduality δ' on (F, \mathcal{A}) entails that the field \mathbb{F} possesses an anti-automorphism α and the vector space \mathcal{A} an α -form $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$.

7.2.2 Consequences of (Oc2): $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \neq 0$ for $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$ in \mathcal{A}

Theorem 7.4 *If an irreducible projection system of dimension not less than three but finite is associated with the system of the subspaces of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and orthocomplementation with the autoduality δ' on \mathcal{A} , equation (7.8), and if δ' is represented by the α -form ϕ , then $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) \neq 0$ for all vectors $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$ in \mathcal{A} or, equivalently, $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) = 0$ implies $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}$.*

Proof A point p of the projection system is represented by a one-dimensional subspace $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{p}$ of \mathcal{A} , $\mathbf{p} \neq \mathbf{0}$, and the meet of two projections is represented by the intersection of the corresponding subspaces of \mathcal{A} . An orthocomplement is also a complement, and condition (Oc2) entails that $p \wedge p' = 0$, or with equations (7.7) and (7.8) that $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{p} \cap (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{p})^{\delta'} = \{\mathbb{F}\mathbf{p}\} \cap \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{p})\} = \{\mathbf{0}\}$. This implies $\phi(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}) \neq 0$.

qed

7.2.3 Consequences of (Oc1): $\alpha'^2 = 1$ and $\phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) = \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})^{\alpha'}$

If the autoduality δ' of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ expresses the orthocomplementation of an irreducible projection system, then statement (Oc1) is equivalent to the condition $\delta'^2 = 1$, the identity map of the set of subspaces of \mathcal{A} onto itself. In order to develop the consequences of this equation, we first prove two lemmata.

Lemma 7.3 [8, p. 101] *If δ is an autoduality of the finite dimensional vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and if \mathcal{M} is a subspace of \mathcal{A} , then the following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{M}^\delta = \{\mathbf{0}\}$
- (ii) $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M}^\delta = \mathcal{A}$
- (iii) $\mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{M}^\delta = \mathcal{A}$

Proof It is $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M}^\delta \leq \mathcal{A}$ and it follows from corollary 7.1 and from the rank formula 4.3 that

$$\nu(\mathcal{A}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{M}^\delta) = \nu(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M}^\delta) + \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{M}^\delta)$$

With theorem E.8 (ii), statement (i) implies (ii) and (iii), statement (ii) implies (i) and (iii), and statement (iii) is equivalent to (i) and (ii) by definition.

qed

Lemma 7.4 [8, p. 110] *If the α -form Φ represents the autoduality δ of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ of finite dimension not less than three, then $\delta^2 = 1$ if and only if $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0$ implies $\phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) = 0$.*

Proof If $\delta^2 = 1$ and $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}^\alpha = 0$, then $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a} \leq \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{b})^\alpha = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{b})^\delta$ according to corollary 7.2 and, consequently, $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{b})^{\delta^2} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b} \leq (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a})^\delta$ i.e. $\phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) = 0$.

Assume now that $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = 0$ implies $\phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) = 0$. If \mathcal{M} is a subspace of \mathcal{A} , then $\phi(\mathcal{M}^\delta, \mathcal{M}) = \{\mathbf{0}\}$, according to equation (7.7). By hypothesis, it is then also $\phi(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{M}^\delta) = \{\mathbf{0}\}$ implying $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{M}^{\delta^2}$. According to corollary 7.1, it is

$$\nu(\mathcal{A}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{M}^\delta) = \nu(\mathcal{M}^\delta) + \nu(\mathcal{M}^{\delta^2})$$

and, therefore, $\nu(\mathcal{M}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}^{\delta^2})$ and $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}^{\delta^2}$ by theorem E.8 (ii).

qed

Theorem 7.5 [8, p. 110] *If the orthocomplementation of an irreducible projection system of dimension not less than three but finite is expressed by the autoduality δ' of the corresponding vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, if δ' is represented by the α -form ϕ , and if $\delta'^2 = 1$, then $\alpha'^2 = 1$, i.e. α' is involutive, and it is $\phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) = \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})^{\alpha'}$ for all vectors \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} .*

Proof In the proof, we substitute α' by α . Take a vector $\mathbf{w} \neq \mathbf{0}$ in \mathcal{A} . By theorem 7.4, it is $\phi(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w}) \neq 0$ and, as a consequence of theorem 7.3, the semi-bilinear form ϕ may be chosen such that $\phi(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w}) = 1$. Define the subspace \mathcal{H} of \mathcal{A} by

$$\mathcal{H} \equiv (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{w})^{\delta'} = \mathcal{S}((\mathbb{F}\mathbf{w})^\alpha) = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \mathbf{a}\mathbf{w}^\alpha \equiv \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{w}) = 0\}$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{w} \not\subseteq \mathcal{H}$, and $\mathcal{H} \cap \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w} = \{\mathbf{0}\}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w} \oplus \mathcal{H}$ by lemma 7.3. We show now

(a) *If \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} are vectors in \mathcal{H} and η, θ elements in \mathbb{F} such that $\eta\theta^\alpha = \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$, then $\theta\eta^\alpha = \phi(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u})$.*

Proof of (a) If \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} are in $\mathcal{H} = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{w})^{\delta'}$, then $0 = \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}) = \phi(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w})$ and also $0 = \phi(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u}) = \phi(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{v})$ according to lemma 7.4. Set now $\eta\theta^\alpha = \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$. Then

$$\phi(\eta\mathbf{w} + \mathbf{u}, \theta\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{v}) = \eta\phi(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w})\theta^\alpha + \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w})\theta^\alpha - \eta\phi(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{v}) - \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \eta\theta^\alpha - \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = 0$$

because $\phi(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w}) = 1$ by hypothesis. But it is also

$$0 = \phi(\theta\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{v}, \eta\mathbf{w} + \mathbf{u}) = \theta\eta^\alpha - \phi(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u})$$

by lemma 7.4, which proves (a).

With $\theta = 1$, it follows

(b) *If \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} are vectors in \mathcal{H} , then $\phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})^\alpha = \phi(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u})$.*

Next, we show

(c) $\alpha^2 = 1$.

Proof of (c) It is $\phi(\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{A}) = \phi(\mathcal{H}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w} \oplus \mathcal{H}) = \phi(\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{H})$ because $\phi(\mathcal{H}, \mathbf{w}) = \{0\}$. It is $\nu(\mathcal{H}) + \nu(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}) = \nu(\mathcal{A}) \geq 3$ by corollary 7.1. Hence, $\nu(\mathcal{H}) = \nu(\mathcal{A}) - 1 \geq 2$ and a pair of independent vectors \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} may be found in \mathcal{H} such that $\phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = 1$. If θ in \mathbb{F} is different from 0, then $\theta^\alpha \neq 0$, too, and there exists an element η in \mathbb{F} such that $\eta\theta^\alpha = 1$. Hence, with (b) and (a),

$$1 = \eta\theta^\alpha = \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})^\alpha = \phi(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}) = \theta\eta^\alpha$$

Furthermore, $1 = (\eta\theta^\alpha)^\alpha = \theta^{\alpha^2}\eta^\alpha$ because α is an anti-automorphism. Therefore, $(\eta^\alpha)^{-1} = \theta^{\alpha^2} = \theta$ for all $\theta \neq 0$ i.e. $\alpha^2 = 1$.

If, finally, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c} are vectors in \mathcal{A} , then $\mathbf{b} = \beta\mathbf{w} + \tilde{\mathbf{b}}$ and $\mathbf{c} = \gamma\mathbf{w} + \tilde{\mathbf{c}}$ with β, γ in \mathbb{F} and $\tilde{\mathbf{b}}, \tilde{\mathbf{c}}$ in \mathcal{H} according to the decomposition $\mathcal{A} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w} \oplus \mathcal{H}$. From

$$0 = \phi(\mathbf{w}, \tilde{\mathbf{b}}) = \phi(\tilde{\mathbf{b}}, \mathbf{w}) = \phi(\mathbf{w}, \tilde{\mathbf{c}}) = \phi(\tilde{\mathbf{c}}, \mathbf{w})$$

and by lemma 7.4, one obtains with (b) and (c) that

$$\phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})^\alpha = (\beta\gamma^\alpha + \phi(\tilde{\mathbf{b}}, \tilde{\mathbf{c}}))^\alpha = \gamma\beta^\alpha + \phi(\tilde{\mathbf{c}}, \tilde{\mathbf{b}}) = \phi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b})$$

and this completes the proof of the theorem.

qed

We have shown that the orthocomplementation of the irreducible projection system \mathcal{S}_a of finite dimension not less than three induces an autoduality δ' on $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$. Hence, the field \mathbb{F} possesses an involutive anti-automorphism α and δ' is represented by the α -form ϕ . If the projectivity $b \leq a$ corresponds to the subspace $\mathcal{M}_b \leq \mathcal{A}$, then the subspace $\mathcal{M}_{b'^a}$ corresponding to b'^a is given by

$$\mathcal{M}_{b'^a} \equiv \mathcal{M}_b^{\delta'} = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathcal{M}_b) = \{0\}\} \quad (7.9)$$

according to equation (7.7). This justifies the notion of b'^a as the *orthogonal* complement of b in \mathcal{S}_a .

7.3 The representation of irreducible, infinite dimensional projection systems

We summarise the results obtained so far: an irreducible component $[0, a]$ of finite rank $\nu(a)$ not less than three is projectively equivalent to the system of subspaces of a left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, which may be chosen to be $\mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)}$. The existence of the single orthocomplement (2.26) in the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} entails the following additional structure of this vector space:¹

- (i) The field \mathbb{F} possesses an involutive anti-automorphism α' : $\alpha'^2 = 1$.
- (ii) The vector space $\mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)}$ possesses a definite semi-bilinear form also termed a *Hermitian scalar product* $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \equiv \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ with the properties: $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}) = (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}) + (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c})$, $(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a}) = (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\alpha'$, $(\eta\mathbf{a}, \theta\mathbf{b}) = \eta(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\theta\alpha'$ for η, θ in \mathbb{F} , and it is $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}) = 0$ if and only if $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}$.
- (iii) Every subspace \mathcal{M}_b of $\mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)}$ representing a projection $b \leq a$ is given by

$$\mathcal{M}_b = \{\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)} : \phi(\mathbf{b}, \mathcal{U}) = \{0\}\}$$

for some subset $\mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)}$.

Statement (iii) is a consequence of equation (7.9) and of the fact that every projection is an orthocomplement.

Let us consider now an irreducible, weakly modular component \mathcal{P} of *infinite rank* of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{PhS} . The set of the subsystems of finite rank of \mathcal{P} is represented by the set of the finite dimensional subspaces of the left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ of infinite dimension representing \mathcal{P} .

Theorem 7.6 [2, p. 466] *Assume that an irreducible projection system \mathcal{P} of infinite rank is represented by the set of subspaces of the left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ of infinite dimension. The statements (i), (ii), and (iii) are valid for the representation of \mathcal{P} if they are valid for the representations of its finite dimensional subspaces.*

Proof Statement (i) is obviously true for the infinitely dimensional case, too.

In order to prove statement (ii), one has to show that the Hermitian scalar product defined on the finite dimensional subspaces can be extended to the total, infinite dimensional vector space. Consider, therefore, a subspace $\mathcal{M}_0 \leq \mathcal{A}$ representing a projection $b_0 < a$ of rank three, and let $\phi_0(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ be a definite α -form induced by the orthocomplementation in \mathcal{P} on \mathcal{M}_0 . Correspondingly, let $\mathcal{M}_1 \supset \mathcal{M}_0$ represent the projection $b_1 > b_0$ of finite rank and $\psi_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ an α -form induced by the orthocomplementation in \mathcal{P} restricted to b_1 . If $\psi_0(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ denotes the restriction of ψ_1 onto \mathcal{M}_0 , then there exists a number $\kappa \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} such that $\phi_0(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \psi_0(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\kappa$ by theorem 7.3. The α -form

$$\phi_{\mathcal{M}_1}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \equiv \psi_1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})\kappa$$

¹The first proof of these results is due to G. Birkhoff and J. von Neumann [5, p. 837 – 843].

is defined on \mathcal{M}_1 and identical with ϕ_0 on \mathcal{M}_0 . A definite α -form ϕ is now constructed for the total vector space \mathcal{A} by setting $\mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y},\mathbf{z}} = \mathcal{M}_0 + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}$ for any triplet $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ of vectors in \mathcal{A} , and $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) = \phi_{\mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y},\mathbf{z}}}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ for vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} in $\mathcal{M}_{\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y},\mathbf{z}}$. This construction defines a Hermitian scalar product on the total, infinitely dimensional vector space \mathcal{A} . Note that the α -form $\phi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ is determined only up to a constant different from 0 as is ϕ_0 .

In order to show (iii), consider first the one-dimensional subspace $\mathcal{M}_p = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{p} < \mathcal{A}$ corresponding to an atom p of \mathcal{P} . The subspace $\mathcal{M}_{p'}$ belonging to the projection p' is given by $\mathcal{M}_{p'} = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{p}) = 0\}$. For an arbitrary projection $b \leq a$, one has

$$b = \bigvee_{p \leq b} p \iff b' = \bigwedge_{p \leq b} p' \iff \mathcal{M}_{b'} = \bigcap_{p \leq b} \mathcal{M}_{p'} \iff \mathcal{M}_{b'} = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathcal{M}_b) = \{0\}\}$$

and, hence, $\mathcal{M}_b = \mathcal{M}_{(b')'} = \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} : \phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathcal{M}_{b'}) = \{0\}\}$, which proves the validity of statement (iii) for any subspace \mathcal{M}_b of the infinitely dimensional vector space \mathcal{A} .

qed

The extension of the Hermitian scalar product from the finite subspaces to the total infinitely dimensional vector space allows to maintain the representation (7.9) of the orthocomplement also for this case.

7.4 The final determination of the vectorspaces $\mathbb{F}^{\nu(a)}$

In order to proceed, it is necessary to additionally specify the field \mathbb{F} . We remind that a projection a is given by the set of its expectation values $E_s(a)$ for all states s . These expectation values are real numbers lying in the interval $[0, 1]$ and are calculated by some prescription from the elements of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$. Hence, the field \mathbb{F} must contain the real numbers \mathbb{R} as a subfield², which limits the choice of \mathbb{F} to the reals themselves, the complex numbers \mathbb{C} , and the quaternions \mathbb{H} according to the theorem of Frobenius [28]. These three fields possess an involutive anti-automorphism (the identity map in \mathbb{R} , complex conjugation in \mathbb{C} , and conjugation in \mathbb{H}) and their Hermitian scalar products have the property, that $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a})$ is real and positive for all vectors $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$ i.e. ϕ is strictly positive.

A strictly positive Hermitian scalar product induces a *norm* of the vector space \mathcal{A} : $\|\mathbf{a}\| = \sqrt{\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a})}$. The defining properties of a vector norm are: $\|\mathbf{a}\| \geq 0$, $\|\mathbf{a}\| = 0$ if and only if $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}$, $\|\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}\| \leq \|\mathbf{a}\| + \|\mathbf{b}\|$. A vector space with a strictly positive Hermitian scalar product is called a *pre-Hilbert space*. With a vector norm available, infinite sequences convergent in this norm and convergent sums of an infinite number of vectors can be defined. A vector space \mathcal{A} is called *complete* if the limit vector $\mathbf{a} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{a}_n$ of every convergent sequence $\{\mathbf{a}_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ of vectors in \mathcal{A} is in \mathcal{A} , too. The pre-Hilbert space \mathcal{A} can be completed to the *Hilbert space* \mathcal{H} by including the limit vectors of all convergent sequences of vectors in \mathcal{A} .

The scalar product $\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ is continuous in both arguments with regard to the vector norm because it is $|\phi(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})| \leq \|\mathbf{a}\| \|\mathbf{b}\|$. As a consequence, the domain of the duality δ' , represented by equation (7.9), can be extended from \mathcal{A} to its completion \mathcal{H} :

$$\mathcal{V}_{a'} \equiv \mathcal{V}^{\delta'} = \{\mathbf{h} \in \mathcal{H} : \phi(\mathbf{h}, \mathcal{V}_a) = \{0\}\} \quad (7.10)$$

defined for any subspace \mathcal{V}_a of \mathcal{H} .

Theorem 7.6 leaves undecided whether the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ whose subspaces represent an irreducible, infinite dimensional projection system is a pre-Hilbert space or a Hilbert space. This question is answered by a theorem due to I. Amemiya and H. Araki [29]:

²A different argument for this statement is provided by Birkhoff and von Neumann [5] (see footnote 31 on p. 836).

Theorem 7.7 *If the lattice $\mathcal{L}(A)$ of all subspaces of a pre-Hilbert space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is weakly modular, then \mathcal{A} is complete i.e. \mathcal{A} is a Hilbert space.*

The proof of this theorem is given in appendix G. As a consequence, a projection being represented by a subspace of a Hilbert space can be represented as well by the projector on this subspace.

We denote the Hilbert spaces over the fields $\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{H}$ by $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}, \mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{H}}$, respectively. In the following passage, we change the notation to the one familiar in quantum mechanics where small greek letters like ϕ, ψ denote vectors (or pure states if normalised) and where the notion of Hermitian scalar product, $(\psi, \phi) \equiv (\phi, \psi)^\alpha$, is used instead of the notion of α -form.

7.4.1 Representation of observables

The representation of observables is obtained by means of their spectral representation, equation (2.10). Projections $Q_A(\xi)$ are represented by projectors $\hat{Q}_A(\xi)$ on subspaces of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} , and the representation of the operator $f(\hat{A})$ corresponding to the observable $f(A)$ is given by the integral

$$f(\hat{A}) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\xi) d\hat{Q}_A(\xi) \quad (7.11)$$

which is the spectral representation of the operator $f(\hat{A})$. The projectors $\hat{Q}_A(\xi)$ are evidently symmetric (for $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}$) or selfadjoint transformations (for $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}$ and $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{H}}$). Equation (7.11) transfers this property to the operators $f(\hat{A})$.

This is particularly obvious in the case of discrete observables where equation (2.10) gets the form

$$f(A) = \sum_n f(\alpha_n) a_n$$

$\{\alpha_n\}$ being the set of all measurement values of A , the spectrum of A , and where a_n , the projection belonging to the measurement value α_n , can be expressed in terms of the spectral decomposition $Q_A(\xi)$, equation (2.9), by

$$a_n = Q_A(\alpha_n + \epsilon_n) - Q_A(\alpha_n - \epsilon_n)$$

with $\epsilon_n > 0$, but so small that the interval $[\alpha_n - \epsilon_n, \alpha_n + \epsilon_n]$ contains only the measurement value α_n .

7.4.2 $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}$

So far, we have shown that an irreducible component of the projection system \mathcal{P}_{pHS} is projectively equivalent to the system of subspaces of the separable Hilbert spaces $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}, \mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{H}}$ over the fields \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C} , and \mathbb{H} , respectively, and that the observables of a physical system are represented by symmetric operators in the case of $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}$ and by selfadjoint operators in the case of $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}$ and of $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{H}}$. In order to differentiate between these possibilities, additional inputs with regard to specific physical situations must be provided.

An isolated particle without inner structure (an isolated point mass) is the most elementary physical system because the system of its observables position \mathbf{x} , momentum \mathbf{p} , angular momentum \mathbf{L} , and energy H is completely determined by the symmetries of physical space-time described *e.g.* by Galilei invariance (see chapter 7 of Ref. [1]). We show now that this observable system cannot be represented by the algebra of symmetric operators acting on $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}$. The Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}$ of a particle can be realised by the set of square integrable real functions on \mathbb{R}^3

$$\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}} = \left\{ \phi: \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ with } \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \phi(\mathbf{x})^2 d^3x < \infty \right\}$$

with the real scalar product

$$(\phi, \psi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \phi(\mathbf{x})\psi(\mathbf{x}) d^3x$$

Any real function of the position operator \mathbf{x} is evidently symmetric, $(\phi, f(\mathbf{x})\psi) = (f(\mathbf{x})\phi, \psi)$.

The space translation

$$\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{x} + \xi\mathbf{e}, \quad \|\mathbf{e}\| = 1$$

of the particle with respect to a fixed coordinate frame is expressed by the action

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow \phi(\mathbf{x} - \xi\mathbf{e})$$

on the Hilbert space vectors ϕ . The Taylor expansion of the function $\phi(\mathbf{x} - \xi\mathbf{e})$ with respect to ξ ,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x} - \xi\mathbf{e}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} (-\xi(\mathbf{e}, \nabla))^n \phi(\mathbf{x}) \equiv (e^{-\xi(\mathbf{e}, \nabla)}\phi)(\mathbf{x})$$

reveals that the generator of an infinitesimal translation in direction \mathbf{e} is the operator $-(\mathbf{e}, \nabla)$. This generator corresponds to the component (\mathbf{e}, \mathbf{p}) of the particle momentum \mathbf{p} up to a real constant [1, Sec. 7.5]. The operator ∇ is antisymmetric in $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}$. Hence, the momentum \mathbf{p} and, consequently, the angular momentum \mathbf{L} are given by antisymmetric operators on $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}$ contradicting the previous result that all observables of a physical system are represented by symmetric operators acting on $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{R}}$. This observation rules out the case $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{R}$.

It is less obvious that quaternion Hilbert spaces do not suit the description of physical systems either. Problems originate here from the non-commutativity of the quaternion multiplication, which makes the construction of a uniquely defined tensor product impossible [30, Sec. 4].

The formation of tensor products is an indispensable tool in order to construct the description of a composite physical system based on the descriptions of its parts. Consider a physical system consisting of two parts with Hilbert spaces \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 *e.g.* an isolated system consisting of two interacting particles where \mathcal{H}_1 is the Hilbert space of the center-of-mass system and \mathcal{H}_2 the Hilbert space of the relative system [1, Sec. 7.6]. Let Ψ denote a vector of \mathcal{H}_1 and ψ a vector of \mathcal{H}_2 , $\{\Phi_n\}$ an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H}_1 and $\{\phi_n\}$ an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H}_2 and write

$$\Psi = \sum_m \eta_m \Phi_m, \quad \psi = \sum_n \theta_n \phi_n$$

The vector $\Psi \otimes \psi$ of the combined system described by the tensor product Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$ possesses then the expansion

$$\Psi_{\text{tot}}^{(1)} = \Psi \otimes \psi = \left(\sum_m \eta_m \Phi_m \right) \otimes \left(\sum_n \theta_n \phi_n \right) = \sum_{m,n} \eta_m \theta_n \Phi_m \otimes \phi_n$$

the tensor product being linear in both factors. The set $\{\Phi_m \otimes \phi_n\}$ is an orthonormal basis of the product space $\mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$. However, the Hilbert space of the combined system may likewise be defined by the tensor product $\mathcal{H}_2 \otimes \mathcal{H}_1$ leading to the expansion

$$\Psi_{\text{tot}}^{(2)} = \psi \otimes \Psi = \sum_{n,m} \theta_n \eta_m \phi_n \otimes \Phi_m$$

with the set $\{\phi_n \otimes \Phi_m\}$ being an orthonormal basis of the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_2 \otimes \mathcal{H}_1$. But $\mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$ and $\mathcal{H}_2 \otimes \mathcal{H}_1$ describe the same physical system if and only if the bijective map $\Phi_m \otimes \phi_n \leftrightarrow \phi_n \otimes \Phi_m$ for all m and n induces an isomorphism between the two Hilbert spaces $\mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$ and $\mathcal{H}_2 \otimes \mathcal{H}_1$. Hence, $\Psi_{\text{tot}}^{(1)}$ must be the same linear combination in terms of the basis vectors $\Phi_m \otimes \phi_n$ as $\Psi_{\text{tot}}^{(2)}$ is in terms of the basis vectors

$\phi_n \otimes \Phi_m$. This implies that $\eta_m \theta_n = \theta_n \eta_m$ i.e. that \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 are Hilbert spaces over the same commutative field.

It is common practice in experimental physics to isolate a spatially confined physical system from its environment. The theoretical description of this situation requires again the possibility to construct tensor product spaces in order to describe the independence of the physical system considered (part 1) from its environment (part 2)³. Physical independence of the two parts is then expressed by the statement that the observable algebra of the total system solely consists of the union of the observables of part 1, which have the form $A \otimes \mathbb{I}$, with the observables of part 2, $\mathbb{I} \otimes B$, which is equivalent to the statement that all observables of system 1 commute with all observables of system 2. Observables of the form $\sum_n A_n \otimes B_n$, with $A_n \neq \mathbb{I}$ and $B_n \neq \mathbb{I}$, describe interactions between the two parts.

One loses this possibility in Hilbert spaces based on quaternions — and alternative solutions to handle the situation in this case are not in sight. The authors of Ref. [30] are aware of this problem: *In [quaternion] quantum mechanics, ... there is no reasonable way of forming a composite system such that all the observables associated with one of the systems commute with all the observables associated with the other ... [which] prevents one at the very start from speaking of absolutely independent systems* [30, p. 211]. But they seem to accept this situation without really discussing its consequences or presenting valuable alternative solutions. To my opinion, one cannot renounce the possibility to construct tensor products in the theoretical description of physical systems as well as the idea of isolated systems in experimental physics. This rules out quaternion Hilbert spaces. Hence, it remains only the case $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}$.

7.4.3 Representation of states and observables in $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}$

An irreducible projection system shall now be represented by the set of the projectors on the subspaces of a complex Hilbert space. First, it will be shown that the representation of the states of this projection system is completely determined by the properties of the expectation values $E_s(a)$, Eqns. (2.12), (2.13), and the additivity property (Ad) for the sets of disjoint projections. The representation of observables by selfadjoint operators acting on $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}$ is already discussed in section 7.4.1. Finally, the usual trace formula for the quantum mechanical expectation value is derived.

An atom p of the projection system corresponds to a projector \hat{P} on a one-dimensional subspace of the complex Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}$. Such a subspace can be parametrised by a unit vector ϕ , on which the projector \hat{P} projects, $\hat{P}(\phi)\phi = \phi$. Consider an orthonormal basis $\{\phi_n\}$ of $\mathcal{H}_{\mathbb{C}}$. Then it is $\hat{P}(\phi_m)\hat{P}(\phi_n) = \delta_{mn}\hat{P}(\phi_m)$, i.e. $\hat{P}(\phi_m) \perp \hat{P}(\phi_n)$ for $m \neq n$ by equation (3.7), and $\sum_n \hat{P}(\phi_n) = I$. The set $\{\hat{P}(\phi_n)\}$ corresponds to the set $\{p(\phi_n)\}$ of mutually disjoint atoms, $p(\phi_n) \perp p(\phi_m)$ if $n \neq m$, with $\bigvee_n p(\phi_n) = I$. In terms of expectation values, one obtains with additivity (Ad)

$$\sum_n E_s(p(\phi_n)) = 1 \quad \text{with} \quad E_s(p(\phi_n)) \geq 0$$

for any orthonormal basis $\{\phi_n\}$ and for every state s . This means that $f_s(\phi) \equiv E_s(p(\phi))$ is a *frame function* for every state s in the sense of Gleason's theorem [31].

Theorem 7.8 (Gleason's theorem) *Let $\mathcal{S} = \{\psi \in \mathcal{H} / \|\psi\| = 1\}$ denote the unit sphere of a complex or real Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and $f(\phi)$ a frame function, i.e. a non-negative real function on \mathcal{S} such that $\sum_n f(\phi_n) = 1$ for any orthonormal basis $\{\phi_n\}$ of \mathcal{H} . For a complex (or real) Hilbert space of dimension not less than three, there exists, for any frame function f , a self-adjoint (or symmetric) operator T defined on \mathcal{H} such that $f(\phi) = (\phi, T\phi)$. The eigenvalues of T are non-negative and T belongs to the trace class with $\text{Tr}(T) = 1$.*

³Arguments that the quantum mechanical description of physical systems is intrinsically non-local making the idea of isolated systems obsolete are deconstructed in chapter 6 of Ref. [1].

An operator with these properties is called a *state operator*.

Consider an atom p and the corresponding projector $\hat{P}(\phi)$. According to Gleason's theorem, there is a state operator T_s for any state s such that

$$E_s(p(\phi)) = (\phi, T_s \phi) = (\phi, T_s \hat{P}(\phi) \phi) = \text{Tr}(T_s \hat{P}(\phi)) \equiv E_s(\hat{P}(\phi)) \quad (7.12)$$

for all vectors ϕ in \mathcal{S} (consider ϕ to be the vector ϕ_1 of an orthonormal basis). A general projection a corresponds to the projector \hat{Q}_a on the closed subspace $\mathcal{V}_a \subseteq \mathcal{H}_C$. If $\{\hat{P}_{a,l}\}$ is the set of projectors on an orthonormal basis $\{\phi_{a,l}\}$ of \mathcal{V}_a , then $\hat{Q}_a = \sum_l \hat{P}_{a,l}$ and, again by virtue of the additivity property (Ad) and of the linearity of the trace, it is

$$E_s(a) = E_s(\hat{Q}_a) = \sum_l E_s(\hat{P}_{a,l}) = \sum_l \text{Tr}(T_s \hat{P}_{a,l}) = \text{Tr}(T_s \hat{Q}_a) \quad (7.13)$$

Let s_p denote an eigenstate to the value 1 of the atom p represented by the projector \hat{P}_p projecting on a one-dimensional subspace of \mathcal{H}_C . It follows from the properties of a state operator and from equation (7.12) that the state operator T_{s_p} is equal to \hat{P}_p . Therefore, there is a one-to-one correspondence between atomic projections and atomic eigenstates as it is in the case of the classical projection systems discussed in section 2.5. The spectral resolution of a state operator has the form $T_s = \sum_n \rho_n^{(s)} \hat{P}_n^{(s)}$ with $0 < \rho_n^{(s)} \leq 1$ and $\sum_n \rho_n^{(s)} = 1$. Every state operator is a convex linear combination of at most countably many atomic projectors. This concludes the construction of the state space.

An observable A is represented by a selfadjoint operator \hat{A} acting on the Hilbertspace \mathcal{H}_C . The distribution function $F_{A,s}$ of the observable A , equation (2.3), is given by

$$F_{A,s}(\xi) = \text{Tr}(T_s \hat{Q}_{\hat{A}}(\xi)) \quad (7.14)$$

where $\hat{Q}_{\hat{A}}(\xi) = \chi_{(-\infty, \xi]}(\hat{A})$ denotes the spectral decomposition of the operator \hat{A} . As a consequence of equation (2.2) and of the linearity of the trace, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E_s(f(A)) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) dF_{A,s}(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) d\text{Tr}(T_s \hat{Q}_{\hat{A}}(\xi)) \\ &= \text{Tr}\left(T_s \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\xi) d\hat{Q}_{\hat{A}}(x)\right) = \text{Tr}(T_s f(\hat{A})) \end{aligned} \quad (7.15)$$

for all functions $f(\xi)$ for which the integrals exist. According to equation (2.7), the basic probability distribution $P_{A,s}(\sigma)$ characterising the observable A is given by

$$P_{A,s}(\sigma) = E_s(\chi_\sigma(A)) = \text{Tr}(T_s \chi_\sigma(\hat{A})) \quad (7.16)$$

With these results, the familiar formalism of quantum mechanics is completely constructed and the intended goal is accomplished.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

The quantitative predictions of quantum theories are intrinsically probabilistic. It is shown in this report that, conversely, the quantum mechanical Hilbert space structure of physical theories can be derived from the probabilistic nature of their quantitative predictions. The main postulate PSP indicates the minimal formal frame of quantitative physical theories namely that such a theory contains two different items, observables and states, and that it assigns a probability measure $P_{A,s}(\sigma)$ to an observable \mathcal{A} and a state s . The function $f(A)$ of the observable A is given already on this level by the relationship $P_{f(A),s}(\sigma) = P_{A,s}(f^{-1}(\sigma))$ for all states enabling the definition of projections as characteristic functions of observables, $a(\sigma) \equiv \chi_{\sigma}(A)$. A few additional regularity conditions compiled in section 3.4 complement the postulate PSP. These postulates entail that the system of the projections of a physical system is a bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, weakly modular, separable, atomic, and additive lattice (see chapters 2 and 3). This is the axiomatic basis of the subsequent mathematical analysis. It is a crucial feature of the physical projection systems that their irreducible components of finite rank are projective geometries (section 4.3), which allows to profit by the well developed algebraic representation theory of projective geometries. The mathematical analysis is carried through in chapters 4 to 7 with the result that classical and quantum mechanical theories based on complex Hilbert spaces are the only formal frames of quantitative physical theories.

One may content oneself with this mathematical analysis. We think, however, that there are general consequences concerning the theoretical description of physical systems, which deserve attention, too. First of all, the notion of state (as well as the notion of observable) is *not* situated in the realm of individual material systems, but in the realm of their theoretical description. This substantiates the standpoint of the statistical interpretation of quantum mechanics. The notion of state stands for the realisation of certain initial and/or boundary conditions on individual systems, which must be discriminated from the measurement of the value of an observable. This difference is not always considered.

Secondly, it is essential and logically proper that the notions of observable and of state are both introduced right at the start of the analysis and on an equal footing. The primary objects of physical theories are the properties of physical systems *i.e.* their observables and observable values, and the quantitative predictions of a theory depend on both, on the observable considered and on the state into which the physical system is prepared. The postulate PSP is, therefore, a natural and evident starting point, which immediately entails the lattice structure of the projection system of an observable, the existence of an orthogonal complement in this lattice, and a definition of disjointness independent of the notion of orthocomplementation, which only allows the clear discrimination between a complement and an orthogonal complement.

Thirdly, the expression $P_{A,s}(\sigma)$ denotes the theoretically predicted probability that the value of the observable A of an individual material system described by the theory and prepared according to the prescription given by the state s lies in the set σ . This definition is meaningful only if the value of an observable is considered an objective property of the individual system, a property which can be determined by an appropriate

measurement. This assumption is self-evident in classical physics, but sometimes contested for quantum mechanics. However, the present mathematical analysis is based on the same set of postulates for the resulting classical and quantum theories, the only possible theoretical frames in physics. Hence, the two types of physical theories rest on identical epistemological foundations. Consequently, quantum theories permit of a realistic and objective view on physical systems as it is uncontestedly accepted for classical theories. The question whether the standpoint of realism and objectivity results in inconsistencies or contradictions within the quantum mechanical formalism is discussed in appendix A: the answer is no.

The feature discriminating between classical and quantum theories is not their epistemological status, but the different structures of the mathematical representation of observables and states. Most significantly, observables are represented by the commutative algebra of real functions on the phase space in classical theories, whereas their quantum mechanical representation forms a non-commutative operator algebra acting on a complex Hilbert space. The identity $P_{f(A),s}(\sigma) = P_{A,s}(f^{-1}(\sigma))$ uniquely determines the classical as well as the quantum mechanical representation of the function $f(A)$ of an observable A . It follows from this fact and from the different structures of the quantum mechanical and the classical observable algebra that there are physical systems, which possess a quantum mechanical but no classical description. A prominent example is the spin system of two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles, the basis of Bohm's representation of the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen *gedankenexperiment* (see footnote 1 of chapter 1) and of Bells theorem [16]. As a consequence, Bell's theorem loses its content and its foundation (see appendix B). The *classical* not the quantum mechanical description of physical reality must be considered incomplete.

A related consequence of these findings is that one should clearly differentiate between the set of the observable values of an individual, material system denoting its physical properties and the set of the theoretical predictions for these values being valid for the whole infinite, theoretical ensemble of similar systems. This difference may be disregarded for classical theories because the system can then always be considered to be in an atomic state providing sharp predictions of the values of *all* observables, which gives the impression that physical theories directly deal with the properties of individual, material systems. In contrast, Heisenberg's uncertainty relations show that the values of observables, quantum mechanically represented by non-commuting operators (incommensurable observables), can not simultaneously be sharply predicted¹ although all these values represent objective properties of individual physical systems. Quantum theories do not provide a simultaneous access to all these values, but classical theories do. However, there is no doubt on empirical grounds that quantum theories are the fundamental frame to describe physical systems, not classical theories. Heisenberg's uncertainty relations are a structural property of quantum theories. Pertaining to experimental practice, they reveal that it is not possible to prepare a physical system in such a way that subsequent measurements of incommensurable observables always yield the same result — a limitation of human command upon nature on principle.

The quantum mechanical structure of physical theories is traced back in this report to the probabilistic nature of their quantitative predictions. This probabilistic nature is, in turn, understood as a consequence of the universal character of physical theories. The far-reaching implications of this rather general characterisation of physical statements still amaze me. They reveal, in my opinion, that the so-called statistical interpretation of the quantum mechanical formalism is not an interpretation among numerous others, but its only correct understanding.

¹This statement needs a qualification. In our context, the uncertainty relations denote the inequality

$$E_s((A - E_s(A))^2) E_s((B - E_s(B))^2) \geq E_s\left(\frac{i}{2}(AB - BA)\right)^2 \quad (8.1)$$

between expectation values. This relationship is a direct consequence of the inequality $E_s((A + i\lambda B)(A + i\lambda B)^*) \geq 0$ valid for all values of the real parameter λ (see *e.g.* [32, p. 223]). The right hand side of equation (8.1) is equal to 0 if $AB = BA$, but also if $AB \neq BA$ if the the state s is an eigenstate to the eigenvalue 0 of the commutator $i(AB - BA)$.

Appendix A

Quantum theory, realism, objectivity, and locality

We stress in chapter 1 that quantum theories, properly understood as probabilistic, are conformable to a realistic, objective, and local view on physical systems. Important items in this context are the insights, first, that the notion of state belongs to the realm of theoretical description implying that a state is not a property of an individual physical system and, secondly, that, in an experiment, the *state preparation* on an individual physical system must be discriminated from the *measurement* of the value of one of its observables. If these distinctions are heeded, then it becomes obvious that a measurement reveals an objective and preexisting property of this system — the point of view of realism and objectivity in physics — and not *e.g.* a property of the mental state of the experimentalist. *Locality* means that the notion of systems isolated from an environment can be theoretically described, that such systems can be experimentally realised, and that a manipulation on one of two mutually isolated systems has no influence on the factual situation of the other.

This point of view is not generally accepted. There are attempts to show that quantum mechanics directly conflicts with the principles of realism and locality not only with local classical theories. Prominent examples are provided by the work of Greenberger et al. [33] or of Stapp [34]. These papers are critically examined in Ref. [1], sections 6.2, 6.3. A particularly seductive version of this kind of arguments is a *gedankenexperiment* given by N. D. Mermin [35]. We first present Mermin's argumentation and then argue why we do not consider it conclusive.

A.1 Mermin's *gedankenexperiment*

Mermin's experimental arrangement resembles the one sketched in footnote 1 of chapter 1. Again, the spin observables and the spin states of two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles are considered. The system of two particles, initially in interaction, separates and the particles fly to two distant stations to the left and to the right. Locality in the above sense is then assumed. Two different observables both with possible observable values $+1$ and -1 are selected for each of the particles, A and B for the left particle and R and S for the right particle. The system is prepared in such a way that it displays the following features after separation:

- (i) A measurement of the observables B and S yields sometimes the value $+1$ for B and for S .
- (ii) A measurement of the observables A and S never yields the value $+1$ for A and for S .
- (iii) A measurement of the observables B and R never yields the value $+1$ for B and for R .
- (iv) A measurement of the observables A and R never yields the value -1 for A and for R .

We use a tensor product notation in order to mathematically represent Mermin's argumentation: vectors of the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = (\mathbb{C}^2)^1 \otimes (\mathbb{C}^2)^r$ are linear combinations of tensor products $\alpha \otimes \rho$ with α in $(\mathbb{C}^2)^1$, ρ in $(\mathbb{C}^2)^r$. The scalar product $(\alpha \otimes \rho, \beta \otimes \sigma) = (\alpha, \beta) (\rho, \sigma)$. The observables A, B, R, S, AR are written as $A \otimes \mathbb{I}, B \otimes \mathbb{I}, \mathbb{I} \otimes R, \mathbb{I} \otimes S, A \otimes R$ with the properties $(A \otimes R)(B \otimes S) = AB \otimes RS$, and $A \otimes R \alpha \otimes \rho = A \alpha \otimes R \rho$. We denote by $\alpha_{\pm}, \beta_{\pm}, \rho_{\pm}, \sigma_{\pm}$ eigenvectors of length 1 to the eigenvalues ± 1 of the observables A, B, R, S and introduce the projections $A_{\pm}, B_{\pm}, R_{\pm}, S_{\pm}$ projecting onto the eigenvectors α_{\pm} and so on. It is $A_+ + A_- = \mathbb{I}$ and $A = A_+ - A_- = 2A_+ - \mathbb{I} = \mathbb{I} - 2A_-$ i.e. the observables A, A_+ , and A_- are equivalent.

Mermin translates now features (i) – (iv) into conditions for the Hilbert space vector Ψ which represents the preparation of the system. Ψ is written in the tensor product basis $\alpha_{\pm} \otimes \rho_{\pm}$:

$$\Psi = c_{++} \alpha_+ \otimes \rho_+ + c_{+-} \alpha_+ \otimes \rho_- + c_{-+} \alpha_- \otimes \rho_+ + c_{--} \alpha_- \otimes \rho_- \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Using the identities $(\psi, P\psi) = (\Psi, P^2\Psi) = (P\Psi, P\Psi) = \|P\Psi\|^2$ valid for a projection P , he states

(i') It is

$$(\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) > 0 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

(ii') $(\Psi, A_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) = 0$, which is equivalent to $A_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi = 0$, implying

$$c_{+-} (\sigma_+, \rho_-) + c_{++} (\sigma_+, \rho_+) = 0 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

(iii') $(\Psi, B_+ \otimes R_+ \Psi) = 0$, which is equivalent to $B_+ \otimes R_+ \Psi = 0$, implying

$$c_{-+} (\beta_+, \alpha_-) + c_{++} (\beta_+, \alpha_+) = 0 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

(iv') $(\Psi, A_- \otimes R_- \Psi) = 0$, which is equivalent to $A_- \otimes R_- \Psi = 0$, implying

$$c_{--} = 0 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Mermin's conversion of features (i) – (iv) into the conditions (i') – (iv') for the vector Ψ makes clear that the former are theoretical predictions.

Exploiting normalisation, $1 = (\Psi, \Psi) = |c_{++}|^2 + |c_{+-}|^2 + |c_{-+}|^2 + |c_{--}|^2$, and equations (A.3) – (A.5) yield

$$(\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) = p \equiv \frac{p_l(1-p_l)p_r(1-p_r)}{1-p_l p_r} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

with

$$p_l = |(\beta_+, \alpha_+)|^2 \quad \text{and} \quad p_r = |(\sigma_+, \rho_+)|^2 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The quantity p is equal to 0 only if p_l or p_r are either equal to 0 or equal to 1. Now, $|(\beta_+, \alpha_+)|^2 = 0, 1$ imply $|(\beta_+, \alpha_-)|^2 = 1, 0$, or $B_+ = A_{\mp}$ or $B = \mp A$, respectively, and similarly for R and S . This is excluded by hypothesis. Therefore, $p > 0$ and features (i) and (i') are met. The maximal value of p equals ≈ 0.09017 according to Mermin. These results show that there are, in fact, states Ψ fulfilling conditions (i') – (iv'). Hence, the system of features (i) – (iv) is quantum mechanically consistent.

Mermin presents now an argumentation that seems to indicate a conflict between quantum mechanics and the positions of realism and locality. To this end, he considers a series of experiments on these two-particle systems, which are prepared according to the state Ψ and where the value of the observable B is measured on the left particles and the value of S on the right particles after their separation. He now exploits features (i) – (iv) in the following way:

- (I) According to equation (A.6), the results $+1$ of the observables B and S will be measured for a fraction $p > 0$ of all experiments in the long run singling out a non-empty subseries containing these results.
- (II) In each experiment of this subseries, the observables A and S could have been measured instead of B and S . If the particles are separated, then the measurement value of S is equal to $+1$ in both cases because of locality. According to property (ii), a measurement of A must yield the value -1 .
- (III) In each experiment of this subseries, the observables B and R could have been measured instead of B and S . If the particles are separated, then the measurement value of B is equal to $+1$ in both cases because of locality. According to property (iii), a measurement of R must yield the value -1 .
- (IV) As a consequence of statements (II) and (III), the value -1 must be assigned to the observables A and R whenever the value $+1$ is measured for B and for S . Hence, taking the whole series of experiments into account we have $(\Psi, A_- \otimes R_- \Psi) \geq (\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) > 0$, which contradicts condition (iv') stating that $(\Psi, A_- \otimes R_- \Psi) = 0$.

It seems, therefore, that quantum mechanics conflicts with the principle of locality. In addition, the position of realism and objectivity asserts that every observable of a physical system always possesses a definite value, which can be determined by a measurement. The above argumentation appears, therefore, convincing. But, *What's wrong with this temptation?*¹

A.2 What's wrong with this temptation?

In fact, a closer analysis reveals several problems of Mermin's interpretation (I) – (IV) of features (i) – (iv). As a general remark, we remember that a physical theory provides probability predictions of observable values and sharp (dispersion free) predictions only for the values of those observables for which the state is an eigenstate. This is not the case for any of the observables $A_{\pm} \otimes \mathbb{I}$, $B_{\pm} \otimes \mathbb{I}$, $\mathbb{I} \otimes R_{\pm}$, $\mathbb{I} \otimes S_{\pm}$ and the state Ψ . For instance

$$\begin{aligned}
0 < (\Psi, A_+ \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) &= |c_{++}|^2 + |c_{+-}|^2 = \frac{1 - p_l}{1 - p_l p_r} < 1 \\
0 < (\Psi, A_- \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) &= 1 - (\Psi, A_+ \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) = \frac{p_l(1 - p_r)}{1 - p_l p_r} < 1 \\
0 < (\Psi, B_+ \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) &= \frac{p_l p_r(1 - p_l)}{1 - p_l p_r} < 1 \\
0 < (\Psi, B_- \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) &= 1 - (\Psi, B_+ \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) < 1
\end{aligned} \tag{A.8}$$

and similarly for the expectation values of the the observables $\mathbb{I} \otimes R_{\pm}$, $\mathbb{I} \otimes S_{\pm}$.

The first problem of Mermin's argumentation is the assumption that the principle of locality is valid for the system prepared according to the state Ψ *i.e.* that the results of the measurement of the observables R or S are independent of the results of any measurement of A or B . But a system prepared according to the state Ψ cannot describe independent particles because of conditions (ii') and (iii'). This becomes evident by taking into account that the operator $A_+ \otimes S_+$ is the product of the two commuting operators $A_+ \otimes \mathbb{I}$ and $\mathbb{I} \otimes S_+$, which can be considered real functions $f(C)$ and $g(C)$ of an operator C according to a theorem of J. von Neumann [22]. A measurement of the observable C with the result $m[C]$ provides a simultaneous measurement of $A_+ \otimes \mathbb{I}$, $\mathbb{I} \otimes S_+$, and $A_+ \otimes S_+ = (A_+ \otimes \mathbb{I})(\mathbb{I} \otimes S_+)$ with the results $f(m[C])$, $g(m[C])$, and $(fg)(m[C])$. Hence, the following relationship between measurement values provides the definition of $m[A_+ \otimes S_+]$:

$$m[A_+ \otimes S_+] = m[A_+] m[S_+] \tag{A.9}$$

¹This is the title of Ref. [35].

We now consider the values of a measurement series of the projection $A_+ \otimes S_+$ in the limit of infinite length

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N m[A_+]_n m[S_+]_n = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N m[A_+ \otimes S_+]_n = (\Psi, A_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

This limit is also equal to the probability to find the measurement value 1 of the observables A_+ , S_+ , and $A_+ \otimes S_+$ in the series. If the observables A_+ and S_+ are considered independent, then the joint probability $P(A_+ = 1 \text{ and } S_+ = 1)$ must be equal to the product $P(A_+ = 1) P(S_+ = 1)$. Therefore,

$$(\Psi, A_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) = (\Psi, A_+ \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) (\Psi, \mathbb{I} \otimes S_+ \Psi) > 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

if locality is required and according to equations (A.8). Hence, if the system is prepared in the state Ψ entailing $(\Psi, A_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) = 0$, then equation (A.11) implies that the observables $A_+ \otimes \mathbb{I}$ and $\mathbb{I} \otimes S_+$ are *not* independent. Equally, $(\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) \neq (\Psi, B_+ \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) (\Psi, \mathbb{I} \otimes S_+ \Psi)$. It cannot be assumed that the measured value of S_+ is the same irrespective whether B_+ , case (i'), or A_+ , case (ii'), is measured simultaneously.

On the other hand, it seems reasonable to assume locality if the particles are separated. How can the situation be managed that the two particles are initially prepared according to the state Ψ and can, nevertheless, lateron be considered free? We sketch the following line of arguments based on the position of realism: the preparation procedure implies that the two particles must initially be subjected to an interaction, which impose the conditions (ii') and (iii') to the system. The interaction ceases if the particles are sufficiently separated. Afterwards, the observable values of the single particles remain constant as long as the particles are free, and these values conform with the predictions (A.8).

The important clue is that the observable algebra of the particles considered free contains only elements of the form $L \otimes \mathbb{I}$ and $\mathbb{I} \otimes R$, the observables describing correlations as $A_+ \otimes R_+$ must be disregarded. In respect of this reduced set of observables, the pure state Ψ is equivalent to a tensor product state $T^l \otimes T^r$, T^l and T^r denoting state operators, positive and selfadjoint operators with trace 1 (*cf.* Mackey's separation postulate S1 in chapter 2). These state operators are determined by the condition that they reproduce the predictions given by the state Ψ for the sets $\{L \otimes \mathbb{I}\}$ and $\{\mathbb{I} \otimes R\}$. Hence, the equations between expectation values

$$E_{T^l}(L) \equiv \text{Tr}_2(T^l L) = (\Psi, L \otimes \mathbb{I} \Psi) \quad \text{and} \quad E_{T^r}(R) \equiv \text{Tr}_2(T^r R) = (\Psi, \mathbb{I} \otimes R \Psi) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

are valid for arbitrary observables L and R of the left and of the right particle, respectively.

In order to calculate T^l and T^r , consider an orthonormal basis $\lambda_i \otimes \rho_m$, $i, m = 1, 2$, of the Hilbert space $(\mathbb{C}^2)^l \otimes (\mathbb{C}^2)^r$. The vector Ψ possesses the expansion $\Psi = c_{11} \lambda_1 \otimes \rho_1 + c_{12} \lambda_1 \otimes \rho_2 + c_{21} \lambda_2 \otimes \rho_1 + c_{22} \lambda_2 \otimes \rho_2$ and the matrix elements of $L \otimes R$ relating to this basis equal

$$(L \otimes R)_{im, jn} \equiv (\lambda_i \otimes \rho_m, L \otimes R \lambda_j \otimes \rho_n) = l_{ij} r_{mn} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

with $l_{ij} = (\lambda_i, L \lambda_j)$ and $r_{mn} = (\rho_m, R \rho_n)$.

The state operators T^l and T^r with matrix elements t_{ij}^l and t_{mn}^r , respectively, can now be evaluated using the identities (A.12). The results are

$$T^l = \begin{pmatrix} |c_{11}|^2 + |c_{12}|^2 & c_{21}^* c_{11} + c_{22}^* c_{12} \\ c_{11}^* c_{21} + c_{12}^* c_{22} & |c_{21}|^2 + |c_{22}|^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad T^r = \begin{pmatrix} |c_{11}|^2 + |c_{21}|^2 & c_{12}^* c_{11} + c_{22}^* c_{21} \\ c_{11}^* c_{12} + c_{21}^* c_{22} & |c_{12}|^2 + |c_{22}|^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Equation (A.13) entails that

$$\text{Tr}_4(L \otimes R) = \text{Tr}_2(L) \text{Tr}_2(R) \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Therefore, the expectation value of $A_+ \otimes S_+$ factorises in regard of the state described by $T^l \otimes T^r$

$$\begin{aligned} E_{T^l \otimes T^r}(A_+ \otimes S_+) &= \text{Tr}_4((T^l \otimes T^r)(A_+ \otimes S_+)) = \text{Tr}_4(T^l A_+ \otimes T^r S_+) \\ &= \text{Tr}_2(T^l A_+) \text{Tr}_2(T^r S_+) = E_{T^l}(A_+) E_{T^r}(S_+) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

and is positive in complete conformity with equation (A.11).

The transition from the pure state Ψ to the state operator $T^1 \otimes T^r$ is not caused by a physical process, but results from the consistent description of the different physical situations. This transition concerns only the state *i.e.* the set of possible theoretical predictions. The properties of the individual, material particles are not touched by this change. In particular, correlations between the values of their observables caused by the initial preparation are, indeed, not displayed by the state operators, but persist nevertheless and may be used as indicated in footnote 1 of chapter 1. It is, therefore, inappropriate to speak of 'entangled states': not the state, a term on the level of theoretical description, is entangled, but individual, material systems are entangled in consequence of a specific state preparation and experimental history.

The lack of locality causes a second problem namely that no *real* experimental situation can match the situation of Mermin's *gedankenexperiment*. The experimenters must decide whether they want to measure B_+ and S_+ or A_+ and S_+ . Only the values of the actually performed measurements are available because it can no longer be assumed that the result of the measurement of the observable S_+ is the same irrespective whether B_+ or A_+ is measured. To treat the values of performed and of unperformed measurements on an equal footing is an act of *counterfactual definiteness*², a situation akin to classical theories where all observable values are considered equally available. Assuming counterfactual definiteness means that one argues on the basis of more information than is factually available — an inadmissible assumption.

A third problem is that Mermin's arguments (I) – (IV) are based on the measurement values of a *subseries* of experiments. But features (i) – (iv) concern *theoretical predictions* of the measurement values and apply uniformly to the *total* series. An argumentation based on a subseries selected according to a criterion foreign to the conditions imposed by the state preparation is likely to be misleading. As for the subseries, Mermin implicitly presupposes either counterfactual definiteness as stated above, or that all measurement values $m[A]$, $m[B]$, $m[R]$, $m[S]$ are sharply predicted *i.e.* that there is an underlying classical theory. But the system of features (i) – (iv) formulated in terms of sharply predicted measurement values is contradictory because all combinations of measurement values conformable to features (iv), (iii), and (ii) exclude the combination $m[B] = m[S] = +1$, the basis of feature (i). Or the other way round, the premise $m[B] = m[S] = +1$ implies that $m[A] = m[R] = -1$ contradicting feature (iv). There are measurement values $m[A]$, $m[B]$, $m[R]$, $m[S]$, which fulfil features (i), (ii), and (iii), but there is no such set, which fulfils all features (i) – (iv). The conclusion is that the system of four observables A , B , R , S exhibiting these features possesses a quantum mechanical, but no classical representation.

That Mermin's argumentation is problematic becomes obvious if the case $(\Psi, A_- \otimes R_- \Psi) = |c_{--}|^2 \geq 0$ is considered. Features (i), (ii), (iii) with equations (A.3) and (A.4) remain valid and equation (A.6) then generalises to

$$(\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi) = (1 - |c_{--}|^2)p \quad (\text{A.17})$$

The greater $(\Psi, A_- \otimes R_- \Psi)$ the smaller is $(\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi)$, and $(\Psi, A_- \otimes R_- \Psi)$ is smaller or equal than $(\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi)$ if $|c_{--}|^2 \leq p/(1+p)$ and greater otherwise. The arguments (I) – (IV) can identically be carried out also for $0 \leq |c_{--}|^2 < 1$ and entail that it is then always $(\Psi, A_- \otimes R_- \Psi) \geq (\Psi, B_+ \otimes S_+ \Psi)$.

Clearly, the inconsistency of Mermin's starting point, features (i) – (iv) interpreted according to (I) – (IV), deprives his argumentation of its foundation and we could have stopped arguing after having stated this point and its consequences. However, the implicit assumption of counterfactual definiteness or of an underlying classical theory, and an insufficient discrimination between the observable values of individual systems and their prediction by a theory are at the root of all attempts I know to show, based on measurement values, the non-locality or non-reality of quantum mechanics, prototypically in Ref. [33] or [34]. The above discussion also provides the opportunity to discuss the nature and the use of entangled systems in the statistical interpretation of quantum mechanics.

²This term ... is used to describe the character of statements about "what could have occurred" in a measurement that we could have performed but did not actually perform [32, p. 608].

Appendix B

There is no classical theory of the spin space of two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles

This particular example is due to N. David Mermin [36, p. 809]. He shows that the system of the nine spin operators $s_1^A, s_1^B, s_1^A s_1^B, s_2^B, s_2^A, s_2^A s_2^B, s_1^A s_2^B, s_2^A s_1^B, s_3^A s_3^B$ of the system of two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles acting on a four-dimensional Hilbert space does not possess a classical hidden variables model. A slight twist in argumentation even reveals that the set of observables, quantum mechanically represented by this nine operators, cannot be represented by a classical theory at all. Here are the arguments:

A 3×3 array of operators \hat{A}_{ij} is derived from Mermin's set: $\hat{A}_{11} = (2/\hbar) s_1^A = \sigma_1^A, \hat{A}_{12} = (2/\hbar) s_1^B = \sigma_1^B, \dots, \hat{A}_{33} = (2/\hbar)^2 s_3^A s_3^B = \sigma_3^A \sigma_3^B$ *i.e.*

$$(\hat{A}_{ij}) = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1^A & \sigma_1^B & \sigma_1^A \sigma_1^B \\ \sigma_2^B & \sigma_2^A & \sigma_2^A \sigma_2^B \\ \sigma_1^A \sigma_2^B & \sigma_2^A \sigma_1^B & \sigma_3^A \sigma_3^B \end{pmatrix}$$

$\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are the Pauli spin matrices. The properties of the spin matrices ($\sigma_i^2 = \mathbb{I}, \sigma_1 \sigma_2 = -\sigma_2 \sigma_1 = i\sigma_3, \sigma_3 \sigma_1 = -\sigma_1 \sigma_3 = i\sigma_2, \sigma_2 \sigma_3 = -\sigma_3 \sigma_2 = i\sigma_1$) and $\sigma_i^A \sigma_j^B = \sigma_j^B \sigma_i^A$ entail that the operators in each of the rows and in each of the columns of the array \hat{A}_{ij} commute. In addition, the products of the three operators in each of the rows and in columns 1 and 2 are equal to $\hat{\mathbb{I}}$, but the product of the operators in column 3 is equal to $-\hat{\mathbb{I}}$. Mermin then argues that this situation cannot be met by the set of values assigned to the nine operators in an atomic state of a hidden variables model.

We argue differently. The operators of a commuting set are real functions of a common operator according to a theorem due to von Neumann [22], or see [1, p. 20] for the present simple case. Hence, there are operators $\hat{R}_1, \hat{R}_2, \hat{R}_3, \hat{C}_1, \hat{C}_2, \hat{C}_3$, and real functions f_{ij}, g_{ij} such that

$$\hat{A}_{ij} = f_{ij}(\hat{R}_i) = g_{ij}(\hat{C}_j) \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2, 3.$$

We consider now the operators $\hat{A}_{ij}, \hat{R}_i, \hat{C}_j, \hat{\mathbb{I}}$ to be the quantum mechanical equivalents of the observables $A_{ij}, R_i, C_j, \mathbb{I}$. This set of observables fulfils the equations $A_{ij} = f_{ij}(R_i) = g_{ij}(C_j)$ because the relationship $\hat{B} = f(\hat{A})$ between operators is valid if and only if $B = f(A)$ for the corresponding observables, *i.e.* if $P_{B,s}(\sigma) \equiv P_{f(A),s}(\sigma) = P_{A,s}(f^{-1}(\sigma))$ in terms of the probability measures (*cf.* equations (2.7), (2.8), and (7.16)). In addition, all products of the observables in a row or in a column, as *e.g.* $A_{11}A_{12}A_{13} = f_{11}(R_1)f_{12}(R_1)f_{13}(R_1) = (f_{11}f_{12}f_{13})(R_1) = \mathbb{I}$, are defined as observables, too, and yield the analogue results as for the operators. Hence, the inequality

$$\mathbb{I} = (A_{11}A_{12}A_{13})(A_{21}A_{22}A_{23})(A_{31}A_{32}A_{33}) \neq (A_{11}A_{21}A_{31})(A_{12}A_{22}A_{32})(A_{13}A_{23}A_{33}) = -\mathbb{I}$$

between the products of observables is defined and valid.

A classical theory for this set of observables assigns real functions $\tilde{A}_{ij}, \tilde{R}_j, \tilde{C}_i, 1$ defined on a phase space to the corresponding observables (see section 2.5), and the equations $\tilde{A}_{ij} = f_{ij}(\tilde{R}_j) = g_{ij}(\tilde{C}_i)$ must be valid according to the arguments already given — in short, $\hat{B} = f(\hat{A})$ is equivalent to $B = f(A)$, which is, in turn, equivalent to $\tilde{B} = f(\tilde{A})$, see equation (2.33). But the above inequality cannot be met by the set of real functions \tilde{A}_{ij} , which all commute. Hence, there is no classical theory for Mermin's nine operators. The obvious reason is that the non-commutative quantum mechanical operator algebra cannot be reconciled with the commutative functional algebra of a classical theory even if the map of the quantum mechanical on the classical observables is restricted to the commutative subalgebras of the quantum mechanical operators. Evidently, neither locality nor the assumption that the predictions of the classical theory should conform to the quantum mechanical predictions play any rôle.

One can prove with similar arguments that no spin space possesses a classical theory (see [1, chapter 3] for a thorough discussion of this topic) except the two-dimensional space of spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ [37]. The crucial point is again that non-commutative quantum mechanical spin algebras cannot be mapped on classical commutative algebras of real functions if the dimension of the Hilbert space exceeds the value two.

In order to discuss the impact of this result on Bell's theorem, we fully cite section II of Bell's paper [16]:

With the example advocated by Bohm and Aharonov [11], the EPR argument is the following. Consider a pair of spin one-half particles formed somehow in the singlet spin state and moving freely in opposite directions. Measurements can be made, say by Stern-Gerlach magnets, on selected components of the spins $\vec{\sigma}_1$ and $\vec{\sigma}_2$. If measurement of the component $\vec{a} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_1$, where \vec{a} is some unit vector, yields the value +1 then, according to quantum mechanics, measurement of $\vec{a} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_2$ must yield the value -1 and vice versa. Now we make the hypothesis [of locality], and it seems one at least worth considering, that if the two measurements are made at places remote from one another the orientation of one magnet does not influence the result obtained with the other. Since we can predict in advance the result of measuring any chosen component of $\vec{\sigma}_2$, by previously measuring the same component of $\vec{\sigma}_1$, it follows that the result of any such measurement must actually be predetermined. Since the initial quantum mechanical wave function does not determine the result of an individual measurement, this predetermination implies the possibility of a more complete specification of the state.

Let this more complete specification be effected by means of parameters λ . It is a matter of indifference in the following whether λ denotes a single variable or a set, or even a set of functions, and whether the variables are discrete or continuous. However, we write as if λ were a single continuous parameter. The result A of measuring $\vec{a} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_1$ is then determined by \vec{a} and λ , and the result B of measuring $\vec{b} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_2$ in the same instance is determined by \vec{b} and λ , and

$$A(\vec{a}, \lambda) = \pm 1, B(\vec{b}, \lambda) = \pm 1 \quad (1)$$

The vital assumption ... is that the result B for particle 2 does not depend on the setting \vec{a} of the magnet for particle 1, nor A on \vec{b} .

If $\rho(\lambda)$ is the probability distribution of λ then the expectation value of the product of the two components $\vec{a} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_1$ and $\vec{b} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_2$ is

$$P(\vec{a}, \vec{b}) = \int A(\vec{a}, \lambda) B(\vec{b}, \lambda) \rho(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (2)$$

This should equal the quantum mechanical expectation value, which for the singlet state is

$$\langle \vec{a} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_1 \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_2 \rangle = -\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b} \quad (3)$$

But it will be shown that this is not possible.

Some might prefer a formulation in which the hidden variables fall into two sets, with A dependent on one and B on the other; this possibility is contained in the one above, since λ stands for any number of variables and the dependences thereon of A and B are unrestricted. In a complete physical theory of the type envisaged by Einstein, the hidden variables would have dynamical significance and laws of motion; our λ can then be thought of as initial values of these variables at some suitable instant.

Bell's theorem now states that "the quantum mechanical expectation values (3) cannot be represented, either accurately or arbitrarily closely, in the form (2)" [16, p. 199] i.e. by a local hidden variables theory.

Bell proves this statement by deducing an inequality for the quantities $P(\vec{a}, \vec{b})$, an improved version of it, based uniquely on equation (2) and the assumptions $|A(\vec{a}, \lambda)| \leq 1$, $|B(\vec{b}, \lambda)| \leq 1$ weaker than (1) and renouncing the condition of strict anticorrelation, was given later on by Clauser et al. [38]:

$$|P(\vec{a}, \vec{b}) - P(\vec{a}, \vec{b}')| + |P(\vec{a}', \vec{b}) + P(\vec{a}', \vec{b}')| \leq 2 \quad (4)$$

valid for any set of directions $\vec{a}, \vec{a}', \vec{b}, \vec{b}'$. But this inequality is violated for some of these sets if the function $P(\vec{a}, \vec{b})$ is replaced by the quantum mechanical expectation values (3), the maximal value of the left-hand side then being $2\sqrt{2}$ (see [1, section 6.1]).

Bell's theorem is true, but in a trivial way. In the text cited above, Bell aims at a classical theory, as defined in section 2.5, of this spin system. His specifying parameter λ corresponds to the carrier of a classical atomic state; the set of all parameter values forms the phase space of the classical theory. The quantities $A(\vec{a}, \lambda)$ and $B(\vec{b}, \lambda)$ represent the predictions for the measurement values of the observables $\vec{a} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_1$ and $\vec{b} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_2$ given by the classical theory for the atomic state with carrier λ . The function $\rho(\lambda)$ is the probability density of the probability measure associated with the state of the classical theory. Finally, equation (2) is the classical expectation value, equation (2.30), of the product $A(\vec{a}, \lambda) B(\vec{b}, \lambda)$ supposed to correspond to the quantum mechanical operator $\vec{a} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_1 \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\sigma}_2$. However, we have shown above that the spin observables of two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles cannot be described by a classical theory. Therefore, expression (2) cannot be a part of a classical representation of this physical system, and to compare the values $P(\vec{a}, \vec{b})$ of equation (2) with the values $-\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}$ of equation (3) has no foundation.

Clauser et al. [38] express the conviction that their proposed experiment "will provide a decisive test between quantum mechanics and local hidden-variables theories". This conviction was confirmed: a sequence of still more refined experimental tests were performed, whose results were finally in an excellent agreement with the quantum mechanical predictions but incompatible with the predictions of Bell's hidden variables model. Hence, Bell's model has been refuted by experiment, and the existence of hidden variables models of Bell's type was convincingly contested by Kochen and Specker [37] — and that is the whole story. Or should be.

However, an other line of argument got the upper hand. Bell was strongly convinced that hidden variable models of quantum theories are possible and that his equations (1) and (2) denote such a "more complete specification" of the quantum mechanical description of the spin system of two spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles. Later on, the experimental falsification of inequality (4) was considered the falsification of the condition of locality expressed by equations (1) and (2) and the experimental validation of the assertion that quantum mechanics be nonlocal, an assertion suggested by the strange properties of entangled systems in the Copenhagen interpretation (see footnote 1 of chapter 1). Bell finally stated the consequences of his theorem as follows [39, p. 153]: "So the quantum correlations are locally inexplicable."¹ In opposition to this, we hold that the Copenhagen interpretation is mistaken, that quantum mechanics is local if the statistical interpretation is adopted, and that Bell's model cannot be the theoretical description of the considered spin system.

¹The progression of the historical events is clearly much more involved than sketched here and interesting. A detailed and valuable account of these events is given by O. Freire Jr. [40].

Appendix C

Elements of probability theory

In this Appendix, central notions and concepts of probability theory based on the axiomatics of A. N. Kolmogorov are presented. These axioms form a widely accepted axiomatic basis of probability theory, which allows to treat discrete and continuous probability distributions on an equal footing. Our summary rests on Gnedenko's textbook of probability theory [20], in particular on its paragraph 8.

In Kolmogorov's axiomatics, probability theory is based on set theory. We renounce an axiomatic definition of sets, which is an involved and controversial issue, but rely on the intuitive understanding of sets as collections of elements. This point of view does not entail fallacies or contradictions in the case of real numbers, the case, which is of main interest for our purposes.

First, we recall some basic definitions of set and order theory [41, p. 2, 5]. The *void* or *empty* set, denoted \emptyset , is the set with no element. If every element of a set σ_1 is also an element of the set σ_2 , then σ_1 is a *subset* of σ_2 , denoted $\sigma_1 \subseteq \sigma_2$. $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$ means $\sigma_1 \subseteq \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_2 \subseteq \sigma_1$. The *union* of the sets σ_1 and σ_2 , denoted $\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2$, is the set of all elements belonging either to σ_1 or to σ_2 or to both. The *intersection* of σ_1 and σ_2 , denoted $\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2$, is the set of all elements which belong to both sets, σ_1 and σ_2 . Let σ be a subset of the set Ω . The *complement of σ relative to Ω* is the totality of elements ω in Ω not contained in σ . It is denoted by $\sigma \setminus \Omega$ or by σ' if the reference set Ω is obvious. The *difference* of two sets $\sigma_1 \subseteq \Omega$ and $\sigma_2 \subseteq \Omega$, denoted $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$, is the totality of elements ω which are in σ_1 but not in σ_2 : $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2 \equiv \sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2'$. Two sets σ_1 and σ_2 are *disjoint*, $\sigma_1 \perp \sigma_2$, if $\sigma_1 \subseteq \sigma_2'$ or, equivalently, if their intersection is void, $\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2 = \emptyset$.

The set inclusion $\sigma_1 \subseteq \sigma_2$ induces a *partial ordering* in Ω , denoted by $\sigma_1 \leq \sigma_2$ (σ_1 *precedes* σ_2 or σ_2 *follows* σ_1), with the properties

- (O1) $\sigma \leq \sigma$ for all subsets σ of Ω .
- (O2) $\sigma_1 \leq \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_2 \leq \sigma_1$ imply $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$ for σ_1 and σ_2 in Ω .
- (O3) $\sigma_1 \leq \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_2 \leq \sigma_3$ imply $\sigma_1 \leq \sigma_3$ for σ_1, σ_2 , and σ_3 in Ω .

If $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are elements of the partially ordered set Ω and if $\sigma_1 \leq \sigma_3$ and $\sigma_2 \leq \sigma_3$, then σ_3 is termed an *upper bound* of σ_1 and σ_2 . If furthermore $\sigma_3 \leq \sigma$ for all sets σ being upper bounds for σ_1 and σ_2 in Ω , then σ_3 is called the *least upper bound*, or the *supremum*, of σ_1 and σ_2 denoted by $\sup(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$. Similarly, one defines a *lower bound* and the *greatest lower bound*, or the *infimum*, of σ_1 and σ_2 denoted by $\inf(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$. It is

$$\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2 = \sup(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2 = \inf(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \quad (\text{C.1})$$

The basic notion of probability theory is the *random experiment*, the possible outcomes ω of which form the *sample space* or the *space of elementary events* Ω . Ω is a set. A subset σ of Ω is called a (*random*) *event*,

which means that the result ω of a random experiment lies in the set σ . The set Σ of random events fulfils the following axioms:

($\Sigma 1$) Ω is an element of Σ .

($\Sigma 2$) If σ_1 and σ_2 are subsets of Ω and elements of Σ , then their complements σ_i' with respect to Ω , the union $\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2$, and the intersection $\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2$ are elements of Σ .

($\Sigma 3$) If the countably infinite subsets $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots$ of Ω are all elements of Σ , then their union $\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2 \cup \dots \equiv \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_n$ and their intersection $\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2 \cap \dots \equiv \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_n$ are elements of Σ .

These three conditions specify a σ -field. Together with Ω , the empty set $\emptyset = \Omega'$ is an element of Σ . Ω is the *certain event*, \emptyset the *impossible event*. σ -fields are distributive, equation (2.5). A partial order in Σ is given by set inclusion. Hence, σ -fields are bounded, complete, distributive, complemented, and, therefore, also orthocomplemented lattices.

A *probability* is a real function P on Σ with the following properties (Kolmogorov axioms):

(K1) The probability $P(\sigma)$ of any event σ in Σ is a real number with $0 \leq P(\sigma) \leq 1$.

(K2) $P(\Omega) = 1$.

(K3) If $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots$ is a finite or a countably infinite set of pairwise disjoint random events *i.e.* $\sigma_n \cap \sigma_m = \emptyset$ for all $n \neq m$, then $P(\bigcup_n \sigma_n) = \sum_n P(\sigma_n)$: P is σ -additive.

A function $P : \Sigma \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with these properties is termed a *probability measure* and the triplet (Ω, Σ, P) a *probability space*.

It is $\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2 = \sigma_1 \cup (\sigma_1' \cap \sigma_2)$ and $\sigma_2 = (\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) \cup (\sigma_1' \cap \sigma_2)$. The righthand sides are unions of disjoint sets. Therefore, $P(\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2) = P(\sigma_1) + P(\sigma_1' \cap \sigma_2)$ and $P(\sigma_2) = P(\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) + P(\sigma_1' \cap \sigma_2)$, which implies

$$P(\sigma_1) + P(\sigma_2) = P(\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2) + P(\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) \quad (\text{C.2})$$

for all subsets σ_1 and σ_2 of Ω .

The *conditional probability* $P(\sigma | \sigma_1)$ is the probability of the event σ under the condition that the event σ_1 with $P(\sigma_1) > 0$ occurs or has occurred. It is

$$P(\sigma | \sigma_1) = \frac{P(\sigma \cap \sigma_1)}{P(\sigma_1)} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

The conditional probability $P(\sigma | \sigma_1)$ is a probability with probability space $(\sigma_1, \Sigma \cap \sigma_1, P(\sigma \cap \sigma_1)/P(\sigma_1))$. Two random events σ_1 and σ_2 are *independent* if $P(\sigma_1 | \sigma_2) = P(\sigma_1)$, $P(\sigma_2) > 0$, or $P(\sigma_2 | \sigma_1) = P(\sigma_2)$, $P(\sigma_1) > 0$: the occurrence of σ_2 does not change the probability of σ_1 and *vice versa*. The random events σ_1 and σ_2 are independent if $P(\sigma_1 \cap \sigma_2) = P(\sigma_1) P(\sigma_2)$.

Let Ω be a *topological space* *i.e.* a space provided with a topology. A family \mathcal{T} of subsets of Ω defines a topology on Ω if

(T1) \mathcal{T} contains \emptyset and Ω ,

(T2) \mathcal{T} contains the union of every one of its subsystems,

(T3) \mathcal{T} contains the intersection of every one of its *finite* subsystems.

The space Ω may carry several topologies. The sets in \mathcal{T} are called the *open sets* of the topological space (Ω, \mathcal{T}) [41, p. 11]. The *Borel σ -field* $\mathcal{B}(\Omega)$ is the σ -field generated by the open subsets of Ω according to the chosen topology. An element $\sigma \in \mathcal{B}(\Omega)$ is called a *Borel set*. Borel σ -fields are particularly suited to describe the set of random events in probability theory.

The case $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}$, the elementary events being real numbers, is of prime importance for our purposes. $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ is generated by the open intervals (α, β) , which create the *usual topology* on \mathbb{R} . Alternatively, $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ may be generated by the set of the intervals $(\alpha, +\infty)$ or of $(-\infty, \alpha)$, or by the set of the closed intervals $[\alpha, \beta]$, or of the semiclosed intervals $(\alpha, \beta]$ or $[\alpha, \beta)$ or $(-\infty, \alpha]$ or $[\alpha, +\infty)$ [41, p. 33].

The Borel σ -field $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ is *separable i.e.* it contains a countable generating set, e.g. the set $\{(-\infty, r_n]\}$, the sequence r_1, r_2, \dots denoting an enumeration of the rational numbers. Isolated real numbers $[\xi]$ are elements of $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$: $[\xi] = (\alpha, \xi] \cap [\xi, \beta)$ with $\alpha < \xi < \beta$. The real number ξ cannot be the intersection of a finite number of open intervals $\alpha < \xi < \beta$ and is, thus, not open in the usual topology of \mathbb{R} . On the other hand, ξ is an infinite intersection of open intervals *i.e.* of the set $\{(\xi - 1/n, \xi + 1/n) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$. In a topology where isolated points are open sets (*discrete topology*) every set is open, a property, which is undesirable for many purposes [41, p. 12]. This explains why only *finite* intersections are admitted in the condition (T3) of a topology.

Let $f : \xi \in D_f \subseteq \Omega \rightarrow f(\xi) \in \Delta_f \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a single valued, measurable, real function or *Borel function* on D_f , D_f denoting the *domain* and Δ_f the *range* of f . The function f is *measurable* if the *full inverse* $f^{-1}(\sigma) \equiv \{\omega \in D_f : f(\omega) \in \sigma\}$ lies in $\mathcal{B}(\Omega)$ for every Borel set σ in $\mathcal{B}(\Delta_f)$. The full inverse image f^{-1} preserves the union and the intersection of Borel sets. The full inverse f^{-1} is defined for $\sigma \subseteq \Delta_f$ in the first instance, but it is readily extended to arbitrary real Borel sets. Define $f^{-1}(\sigma) = \emptyset$ for $\sigma \subseteq \Delta_f'$ and use the identity $f^{-1}(\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2) = f^{-1}(\sigma_1) \cup f^{-1}(\sigma_2)$. It is then

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(\sigma) &= f^{-1}(\sigma \cap (\Delta_f \cup \Delta_f')) = f^{-1}((\sigma \cap \Delta_f) \cup (\sigma \cap \Delta_f')) \\ &= f^{-1}(\sigma \cap \Delta_f) \cup f^{-1}(\sigma \cap \Delta_f') = f^{-1}(\sigma \cap \Delta_f) \cup \emptyset = f^{-1}(\sigma \cap \Delta_f) \end{aligned}$$

The function $f^{-1}(\sigma \cap \Delta_f)$ is defined for all real Borel sets σ .

A *stochastic variable* or *random variable* X is a measurable real function on the sample space Ω of a probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{B}(\Omega), P)$. The probabilistic characteristics of the stochastic variable X are determined by its *distribution function* $F_X(\xi)$, the probability of the random event '*the value of X is less or equal than ξ* ':

$$F_X(\xi) = P(X \leq \xi) \equiv P((-\infty, \xi]) \quad (\text{C.4})$$

The distribution function is characterised by the following properties

1. $0 \leq F_X(\xi) \leq 1$
2. $F_X(\xi)$ monotonously increases from $\lim_{\xi \rightarrow -\infty} F_X(\xi) = 0$ to $\lim_{\xi \rightarrow +\infty} F_X(\xi) = 1$ (C.5)
3. $F_X(\xi)$ is continuous from the right: $\lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} F_X(\xi + \epsilon) = F_X(\xi)$

$F_X(\xi)$ is *discontinuous* at $\xi = \xi_0$ if $\lim_{\epsilon \downarrow 0} (F_X(\xi_0) - F_X(\xi_0 - \epsilon)) > 0$. A distribution function is discontinuous at most at countably infinite values of its argument [20, p. 123].

The distribution function $F_X(\xi)$ defines a real probability space $(\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}), P_X)$ where the probability measure P_X is generated by

$$P_X((\xi_1, \xi_2]) = F_X(\xi_2) - F_X(\xi_1) \text{ for } \xi_1 < \xi_2$$

The probability of an arbitrary interval follows from σ -additivity. The stochastic variable X corresponds to the linear function $x : \xi \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \xi$ with respect to the probability space $(\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}), P_X)$.

The *expectation value* of the stochastic variable $f(X)$ is given by the Stieltjes integral [18, p. 97]

$$E(f(X)) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(\xi) dF_X(\xi) \quad (\text{C.6})$$

The nonnegative *probability density* $\rho_X(\xi)$ of a stochastic variable X is defined by $dF_X(\xi) = \rho_X(\xi) d\xi$. The density $\rho_X(\xi)$ contains delta distributions at the discontinuity points of the distribution function $F_X(\xi)$. It is

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \rho_X(\xi) d\xi = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dF_X(\xi) = F_X(+\infty) - F_X(-\infty) = 1$$

Appendix D

Compatibility in weakly modular lattices

The theorems in this appendix concern the compatibility of elements in weakly modular lattices. They are due to C. Piron [3, p. 25 – 28]. All theorems in this appendix refer to bounded, complete, orthocomplemented, and weakly modular lattices \mathcal{L} .

Theorem D.1 *Two elements a and b in \mathcal{L} are compatible, $a \leftrightarrow b$, if and only if one of the following five equivalent conditions applies:*

$$(x \wedge y) \vee (x' \wedge y) = y \quad [= (x \vee x') \wedge y] \quad (\text{D.1})$$

$$(x \vee y) \wedge (x' \vee y) = y \quad [= (x \wedge x') \vee y] \quad (\text{D.2})$$

$$(x \vee y) \wedge y' = x \wedge y' \quad [= (x \wedge y') \vee (y \wedge y')] \quad (\text{D.3})$$

$$(x \wedge y) \vee y' = x \vee y' \quad [= (x \vee y') \wedge (y \vee y')] \quad (\text{D.4})$$

$$(x \wedge y) \vee (x' \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge y') \vee (x' \wedge y') = I \quad (\text{D.5})$$

where either x is equal to a or to a' and y is equal to b or to b' , or x is equal to b or to b' and y is equal to a or to a'

Proof The bracketed expressions in the lines (D.1) – (D.4) indicate the distributive relationships involved. Necessity is obvious in all cases.

As for sufficiency, we show first the equivalence of conditions (D.1) – (D.5).

(a) (D.1) and (D.2) are equivalent and (D.3) and (D.4) are equivalent because they are dual pairs.

(b) (D.1) implies (D.4). In an arbitrary lattice it is $(x \wedge y) \vee y' \leq x \vee y'$ by monotony. Weak modularity (theorem 3.3), De Morgan's identities (theorem 2.3), and (D.1) yield

$$(x \wedge y) \vee y' = (x \vee y') \wedge ((x' \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge y) \vee y') = (x \vee y') \wedge (y \vee y') = x \vee y'$$

(c) (D.3) implies (D.1). It is $x' \wedge y \leq y$. With weak modularity and with (D.3), where the pair $\{y, y'\}$ is substituted by $\{y', y\}$, one obtains

$$y = (x' \wedge y) \vee ((x \vee y') \wedge y) = (x' \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge y)$$

(d) (D.1) obviously implies (D.5).

(e) (D.5) implies (D.1) and (D.2). Because of the monotony of join and meet, it is in an arbitrary lattice

$$w \equiv (x \wedge y) \vee (x' \wedge y) \leq y \leq (x \vee y) \wedge (x' \vee y) \equiv z$$

It follows from $w \leq z$ and from theorems 3.3 and 2.3 that

$$w = (x \vee y) \wedge (x' \vee y) \wedge ((x' \wedge y') \vee (x \wedge y') \vee (x \wedge y) \vee (x' \wedge y)) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x' \vee y) = z$$

by hypothesis. Therefore, $w = y$, which is condition (D.1), and $z = y$, which is condition (D.2).

Hence, conditions (D.1) – (D.5) are all equivalent.

The distributive laws (Di1) and (Di2) are a consequence of the lattice axioms if one of their projections a , b , c is equal to 0 or to I . The conditions (D.1) – (D.4) represent the remaining cases if the projections a , b , c , in (Di1) and (Di2) are chosen from the set $\{x, x', y, y'\}$. This concludes the proof of the theorem.

qed

Theorem D.2 Let a and b_i , $i \in \mathbb{I}$, be elements in \mathcal{L} . If $a \leftrightarrow b_i$ for all $i \in \mathbb{I}$, then

$$a \wedge \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i = \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a \wedge b_i) \quad (\text{D.6})$$

and

$$a \vee \bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i = \bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a \vee b_i) \quad (\text{D.7})$$

Proof In an arbitrary complete lattice, it is $\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a \wedge b_i) \leq a \wedge \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i$ because $c_i \equiv a \wedge b_i \leq a \wedge \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \equiv d$ for all i in \mathbb{I} by (Mo2), and the assertion follows from the repeated application of (Mo3). Hence, applying theorem 3.3 yields

$$a \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a \wedge b_i) \vee \left[\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a' \vee b'_i) \wedge a \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) \right]$$

But $a \leftrightarrow b_i$ implies $(a' \vee b'_i) \wedge a = b'_i \wedge a$, and with the idempotence law one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a' \vee b'_i) \wedge a \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) \right] &= \bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} ((a' \wedge b'_i) \wedge a) \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = \bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (b'_i \wedge a) \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) \\ &= \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b'_i \right) \wedge a \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right)' \wedge a \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

which proves the distributivity relation (D.6).

In order to prove (D.7), note that $a \vee \bigwedge_i b_i \leq a \vee b_i$ by (Mo3), which implies $a \vee \bigwedge_i b_i \leq \bigwedge_i (a \vee b_i)$ by (Mo4). Hence, one obtains with theorem 3.3

$$a \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a \vee b_i) \right) \wedge \left(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a' \wedge b'_i) \vee a \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) \right)$$

and with the idempotence law and the hypothesis of the theorem

$$\begin{aligned} \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a' \wedge b'_i) \vee a \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) &= \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} ((a' \wedge b'_i) \vee a) \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) \\ &= \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} (a \vee b'_i) \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = a \vee \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b'_i \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = a \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right)' \vee \left(\bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i \right) = I \end{aligned}$$

qed

Theorem D.3 Let a and $b_i, i \in \mathbb{I}$, be elements in \mathcal{L} . If $a \leftrightarrow b_i$ for all i in \mathbb{I} , then $a \leftrightarrow \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i$ and $a \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i$.

Proof According to theorem D.2, it is

$$[(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i) \wedge a'] \vee a = \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} [(b_i \wedge a') \vee a] = \bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} [b_i \vee a] = (\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i) \vee a$$

This is condition (D.4) of theorem D.1, which entails that $(\bigvee_{i \in \mathbb{I}} b_i) \leftrightarrow a$. The second assertion is shown similarly.

qed

Theorem D.4 Let a, b, c three elements in \mathcal{L} . It is $a \wedge (b \vee c) = (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c)$ and $a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge (a \vee c)$ whenever one of the three elements is compatible with each of the other two elements.

Proof The case $a \leftrightarrow b, a \leftrightarrow c$ is shown by theorem D.2. In addition, elements b and c are equivalent in the statements to prove. The only case yet to show is, therefore, $c \leftrightarrow a$ and $c \leftrightarrow b$. It is then $a \wedge b \leftrightarrow c$ by theorem D.3 and $a \wedge b \leftrightarrow a$ by weak modularity. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} (a \wedge b) \vee (a \wedge c) &= ((a \wedge b) \vee a) \wedge ((a \wedge b) \vee c) = a \wedge ((a \wedge b) \vee c) \\ &= a \wedge (a \vee c) \wedge (b \vee c) = a \wedge (b \vee c) \end{aligned}$$

by, first, applying equation (D.7) to $a \wedge b \leftrightarrow c$ and $a \wedge b \leftrightarrow a$, then absorption on the first factor, equation (D.7) with the hypotheses $c \leftrightarrow a$ and $c \leftrightarrow b$ on the second factor, and, finally, again absorption. The relationship $a \vee (b \wedge c) = (a \vee b) \wedge (a \vee c)$ follows from duality.

qed

Appendix E

Vector spaces and adjoint vector spaces

In this Appendix, basic definitions and theorems concerning vector spaces and their adjoint spaces are compiled. Particular emphasis is laid on the structure of the set of subspaces of a vector space. We follow the textbook of R. Baer [8, II].

E.1 Left vector spaces

E.1.1 Definitions and first consequences

A *left vector space* is a pair $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ consisting of a (not necessarily commutative) field \mathbb{F} , the scalars, and of a commutative group \mathcal{A} , the vectors. Instead of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, we also write $\mathcal{A}_{\mathbb{F}}$ or simply \mathcal{A} if there are no ambiguities. The scalars η, η_1, η_2 operate on the vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$ according to the rules listed below.

$$\begin{aligned} (a) \quad & \eta \in \mathbb{F}, \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \longrightarrow \eta \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \\ (b) \quad & (\eta_1 + \eta_2) \mathbf{a} = \eta_1 \mathbf{a} + \eta_2 \mathbf{a} \\ (c) \quad & \eta(\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2) = \eta \mathbf{a}_1 + \eta \mathbf{a}_2 \\ (d) \quad & (\eta_2 \eta_1) \mathbf{a} = \eta_2(\eta_1 \mathbf{a}) \end{aligned}$$

The product $\eta \mathbf{a}$ is unique and it is

$$0 \mathbf{a} = \eta \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{0}$$

where 0 is the null element of \mathbb{F} and $\mathbf{0}$ the null element of \mathcal{A} . Similarly

$$(-\eta) \mathbf{a} = \eta(-\mathbf{a}) = -(\eta \mathbf{a})$$

for all η in \mathbb{F} and \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} .

The set theoretical inclusion defines a *partial order* in the set of subsets of a vector space. A set Φ of such subsets is *totally ordered* if, for any pair \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{T} in Φ , it is either $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ or $\mathcal{T} \subseteq \mathcal{S}$.

A *subspace* $\mathcal{U}_{\mathbb{F}}$ of the vectorspace $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is a pair $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{U})$ consisting of the field \mathbb{F} and of the non-empty subset \mathcal{U} of \mathcal{A} with the properties

- (i) $\mathbf{a}_1 - \mathbf{a}_2$ is in \mathcal{U} if \mathbf{a}_1 and \mathbf{a}_2 are in \mathcal{U} .
- (ii) $\eta \mathbf{a}$ is in \mathcal{U} for all η in \mathbb{F} and \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{U} .

We denote by the relationship $\mathcal{U} \leq \mathcal{A}$ that \mathcal{U} is a subspace of \mathcal{A} , and by $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ that \mathcal{S} is a subset of \mathcal{A} . The subspace 0 with the property $0 \leq \mathcal{U}$ for every subspace \mathcal{U} consists of the set $\{\mathbf{0}\}$ and differs from the empty set \emptyset .

The *intersection* $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$ of two subspaces \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} is the set of all elements in \mathcal{A} which belong to \mathcal{M} and to \mathcal{N} *i.e.* it is identical with the intersection of \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} as sets. The intersection of two subspaces is a subspace. The intersection $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$ is the greatest vector space that is contained in \mathcal{M} and in \mathcal{N} . The generalisation of these statements to a set of subspaces is obvious.

The *sum* $\sum_{i \in \mathbb{I}} \mathcal{V}_i$ of the set of subspaces $\{\mathcal{V}_i : i \in \mathbb{I}\}$, \mathbb{I} being some index set, is the set of all *finite* sums of vectors out of this set of subspaces [8, p. 9], in particular, it is $\mathbf{x} + \mathcal{M} \equiv \{\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{m} : \mathbf{m} \in \mathcal{M}\}$. The sum of an infinite set of subspaces is, therefore, defined. The sum $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}$ is the smallest subspace that contains \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} . The sum of finitely many subspaces is a subspace. The sum of a set of subspaces is different from their union as sets. In lattice theoretical terms, intersections correspond to meets, sums correspond to joins of projections.

With the above definitions, the *modular law* is valid:

Theorem E.1 (Modular law) [8, p. 9] *If $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N}$, and \mathcal{U} are subspaces of some vector space, then $(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{M} + (\mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N})$.*

Proof It follows from $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{M} + \mathcal{U}$, $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N}$, $\mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{M} + \mathcal{U}$, and $\mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{N}$ that $\mathcal{M} + (\mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N}) \leq (\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{N}$. Conversely, consider any vector \mathbf{n} in $(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{N}$. Then \mathbf{n} belongs to \mathcal{N} and it is $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{u}$ with \mathbf{m} in \mathcal{M} and \mathbf{u} in \mathcal{U} . Now $\mathbf{n} - \mathbf{m}$ is in \mathcal{N} because $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N}$. Hence, $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{n} - \mathbf{m}$ is in $\mathcal{N} \cap \mathcal{U}$. Therefore, $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{u}$ belongs to $\mathcal{M} + (\mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N})$ and, consequently, $(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{U}) \cap \mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{M} + (\mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N})$.

qed

Lemma E.1 [8, p. 11] *The union of a totally ordered set of subspaces is a subspace.*

Proof If Φ is a totally ordered set of subspaces of a vector space and if \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{T} are different subspaces in Φ , then one and only one of the relations $\mathcal{S} < \mathcal{T}$ and $\mathcal{T} < \mathcal{S}$ is valid. Denote by \mathcal{U} the union of all subspaces in Φ *i.e.* a vector belongs to \mathcal{U} if and only if it belongs to at least one subspace in Φ . If \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are vectors in \mathcal{U} , then there exist subspaces \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} in \mathcal{U} such that \mathbf{x} is in \mathcal{X} and \mathbf{y} is in \mathcal{Y} . One of these subspaces contains the other by hypothesis, $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ say. Then \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} and $\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}$ are in \mathcal{Y} and, consequently, in \mathcal{U} . With \mathbf{x} in \mathcal{X} is also $\eta\mathbf{x}$ in \mathcal{X} for any number η , and $\eta\mathbf{x}$ is in \mathcal{U} , too. Hence, \mathcal{U} is a subspace.

qed

E.1.2 Zorn's lemma, the existence of a complement

In order to formulate Zorn's lemma, we need two definitions. Let \mathcal{S} be a partially ordered set and \mathcal{T} some subset of \mathcal{S} . An element u in \mathcal{S} is an *upper bound* of \mathcal{T} if $t \leq u$ for all elements t in \mathcal{T} . An element m in \mathcal{T} is a *maximal element* of \mathcal{T} if $m \leq t$ for t in \mathcal{T} implies $m = t$.

Lemma E.2 (Zorn's lemma) [8, p. 310] *A non-empty partially ordered set \mathcal{S} possesses at least one maximal element if every totally ordered subset \mathcal{T} of \mathcal{S} possesses an upper bound in \mathcal{S} .*

Zorn's lemma is equivalent to Hausdorff's maximum principle as well as to Zermelo's axiom of choice and to the well-ordering theorem in the Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory (see sections 68 – 70 of Ref. [25]).

Theorem E.2 (Complementation theorem) [8, p. 12] *If \mathcal{M} is a subspace of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, then there exists a subspace \mathcal{N} of \mathcal{A} such that $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = 0$.*

Proof The set Θ of all subspaces \mathcal{W} of \mathcal{A} with the property $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{W} = 0$ contains the subspace 0 and is, therefore, not empty. If Φ is a totally ordered subset of Θ , then we form the union \mathcal{U} of all subspaces in Φ . It follows from the construction of Θ that $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{U} = 0$ and from lemma E.1 that \mathcal{U} is a subspace of \mathcal{A} , too. Therefore, \mathcal{U} belongs to Θ and is an upper bound of Φ , and the set Θ fulfils the hypotheses of Zorn's lemma E.2. Hence, there exists a subspace \mathcal{N} of \mathcal{A} , a maximal element of Θ , with the properties

$$\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{N} < \mathcal{S}, \quad \mathcal{S} \text{ some subspace of } \mathcal{A}, \text{ implies } \mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{S} > 0.$$

Consider now the subspace $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}$ of \mathcal{A} and any vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} which does not belong to \mathcal{N} . Then it is $\mathcal{N} < \mathcal{N} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{a}$ and it follows that $\mathcal{M} \cap (\mathcal{N} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{a}) > 0$. Hence, there exists a vector $\mathbf{m} \neq \mathbf{0}$ in this intersection such that \mathbf{m} is in \mathcal{M} and $\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{n} + \eta\mathbf{a}$ with \mathbf{n} in \mathcal{N} and $\eta \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} . Therefore, $\mathbf{a} = \eta^{-1}(\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{n})$ belongs to $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}$, which proves that $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{A}$ i.e. \mathcal{N} is the desired subspace.

qed

If \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} are subspaces of a vector space \mathcal{A} with $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = 0$, then \mathcal{N} is termed a *complement of \mathcal{M} in \mathcal{A}* . If \mathcal{N} is a complement of \mathcal{M} in \mathcal{A} and $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{B} \leq \mathcal{A}$, then it is obviously $\mathcal{M} \cap (\mathcal{N} \cap \mathcal{B}) = 0$ and $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{B} = (\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) \cap \mathcal{B} = \mathcal{M} + (\mathcal{N} \cap \mathcal{B})$ by the modular law E.1. Therefore,

Corollary E.1 [8, p. 12] *If the subspace \mathcal{M} is contained in the subspace \mathcal{B} of the vector space \mathcal{A} and if \mathcal{N} is a complement of \mathcal{M} in \mathcal{A} , then $\mathcal{N} \cap \mathcal{B}$ is a complement of \mathcal{M} in \mathcal{B} .*

The *direct sum* $\mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{N}$ is the sum of the two subspaces \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} of \mathcal{A} provided that their intersection is void, $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = 0$. Direct sums correspond to the join of disjoint projections. Direct sums are associative $(\mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{N}) \oplus \mathcal{U} = \mathcal{M} \oplus (\mathcal{N} \oplus \mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{N} \oplus \mathcal{U}$ with $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{M} = 0$ because $\mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{N}$ implies $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = 0$ by definition, and $\mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{M} = \mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N} = 0$ is a consequence of $\mathcal{U} \cap (\mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{N}) = 0$ and of $\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{N}$. As for the converse: the basis of the sum of two subspaces \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} is the union of their bases, the basis of the intersection $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$ is the intersection of their bases because of lemma E.4, and the set $\{0\}$ is the basis of 0 . Hence, $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{M} = 0$ implies $\mathcal{U} \cap (\mathcal{M} \oplus \mathcal{N}) = 0$.

E.1.3 Linear independence, existence of a basis

The set $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_k\}$ of vectors of a vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is termed *linearly independent* if the equation $\sum_{i=1}^k \eta_i \mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{0}$ with η_i in \mathbb{F} implies $\eta_i = 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$. This definition entails in particular that the vectors \mathbf{a}_i of this set are all different. A *subset \mathcal{B} of \mathcal{A} is linearly independent* if all its finite subsets are linearly independent. Conversely, the subset \mathcal{B} of \mathcal{A} is *linearly dependent* if there exists a set of finitely many vectors $\{\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k\}$ and numbers $\{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_k\}$ in \mathbb{F} , not all equal to 0, such that $\sum_{i=1}^k \eta_i \mathbf{b}_i = \mathbf{0}$.

Lemma E.3 [8, p. 13] *The subset \mathcal{S} of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is linearly independent if and only if none of the vectors in \mathcal{S} is linearly dependent on the remaining vectors in \mathcal{S} .*

Proof If \mathcal{S} is linearly dependent, then there exists a set of different vectors $\{\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k\}$ and numbers $\{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_k\}$ in \mathbb{F} , not all $\eta_i = 0$, such that $\sum_{i=1}^k \eta_i \mathbf{b}_i = \mathbf{0}$. Assume e.g. that $\eta_1 \neq 0$. Then $\mathbf{b}_1 = \sum_{i=2}^k -\eta_1^{-1} \eta_i \mathbf{b}_i$ and the vector \mathbf{b}_1 depends on the set of vectors $\{\mathbf{b}_2, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k\}$ all different from \mathbf{b}_1 . The converse of this statement is an immediate consequence of definitions.

qed

A subset \mathcal{B} of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is a *basis of \mathcal{A}* if \mathcal{B} is an independent set and every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} depends on \mathcal{B} i.e. for any vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} , there is a finite set of vectors $\{\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k\}$ in \mathcal{B} and numbers $\{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_k\}$ in \mathbb{F} such that $\mathbf{a} = \sum_{i=1}^k \eta_i \mathbf{b}_i$.

Lemma E.4 [8, p. 13] *If \mathcal{B} is a basis of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, then every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} is represented in one and only one way in the form*

$$\mathbf{a} = \sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{B}} \eta(\mathbf{b})\mathbf{b}$$

with $\eta(\mathbf{b})$ in \mathbb{F} and where only a finite number of the $\eta(\mathbf{b})$ are different from 0.

Proof The proof is an immediate consequence of our definitions: the set $\{\sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{B}} \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}\}$ consists of all vectors of the form $\sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{B}} \eta(\mathbf{b})\mathbf{b}$ where only a finite number of $\eta(\mathbf{b})$ are different from 0, and this set is equal to \mathcal{A} . $\sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{B}} \eta(\mathbf{b})\mathbf{b} = \sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{B}} \eta'(\mathbf{b})\mathbf{b}$ implies $\sum_{\mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{B}} (\eta(\mathbf{b}) - \eta'(\mathbf{b}))\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\eta(\mathbf{b}) = \eta'(\mathbf{b})$ because every finite set of vectors in \mathcal{B} is independent.

qed

Theorem E.3 (Existence theorem) [8, p. 14] *Every vector space possesses a basis.*

Proof If the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ consists only of the set $\{\mathbf{0}\}$, then the vector $\mathbf{0}$ is its basis. Otherwise, every vector $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$ forms an independent set. Hence, the set Θ of all independent subsets of \mathcal{A} is not empty. Consider a subset Φ of Θ , which is totally ordered by inclusion and the union \mathcal{U} of all sets in Φ . We show now that \mathcal{U} is an upper bound of Φ in Θ i.e. that \mathcal{U} is linearly independent. Assume that there exists a set of vectors $\{\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k\}$ in \mathcal{U} and numbers $\{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_k\}$ in \mathbb{F} such that $\sum_{i=1}^k \eta_i \mathbf{b}_i = \mathbf{0}$. Every vector \mathbf{b}_i belongs to some set \mathcal{B}_i in Φ , which is totally ordered by inclusion. Therefore, there exists an index m such that $\mathcal{B}_i \subseteq \mathcal{B}_m$ for every index i . But then the vectors $\{\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_k\}$ belong to the independent set \mathcal{B}_m , and this implies that $\eta_i = 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$.

Hence, \mathcal{U} is linearly independent and the hypotheses of Zorn's lemma are fulfilled for Θ . Consequently, there is a maximal element \mathcal{B} in Θ i.e. \mathcal{B} is not a proper subset of an independent set. Assume now, that the vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} does not belong to \mathcal{B} . Then the set $\{\mathcal{B}, \mathbf{a}\}$ is dependent, which means that the vector \mathbf{a} depends on \mathcal{B} because \mathcal{B} is a maximal independent set. Therefore, \mathcal{B} is a basis of \mathcal{A} .

qed

Theorem E.4 *Any two bases of a vector space possess the same number of elements.*

Proof The linear dependency of a vector on a *finite* set of vectors is an instance of algebraical dependency as discussed in section 4.2. If the vector space under consideration possesses a finite basis, then the theorem is a consequence of Steinitz's exchange lemma, lemma 4.4, and of the remarks thereafter. The proof for general vector spaces is based on Zorn's lemma and is not elementary. We refer to Ref. [8, p. 14 – 16].

qed

The number of elements of a basis of the vector space \mathcal{A} is its *dimension* $\nu(\mathcal{A})$. The condition that only finite sums of vectors are permitted allows to consider infinite dimensional vector spaces, too. However, some proofs of the subsequent lemmata and theorems become involved in this case and necessitate the methods of transfinite set theory [8, p. 20 – 24]. In addition, it is not necessary to take into account vector spaces of infinite dimension in order to derive the results of chapters 6 and 7. Therefore, we assume in the remaining part of this appendix *that all vector spaces possess finite dimension*.

Two vector spaces $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{B})$ are *isomorphic*, $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A}) \simeq (\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{B})$, if there is a one-to-one map σ of the vectors of \mathcal{A} onto the vectors of \mathcal{B} such that

$$(\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2)^\sigma = (\mathbf{a}_1)^\sigma + (\mathbf{a}_2)^\sigma \quad \text{and} \quad (\eta \mathbf{a})^\sigma = \eta \mathbf{a}^\sigma$$

for all vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$ in \mathcal{A} and all scalars η in \mathbb{F} . Isomorphisms map bases onto bases and subspaces onto subspaces. Hence, the systems of subspaces of two isomorphic vector spaces are projectively equivalent. A vector space is isomorphic to itself, an inverse isomorphism σ^{-1} exists for every isomorphism σ , and isomorphisms are transitive. Isomorphism is, therefore, an equivalence relation.

Theorem E.5 [8, p. 16] *Two finite dimensional vector spaces $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{B})$ are isomorphic if and only if their dimensions are equal.*

Proof Isomorphic vector spaces have the same dimension because isomorphisms map bases onto bases. Assume, conversely, that the \mathbb{F} -spaces \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} have the same dimension n . Then \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} possess bases $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n\}$ and $\{\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2, \dots, \mathbf{b}_n\}$, and there exists the trivial one-to-one map $\sigma: \mathbf{a}_k \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^\sigma = \mathbf{b}_k$ for $k = 1, \dots, n$ between the elements of the bases. Every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} possesses a unique representation in terms of basis vectors

$$\mathbf{a} = \sum_{k=1}^n \eta_k \mathbf{a}_k$$

with η_k in \mathbb{F} , lemma E.4. The map σ between the basis vectors is then extended to an isomorphism σ of \mathcal{A} onto \mathcal{B} by linearity

$$\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{a}^\sigma = \sum_{k=1}^n \eta_k \mathbf{a}_k^\sigma \equiv \sum_{k=1}^n \eta_k \mathbf{b}_k$$

qed

The quintessence of theorems E.3, E.4, and E.5 is that there exists essentially, *i.e.* up to isomorphisms, only one vector space of finite dimension n for a given field \mathbb{F} . The prototype of this vector space is \mathbb{F}^n , the vector space of n -tuples (η_1, \dots, η_n) of elements of the field \mathbb{F} . Let $\mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n$ be a basis of some vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ of dimension n . The isomorphism between $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and \mathbb{F}^n is given by the map

$$\mathbf{a} = \sum_{k=1}^n \eta_k \mathbf{a}_k \in \mathcal{A} \quad \longleftrightarrow \quad (\eta_1, \dots, \eta_n) \in \mathbb{F}^n$$

The basis vector \mathbf{a}_k corresponds to the n -tuple $(0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0)$ where the number 1 is at position k . The vector space \mathbb{F}^1 is the set $\{\eta(1) : \eta \in \mathbb{F}\} \equiv \{(\eta) : \eta \in \mathbb{F}\}$, and it is isomorphic to the field \mathbb{F} .

E.1.4 Quotient spaces and dimension formulae

Let \mathcal{M} be a subspace of the vector space \mathcal{A} . Two vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} of \mathcal{A} are called *congruent modulo \mathcal{M}* , denoted by $\mathbf{a} \equiv \mathbf{b} \pmod{\mathcal{M}}$, if the difference $\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{b}$ belongs to \mathcal{M} , or, equivalently, if there is a vector \mathbf{m} in \mathcal{M} such that $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{m}$. Congruence modulo \mathcal{M} is reflexive, symmetric, and transitive and, therefore, an equivalence relation causing the splitting of \mathcal{A} into disjoint equivalence classes, the *cosets of \mathcal{A} with respect to \mathcal{M}* . If \mathbf{c} is a vector of the coset \mathcal{C} , then $\mathcal{C} = \mathbf{c} + \mathcal{M}$. Because \mathcal{A} is a commutative group, the cosets of \mathcal{A} with respect to \mathcal{M} form a commutative group, too, the *quotient group \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M}* ; the sum $\mathcal{C}_1 + \mathcal{C}_2$ of two cosets consists of the sums $\mathbf{c}_1 + \mathbf{c}_2$, the vectors \mathbf{c}_i being in \mathcal{C}_i . The subspace \mathcal{M} is a coset of \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} namely its 0-element, $\mathcal{C} + \mathcal{M} = \mathcal{C}$. The quotient group \mathcal{M}/\mathcal{M} consists only of the coset \mathcal{M} *i.e.* it is isomorphic to the commutative group $\{0\}$. If \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{M} are subspaces of \mathcal{A} such that $0 \leq \mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$, then a coset \mathcal{C} of \mathcal{M}/\mathcal{N} is characterised by the following condition: \mathbf{c}_1 and \mathbf{c}_2 are vectors in \mathcal{C} if and only if \mathbf{c}_1 and \mathbf{c}_2 are in \mathcal{M} and the difference $\mathbf{c}_1 - \mathbf{c}_2$ is in \mathcal{N} . Consequently, it is $\mathcal{M}/0 \simeq \mathcal{M}$.

The cosets of \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} can be multiplied from the left by elements of the field \mathbb{F} . If the vector \mathbf{c} is an element of the coset \mathcal{C} , then $\eta\mathbf{c}$ is an element of the coset $\eta\mathcal{C}$ for any element η in \mathbb{F} . Hence, the quotient group is also a left vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M})$ over the field \mathbb{F} , the *quotient space of \mathcal{A} with respect to the subspace \mathcal{M}* .

Theorem E.6 (Isomorphism law) [8, p. 11] *If \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} are subspaces of a vector space, then $(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N})/\mathcal{M}$ is isomorphic to $\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})$.*

Proof Every vector \mathbf{x} in $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}$ is a sum, $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{n}$, where \mathbf{m} is in \mathcal{M} and \mathbf{n} is in \mathcal{N} . Hence, each coset \mathcal{X} of the quotient group $(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N})/\mathcal{M}$ contains vectors of \mathcal{N} . The intersection $\mathcal{X} \cap \mathcal{N} \equiv \mathcal{Y}$ is, therefore, not empty. Let \mathbf{y}_1 and \mathbf{y}_2 be vectors of \mathcal{Y} . Then these vectors are in \mathcal{N} , and the difference vector $\mathbf{y}_1 - \mathbf{y}_2$ is in \mathcal{N} and in \mathcal{M} because it is also a difference of vectors in \mathcal{X} . Therefore, \mathcal{Y} is a coset of $\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})$.

Now, \mathbf{y}_1 and \mathbf{y}_2 are in \mathcal{N} and $\mathbf{y}_1 - \mathbf{y}_2$ is in \mathcal{M} (and in \mathcal{N}). If \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 are vectors in $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{Y}$, then $\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{m}_i + \mathbf{y}_i$ with \mathbf{m}_i in \mathcal{M} and \mathbf{y}_i in \mathcal{Y} (and in \mathcal{N}), and the difference vector $\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2 = \mathbf{m}_1 - \mathbf{m}_2 + \mathbf{y}_1 - \mathbf{y}_2$ is in \mathcal{M} . Therefore, $\mathcal{X} \equiv \mathcal{M} + \mathcal{Y}$ is a coset of $(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N})/\mathcal{M}$. The maps $\mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X} \cap \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{Y}$ and $\mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathcal{M} + \mathcal{Y} = \mathcal{X}$ are reciprocal maps between the cosets of the quotient groups $(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N})/\mathcal{M}$ and $\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})$ and, consequently, one-to-one. The single-valued map $\mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathcal{X} = \mathcal{M} + \mathcal{Y}$ between cosets is a group isomorphism because the addition of subsets is associative and commutative.

qed

As an application, consider a subspace \mathcal{M} of the vector space \mathcal{A} and its complement \mathcal{N} in \mathcal{A} . Then it is

$$\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N})/\mathcal{M} \simeq \mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) = \mathcal{N}/0 \simeq \mathcal{N}$$

Hence, the complement \mathcal{N} of \mathcal{M} in \mathcal{A} is uniquely determined by \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{M} .

Theorem E.7 (General dimension formula) [8, p. 17] *If \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} are finite dimensional subspaces of a vector space, then*

$$\nu(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) = \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) + \nu(\mathcal{M}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) + \nu(\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}))$$

Proof According to the complementation theorem E.2 and to the above remark, there are uniquely determined subspaces \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{V} such that

$$\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \oplus \mathcal{U} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{N} = (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \oplus \mathcal{V}$$

It follows from the isomorphism law E.6 that

$$\mathcal{M}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) = (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) + \mathcal{U}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \simeq \mathcal{U}/(\mathcal{U} \cap (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) = \mathcal{U}/0 \simeq \mathcal{U}$$

and, therefore, $\nu(\mathcal{U}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}))$ and likewise $\nu(\mathcal{V}) = \nu(\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}))$. It is, furthermore, $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N} = (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \oplus \mathcal{U} \oplus \mathcal{V}$ because direct sums are associative and $(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \oplus (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) = (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})$.

Consequently, a basis of $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}$ is composed of the bases of the vector spaces $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$, \mathcal{U} , and \mathcal{V} with $(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \cap \mathcal{U} = (\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \cap \mathcal{V} = \mathcal{U} \cap \mathcal{V} = 0$. Therefore, it is

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) &= \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) + \nu(\mathcal{U}) + \nu(\mathcal{V}) \\ &= \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) + \nu(\mathcal{M}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) + \nu(\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) \end{aligned}$$

qed

If, in addition, $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N}$, then we have

Theorem E.8 [8, p. 18] *If $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N}$ are finite dimensional subspaces of a vector space, then it is*

$$(i) \nu(\mathcal{N}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{N}/\mathcal{M})$$

(ii) If $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N}$ and $\nu(\mathcal{M}) = \nu(\mathcal{N})$, then $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{N}$.

Proof If $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{N}$, then theorem E.7 gives

$$\nu(\mathcal{N}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{M}/\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{N}/\mathcal{M})$$

and it is $\nu(\mathcal{M}/\mathcal{M}) = 0$. This proves (i). Statement (i) and $\nu(\mathcal{M}) = \nu(\mathcal{N})$ entail $\nu(\mathcal{N}/\mathcal{M}) = 0$ and, therefore, $\mathcal{N}/\mathcal{M} = 0$ or $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{M}$, which proves (ii).

qed

Corollary E.2 If \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} are finite dimensional subspaces of a vector space, then

$$\nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{N}) = \nu(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) + \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})$$

Proof Applying statement (i) of theorem E.8 onto the subspace $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$ of \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} yields

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(\mathcal{M}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) &= \nu(\mathcal{M}) - \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \\ \nu(\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) &= \nu(\mathcal{N}) - \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we obtain with the general dimension formula E.7

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{N}) &= \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) + \nu(\mathcal{M}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) + \nu(\mathcal{N}/(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N})) \\ &= \nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(\mathcal{N}) - \nu(\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}) \end{aligned}$$

qed

The results of corollary E.2 and of theorem E.8, (ii) correspond to theorem 4.3 and to a result in the proof of theorem 4.4.

E.2 The adjoint space

The content of Ref. [8, II.3] is compiled here. A *linear form over the vectorspace* $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is a single valued map $f: \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}f \in \mathbb{F}$ with the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2)f &= \mathbf{a}_1f + \mathbf{a}_2f \quad \text{for } \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2 \in \mathcal{A} \\ (\eta\mathbf{a})f &= \eta(\mathbf{a}f) \quad \text{for } \eta \in \mathbb{F}, \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \end{aligned}$$

i.e. f is a linear map on vectors in \mathcal{A} , which is written as a multiplication from the right. This notation provides advantages compared to a functional notation, $f(\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2) = f(\mathbf{a}_1) + f(\mathbf{a}_2)$ and $f(\eta\mathbf{a}) = \eta f(\mathbf{a})$.

The *adjoint space* $L(\mathcal{A})$ of \mathcal{A} is the set of all linear forms over \mathcal{A} . The rule

$$\mathbf{a}(f_1 + f_2) = \mathbf{a}f_1 + \mathbf{a}f_2 \quad \text{for } \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}, f_1, f_2 \in L(\mathcal{A})$$

defines an commutative addition in $L(\mathcal{A})$ where the null element in $L(\mathcal{A})$ is characterised by the condition that $\mathbf{a}0_{L(\mathcal{A})} = 0_{\mathbb{F}}$ for all vectors \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} . The rule

$$\mathbf{a}(f\eta) = (\mathbf{a}f)\eta = \mathbf{a}f\eta \quad \text{for } \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}, f \in L(\mathcal{A}), \eta \in \mathbb{F}$$

defines a multiplication from the right of a linear form with elements of \mathbb{F} with the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned} (a') \quad & f \in L(\mathcal{A}), \eta \in \mathbb{F} \longrightarrow f\eta \\ (b') \quad & f(\eta_1 + \eta_2) = f\eta_1 + f\eta_2 \\ (c') \quad & (f_1 + f_2)\eta = f_1\eta + f_2\eta \\ (d') \quad & f(\eta_1\eta_2) = (f\eta_1)\eta_2 \end{aligned}$$

where f, f_1, f_2 are elements of $L(\mathcal{A})$ and η, η_1, η_2 are in \mathbb{F} . The product $f\eta$ is unique; $f0 = 0$ and $f1 = f$. The multiplication of a linear form with a number must be a multiplication from the right. If the multiplication in $L(\mathcal{A})$ were from the left, then it were mandatory to set

$$\mathbf{a}(\eta f) = (\eta \mathbf{a})f = \eta(\mathbf{a}f)$$

because multiplication in \mathcal{A} is from the left. But then

$$\mathbf{a}((\eta_1\eta_2)f) = \mathbf{a}(\eta_1(\eta_2 f)) = (\eta_1 \mathbf{a})(\eta_2 f) = \eta_2\eta_1(\mathbf{a}f) \neq \eta_1\eta_2(\mathbf{a}f)$$

if the multiplication in \mathbb{F} is not commutative. The rule (d') ensures that the series of equations

$$\mathbf{a}(f(\eta_1\eta_2)) = \mathbf{a}((f\eta_1))\eta_2 = (\mathbf{a}(f\eta_1))\eta_2 = (\mathbf{a}f)\eta_1\eta_2$$

is consistent.

The rules $(a') - (d')$ make $L(\mathcal{A})$ a right vector space over the field \mathbb{F} which may be denoted by $(L(\mathcal{A}), \mathbb{F})$. A dimension can be assigned to $L(\mathcal{A})$ as to every vector space.

Theorem E.9 [8, p. 26] *If the dimension $\nu(\mathcal{A})$ is finite, then $\nu(L(\mathcal{A})) = \nu(\mathcal{A})$.*

Proof Let $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n\}$ be a basis of the vector space \mathcal{A} of dimension $\nu(\mathcal{A}) = n$. Consider $\mathbf{a} = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \mathbf{a}_k$, define $\phi_k = \mathbf{a}_k f$ for f in $L(\mathcal{A})$ and the linear forms f_1, \dots, f_n by the condition $\mathbf{a}_k f_j = \delta_{kj}$. This definition is consistent because we may assign an arbitrary number η_k to each basis vector \mathbf{a}_k and define the linear form f by the prescription that $\mathbf{a}_k f = \eta_k$ and, hence, $\mathbf{a}f = (\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \mathbf{a}_k)f = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \mathbf{a}_k f \equiv \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \eta_k$. The spaces \mathcal{A} and $L(\mathcal{A})$ are linear and, therefore, $\mathbf{a}f_j = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \mathbf{a}_k f_j = \alpha_j$ and

$$\mathbf{a}f = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \mathbf{a}_k f = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \phi_k = \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{a}f_k \phi_k = \mathbf{a} \sum_{k=1}^n f_k \phi_k$$

for every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} , which implies that $f = \sum_{k=1}^n f_k \phi_k$. Hence, any linear form f in $L(\mathcal{A})$ can be represented as a right linear combination $\sum_{k=1}^n f_k \phi_k$ of the linear forms f_1, \dots, f_n , and it is $f = 0$ if and only if $\phi_k = 0$ for all values of k i.e. the set $\{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ is a basis of the right vector space $L(\mathcal{A})$.

qed

The vector spaces \mathcal{A} and $L(\mathcal{A})$ are, in general, not isomorphic although they possess equal dimension. Because an 'isomorphism' $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^\sigma \in L(\mathcal{A})$ must fulfil the equation $(\eta \mathbf{a})^\sigma = \mathbf{a}^\sigma \eta$ for all \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} and η in \mathbb{F} which entails

$$\mathbf{a}^\sigma \eta_1 \eta_2 \equiv (\mathbf{a}^\sigma \eta_1) \eta_2 = (\eta_1 \mathbf{a})^\sigma \eta_2 = (\eta_2 \eta_1 \mathbf{a})^\sigma = \mathbf{a}^\sigma \eta_2 \eta_1$$

i.e. either \mathcal{A} is the null space or \mathbb{F} is commutative. However, it is $\mathcal{A} \simeq L(L(\mathcal{A}))$ if the dimension of \mathcal{A} is finite. $L(L(\mathcal{A}))$, the adjoint of the adjoint of \mathcal{A} , is a left vector space like \mathcal{A} . A linear form \mathbf{a}^* over $L(\mathcal{A})$ is defined by the condition $\mathbf{a}^* f = \mathbf{a}f$ for all f in $L(\mathcal{A})$. It is not difficult to verify that \mathbf{a}^* is really a linear form over $L(\mathcal{A})$ and that the map $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^* \in L(L(\mathcal{A}))$ is an isomorphism if the dimension of \mathcal{A} is finite. If the dimension of \mathcal{A} is infinite, then the map $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^*$ induces an isomorphism of \mathcal{A} onto a proper subspace \mathcal{A}^* of $L(L(\mathcal{A}))$ [8, p. 28].

E.2.1 The Galois correspondence between \mathcal{A} and $L(\mathcal{A})$

In the following passage, the product $\mathcal{M}N$ is the set of all elements $\mathbf{a}f$ in \mathbb{F} with \mathbf{a} in the subset $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and f in the subset $N \subseteq L(\mathcal{A})$. We define now two related set functions $E(\mathcal{M})$ and $\mathcal{S}(N)$:

Let $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. Then $E(\mathcal{M})$ is the set of all linear forms f in $L(\mathcal{A})$ such that $\mathcal{M}f = \{0\}$.

Let $N \subseteq L(\mathcal{A})$. Then $\mathcal{S}(N)$ is the set of all vectors \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} such that $\mathbf{a}N = \{0\}$.

It is not difficult to verify the following statements:

$E(\mathcal{M})$ is a subspace of $L(\mathcal{A})$.

$\mathcal{S}(N)$ is a subspace of \mathcal{A} .

If \mathcal{M}_1 is a subset of \mathcal{M}_2 , then $E(\mathcal{M}_2)$ is a subspace of $E(\mathcal{M}_1)$.

If N_1 is a subset of N_2 , then $\mathcal{S}(N_2)$ is a subspace of $\mathcal{S}(N_1)$.

$\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{S}(E(\mathcal{M}))$

$N \subseteq E(\mathcal{S}(N))$

$E(\mathcal{M}) = ESE(\mathcal{M})$

$\mathcal{S}(N) = SES(N)$

$\mathcal{M}E(\mathcal{M}) = \{0\}$

$\mathcal{S}(N)N = \{0\}$

These relationships reveal that the subspaces of the form $\mathcal{S}(N)$ and $E(\mathcal{M})$ represent special classes of subspaces of \mathcal{A} and of $L(\mathcal{A})$, respectively. The following statements characterise these classes.

Lemma E.5 [8, p. 29] *If \mathcal{M} is a subspace of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$, then $E(\mathcal{M})$ is isomorphic to $L(\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M})$ and $L(\mathcal{M})$ is isomorphic to $L(\mathcal{A})/E(\mathcal{M})$.*

Proof Every linear form f in $E(\mathcal{M})$ fulfils the equation $\mathcal{M}f = 0$ by hypothesis. If \mathcal{X} is a coset of \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} , then $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{M} + \mathbf{x}$ for every vector \mathbf{x} in \mathcal{X} . Therefore, $\mathcal{X}f = (\mathcal{M} + \mathbf{x})f = \mathbf{x}f$ is a uniquely determined element of \mathbb{F} , and the map $l_f: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}f = \mathbf{x}f$ is a linear form over the vector space \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} . If f and g are two linear forms in $E(\mathcal{M})$, which generate the same linear form over \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} , $l_f = l_g$, then

$$\mathbf{x}f = \mathcal{X}l_f = \mathcal{X}l_g = \mathbf{x}g$$

for every vector \mathbf{x} in \mathcal{A} because every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} is in exactly one coset $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{a})$ of \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} . Hence $f = g$, and the map $f \rightarrow l_f$ generates an isomorphism of $E(\mathcal{M})$ into $L(\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M})$.

If, finally, l is a linear form over \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} , then a linear form f over $E(\mathcal{M})$ may be defined by the rule

$$\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{a})l = (\mathcal{M} + \mathbf{a})f = \mathbf{a}f$$

where $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{a})$ denotes the uniquely determined coset of \mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M} which contains the vector \mathbf{a} , and it is obvious from this definition that f is in $E(\mathcal{M})$ and that $l = l_f$. Therefore, we have shown that $E(\mathcal{M}) \simeq L(\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M})$.

If f denotes a linear form over \mathcal{A} and $f_{\mathcal{M}}$ its restriction on the subspace \mathcal{M} of \mathcal{A} , then, by definition, it is $\mathbf{m}f_{\mathcal{M}} = \mathbf{m}f$ for all vectors \mathbf{m} in \mathcal{M} and $\mathbf{a}f_{\mathcal{M}} = 0$ for any vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} but not in \mathcal{M} i.e. $f_{\mathcal{M}}$ is in $L(\mathcal{M})$. Clearly,

$$(f_1 + f_2)_{\mathcal{M}} = f_{1\mathcal{M}} + f_{2\mathcal{M}} \quad \text{and} \quad (f\eta)_{\mathcal{M}} = (f_{\mathcal{M}})\eta$$

for f, f_1, f_2 in $L(\mathcal{A})$ and η in \mathbb{F} . It is $f_{\mathcal{M}} = 0$ exactly if f is in $E(\mathcal{M})$. Hence $E(\mathcal{M})$ is the kernel of the homomorphism

$$f \in L(\mathcal{A}) \rightarrow f_{\mathcal{M}} \in L(\mathcal{M})$$

and this map induces an isomorphism between $L(\mathcal{A})/E(\mathcal{M})$ and $L(\mathcal{M})$ as a consequence of the homomorphism theorem for groups [25, p. 32].

qed

Lemma E.6 [8, p. 29] *If \mathcal{M} is a subspace of the finite dimensional vector space \mathcal{A} , then*

$$(i) \nu(L(\mathcal{A})) = \nu(L(\mathcal{M})) + \nu(L(\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M}))$$

$$(ii) \nu(E(\mathcal{M})) = \nu(\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{M})$$

Proof Statement (i) is a consequence of theorem E.9 and theorem E.8 (i), and statement (ii) follows from theorem E.9 and lemma E.5.

qed

It is not difficult to see that $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{S}(E(\mathcal{M}))$ for a subset \mathcal{M} of a vector space \mathcal{A} . There is, however, a stronger statement:

Lemma E.7 [8, p. 30] *If \mathcal{M} is a subspace of a vector space \mathcal{A} , then $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{S}(E(\mathcal{M}))$.*

Proof It is $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{S}(E(\mathcal{M}))$. Let now \mathcal{M} be a subspace of \mathcal{A} and \mathbf{b} any vector of \mathcal{A} which does not belong to \mathcal{M} . Construct the vector space $\mathcal{M} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}$; it is $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b} = 0$ by hypothesis. According to the complementation theorem E.2, there is a subspace \mathcal{N} of \mathcal{A} such that $\mathcal{A} = (\mathcal{M} \oplus \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}) \oplus \mathcal{N}$. Hence, there is, for every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} , a unique decomposition

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}' + \eta(\mathbf{a})\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{a}''$$

with \mathbf{a}' in \mathcal{M} , $\eta(\mathbf{a})$ in \mathbb{F} , and \mathbf{a}'' in \mathcal{N} . The rule

$$\mathbf{a}g = \eta(\mathbf{a})$$

defines a linear form g over \mathcal{A} with the property that $\mathcal{M}g = \{0\}$ and $\mathbf{b}g = 1$ i.e. the linear form g belongs to $E(\mathcal{M})$ and the vector \mathbf{b} does not belong to $\mathcal{S}(E(\mathcal{M}))$. Hence, there is no vector outside of \mathcal{M} , which belongs to $\mathcal{S}(E(\mathcal{M}))$.

qed

If \mathcal{A} is a finite dimensional vector space, then the adjoint space $L(\mathcal{A})$ is a right vector space of equal dimension, theorem E.9, and it is $\mathcal{N} = E(\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}))$ for any subspace \mathcal{N} of $L(\mathcal{A})$ by a statement similar to lemma E.7. These findings may be summarised in the

Theorem E.10 [8, p. 32] *If \mathcal{A} is a finite dimensional vector space, then the Galois correspondences E and \mathcal{S} are reciprocal dualities between the partially ordered sets of the subspaces of \mathcal{A} and of $L(\mathcal{A})$, respectively.*

There are, in addition, the dimension formulae

Theorem E.11 [8, p. 33] *If \mathcal{A} is a vector space of finite dimension n , \mathcal{M} a subspace of \mathcal{A} , and \mathcal{N} a subspace of $L(\mathcal{A})$, then*

$$(i) n = \nu(\mathcal{A}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}) + \nu(E(\mathcal{M}))$$

$$(ii) n = \nu(L(\mathcal{A})) = \nu(\mathcal{N}) + \nu(\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{N}))$$

Proof These statements are an immediate consequence of theorem E.8 (i), of lemma E.6 (ii), and of the complete symmetry between \mathcal{A} , $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$, E and $L(\mathcal{A})$, $\mathcal{N} \leq L(\mathcal{A})$, \mathcal{S} .

qed

Appendix F

Projectivities and semilinear maps

The content of this appendix is based on the section III.1 of Ref. [8]. *Finite dimension of all vector spaces* is assumed in this appendix.

F.1 Projectivities upon vector spaces

A *projectivity of the vector space* $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto the vector space $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ is a map π of the system of subspaces of \mathcal{A} onto the system of subspaces of \mathcal{B} with the properties (P1) and (P2) [8, p. 40]:

(P1) If \mathcal{M} is a subspace of \mathcal{A} , then \mathcal{M}^π is a uniquely determined subspace of \mathcal{B} , and there is exactly one subspace $\mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{A}$ for a subspace $\mathcal{N} \leq \mathcal{B}$ such that $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{M}^\pi$.

(P2) If \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 are subspaces of \mathcal{A} , then $\mathcal{M}_1 \leq \mathcal{M}_2$ if and only if $\mathcal{M}_1^\pi \leq \mathcal{M}_2^\pi$.

Properties (P1) and (P2) imply

(P3) $\mathcal{M}_1 = \mathcal{M}_2$ if and only if $\mathcal{M}_1^\pi = \mathcal{M}_2^\pi$; $\mathcal{M}_1 < \mathcal{M}_2$ if and only if $\mathcal{M}_1^\pi < \mathcal{M}_2^\pi$.

(P4) Projectivities preserve intersections and sums.

(P5) $\{0_{\mathcal{A}}\}^\pi = \{0_{\mathcal{B}}\}$ and $\mathcal{A}^\pi = \mathcal{B}$.

(P6) Projectivities preserve the covering property and, therefore, map points onto points.

(P7) Projectivities preserve distributivity, (D1) and (D2), and modularity (3.1).

A set $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_n\}$ of vectors in \mathcal{A} is termed *an independent set* in section E.1.3 if $\sum_{k=1}^n \eta_k \mathbf{s}_k = \mathbf{0}$ implies $\eta_k = 0$ for all indices k . If \mathcal{S} is an independent set of vectors, then the set $\{p_k \equiv \mathbb{F}\mathbf{s}_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ of one-dimensional subspaces of \mathcal{A} or *points* is termed *a set of independent points*. This definition corresponds to the one given in section 4.2 where the set $\{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$ of atoms is independent if $p_j \not\leq \bigvee_{i \neq j} p_i$ for every index j , $1 \leq j \leq n$. It is $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{s}_j \not\leq \sum_{i \neq j} \mathbb{F}\mathbf{s}_i$ if and only if $\mathbf{s}_j \neq \sum_{i \neq j} \eta_i \mathbf{s}_i$ for any set $\{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_n\}$ of numbers in \mathbb{F} . Hence, we have

Lemma F.1 *A set of points $\{\mathbb{F}\mathbf{s}_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ is a dependent (an independent) set if and only if the set of the vectors $\{\mathbf{s}_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ is linearly dependent (independent).*

Likewise, a set of points $\{\mathbb{F}\mathbf{s}_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ is a *basis of the subspace* $\sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{F}\mathbf{s}_k$ of \mathcal{A} if the set $\{\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_n\}$ is linearly independent.

(P8) Projectivities map a set of dependent (independent) points onto a set of dependent (independent) points.

(P9) Projectivities map a basis onto a basis.

(P10) Projectivities preserve dimension: if there exists a projectivity π of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$, then it is $\nu(\mathcal{M}) = \nu(\mathcal{M}^\pi)$ for every subspace \mathcal{M} of \mathcal{A} . It is, in particular, $\nu(\mathcal{A}) = \nu(\mathcal{B})$.

The equivalence of properties (P1) – (P10) with the corresponding properties listed in section 6.1 is obvious.

F.2 Semilinear maps

In order to discuss the relationship between two vector spaces $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ being connected by a projectivity, a generalisation of the notion of a 'linear map between vector spaces' is needed. A *semilinear map* σ of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ consists of a pair (σ', σ'') of maps where σ' is a field isomorphism of \mathbb{F} onto \mathbb{G} and σ'' is an isomorphism of the additive group \mathcal{A} onto the additive group \mathcal{B} such that

$$(\mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2)^{\sigma''} = \mathbf{a}_1^{\sigma''} + \mathbf{a}_2^{\sigma''} \quad (\text{F.1})$$

$$(\eta \mathbf{a})^{\sigma''} = \eta^{\sigma'} \mathbf{a}^{\sigma''} \quad (\text{F.2})$$

for every number η in \mathbb{F} and all vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2$ in \mathcal{A} .

If there is no risk of confusion, then we use the symbol σ for both maps σ' and σ'' . Equation (F.2) then simply becomes $(\eta \mathbf{a})^\sigma = \eta^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma$. A map of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ is linear if $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{G}$ and $\sigma' = 1$. The following example shows that the concept of semilinearity is more general than the concept of linearity. Let $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{G} = \mathbb{C}$, the field of complex numbers, and let σ' be the map $\sigma' : \gamma \in \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \gamma^{\sigma'} = \bar{\gamma}$, the complex conjugate of γ , and, finally, $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{B} = \mathbb{C}^n$ and $\sigma'' : (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n) \rightarrow (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n)^{\sigma''} = (\bar{\gamma}_1, \dots, \bar{\gamma}_n)$. The map $\sigma = (\sigma', \sigma'')$ is semilinear but not linear.

Lemma F.2 [8, p. 42] *Semilinear maps induce projectivities.*

Proof Let $\sigma = (\sigma', \sigma'')$ denote a semilinear map of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto the vector space $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ and \mathcal{M} a subspace of \mathcal{A} . The set $\mathcal{M}^{\sigma''} = \{\mathbf{m}^{\sigma''} : \mathbf{m} \in \mathcal{M}\}$ is a subspace of \mathcal{B} because there is exactly one number η in \mathbb{F} to a number θ in \mathbb{G} such that $\theta = \eta^{\sigma'}$, and the vector $\theta \mathbf{m}^{\sigma''} = \eta^{\sigma'} \mathbf{m}^{\sigma''} = (\eta \mathbf{m})^{\sigma''}$ is in $\mathcal{M}^{\sigma''}$ if and only if \mathbf{m} is in \mathcal{M} . Hence, the map $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}^{\sigma''} \leq \mathcal{B}$ is a projectivity of \mathcal{A} onto \mathcal{B} .

qed

Lemma F.3 [8, p. 43] *If the dimension of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is greater or equal than two, then*

(i) *If the single-valued map σ of \mathcal{A} into itself satisfies the conditions $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^\sigma = \mathbf{a}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}^\sigma$ for \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} and $\mathcal{M}^\sigma \leq \mathcal{M}$ for every subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$, then it is either $\mathcal{A}^\sigma = \{\mathbf{0}\}$, i.e. $\sigma = 0$, or σ is a semilinear map.*

(ii) *The map σ of \mathcal{A} into itself is a semilinear map which satisfies the condition $\mathcal{M}^\sigma \leq \mathcal{M}$ for every subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$ if and only if there exists a number $\kappa \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} such that $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \kappa \mathbf{a}$.*

Proof Define the map σ by the condition $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \kappa \mathbf{a}$ for all vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} where $\kappa \neq 0$ is a fixed number in \mathbb{F} . The map σ satisfies $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^\sigma = \mathbf{a}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}^\sigma$ for \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} and $\mathcal{M}^\sigma = \mathcal{M}$ for every subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$. Now it is

$$(\eta \mathbf{a})^\sigma = \kappa \eta \mathbf{a} = \kappa \eta \kappa^{-1} \kappa \mathbf{a} \equiv \eta^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma$$

for \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} and η in \mathbb{F} , and $\eta^\sigma = \kappa\eta\kappa^{-1}$ is an inner automorphism of \mathbb{F} . Hence, σ is a semilinear map which induces the identity projectivity. This proves the necessity of statement (ii) if $\kappa \neq 0$.

Assume now that the single-valued map σ satisfies the conditions $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^\sigma = \mathbf{a}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}^\sigma$ for \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} and $\mathcal{M}^\sigma \leq \mathcal{M}$ for every subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$. Clearly, it is $\mathbf{0}^\sigma = \mathbf{0}$. The second condition implies that $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a})^\sigma \leq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{a}$ for every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} . Consequently, \mathbf{a}^σ is in $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a}$, and if $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$, then there is exactly one number $\kappa(\mathbf{a})$ in \mathbb{F} such that $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \kappa(\mathbf{a})\mathbf{a}$. If \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are two linearly independent vectors in \mathcal{A} , then $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}$ are all different from $\mathbf{0}$, and it is

$$\kappa(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})\mathbf{a} + \kappa(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})\mathbf{b} = \kappa(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}) = (\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^\sigma = \mathbf{a}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}^\sigma = \kappa(\mathbf{a})\mathbf{a} + \kappa(\mathbf{b})\mathbf{b}$$

and, therefore, $\kappa(\mathbf{a}) = \kappa(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}) = \kappa(\mathbf{b})$ because \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are independent.

Assume, finally, that $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{b} \neq \mathbf{0}$ are linearly dependent vectors in \mathcal{A} . Since the dimension of \mathcal{A} is greater or equal than two, there exists a vector \mathbf{c} in \mathcal{A} which is independent of \mathbf{a} and of \mathbf{b} . This implies that $\kappa(\mathbf{a}) = \kappa(\mathbf{c}) = \kappa(\mathbf{b})$ and we have shown that $\kappa(\mathbf{a}) = \kappa(\mathbf{b}) = \kappa$ for any two vectors $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{b} \neq \mathbf{0}$ in \mathcal{A} . Therefore,

$$\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \kappa\mathbf{a}$$

for every \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} with a fixed number κ in \mathbb{F} . If $\kappa = 0$, then $\sigma = 0$, and if $\kappa \neq 0$, then σ is a semilinear map as already shown. This completes the proof of the lemma.

qed

The second statement of this lemma characterises semilinear maps inducing the identity projectivity.

Corollary F.1 [8, p. 44] *If the vectors $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{b} \neq \mathbf{0}$ of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ generate the same point, $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}$, then there exists a semilinear map σ such that $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{a}^\sigma$ and $\mathcal{M}^\sigma = \mathcal{M}$ for every subspace \mathcal{M} of \mathcal{A} .*

Proof $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}$ signifies that the sets $\{\eta\mathbf{a} : \eta \in \mathbb{F}\}$ and $\{\theta\mathbf{b} : \theta \in \mathbb{F}\}$ are identical. Hence, there exists a number κ in \mathbb{F} such that $\mathbf{b} = \kappa\mathbf{a}$. The hypotheses $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{b} \neq \mathbf{0}$ entail that $\kappa \neq 0$, and σ is the semilinear map defined by $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{a}^\sigma = \kappa\mathbf{a}$ with the property $\mathcal{M}^\sigma = \mathcal{M}$ for every subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$ according to lemma F.3, item (ii).

qed

Corollary F.2 [8, p. 44] *If the dimension of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is greater or equal than two, then the semilinear maps σ and τ of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ induce the same projectivity if and only if there is a number θ in \mathbb{G} such that $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \theta\mathbf{a}^\tau$ for every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} .*

Proof The maps σ and τ induce the same projectivity if and only if $\sigma\tau^{-1}$ induces the identity projectivity on \mathcal{A} . According to lemma F.3, this is equivalent to the existence of a number $\kappa \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} such that $\mathbf{a}^{\sigma\tau^{-1}} = \kappa\mathbf{a}$ for every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} . But this is, in turn, equivalent to $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = (\kappa\mathbf{a})^\tau = \kappa^\tau\mathbf{a}^\tau \equiv \theta\mathbf{a}^\tau$ with $\theta = \kappa^\tau$.

qed

Lemma F.3 and corollary F.2 cease to be true if $\nu(\mathcal{A}) = 1$ because $\{\mathbf{0}\}$ is then the only proper subspace of \mathcal{A} and there are no pairs $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{b} \neq \mathbf{0}$ of linearly independent vectors in \mathcal{A} . The relationship $\kappa(\mathbf{a}) = \kappa(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}) = \kappa(\mathbf{b})$ cannot be derived in this case.

F.3 A fundamental theorem of projective geometry

Semilinear maps induce projectivities according to lemma F.2. The converse is also true provided that the dimension of the vectorspace is not less than three.

Theorem F.1 [8, p. 44] *If the dimension of the vector space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is not less than three, then every projectivity π of \mathcal{A} onto a vectorspace $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ is induced by a semilinear map.*

Proof The proof is accomplished in several steps. It is assumed that vector spaces $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ and $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ and a projectivity π of \mathcal{A} onto \mathcal{B} are given. Projectivities preserve dimension, property (P10), $\nu(\mathcal{M}^\pi) = \nu(\mathcal{M})$ for every subspace \mathcal{M} of \mathcal{A} . In particular, there exists, for a vector $\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ in \mathcal{A} , a vector $\mathbf{x}' \neq \mathbf{0}_B$ in \mathcal{B} such that $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}'$ with $\nu(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}) = \nu(\mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}') = 1$ i.e. $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}'$ are corresponding points. Now, we prove first

(1) *If $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ are two different points in \mathcal{A} and if \mathbf{x}' is a vector in \mathcal{B} such that $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}'$, then there exists exactly one vector $\mathbf{y}' = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y})$ in \mathcal{B} such that $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}'$ and $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}')$.*

Proof of (1) The relationship $\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \leq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ implies $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi \leq (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi + (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi$. Because $\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$ and, hence, $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi$ are points, there is a vector \mathbf{z}' in \mathcal{B} such that $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}'$, and \mathbf{z}' is necessarily in $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi + (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi$. It follows from $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}'$ that there exists a number θ in \mathbb{G} and a vector \mathbf{t}' in $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi$ such that

$$\mathbf{z}' = \theta\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{t}'$$

If θ is equal to 0, then \mathbf{z}' is in $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi$ i.e. $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi \leq (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi$ and, consequently, $\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) \leq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$. But this implies that \mathbf{x} is in $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ and $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ which is excluded by hypothesis. The case $\mathbf{t}' = \mathbf{0}_B$ can be excluded with similar arguments: \mathbf{z}' is then in $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi$ and $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi \leq (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi$ and so on. Hence, we may form $\mathbf{y}' = \theta^{-1}\mathbf{t}'$. The vector \mathbf{y}' in \mathcal{B} is different from $\mathbf{0}_B$ and is in $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi$ and, therefore, $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}'$. In addition, it is $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}' = \mathbb{G}(\theta^{-1}\mathbf{z}') = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}')$ and the vector \mathbf{y}' meets all requirements.

Consider now a second vector \mathbf{y}'' in \mathcal{B} such that $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}''$ and $(\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}'')$ which implies $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}' = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}''$ and $\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}') = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}'')$. Hence, there are numbers θ and κ in \mathbb{G} , both different from 0, such that $\mathbf{y}' = \theta\mathbf{y}''$ and $\mathbf{x}' - \theta\mathbf{y}'' = \kappa(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}'')$. But $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}'$ and $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}'' = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}'$ are different points, and \mathbf{x}' and \mathbf{y}'' are linearly independent by lemma F.1. Therefore, $(1 - \kappa)\mathbf{x}' - (\theta - \kappa)\mathbf{y}'' = \mathbf{0}_B$ implies $1 = \kappa = \theta$ and $\mathbf{y}'' = \mathbf{y}'$ as we claimed.

qed

The function \mathbf{h} can be normalised so that $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{0}_A) = \mathbf{0}_B$ for every pair \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}' with $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}'$ because $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{0}_A)^\pi = \{\mathbf{0}_A\}^\pi = \{\mathbf{0}_B\} = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{0}_B$, and it is $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{0}_B$ if and only if $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{0}_A$ because $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y})$ is uniquely determined and different from $\mathbf{0}_B$ if $\mathbf{y} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$.

(2) *It is $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{y}'$ if and only if $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}'$.*

Proof of (2) This statement is an immediate consequence of the uniqueness of the function \mathbf{h} because the defining conditions of $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{y}'$ and of $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}'$ are identical namely

$$(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}', \quad (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}'), \quad (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}'$$

qed

The presupposition that the dimension of the vector space \mathcal{A} is at least equal to three is essential in the subsequent steps (3), (4), and (5).

(3) If $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ are three linearly independent vectors in \mathcal{A} , then $\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}))$.

Proof of (3) It is

$$\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) \leq (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z})) \equiv \mathcal{J}$$

because $\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) \leq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}$ and $\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) \leq \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z})$ and because of monotony (Mo4). Conversely, if \mathbf{j} is a vector of \mathcal{J} , then $\mathbf{j} = v\mathbf{y} + \zeta\mathbf{z} = \gamma(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z})$ with v, ζ, γ, δ in \mathbb{F} . The vectors $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ are independent. Hence, $\gamma + \delta = 0, v = -\gamma, \zeta = -\delta$, which implies $\mathbf{j} = v(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z})$. Therefore, $\mathcal{J} \leq \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z})$.

qed

(4) If $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ are three linearly independent vectors in \mathcal{A} , then the equations $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{y}'$ and $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{z}'$ imply $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{z}'$.

Proof of (4) According to the hypotheses, one has

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi &= \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}', & (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi &= \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}', & (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{z})^\pi &= \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}' \\ (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi &= \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}'), & (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi &= \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{z}') \end{aligned}$$

The independence of $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ entails the independence of $\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{z}'$ because of property (P8) and of lemma F.1. Hence, statement (3) may be applied to the set $\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{z}'$ as well as to the set $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$, which yields

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi &= ((\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z})))^\pi \\ &= ((\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi + (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{z})^\pi) \cap ((\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi + (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi) \\ &= (\mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}' + \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}') \cap (\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}') + \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{z}')) \\ &= \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{y}' - \mathbf{z}') \end{aligned}$$

But the validity of the three equations

$$(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}', \quad (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{y}' - \mathbf{z}'), \quad (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{z})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}'$$

is equivalent to the statement $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{z}'$.

qed

(5) If $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ are three linearly independent vectors in \mathcal{A} , then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) &= (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}) \\ \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}) &= (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof of (5) We proceed as in the proof of statement (3). It is

$$\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) \leq (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}) \equiv \mathcal{J}$$

If \mathbf{j} is a vector in \mathcal{J} , then $\mathbf{j} = \alpha(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \beta\mathbf{z} = \gamma(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}) + \delta\mathbf{y}$ yielding $\alpha = \gamma, -\alpha = \delta, \beta = -\gamma$ because of the independence of $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$. Therefore, $\beta = -\alpha$ and $\mathbf{j} = \alpha(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z})$ which implies that $\mathcal{J} \leq \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z})$. The second assertion is shown similarly.

qed

(6) If $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}$ is a point, if $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}'$, and if $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} \cap (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) = 0$, then $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{z})$.

Proof of (6) We distinguish two cases:

Case (i) The vectors $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ are linearly independent. With $\mathbf{y}' = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y})$ and $\mathbf{z}' = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{z})$ and according to step (1), it is

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi &= \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}', & (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi &= \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}', & (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{z})^\pi &= \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}' \\ (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi &= \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}'), & (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi &= \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{z}') \end{aligned}$$

The set $\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{z}'$ is linearly independent because the set $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ is linearly independent. Hence, with (5)

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi &= ((\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}))^\pi \\ &= ((\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}))^\pi + (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{z})^\pi) \cap ((\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi + (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi) \\ &= (\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}') + \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}') \cap (\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{z}') + \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}') \\ &= \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}' - \mathbf{z}') \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}))^\pi &= ((\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}) \cap (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}) + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}))^\pi \\ &= ((\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi + (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{z})^\pi) \cap ((\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{z}))^\pi + (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi) \\ &= (\mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}' + \mathbb{G}\mathbf{z}') \cap (\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{y}' - \mathbf{z}') + \mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}') \\ &= \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{y}' + \mathbf{z}') \end{aligned}$$

It follows from the considerations in step (1) and from the results just derived that $(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})' = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})$ fulfils

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})' &= (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{y}' + \mathbf{z}') \\ \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - (\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})') &= (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{x} - (\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}' - (\mathbf{y}' + \mathbf{z}')) \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $(\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})' = \mathbf{y}' + \mathbf{z}'$. Hence,

$$\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}) = (\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z})' = \mathbf{y}' + \mathbf{z}' = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{z})$$

which proves case (i).

Case (ii) The vectors $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ are not independent. It is $\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ by hypothesis. If $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{0}_A$ or $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{0}_A$, then there is nothing to prove because $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{0}_A) = \mathbf{0}_B$. Assume, therefore, that $\mathbf{y} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ and $\mathbf{z} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$. It follows from our hypotheses that $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ and $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}$, and that $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}$ are two different points. Because the dimension of \mathcal{A} is greater or equal than three, there exists a point $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}$ such that the points $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{z}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}$ are independent. Then the following statements are true:

- Either it is $\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z} = \mathbf{0}_A$ or $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{w}$ are independent.
- $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}$ are independent.
- $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{y}$ are independent.

Applying the result of case (i) several times and heeding the convention $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{0}_B$ if $\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z} = \mathbf{0}_A$, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{w}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}) &= \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}) \\ &= \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{y}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{z}) \\ &= \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{w}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{z}) \end{aligned}$$

yielding the desired result $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{z})$. This completes the proof of (6).

qed

With these preparations, we are now able to construct the semilinear map of the theorem. We begin the construction by choosing three linearly independent vectors $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}$ in \mathcal{A} . This is possible because the dimension of \mathcal{A} is greater or equal than three. $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u}$ is a point and there exists a vector $\mathbf{u}' \neq \mathbf{0}_B$ in \mathcal{B} such that $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{u}'$. According to step (1), there exist uniquely determined vectors \mathbf{v}' and \mathbf{w}' in \mathcal{B} such that $\mathbf{v}' = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{v})$ and $\mathbf{w}' = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{w})$. Statements (2) and (4) then yield

(7) *If $\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}\}$ is a set of linearly independent vectors in \mathcal{A} , then there exists a unique set $\{\mathbf{u}', \mathbf{v}', \mathbf{w}'\}$ of linearly independent vectors in \mathcal{B} such that $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{y}'$ for any two distinct elements \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} chosen from the set $\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}\}$.*

If $\mathbf{t} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ is a vector in \mathcal{A} , then $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{t}$ is different from at least two of the points $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{v}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}$.

(8) *If $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ are two different points of the set $\{\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{v}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}\}$ and if $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{t} \neq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{t} \neq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$, then $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{y}', \mathbf{t})$.*

Proof of (8) It is $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{0}_A) = \mathbf{0}_B$ for $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}$. Assume now $\mathbf{t} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$. Without loss in generality, one may choose $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{u}$ and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{v}$. If the point $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{t}$ is not on the line $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{v}$, then $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{t}$ are three linearly independent vectors. It is then $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{v}'$ because of (7), and it follows with $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{t}'$ that $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}', \mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{t}'$ according to (4), which proves statement (8) for this case. If $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{t} \leq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{u} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{v}$, then our hypotheses entail that $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{t}$ is neither in $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}$ nor in $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{v} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}$, i.e. $\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{w}$ and $\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}$ are linearly independent sets, and it follows again with statement (7) that $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}', \mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w}', \mathbf{t})$.

qed

Hence, we have shown that at least two of the three values $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{t}), \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}', \mathbf{t}), \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{w}', \mathbf{t})$ are defined for every vector $\mathbf{t} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ in \mathcal{A} , and that all defined values are equal. We denote this common value by \mathbf{t}^σ .

(9) *If \mathbf{x} denotes one of the three different vectors $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}$ and if $\mathbf{t} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ is a vector in \mathcal{A} , then $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{t})$ is defined and equal to the uniquely determined value \mathbf{t}^σ in at least two of the three possible cases.*

As a consequence of the remarks after statement (1), one may define $\mathbf{0}_A^\sigma = \mathbf{0}_B$. Therefore, we have found a single-valued map $\sigma: \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^\sigma \in \mathcal{B}$. This map has the following properties:

(10) *For every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} , there exists a uniquely defined vector \mathbf{a}^σ in \mathcal{B} such that $(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{a}^\sigma$.*

This is an obvious consequence of the definition of the function \mathbf{h} in (1).

(11) *It is $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^\sigma = \mathbf{a}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}^\sigma$ for \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{A} .*

Proof of (11) At least one of the points $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{v}, \mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}$ is not on the line $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}$ because the vectors $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}$ introduced in statement (7) are linearly independent. Assume that $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u} \not\leq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{a} + \mathbb{F}\mathbf{b}$. Then it follows from the definition of the map σ and from statement (6) that

$$(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^\sigma = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{a}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}', \mathbf{b}) = \mathbf{a}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}^\sigma$$

qed

(12) The map σ is an isomorphism of the additive group \mathcal{A} onto the additive group \mathcal{B} .

Proof of (12) If $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{B}$, then $\{\mathbf{0}_\mathcal{B}\} = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{a}^\sigma = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a})^\pi$ by (10). This entails $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{A}$. Hence, σ is an isomorphism of \mathcal{A} into \mathcal{B} because $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \mathbf{b}^\sigma$ implies $(\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{b})^\sigma = \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{B}$ and, in turn, $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b}$.

Let now $\mathbf{b} \neq \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{B}$ be a vector in \mathcal{B} . Then $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{b}$ is a point of the vector space $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$, and it follows from properties (P1) and (P6) that there is exactly one point a of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ such that $a^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{b}$. This point a is different from at least one of the independent points $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u}$, $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{v}$, $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{w}$. Without loss in generality, we may assume that $a \neq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{u}$. Then $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{b} \neq \mathbb{G}\mathbf{u}^\sigma$.

Consider now the point $\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbf{b})$ on the line

$$\mathbb{G}\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbb{G}\mathbf{b} = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u})^\pi + a^\pi = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{u} + a)^\pi$$

Again, there exists exactly one point $p \leq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{u} + a$ such that $p^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbf{b})$. It is $a \neq p$ because $a^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{b} \neq \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}) = p^\pi$. There is a vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} such that $a = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{a}$ and $p = \mathbb{F}(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{a})$ because these two equations determine the vectors \mathbf{a} and $(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{a})$ only up to numbers different from 0. Statements (10) and (11) then imply

$$\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbf{b}) = p^\pi = (\mathbb{F}(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{a}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{a})^\sigma = \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbf{a}^\sigma)$$

In addition, it is $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{b} = a^\pi = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{a}^\sigma$. Hence, there are numbers κ and η different from 0, such that $\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbf{b} = \kappa(\mathbf{u}^\sigma + \mathbf{a}^\sigma)$ and $\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \eta\mathbf{b}$ implying $(1 - \kappa)\mathbf{u}^\sigma + (1 - \kappa\eta)\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0}$. Now, $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{u}^\sigma \neq \mathbb{G}\mathbf{b}$ by hypothesis, which implies that \mathbf{u}^σ and \mathbf{b} are linearly independent. Therefore, $\kappa = \kappa\eta = 1$ and there exists, for any vector \mathbf{b} in \mathcal{B} , a vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} such that $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{a}^\sigma$, and it is shown that $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{A}^\sigma$.

qed

(13) It is $\mathcal{M}^\pi = \mathcal{M}^\sigma$ for every subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$.

This is an immediate consequence of (10) and (12).

If $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{A}$ is a vector in \mathcal{A} and $\eta \neq 0$ a number in \mathbb{F} , then $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{a}^\sigma = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a})^\pi = (\mathbb{F}(\eta\mathbf{a}))^\pi = \mathbb{G}(\eta\mathbf{a})^\sigma$. The map $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}^\sigma$ is single-valued. Therefore, there exists exactly one number $\theta(\eta, \mathbf{a}) \neq 0$ in \mathbb{G} such that $(\eta\mathbf{a})^\sigma = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{a})\mathbf{a}^\sigma$. With $\theta(0, \mathbf{a}) = 0$, the defining formula $(\eta\mathbf{a})^\sigma = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{a})\mathbf{a}^\sigma$ holds for every number η in \mathbb{F} and for every vector \mathbf{a} in \mathcal{A} .

(14) If $\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathbf{y} \neq \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{A}$ are vectors in \mathcal{A} , then $\theta(\eta, \mathbf{x}) = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{y})$ for every number η in \mathbb{F} .

Proof of (14) Assume, first, that $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ are distinct points. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \theta(\eta, \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y})\mathbf{x}^\sigma + \theta(\eta, \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y})\mathbf{y}^\sigma &= \theta(\eta, \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y})(\mathbf{x}^\sigma + \mathbf{y}^\sigma) = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y})(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y})^\sigma \\ &= (\eta(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}))^\sigma = (\eta\mathbf{x} + \eta\mathbf{y})^\sigma = (\eta\mathbf{x})^\sigma + (\eta\mathbf{y})^\sigma \\ &= \theta(\eta, \mathbf{x})\mathbf{x}^\sigma + \theta(\eta, \mathbf{y})\mathbf{y}^\sigma \end{aligned}$$

With $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$, it is $\mathbb{G}\mathbf{x}^\sigma = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x})^\pi \neq (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{y})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{y}^\sigma$ i.e. the vectors \mathbf{x}^σ and \mathbf{y}^σ are linearly independent which implies that

$$\theta(\eta, \mathbf{x}) = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}) = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{y})$$

If $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$, then there exists a point $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{z} \neq \mathbb{F}\mathbf{x} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{y}$ and it is $\theta(\eta, \mathbf{x}) = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{z}) = \theta(\eta, \mathbf{y})$ for arbitrary vectors $\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathbf{y} \neq \mathbf{0}_\mathcal{A}$ in \mathcal{A} .

qed

The number $\theta(\eta, \mathbf{a})$, defined for all numbers η in \mathbb{F} and equal for all vectors $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ in \mathcal{A} , is now denoted by η^σ . Hence, σ is a single-valued map of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ into $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ such that

$$(15) \quad (\eta \mathbf{a})^\sigma = \eta^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma \text{ for } \eta \text{ in } \mathbb{F} \text{ and } \mathbf{a} \text{ in } \mathcal{A}.$$

We show, finally, that

(16) σ is an isomorphism of the field \mathbb{F} onto the field \mathbb{G} .

Proof of (16) If η and θ are numbers in \mathbb{F} and if $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ is a vector in \mathcal{A} , then statement (15) implies that

$$(\eta + \theta)^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma = ((\eta + \theta)\mathbf{a})^\sigma = (\eta\mathbf{a} + \theta\mathbf{a})^\sigma = (\eta\mathbf{a})^\sigma + (\theta\mathbf{a})^\sigma = \eta^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma + \theta^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma = (\eta^\sigma + \theta^\sigma) \mathbf{a}^\sigma$$

and it is $(\eta + \theta)^\sigma = \eta^\sigma + \theta^\sigma$ because $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ if and only if $\mathbf{a}^\sigma \neq \mathbf{0}_B$. Analogously,

$$(\eta\theta)^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma = ((\eta\theta)\mathbf{a})^\sigma = (\eta(\theta\mathbf{a}))^\sigma = \eta^\sigma (\theta\mathbf{a})^\sigma = \eta^\sigma \theta^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma$$

implying $(\eta\theta)^\sigma = \eta^\sigma \theta^\sigma$.

If now $\theta \neq 0$ is a number in \mathbb{G} and $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{0}_A$ a vector in \mathcal{A} , then there exists a vector \mathbf{s} in \mathcal{A} such that $\mathbf{s}^\sigma = \theta\mathbf{a}^\sigma$ because of (12). Then statement (13) implies that

$$(\mathbb{F}\mathbf{s})^\pi = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{s}^\sigma = \mathbb{G}(\theta\mathbf{a}^\sigma) = \mathbb{G}\mathbf{a}^\sigma = (\mathbb{F}\mathbf{a})^\pi$$

and, consequently, that $\mathbb{F}\mathbf{s} = \mathbb{F}\mathbf{a}$. Hence, there is a number $\eta \neq 0$ in \mathbb{F} such that $\mathbf{s} = \eta\mathbf{a}$, and it follows from (15) that

$$\theta\mathbf{a}^\sigma = \mathbf{s}^\sigma = (\eta\mathbf{a})^\sigma = \eta^\sigma \mathbf{a}^\sigma$$

and that $\theta = \eta^\sigma$ because $\mathbf{a}^\sigma \neq \mathbf{0}_B$. Together with the correspondence $\theta = 0 \leftrightarrow \eta = 0$ one obtains $\mathbb{G} = \mathbb{F}^\sigma$.

qed

To summarise: it follows from statements (12), (13), (15), (16) that σ is a semilinear map of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ onto $(\mathbb{G}, \mathcal{B})$ which induces the given projectivity π . This completes the proof of the theorem.

qed

Appendix G

The theorem of Amemiya and Araki

Theorem G.1 ([29]) *If the lattice $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$ of all subspaces of a pre-Hilbert space $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ is weakly modular, then \mathcal{A} is complete i.e. \mathcal{A} is a Hilbert space.*

Proof The orthocomplementation in \mathcal{A} corresponds to an autoduality δ on $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$ and δ is represented by the Hermitian scalar product ϕ of $(\mathbb{F}, \mathcal{A})$ according to equation (7.7). The proof is performed in five steps:

(1) *It is $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M}^\delta = \mathcal{A}$ for any subspace $\mathcal{M} \leq \mathcal{A}$.*

It is $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M}^\delta \subseteq \mathcal{A}$. In order to show that $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M}^\delta$, it suffices to prove that every atom p in $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A})$ precedes $\mathcal{M} \vee \mathcal{M}^\delta$ i.e. that every vector \mathbf{p} of the one-dimensional subspace equivalent to p is in $\mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M}^\delta$. It is nothing to prove for atoms preceding \mathcal{M} or \mathcal{M}^δ . Consider, therefore, an atom p with $p \not\leq \mathcal{M}$ and $p \not\leq \mathcal{M}^\delta$. It follows from the covering property (Cov) and from theorem 3.5 that

$$q = (\mathcal{M} \vee p) \wedge \mathcal{M}^\delta \quad \text{and} \quad r = (\mathcal{M}^\delta \vee p) \wedge \mathcal{M}$$

are atoms. By weak modularity, \mathcal{M}^δ is compatible with q and with $\mathcal{M}^\delta \vee p$; and compatibility in relation to \mathcal{M} and to \mathcal{M}^δ is equivalent. Hence with theorem D.4,

$$\begin{aligned} q \vee r &= q \vee \{(\mathcal{M}^\delta \vee p) \wedge \mathcal{M}\} = \{q \vee \mathcal{M}^\delta \vee p\} \wedge \{q \vee \mathcal{M}\} \\ &= \{[(\mathcal{M} \vee p) \wedge \mathcal{M}^\delta] \vee \mathcal{M}^\delta \vee p\} \wedge \{[(\mathcal{M} \vee p) \wedge \mathcal{M}^\delta] \vee \mathcal{M}\} \\ &= \{\mathcal{M}^\delta \vee p\} \wedge \{\mathcal{M} \vee p\} \geq (\mathcal{M}^\delta \wedge \mathcal{M}) \vee p = 0 \vee p = p \end{aligned}$$

by absorption (Ab1), by weak modularity, and by inequality (2.22). Therefore, step (1) states that any vector \mathbf{p} of the one-dimensional subspace equivalent to the atom $p \leq q \vee r$ is a linear combination of a vector \mathbf{q} in \mathcal{M}^δ and of a vector \mathbf{r} in \mathcal{M} .

(2) *Let \mathcal{H} denote the completion of \mathcal{A} with respect to the norm induced by the strictly positive Hermitian scalar product ϕ and \mathcal{H}_1 a subspace of \mathcal{H} , $\mathcal{H}_1 = (\mathcal{H}_1^\delta)^\delta$, where \mathcal{H}_1^δ is of finite dimension and the duality δ represents the orthocomplementation in \mathcal{H} (cf. equation (7.10)). Then $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{H}_1$ is dense in \mathcal{H}_1 i.e. every vector in \mathcal{H}_1 is the limit vector of a convergent series of vectors in $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{H}_1$.*

Let $\mathbf{g}_1, \dots, \mathbf{g}_n$ be an orthonormal basis with respect to ϕ of \mathcal{H}_1^δ . Because \mathcal{A} is dense in \mathcal{H} and, hence, also in $\mathcal{H}_1^\delta \leq \mathcal{H}$, there are vectors $\mathbf{g}_1^m, \dots, \mathbf{g}_n^m$ in \mathcal{A} such that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{g}_i^m = \mathbf{g}_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Let, in addition, \mathbf{h} be any vector in \mathcal{H}_1 and $\{\mathbf{h}^m\}$ be vectors in \mathcal{A} such that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{h}^m = \mathbf{h}$. Let, finally, the numbers η_i^m be the solutions of the equations

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i^m \phi(\mathbf{g}_i^m, \mathbf{g}_j) = \phi(\mathbf{h}^m, \mathbf{g}_j)$$

for $j = 1, \dots, n$. For all numbers i and j in $\{1, \dots, n\}$ and for any value $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a number $M(\epsilon)$ such that $|\phi(\mathbf{h}^m, \mathbf{g}_j)| < \epsilon$ and $|\phi(\mathbf{g}_i^m, \mathbf{g}_j) - \delta_{ij}| < \epsilon$ for all values of $m > M(\epsilon)$. Hence, $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \eta_i^m = 0$. The vectors

$$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}^m \equiv \mathbf{h}_m - \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i^m \mathbf{g}_i^m$$

are in \mathcal{A} and in $(\mathcal{H}_1^{\tilde{\delta}})^{\tilde{\delta}} = \mathcal{H}_1$ because $\phi(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}^m, \mathbf{g}_j) = 0$ by construction. For any vector \mathbf{h} in \mathcal{H}_1 , there is a sequence of vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}^m$ in $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{H}_1$ such that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{\mathbf{h}}^m = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{h}^m = \mathbf{h}$.

(3) If \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} are vectors in \mathcal{H} not equal to $\mathbf{0}$ with $\phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = 0$, then there exist sequences $\{\mathbf{u}_n\}$ and $\{\mathbf{v}_n\}$ of vectors in \mathcal{A} such that

$$(i) \quad \phi(\mathbf{u}_l, \mathbf{v}_m) = \phi(\mathbf{u}_l, \mathbf{v}) = \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}_m) = 0 \text{ for all } l, m$$

$$(ii) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{u}_n = \mathbf{u} \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{v}_n = \mathbf{v}.$$

Let $\{\epsilon_n\}$ be a sequence of real numbers $\epsilon_n > 0$ such that $\epsilon_1 > \|\mathbf{u}\|$, $\epsilon_1 > \|\mathbf{v}\|$, and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \epsilon_n = 0$. The proof is done by induction starting with $\mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{v}_1 = \mathbf{0}$. Assume now that sequences $\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{n-1}$ and $\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{n-1}$ are constructed such that condition (i) is fulfilled for all $l, m \leq n-1$ and that $\|\mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}\| < \epsilon_m$ and $\|\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{v}\| < \epsilon_m$ for all $m \leq n-1$. The task consists now in finding two vectors \mathbf{u}_n and \mathbf{v}_n such that condition (i) is valid for all $l, m \leq n$, that $\|\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbf{u}\| < \epsilon_n$, and $\|\mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v}\| < \epsilon_n$. The task is achieved using the result of step (2). Take the subspace generated by $\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{n-1}, \mathbf{v}$ as $\mathcal{H}_1^{\tilde{\delta}}$ and find a vector \mathbf{u}_n in $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{H}_1$ such that $\|\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbf{u}\| < \epsilon_n$. Then take the subspace generated by $\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_n, \mathbf{u}$ as $\mathcal{H}_1^{\tilde{\delta}}$ and find \mathbf{v}_n in $\mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{H}_1$ such that $\|\mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v}\| < \epsilon_n$.

(4) For any vector \mathbf{v} in \mathcal{H} , there is a vector \mathbf{w} in \mathcal{A} such that $\mathbf{w} \neq \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{w} \neq \mathbf{v}$, and $\phi(\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}) = 0$.

The case $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$ is trivial. If $\mathbf{v} \neq \mathbf{0}$, choose a vector $\tilde{\mathbf{w}} \neq \mathbf{v}$ in \mathcal{A} such that $\phi(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}, \mathbf{v}) \neq 0$ and

$$\mathbf{w} = \phi(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}) \phi(\tilde{\mathbf{w}}, \mathbf{v})^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}$$

(5) To conclude the proof of the theorem, take the vectors $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{v}$ and \mathbf{v} , the vectors \mathbf{w} and \mathbf{v} from step (4), and construct the sequences $\{\mathbf{u}_n\}$ and $\{\mathbf{v}_n\}$ of step (3). Let \mathcal{S} be the subspace

$$\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{A} : \phi(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{u}_n) = 0 \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}\}$$

of \mathcal{A} . Because $\phi(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{u}_n) = 0$ for all \mathbf{s} in \mathcal{S} and all n in \mathbb{N} , it is also $\phi(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{u}) = 0 = \phi(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s})$ for all \mathbf{s} in $\mathcal{S} \leq \mathcal{A}$ i.e. the vector \mathbf{u} is in \mathcal{S}^{δ} — the duality δ is taken with respect to \mathcal{A} . It is $\mathcal{S}^{\delta} \leq \mathcal{A}$ according to step (1) and, hence, \mathbf{u} is in \mathcal{A} . Therefore, it is $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{u}$ with \mathbf{w} in \mathcal{A} and \mathbf{u} in \mathcal{A} , which implies that \mathbf{v} is in \mathcal{A} because \mathcal{A} is a linear space. This is valid for an arbitrary vector $\mathbf{v} \neq \mathbf{0}$ in \mathcal{H} and the vector $\mathbf{0}$ is in \mathcal{A} as well as in \mathcal{H} . Hence, $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{H}$.

qed

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